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Harmonic Parallelism versus Harmonic Serialism: The Case of Nasal Place Assimilation in Modern Colloquial Persian

Mufleh Salem M. Alqahtani
King Saud University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

This paper elaborates on the comparison between Harmonic Parallelism (HP) and Harmonic Serialism (HS) as Optimality Theory (OT) models concerning nasal place assimilation in Modern Colloquial Persian. The data of this study were harvested from extant literature on place assimilation, including books, articles, and theses. Also, four native speakers (two males and two females) of Persian from Tehran were consulted to verify data extracted from the literature. The study concludes that place assimilation in this variety of Persian is restrictively regressive due to the impact of the coda condition when dealing with the serial application of place assimilation; hence, regressive place assimilation is executed in two steps where the first one is to delete the place feature of the coda which facilitates the leftward spread of the place feature of the following onset, as the second step; i.e., feeding order. HP encounters difficulty generalizing the place assimilation above since it is inherently derivational. Unlike HP, HS successfully expresses the serial relation beyond nasal place assimilation in Modern Colloquial Persian. Furthermore, HS can explain the directional asymmetry in place assimilation in Modern Colloquial Persian.

Keywords: *modern colloquial Persian, nasal place assimilation, harmonic parallelism, harmonic serialism, optimality theory*

1 Introduction

The current study sheds light on the comparison between HP and HS regarding nasal place assimilation in Modern Colloquial Persian as a style of informal speech mostly spoken in Tehran.

The consonant inventory Modern Colloquial Persian in Table 1 presents 23 consonants in the conventional arrangement based on place and manner of articulation as per Windfuhr (1987), Mahootian (1997), and Hosseini (2014), Bijankhan (2018), Alqahtani (2020). The following table provides the reader with the features of the relevant consonants of Modern Colloquial Persian.¹

¹ The author referred to Durand's (1990) version of distinctive features.

Table 1: Manners and places of articulation of the consonants of Modern Colloquial Persian (Windfuhr 1987; Mahootian 1997; Hosseini 2014; Bijankhan 2018; Alqahtani 2020)

	Bilabial	Labio-dental	Dental	Alveolar	Post-alveolar	Palatal	Uvular	Glottal
Plosives	p b		t d			c ɟ	g	ʔ
Nasals	m			n				
Fricatives		f v		s z	ʃ ʒ		χ	h
Affricates					tʃ dʒ			
Approximants				r		j		
Lateral approximant				l				

Table 2: The list of features of the relevant Modern Colloquial Persian consonants (Bijankhan 2018)

Features in Colloquial Persian	p	b	t	d	c	ɟ	ʔ	m	n	f	v	s	z	ʃ	ʒ	h	χ	g	tʃ	dʒ	r	j	l	
Consonant	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+
Sonorant	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+
Approximant	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+
Continuant	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	±	±	+	+	-	-
Nasal	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Lateral	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
Voice	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+
Coronal	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	+	+
Anterior	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+
Distributed	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	±	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	-	+	±	±
Labial	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Dorsal	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-
High	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
Back	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Low	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Place assimilation has been considered an adaptation to the listener’s need and an articulatorily motivated process (Kohler 1991, 1992; Mohanan 1993; Jun 1995). Several implicational statements on place assimilation have been established in Mohanan’s (1993) and Jun’s (1995) typological works. These statements are summarized below:

(1) Jun’s (1995: 92) implicational statements on place assimilation:

- a. Target manner:
 - i. If fricatives or non-nasal sonorants are targets of place assimilation, so are stops.

- ii. If stops are targets of place assimilation, so are nasals.
 - b. Target Place:
 - i. If velars are targets of place assimilation, so are labials.
 - ii. If labials are targets of place assimilation, so are coronals.
 - c. Trigger manner:
 - i. If non-nasal sonorants trigger place assimilation, so do nasals and fricatives.
 - ii. If nasals or fricatives trigger place assimilation, so do stops.
 - d. Trigger place:
 - If coronals are triggers, so are velars.
 - e. Syllable positions:
 - If the onset is the target, so is the coda.

With regard to syllable position, codas are more likely to be liable to assimilation cross- and intra-linguistically than onsets (Webb 1982; Jun 1995; Lamont 2015); i.e., place assimilation is regressive primarily. By contrast, Webb (1982: 317) mentions that progressive assimilation, where the onset is the target, is rare. Accordingly, nasal place assimilation in Modern Colloquial Persian is regressive, as it targets the nasals /n/ and /m/, which are followed by consonants produced at different places of articulation. The deletion of the place of articulation for the nasals /n/ and /m/ results in the placeless nasal **N** (the bold capital **N** indicates the placeless nasal), which facilitates the spread of the place feature of the following onset leftwards, as the final step. The examples of regressive place assimilation in this variety of Persian are shown in (2):

(2) Examples of the regressive place assimilation of nasal stops in Modern Colloquial Persian

i)	a.	/panbe/ →	/pa N be/ →	[pambe]	‘cotton’
	b.	/tanbaku/ →	/ta N baku/ →	[tambaku]	‘tobacco’
ii)	a.	/tænvir/ →	/tæ N vir/ →	[tæŋvir]	‘enlightenment /illumination’
	b.	/kamfor/	/ka N for/	[kaŋfor]	‘camphor’
iii)	a.	/mænfæʔ/ →	/mæ N fæʔ/ →	[mæŋfæʔ]	‘origin’
iv)	a.	/bance/ →	/ba N ce/ →	[baŋce]	‘container’
v)	a.	/mænguʃ/ →	/mæ N guʃ/ →	[mæŋguʃ]	‘engraved’

Based on the data above, nasals assimilate in place rather than orals in Modern Colloquial Persian since the place contrasts in nasals are less perceptible than those in oral stops; thus, native speakers of Modern Colloquial Persian tend to neutralize place contrasts in oral stops less than in nasals. This finding is supported by Jun (1995, 2004) and Blevins (2005), who investigated cross-linguistic place assimilation. They agree that nasal consonant place assimilation is perceptually more tolerable than oral consonant place assimilation because the former involves less perceptual change. Two points are relevant regarding the surface forms above; first, codas have no independent place of articulation from the following onset, which

would otherwise violate the Coda Condition. Therefore, regressive place assimilation is utilized to avoid such a violation. The second point is peculiar to the regressive place assimilation itself being inherently derivational: the place assimilation is a two-step process where the spreading of the licensed place feature occurs after the deletion of the unlicensed one. Thus, per the coda condition, the place feature of a coda is not permitted unless it is associated with the place feature of the following onset or if a coda has the same place feature as does the following onset (Poser 1982; Mascaró 1987; Itô 1989; Goldsmith 1990; Cho 1990; Kiparsky 1993; McCarthy 2008, 2016). Therefore, the first step is to delete the place feature of the coda if different from the place feature of the following onset, /n, m/ → N. The final step is the spread of the place feature to the left of the onset. Consider the following representation of /panbe/ → [pambe] ‘cotton.’

(3) /panbe/ → [pambe] ‘cotton’

The next section explores the previous analyses of place assimilation in Persian varieties. The following sections analyze nasal place assimilation in modern colloquial Persian in light of harmonic parallelism and serialism. After that, section 5 summarizes the current study and its findings.

2 The Previous Analyses of Place Assimilation in Persian Varieties

Place assimilation has been the subject of previous investigations by scholars who conducted their studies on the phonology of Persian varieties, including Aldaghi & Tavakoli (2011), Zahedi & Fakharian (2011), Okati et al. (2012), Hosseinzadeh et al. (2014), Saeedi & Atabakhsh (2015), Atabakhsh & Saeedi (2016), Soohani (2017). They all agree upon place assimilation in Persian varieties being regressive, targeting nasal consonants followed by onsets of the following syllables with different places of articulation; hence, the place features of codas in the coda position are determined by the onsets of the following syllables to conform to coda condition. However, those scholars differ in terms of the way they account for place assimilation in Persian varieties. For instance, Aldaghi & Tavakoli (2011), Okati et al. (2012), and Saeedi & Atabakhsh (2015) descriptively account for place assimilation in Sabzevari Persian, Sistani Persian of Iran, and the speech of North Khuszestan. However, their studies do not exhibit a cause-and-effect relationship. On the other hand, Hosseinzadeh et al. (2014) and Atabakhsh & Saeedi (2016) refer to rule-based theory to account for place assimilation in Eghlidian Persian and Dezfuli-Shushtari speech in Iran. The rule-based theory is not exempt from criticism since it encounters two problems: *Duplication and Conspiracy problems* (Kenstowicz & Kisseberth 1977; Zuraw & Lu 2009). Kenstowicz & Kisseberth (1977) express the *Duplication problem* as the case where morpheme structure changes and rules duplicate each other’s effects. The *Conspiracy problem*, as demonstrated by Zuraw & Lu

(2009), is the case where different rules in different languages aim for the same surface pattern. Zahedi & Fakharian (2011) analyze place assimilation in Modern Persian using Feature Geometry, which grew out of Autosegmental Phonology. However, this theory and autosegmental phonology are subject to criticism as they are continuations of rule-based theory. Goldsmith (1990: 1) mentions that autosegmental phonology is a “direct continuation of the traditional works in generative phonology codified in Chomsky and Halle’s *Sound Pattern of English* in 1968.” Goldsmith (1979: 202) reports that the difference between autosegmental theory and the SPE is “the development of a multi-linear phonological analysis in which different features may be placed on separate tiers, and in which the various tiers are organized by ‘association lines’”. Therefore, these theories encounter the *Duplication* and *Conspiracy* problems discussed above. Unlike the above phonological approaches, the issues mentioned earlier can be solved by Optimality Theory (OT) because it eliminates the use of rules and derivations and replaces them with well-formedness constraints which interact to determine the actual output (Prince & Smolensky 1993; McCarthy & Prince 1995; Lombardi 2001: 1). Accordingly, Soohani (2017) accounts for place assimilation in Iranian Balochi dialects using Standard Optimality Theory (Parallel OT) as a framework. Parallel OT successfully addresses many problematic issues in phonology even though it encounters an obstacle in accounting for other phonological phenomena, including phonological opacity, process interaction, and some cases of variation (Prince & Smolensky, 1993; Rakhieh, 2009; Al Taisan, 2022; Alqahtani 2023).

With respect to the scholars above, none of them compares Harmonic Parallelism (HP) and Harmonic Serialism (HS) concerning nasal place assimilation in Modern Colloquial Persian. Therefore, the current study aims to reveal which OT model can express nasal place assimilation as inherently derivational (Poser 1982; Mascaró 1987; Itô 1989; Goldsmith 1990; Cho 1990; Kiparsky 1993; McCarthy 2008, 2016). To achieve the goal of this study, it is crucial to address the question of “Which OT model captures the generalization about nasal place assimilation in Modern Colloquial Persian?”. The following section is particularly about the analysis of nasal place assimilation in Modern Colloquial Persian using HP.

3 Data Analysis within Harmonic Parallelism (HP)

Harmonic Parallelism (HP) is an OT model in which the ultimate output is determined after a single pass through GENERATOR (GEN) and EVALUATOR (EVAL) (McCarthy 2000). This mechanism is shown in the following diagram.

(4) Parallel architecture for OT

Input → **GEN** → cand-set → **EVAL** → Output (McCarthy 2000: 502)

Regarding the above diagram, this section explores whether HP can capture the generalization about nasal place assimilation in Modern Colloquial Persian. Before any further analysis, let us consider the following OT constraints:

(5) OT constraints:

- a. CODA-COND (Goldsmith 1990; Itô 1989)
Assign one violation mark every coda consonant that does not license a place feature.
- b. HAVE-PL (McCarthy 2016)
Assign one violation mark for every placeless segment.
- c. IDENT(PL) (McCarthy & Prince 1995: 16)²
Assign one violation mark for every place feature in the input that differs from its corresponding place feature in the output.

Regarding the list of OT constraints above, HAVE-PL is the highest-ranked constraint, which opposes candidates with coda consonants that have unlicensed place features. CODA-COND, as the second most highly ranked constraint, also opposes candidates with unlicensed coda consonants. IDENT(PL), being the lowest-ranked constraint, guarantees that the place feature of the input and output remains fully faithful. Consider the following set of OT constraints.

(6)

HAVE-PL >> CODA-COND >> IDENT(PL)

The above set of OT constraints is used to evaluate the candidates for the input /panbe/ ‘cotton’ in the following tableau:

Tableau [I] *Evaluating the candidates of the input /panbe/ ‘cotton.’*

HAVE-PL >> CODA-COND >> IDENT(PL)

/panbe/	HAVE-PL	CODA-COND	IDENT(PL)
a. panbe		*!	
b. paNbe	*!		*
c. pambe			*

Based on the tableau above, candidate (c), as the desired output, has been chosen as optimal since it avoids the violation of HAVE-PL and CODA-COND, unlike candidates (a) and (b). Although candidate (a) is the most faithful output to the input /panbe/, it fails to be optimal due

² This constraint is shortened in tableaux to IDENT(PL).

to the violation of CODA-COND. Candidate (b) satisfies CODA-COND through the deletion of the place feature of a coda, which consequently incurs the violation of HAVE-PL.

Although HP reveals candidate (c) as the true optimal output, there are two comments on this model. First, this model has only two levels, i.e., the underlying and surface levels, which are incapable of capturing generalisations about place assimilation because they are essentially derivational. In other words, regressive place assimilation requires intermediate steps that cannot be expressed in two levels. Secondly, GEN (Generator) in HP, according to McCarthy (2000), is unrestricted and would also produce the output [pambe], which is equal in evaluation to [pambe].³ Consider the following tableau:

Tableau [II] *Evaluating the candidates of the input /panbe/ ‘cotton.’*

/panbe/	HAVE-PL >>CODA-COND>>IDENT(PL)		
	HAVE-PL	CODA-COND	IDENT(PL)
a. panbe		*!	
b. paNbe	*!		*
c. pambe			*
d. pande			*

The tableau fails to identify candidate (c), i.e., the desired output, as optimal, since both candidate (c) and candidate (d) equally violate IDENT(PL). This shows that HP fails to capture the generalization about any derivational process, including place assimilation.⁴ Thus, invoking a derivational model that potentially accounts for any derivational process, including place assimilation, is crucial. To differentiate between candidates (c) and (d), it is worth mentioning that candidate (d), produced by progressive place assimilation, targets the onset with a different place articulation from the preceding coda, whereas candidate (c), produced by regressive place assimilation, targets the preceding coda with a different place articulation from the following onset. Consider the following derivational orders of regressive and progressive place assimilation in Modern Colloquial Persian:

(7)

a. The derivational order of the regressive place assimilation in Modern Colloquial Persian:

Underlying representation	/panbe/ ‘cotton’
Deleting the place feature of the coda:	paNbe

³ McCarthy (2016) states that through GEN in Parallel OT many changes are made at once when producing a candidate: To put it simply, one or more operations are applied together by GEN in Parallel OT.

⁴ Parallel OT apparently fails to explain why place assimilation is from the onset to the coda and never the other way around (McCarthy 2016).

Spreading the place feature of the following onset leftwards:	pambe
Surface	[pambe]

b. The derivational order of the progressive place assimilation in Modern Colloquial Persian

Underlying representation	/panbe/ ‘cotton’
Deleting the place feature of the onset:	panʔe ⁵
Spreading the place feature of the coda rightwards:	pande
Surface	*[pande]

The above asymmetry can successfully be explained by Harmonic Serialism (HS), as demonstrated in the following section.

4 Data Analysis within Harmonic Serialism (HS)

Harmonic Serialism (HS) explains the asymmetry in place assimilation in Modern Colloquial Persian discussed in the previous section since GEN in this model, unlike Parallel OT, is restricted to one change in every step, i.e., gradualness.⁶ This means that GEN in HS is not a one-time process, as it is in Parallel OT, and thus produces a new candidate set after each change (McCarthy 2016). HS is merely a derivational version of Classical OT where multiple passes are made by the input through the same set of constraints until the derivation coverages (McCarthy 2016). The HS-OT model is presented by McCarthy (2016: 50) in the following flowchart.

⁵ McCarthy (2016) notes that deleting the place feature from the onset yields the placeless ʔ.

⁶ McCarthy (2010) states that Harmonic Serialism results in a more restrictive typology of place assimilation, unlike parallel OT, due to gradualness and harmonic improvement.

(8) HS flowchart (McCarthy 2016: 50):

In HS, CODA-COND must dominate HAVE-PL and IDENT(PL) to apply the first derivational step, i.e., deleting the place feature of the preceding coda that differs from the following onset. Consider the following constraint ranking in HS-OT.

(9) CODA-COND >>HAVE-PL>>IDENT(PL)

The HS-OT analysis of the candidates derived from the input /panbe/ ‘cotton’ is shown below:

Tableau [III]: Step 1: Deleting the place feature of a coda: /panbe/ → /paNbe/
 CODA-COND >>HAVE-PL >>IDENT(PL)

/panbe/	CODA-COND	HAVE-PL	IDENT(PL)
a. panbe	*!		
b. paNbe		*	*
c. pan?e	*!	*	*

In the tableau above, candidate (b) has been determined as optimal due to its correspondence with the CODA-COND constraint. On the other hand, the same constraint is fatally violated by candidates (a) and (c) since the coda in both candidates is not licensed by the following onset. Consequently, they are eliminated. Candidate (b), distinguished as optimal, serves as the input in the following tableau as the next step.

Tableau [IV]: Step 2: Spreading the place feature of the following onset leftwards: /paNbe/→ [pambe]

CODA-COND >> HAVE-PL >> IDENT(PL)			
/paNbe/	CODA-COND	HAVE-PL	IDENT(PL)
a. paNbe		*!	
b. \wp pambe			*
c. paN \wp e		*!*	

The placeless nasal in candidates (a) and (c) incurs the fatal violation of HAVE-PL. As a result, candidate (b) is chosen as optimal. The final step in the next tableau shows the convergence [pambe], which is the input in this step: the loop of GEN/EVAL terminates.

Tableau [V]: Step 3: Convergence

CODA-COND >> HAVE-PL >> IDENT(PL)			
/pambe/	CODACOND	HAVE-PL	IDENT(PL)
a. \wp pambe			

In summary, HP has been shown as an OT model capable of accounting for any one-step process since it is of a two-level representation. However, this OT model encounters difficulty accounting for any phonological process that is inherently derivational, in this case, place assimilation in Modern Colloquial Persian; hence, candidates liable to regressive and progressive place assimilation satisfy the coda condition since the serial relation is not considered. As a result, HP cannot account for this asymmetry. In contrast, HS, concerned with the serial relation of place assimilation, successfully accounts for this asymmetry since gradualness and Harmonic improvement are its core properties. In this case, the impact of the coda condition on place assimilation in Modern Colloquial Persian is revealed by considering intermediate steps between the input and output, where every step is restricted to one and only one change. Deleting the place feature of the onset as the first step for the progressive place assimilation incurs the violation of the coda condition, while deleting the place feature of the coda would meet the same condition. This shows there is no possible progressive place

assimilation in Modern Colloquial Persian due to the coda condition when using HS rather than HP.

5 Conclusion

The current research manifests the comparison of HS and HP as OT models, dealing with the nasal place assimilation in Modern Colloquial Persian. The directionality of nasal place assimilation in this variety of Persian is regressive due to the coda condition; hence, it is run by two steps where the first step is the deletion of the place feature of the coda, and the second step is to spread the place feature of the following onset leftwards. Intermediate steps are required to express the process of nasal place assimilation in Modern Colloquial Persian. Accordingly, HP encounters an obstacle in accounting for the serial relation behind regressive place assimilation in Modern Colloquial Persian since it has two representation levels, i.e., input and output. Furthermore, the impact of the coda condition on nasal place assimilation in Persian is not revealed when using HP since GEN makes many changes once when producing a candidate. As a result, both the progressive place assimilation and the regressive place assimilation match with the coda condition. However, the progressive place assimilation, which does not exist in this variety of Persian, violates the coda condition in a serial relation where every step is restricted to one change only. Therefore, this serial relation has successfully been addressed by HS, where its properties are gradualness and Harmonic improvement. To put it simply, HS exerts the influence of the coda condition on place assimilation in Modern Colloquial Persian. The findings in this paper underscore the role of HS in accounting for other types of assimilation, including manner assimilation and total assimilation in different varieties of Persian.

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*Mufleh Salem M. Alqahtani Department of Linguistics, College of Language Sciences
King Saud University
Saudi Arabia
e-mail: mqahtani1@ksu.edu.sa*

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Expressing Intensification in the Chasu Language of Tanzania

Rafiki Y. Sebonde, The University of Dodoma, Tanzania

*While a number of studies have been conducted about expressing intensification in languages such as English, less attention is given to Bantu languages on the topic. This paper, therefore, explores strategies used to express intensity in Chasu, a language of the Bantu family spoken in Same District of Kilimanjaro, Tanzania. The study is guided by the Functional-typological approach which assumes that linguistic structures such as intensifiers are shaped by their communicative and cognitive functions such as emphasis and expressing degree or speaker's stance. The approach propagates also that the structure of intensifiers is typologically diverse across languages. The study employs a descriptive research approach using data from both spoken and written forms. Spoken data were elicited through sociolinguistic interviews using 30 native speakers of Mamba Myamba Ward of Same District in order to capture conversations of everyday language use. To complement spoken data, written forms were reviewed from a Chasu hymn book to record sentences, phrases, and words with intensifiers. Transcription of recorded data was done using Chasu orthography followed by content analysis. The findings of this study reveal the use of both morphological and lexical strategies. In morphological strategy, intensification in Chasu is expressed by a morpheme **-ish-a** embedded as a suffix after the verb root and adjectives like in **kund-ish-a** (love so much) and **mbah-ish-a** (very big) respectively. From lexical strategy, intensifiers are expressed through adverbs **haiwa** and **pere** modifying adjectives and verbs. In addition, ideophonic adverbs, verbal and adjectival reduplication are strategies for expressing intensification in Chasu. Furthermore, there were few incidences of the use of borrowed Swahili intensifiers **sana** and **kabisa**. The study recommends more studies on expression of intensification in Bantu languages to widen up the knowledge scope and theoretical understanding. It also recommends a comparative study examining the structural diversity of intensifiers across languages.*

Keywords: *intensifiers, Chasu, adverbs, adjectives, ideophones, reduplications*

1 Introduction

The study on various aspects of intensification and the way of its expression in spoken and written discourse has been of great interest for some decades. Various scholars have made interesting contributions especially in the conceptualization, classification of intensifiers, and the patterns and frequency of their occurrence in the sentences. Quirk et. al (1985), for example, conceptualized intensifiers as linguistic devices that boost the meaning of a property upward from an assumed norm. Intensifiers “indicate a point on an abstractly conceived intensity scale, and the point on the indicated may be relatively low or relatively high” pp 589. Quirk, et.al (1985) divide intensifiers into emphasers, which have a general heightening effect and are generally attributive only; amplifiers (maximizers, boosters), which scale upwards from assumed norms and are central adjectives if they are inherent, and denote a high or extreme degree, and down toners (approximators e.g. *almost*; compromisers e.g. *more or less*; diminishers e.g. *partly*; minimizers e.g. *hardly*) which are having a lowering effect usually scaling downwards from assumed norms. Intensification helps to highlight what is being said and how it relates to the impact it may make to the interlocutor. In a broader definition, intensity involves such range of linguistic phenomena as a change in the degree of an attribute to and

side (decreasing or increasing) size of an object, the strength of an action, and value of an object or action. According to Bolinger (1972), intensifiers are adverbs that scale the quality of an adjective or adverb up, hence referred as degree words. Quirk, et. al (1985) address them as amplifiers while Tagliamonte (2008) categorises them as adverbs that boost or minimize meaning.

Furthermore, Rodionova (2004) in Siddikova & Zubareva (2020) postulates that intensity can be applied not only to the attribute of an object, or phenomena but also the attitude towards it. This may happen when the speaker gives a persuasive speech aiming at imparting certain views and opinions to the potential audience. Siddikova & Zubareva (2020) claim that the combination of attitude to the phenomena with the use of various expressive means which express the value of the degree of attributes, intensify the communication effect. In broader conceptualization of this category, intensity includes such a range of phenomena as a change in the degree of an attribute such as expressiveness, emotionality, evaluativity, and imagery. It includes attributes to any side either of increase or decrease of an object, the size of an object, the strength of an action and the value of an object.

Concerning the importance of intensification, Labov (1985:43) hypothesizes that “at the heart of the social and emotional expression is the linguistic feature of intensity”. Partington (1973:178) adds that intensification, in the communication process is a vehicle for impressing, praising, persuading, insulting and generally influencing the listeners’ reception of the message. In addition, intensifiers can express an interpersonal message, which signals personal commitment and their judgments of truth and value (Lorenz 1999: 24). Linguistically, the use of intensifiers is the most typical way of realizing intensification to show the attitudinal meaning. From the systemic functional perspective, intensifiers serve a modal function, and they convey an interpersonal meaning and provide information about the social and emotional stance of the speaker (Labov 1985; Partington 1993; Halliday 1994; Peters 1994; Klerk 2006). Generally, the intensifiers are used when the speakers of a language intend to use words to scale upward or scale downward the meaning of an object when delivering the message through words.

Speaking of intensifying adverbs, Huddleton & Pullum (2000) assert that intensifying adverbs should not be viewed as either grammatical or lexical category, but they do have grammatical properties, although not insufficiently defined, unless their functional significance is described. Intensifiers help to highlight what is being said and related to the basic human need to make an impact on the interlocutor especially when the speaker gives a persuasive speech aiming at instilling certain views and opinions to the potential addressee. In another study, Zhiber & Korotina (2019) describe that intensifying adverbs have undergone some evolution through the process of grammaticalization and delexicalization. In addition, Tagliamonte (2008) posits that the evidence of change *very* is quickly moving out of favor and *rely* has expanded dramatically. Moreover there is evidence to suggest that some intensifiers are undergoing delexicalization but not as part of continual longitudinal process, instead the profile of change reveals recycling, suggesting that the mechanics of intensifiers renewal may be more complex than previously thought.

In the study of expressing levels of intensity in Xhosa English, de Klerk (2005) classifies intensifiers as subclass of adverb that amplifies or adds emphasis to words (adjectives or verbs) which are gradable, or capable of a range of force, by either scaling them upwards or downwards in degree of intensity. The intensifiers can heighten the meaning or lower its effect. Intensifiers with a positive function are called amplifiers and those with strongest degree of intensification are maximizers, while those at the end of the scale are minimizers; for example,

hardly or *scarcely*. Intensifiers are technically described as a subcategory of subjunct along with emphasizees, focusing adverbs and others (Chalker & Weiner 1998).

In Bantu languages, adverbs have been studied as a word category which modify the word categories such as verbs and adjectives that precede them immediately. Adverbs of magnitude have been identified in Kinyakyusa, a language in Tanzania, expressing intensifiers using ideophonic adverbs. In the study of adverbs in Kinyakyusa, Lusekelo (2010) describes that, adverbs of magnitude may modify verbs or adjectives that immediately precede them. On a study of intensifying ideophone in three Luhya languages, Bowler and Gluckman (2017) assert that the Luhya ideophones select for semantic class of lexical items that they can co-occur with to intensify. Ideophones in Luhya commonly co-occur with verbs and adjectives, and for few cases with nouns. For example; Llogoori (one of the Luhya languages) ideophone *ti* combines with lexical item *mwamu* (adjective) or *chafu* (adjective) to describe ‘darkness’ or ‘dirtiness’ respectively, while *zi* combines with lexical items *zilu* (adjective) or *chinganu* (adjective) describing ‘stillness’ or ‘coldness’. Ideophone *mno* co-occurs with *kuyaanza*, (verb) *mahooru*, (noun) and *ndugi* (adjective) describing ‘to be happy’, ‘longing’ and ‘sweet’ respectively. Generally, ideophones in Luhya languages are behaving typically like the way adverbial element does to intensify lexical items such as verbs, adjectives and nouns.

Moreover, in Bantu linguistics, intensification has also been expressed through the use of full or partial reduplication of adjectives or verbs for emphatic purposes. Examples can be borrowed from Zulu words such as adjective *khulu* ‘big’ to *khulukhulu* ‘very big’; the verb *hamba* ‘go’ to *hambahamba* ‘go a lot’ (Downing 2001) and from Swahili language the verb *piga* ‘strike’ to *pigapiga* ‘strike repeatedly or hard’ (Hyman 2009) whereas reduplication expresses habitual action or intensive actions.

Though the study of intensification has been discussed widely with various studies being conducted in English and other languages like Chinese, less is studied regarding intensifiers particularly in Bantu linguistics. This study therefore, sought to describe the formation, categorization of strategies and functions; and patterns of distribution of intensifiers in Chasu, a Bantu language spoken in Same District of Kilimanjaro Region, Tanzania. This study did not delve in to the comparative part of intensifiers across languages.

1.1 Chasu language and context

The study of expressing intensifiers is conducted in Same District - Kilimanjaro Tanzania, where Chasu speakers live. Chasu is a Bantu language predominantly spoken in Same and Mwanza Districts, the Northeastern part of Tanzania (Mreta 1998). Mreta (1998 as cited in Yohana 2009) clarifies that Chasu is sub-divided into two major dialects, the Northern Chasu dialect spoken in Mwanza District, and the Southern Chasu dialect spoken in Same District. Regarding classification, Guthrie (1948) classifies Chasu in Zone G (Shambala group) and coded G.22 whereby, Northern Chasu is designated G.22A and Southern Chasu as G.22B (Msuya and Mreta 2021). Southern Chasu, the target dialect of the current study, contains sub-varieties such as Kisuji/Kimamba, Kimakasa-papa, Kimbagha and Kigonja (Kotz 1909; Kagaya 1989; Omari 1991; Mreta 1998). The present study has focused into the Kisuji/Kimamba variety which is spoken in Mamba Myamba ward. Other studies that have been conducted on this variety include, language contact and sociolinguistic analysis of variation, language shift, code-switching and socio-stratification, lexical borrowing and numerical system, naming practices and mode of address, and lexical borrowing and semantic change (Yohana 2009; Sebonde 2012; 2014; 2020; & 2025). Chasu, like other Ethnic

Community Languages in Tanzania, has been affected by other languages due to the long-term contact with Kiswahili and English resulting into bilingualism, lexical change, code-switching and code mixing, and semantic change. However, Chasu is still spoken in some domains such as several religious contexts, funerals, local markets, local wedding ceremonies, and other traditional ceremonies (Sebonde 2014), *ndethi* ‘for cursing’ and *maatha* ‘for litigation’ (Msuya 2014). The co-existence of Chasu, Kiswahili and English may have affected some grammatical features including strategies of expressing intensification. This study has concentrated on examining strategies of expressing intensification in Chasu speech community.

2 Theoretical framework

The study of expressing intensification in Chasu language is guided by the Functional-typological approach which is a combination of two linguistic inquiries; functional linguistics and typological linguistics. This approach is based on the foundational works by Givón (1979), Comrie (1989) and Croft (2003) who provide a framework on studying intensifiers offering a glance emphasizing their functional roles and typological variation. Their effort was to integrate functionalism’s focus on communication with typology’s cross-linguistics perspective. The functionalism adopts the idea that linguistic structures are fashioned by communicative functions such as expressing meaning, facilitating interaction or optimizing their cognitive processing. On the other side, typology focuses on classification of comparison of languages to identify their universal features, constraints and variations. For more emphasis, Plank adds that:

Typological research commences by identifying differences among languages, as opposed to traits shared universally. Typology’s remit then is to determine whether these individual differences are interrelated or independent of each other.

(Plank 2001: 1399)

Generally the functional-typologists are interested on one hand, studying the communicative functional motivation behind linguistic structures and on the other hand, emphasizing on the cross linguistic variation of languages.

The functional-typological approach suits this study as it focuses more on the functional roles of intensifiers emphasizing how they are shaped within and across languages. The approach helps classifying the intensifiers, cataloging their forms, distribution and functions enlightening with how they converge or diverge from cross-linguistic tendencies. It helps to guide the study on how intensifiers function and correlate with other grammatical features such as word order across languages. The approach serves in examining the functional roles of intensifiers such emphasizing degree, expressing speakers’ attitude or structuring discourse.

3 Methodology

Most of the studies on strategies to express intensification adopted the use of different corpora such as British National Corpus (BNC) (Yujie 2017), and The Corpus of the Contemporary American English (COCA) (Zhiber & Korotina 2019) in collecting linguistic forms which could be used in examining, categorizing, and identification of intensifiers. However, the data for the study at hand were elicited using two major sources; written and spoken. The spoken

linguistics forms were elicited through sociolinguistic interviews involving 30 informants from Chasu community of Same District-Kilimanjaro Region where the Southern Chasu Dialect is spoken. Informants included both males and females of different age groups from Mamba Myamba ward specifically from Goha, Mang'a, Mteke, Kirore, Kambeni, and Mramba villages. The study used descriptive research and the informants were selected through snowball sampling and being engaged into various topics of interest such as soccer, daily activities including trading, farming, hunting, and stories about their school life experience. Before data collection, consent was sought from the informants to participate in the study, and to be recorded. Through these sociolinguistic interviews, audio recorded short speeches from day-to-day language were gathered. From these speeches about 86 linguistic structures in form of sentences, lexical items, and phrases with intensifiers were extracted. To complement the spoken data, the written linguistic forms were collected from Chasu hymn book (Nyimbo za Mtaso 1967). The book was purposively selected based on the fact that, it contains hymns written in Chasu with very few incidences of borrowed words from Kiswahili, the national language in Tanzania, and a language which is currently used by Chasu speakers in different domains such as church, market, schools, and village meetings (Sebonde 2014). The Chasu hymn book is written using Kisuji/Kimamba sub-dialect hence aligning with spoken data which were gathered in Mamba Myamba ward. About 170 tokens in form of sentences, phrases and expressions were reviewed and collected. The transcription of data from interviews was made from the recorded text using Chasu orthography followed by the content analysis to categorize strategies of expressing intensification of Chasu. Since intensifiers have traditionally been associated with adjectives, adverbs (Palacios & Ignacio 2016), verbs, nouns, and prepositions (Bolinger 1972), and ideophonic adverbs (Lusekelo 2010 and Bowler & Gluckman 2017), the analysis of this study was geared into identifying patterns with combination of verbs + adverbs intensifiers, adjectives + adverbs, verbs + intensifying morpheme, adjectives + intensifying morphemes, verb +intensifying morpheme +adverb, ideophonic adverb, and reduplications of linguistic aspects. There were no incidences with patterns involving a combination of nouns or prepositions in this particular study.

4 Results and discussion

In this section, the study gives a description and the strategies used to express intensification in Chasu language. It starts with a description of linguistic patterns involving intensifiers and their distribution in the Chasu sentences. The following are the linguistic patterns bearing combinations of adverbial intensifiers co-occurring with the linguistic forms they modify, being a verb, an adjective or an adverb.

Table 1: Linguistic patterns with Chasu intensifiers

SN	Patterns	Occurrences
1	verbs + adverbs intensifiers	22
2	adjectives + adverbs	12
3	verb root + intensifying morpheme <i>-ish-a</i>	110
4	adjectives + intensifying morphemes <i>-ish-a</i>	56
6	verb +intensifying morpheme <i>-ish-a</i> +adverb	15
7	adjective + intensifying morpheme <i>-ish-a</i> +adverb	2
8	adjective + ideophonic adverb	8
9	verb +intensifying morpheme <i>-ish-a</i> +ideophonic adverb	12
10	verbs + ideophonic adverb	10
11	reduplication	9

The following examples in (1a-g) depict various patterns of Chasu intensifiers as in Table 1.

- (1) a. *Ni- Ø-end-**ish-a** lila i-sanga l-ed-**ish-a***
1SG-PRS-want-INT-FV that 5.land 5-beautiful-INT-FV
‘I **highly** need that **very** beautiful land’
- b. *Twa- Ø-ku- gwir-**ish-a***
1PL- PRF-2OPSG- trust-INT-FV
‘We **highly** trust you’
- c. *Tu-ne-von-a nkalamo y-edi **haiwa***
2PL-FUT-see-FV 9.salvation 9-good **ADV**
‘We shall see a **very good** salvation’
- d. *Ni- Ø-ag-**ish-a** **haiwa***
1SG-PRS-grieve-INT-FV **ADV**
‘I am **so much** grieving’
- e. *U-ni-ož-e iki ni-el-**ish-e** **chwe***
2SG-OP1SG-wash-SBJ now SBJ 1SG-clean-INT- FV/SBJ **IDEO**
‘Wash me now to be **exceedingly very** clean’
- f. *Shuke ni ny-ewa **chwe***
10.cloth COP 9-white **IDEO**
‘Clothes are **exceedingly white**’
- g. *Vi-ogwe vya- Ø sia **pere***
8.potato 8-PRF-finish-FV **ADV**
‘Potatoes are finished **completely**’

The most occurred linguistic pattern with intensifiers is a verb root co-occurring with an intensifying morpheme *-ish-a* as in example (1a) and (1b); an adjective with intensifying

morpheme *-ish-a* as in (1a); *led-ish-a*; verb root with intensifying morpheme *-ish-a* followed by intensifying adverb *haiwa* as in (1d); adjective followed by an adverb *haiwa* as in (1c); verb root with morpheme *-ish-a* followed by ideophonic adverb *chwe* as in (1e); adjective with ideophonic adverb *chwe* as in (1f) and verb followed by an intensifying adverb *pere* as in 1(g).

It was mentioned in the introduction part that Chasu is one of the Ethnic Community Languages in Tanzania, having a high contact with Swahili and English languages. As a result, there has been a language shift in some domain of language use, lexical borrowing and code-switching. In the study at hand, the data also indicate that, in Chasu language, there were few incidences of borrowed intensifiers from Kiswahili. Out of 86 linguistic forms gathered from the conversations, 13 had borrowed forms of Swahili intensifiers *sana*, *kabisa*, and *zaidi* as observed in the examples (2a-d) below.

- (2) a. *Tu- Ø pat-i-e ma-jeraha ma-dori sana*
1PL-PST-got-FV 6.bruise 6-small ADV
'We got some **very** few bruises'
- b. *Va-ntu ve-ki-lwan-a sana*
2.people 3PL-PTCP-fight-FV ADV
'People were **so much** fighting'
- c. *Shughuli ž-angu že-n-ink-a pesa ni-žo ne- Ø-ži-kund-i-e zaidi*
10.activity 10-POSS 10-OBJ-give-FV 10.money COP-REL 1SG-PRF-10.OP-love-APP-FV ADV
'Those activities which pay me are the ones I love **most**'
- d. *Ni ki-ntu ki-kuži sana*
COP 7-thing 7-difficult ADV
'Is a **very** difficult thing'

It is worth noting that there were no data from the Chasu hymn with incidences of borrowed intensifiers from Swahili language.

4.1 Expression of Chasu intensification

As asserted above, Chasu is among the languages of the Bantu family, hence reflects agglutinative nature of Bantu linguistics in verbs and adjectives. Therefore, while in other languages like English, intensifiers are manifested in free forms such as adverbs and adjectives, in Chasu language, intensifiers are categorically expressed using morphological and lexical strategies, and a combination of both.

4.1.1 Morphological strategy

Morphologically, Chasu is expressing intensification using a bound morpheme *-ish-a*, a suffix attached as a final morpheme to a verb, an adverb, or adjective expressing intensification of a precedent word. The following examples in (3a-h) describe the manifestation of the morpheme *-ish-a* in Chasu linguistic expression.

- (3) a. *Ni-Ø-end-ish-a lila i-sanga l-ed-ish-a*
1SG-PST-want-INT-FV that 5.land 5-beautiful-INT-FV
'I **highly** need that **very** beautiful land'
- b. *Twa- Ø- ku-gwir-ish-a*
1PL- PRS-2OPSG-trust-INT-FV
'We **highly** trust you'
- c. *E- Ø ni- kund-ish-a mi*
3SG- PRS-1OPSG -love- INT-FV me
'He loves me **so** much'
- d. *Va-lao v-ed-ish-a*
2.angel 2-beautiful-INT-FV
'**Very** beautifully angles'
- e. *Mbonea nyink-ish-a*
10.mercy 10.many-INT-FV
'So **exceedingly** mercy'
- f. *He u-la m-zi m-bah-ish-a*
In that 5.city 5-big-INT-FV
'In that **very** big city'
- g. *Ni-ne-m-many-a nento-sh-a*
1SG-FUT-3OPSG-know-FV well-INT-FV
'I will know him **very** well'

In example (3a-c) the bound morpheme *-ish-a* is attached to the verb roots *-enda*; 'need'; *gwira*-'trust'; *kunda* 'love' respectively, to express degree or the intensity of the action, meaning that an action is performed in greater force, or degree of frequency. On the other hand, examples (3d-g), the bound morpheme *-ish-a* is affixed to an adjective *-edi-* 'beautiful'; *nyinki* 'many or much'; *mbaha* 'big' and *nento* 'good' respectively, to express emphasis to scale up the meaning of an adjective. Comparing to other Bantu languages, the morphological strategy in Chasu is different from Kiswahili, a highly spoken, and a national language in Tanzania which lacks suffix as where lexical items *sana*, *mno*, and *kabisa* are used to express intensification.

4.1.2 Lexical strategy

The following intensifiers are at the word level category. These include lexical items with ideophonic adverbs, adverbial, verbal and adjectival reduplication, and numerals.

4.1.2.1 Ideophonic expressions

When expressing intensifying adverbs in English language, Zhiber & Korotina (2019) argue that the context and the precedent linguistic item determine the meaning and the connotation of intensifying adverbs. As mentioned in the introductory part, ideophonic adverbs are among the expressions which intensify adjectives and verbs or sometimes nouns. Crystal (1997:198)

describes an ideophone as a “...term used in linguistics and phonetics for any vivid representation of an idea in sound, such as occurs through onomatopoeia” It is a “a vivid representation of an idea in sound...a word, often onomatopoeic, which describes a predicate, qualificative or adverb in respect to manner, colour, sound, smell, action, state or intensity” (Doke 1935: 118, as cited in Voeltz and Kilian-Hatz 2001). In Bantu linguistics, Crystal specifies that an ideophone is “the name of a particular word class containing sound symbolic words”.

In Chasu, the study has revealed that there are several ideophonic adverbial elements which express intensity in different linguistics patterns. These expressions include pairs in which the intensifiers *twa*, *chi* and *chwe* modify adjectives or verbs. These adverbs express a sense of absoluteness for something that is ‘so colourful’ or ‘coloured’; ‘so black’, ‘dark’ or ‘dirty’; so ‘clean’ or ‘white’ respectively. The first expression involves an adjective with an ideophone which functions to intensify or modify adjectives. The major ones are adjectives of main colors such as red, black and white which co-occur with ideophones to express the intensity of the colour as in examples (4a-c).

- (4) a. *Sakame nkundu twa*
9.blood 9-red IDEO
‘The blood so red’
- b. *M-bora m-jiru chi*
1.girl 1-black IDEO
‘The girl so black/darkish’
- c. *Shuke ny-ewa chwe*
9. cloth 9-white IDEO
‘The cloth so white’

The second expression involves a verb co-occurring with an ideophonic adverb to express the intensity of the action in Chasu as in examples (5a-c). These are the same ideophonic expressions which co-occur with the adjectives of colour in (4a-c) above and they connote a synonymic meaning as (5a-c).

- (5) a. *Ma-embe e- Ø-rotom-e twa*
6.mango 6 PST-ripe-FV IDEO
‘Mangoes are so ripe/colourful/reddish’
- b. *Shuke i- Ø-jirar-e chi*
9.cloth 9-PST-dirty-FV IDEO
‘The cloth is very dirty’
- c. *Mazi i- Ø-eli-e chwe*
9.water 9-PST- clean-FV IDEO
‘The water is so clean’

These findings align with the study by Lusekelo (2010) on Kinyakyusa adverbs. He argues that ideophonic expression in Kinyakyusa function to intensify verbs as in: *Tu-tunywik-e tunyu* ‘we fell down heavily’ where the word *tunyu* is an ideophonic expression modifying the verb

tunywika ‘fall’. He also adds that ideophonic adverbs can also function to modify adjectives as in *umwa-ana-ke n-titu pii* ‘His/her child is very black’. The ideophone *pii* modifies the adjective *ntitu* ‘black’.

The third expression involves a verb attached with the intensifying morpheme **–ish-a** co-occurring with an ideophonic adverb to express a very high intensity of the action as in examples (6a-c).

- (6) a. *Sakame i- Ø-rotom ish-e twa*
9.blood 9-PST-red-INT-FV **IDEO**
‘The blood is so so reddish/colourful’
- b. *U-ni-oz-e ni-el-ish-e chwe*
2SG-1OPSG- wash-SBJ 1SG-clean- INT-SBJ **IDEO**
‘Wash me to be very very clean’
- c. *Mw-ango u- Ø-jirar-ish-e chi*
3.door 3-PST-dirty- INT **IDEO**
‘The door is very very dirty’

This expression is different from other studies like that of Lusekelo (2010) in Kinyakyusa and Bowler and Gluckman (2017) in Luhya languages where intensification is not expressed through the use of bound morphemes. In addition, the ideophonic adverbial expressions are same as those of Luhya languages in selecting verbs and adjectives to co-occur with. However, Chasu ideophones do not select nouns as in Luhya languages do.

Moreover, in this study we observed that Chasu expresses intensification through the use of adverbial ideophone which do not involve colours, or tidiness as in examples (7a-f).

- (7) a. *Mwango u- Ø-dind-i-e ndi*
3.door 3-PST- tight- FV **IDEO**
‘The door is **so** tight’
- b. *Mazi i- Ø- zu-e ndi*
9.water 9-PST-full-FV **IDEO**
‘The water is **so** full’
- c. *A- Ø-huzy-a chwi*
3SG-PRF-quite-FV **IDEO**
‘She is **so** quite’
- d. *Mazi i- Ø-ho-i-e do*
9.water 9- PST- cold- FV **IDEO**
‘The water is so/very cold’
- e. *Ma-hemba e-sh-a veke*
6.maize 6-hot-PRS-FV **IDEO**
‘The maize are so hot’

- f. *A-fikw-a tiki*
3SG- PRF-exhaust-FV **IDEO**
'She/he is **very/so** exhausted'

In (7a-f) the ideophonic adverbs select only a verb to co-occur with. These include adverbial ideophones such as *ndi* 'very tight or extremely full' as in (7a) and (b); *chwi* 'extremely quite' as in (7c); *do* 'very cold' as in (7e); *veke* 'very hot'; and *tiki* very tired as in (7f).

4.1.2.2 Adverbial expression

Like in other languages, Chasu is using adverbs as a strategy to express intensification. These adverbs precede verbs they are modifying as in (8a) *haiwa*; 'so much' and (8b) *pere*; 'complete'. While the adverb *haiwa* may modify a verb with the adverbial morpheme *-ish-a*, the adverb *pere* does not have a pattern that takes the adverbial morpheme. The adverb *haiwa* may also modify an adjective as in (8c) as it modifies the adjective 'beautiful'.

- (8) a. *E- Ø- m-kund-i-e haiwa*
3SG-PRS- OP3SG-love-FV **ADV**
'He/she loves him **so much**'
- b. *Ma-hemba a- Ø- si-a pere*
6.maize 6-PRF-finish-FV **ADV**
'Maize are **completely** finished'
- c. *M-bora w-ed-ish-a haiwa*
1.girl 1-beautiful-INT-FV **ADV**
'A **very very** beautiful girl'

The findings of this study in this part align with the study in Kinyakyusa by Lusekelo (2010) as shown in example *ba-gog-ile aka-kuku aka-nini fiijo*; 'They killed the very small hen'. The adverb *fiijo* 'much' intensifies the meaning of the adjective *akanini* 'small'.

4.1.2.3 Reduplication

Reduplication is one of the characteristics of Bantu languages (Ashton 1944). Reduplication occurs as a full or entire word stem or when part of a word is repeated to create a new form with modified meaning (Hurskainen 2024). It involves copying the entire word or stem or a partial phonological or morphological elements to express meanings like repetition or multiple occurrence of event (Gibson & Yoneda 2018), intensity, plurality, diminution or aspectual distinction, iterative or continuous action. Speaking of traditional Bantu grammars, Hyman (2008), claims that reduplication can be manifested in verbs, nouns, adjectives, numerals, pronouns, and demonstratives signifying specific semantic properties. However, based on the works by Downing (1997), verb duplication is widespread in the family of Bantu languages signifying that the action verb is done on a small scale, or little by little or from time to time. Ashton (1944) as cited in Lodhi (2004) stresses that reduplication is used to express various phases of intensiveness, including, to emphasize, to increase or extend the idea contained in the word, to express abundance or diversity; to lessen or modify the force of a word; to express continuous action, or state to express a distributive idea. In Chasu language, reduplication

occurs in form of verbs, adverbs, and numerals. Reduplication occurs as full reduplication of verb root as in the following constructions:

- (9) a. *Vana ve-lonza-lonza he mtaso*
'Children are **repetitively shouting** in church'
- b. *Tura-tonga-tonga he kiete mira si misi yose*
'We **frequently go** to the market but not everyday'

In example (9a), the verb *lonza* 'shout' the action is repetitively done to express continuity of action, while the *tonga* 'go' the action is repeated but in lesser force.

Reduplication in Chasu occurs through repetition of adverbs like in *fia* 'fast' occur and the repetition implies the action is done excessively fast and *mpoa* 'slowly' to imply that the action is done excessively slowly as in (10a) and (10b) respectively.

- (10) a. *Tongani fia-fia:*
'Go fast repeatedly'
- b. *Tula viogwe mpoa-mpoa*
'We eat potatoes very slowly'

Moreover, in Chasu, reduplication is also manifested through repetition of numerals like in (11a-b).

- (11) a. *Tuhandie mbeu mbiri-mbiri*
'We planted **two seeds distributively**'
- b. *Ngiani mmwe-mmwe*
'Get inside **one by one**'

The numerals in (11a) and 11(b) *mbiri* 'two' and *mwe* 'one' respectively are repetitions used to express distribution of action.

These examples indicated repetition or habitual action, and the action amplifies the action's force to do excessively or lesser. These findings align with the Swahili study by Makino (2014 & 2016) as he says that full reduplication involves the repetition of verb stem and can be used to convey habitual action or increase degree. Gibson and Yoneda (2018) add that in Swahili full verb reduplication used to convey multiple occurrence of an event or plurality of the event as in *Yule mbwa ana-bweka-bweka* 'That dog habitually barks'; The verb *bweka* 'bark' in this context is expressing that the action is done habitually.

5 Conclusion and recommendations

This study has attempted to examine the expression of intensification in Chasu language of Same District in Tanzania. The study sought to explore which strategies are used by Chasu speakers to express intensification in both written and spoken forms. The study has revealed

that Chasu language speakers are using both morphological and lexical strategies to express intensification, but there were some incidences with the interaction between morphological and lexical forms. Morphological strategy involves suffix *ish-a* attached to a verb root or adjective is used to express intensity of action. Lexical strategy has involved the use of adverb *haiwa* and *pere*, ideophonic adverbs *chwe*, *chi*, *twa* which involve colours, and *chwi*, *tiki*, *veke*, *do* which do not involve colours, and verbal and adverbial reduplication. There were few incidences of borrowed intensifiers *sana* and *kabisa* from Kiswahili. While other languages commonly use the lexical strategy to express intensification, this study contributes to the body of knowledge coming from the use of morphological strategy which might be a characteristic of Bantu languages due to their agglutinative nature of this language family. This study recommends further studies in other Bantu languages so as to come with examine strategies of how intensifiers are expressed, typology and their functions. In addition, a comparative study may be conducted to examine similarities and differences between Bantu and non-Bantu languages. Further studies can be done on expression of intensification to the endangered languages to document and to examine the impacts of multilingualism in those contexts.

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Rafiki Y. Sebonde
Department of Foreign Languages and Literature
The University of Dodoma
P.O. Box 259 Dodoma, Tanzania
e-mail: rafiki.sebonde@udom.ac.tz
rafikisebonde2@gmail.com

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Nominal Categories in Bishnupriya Manipuri and Manipuri

Thokchom Dhanapyari Devi, Manipur University, Imphal

Aheibam Linthoingambi Chanu, AICTE, Delhi

The title clearly reflects a comparative focus between Bishnupriya Manipuri (Indo-Aryan) and Manipuri (Tibeto-Burman). It explores typological distinctions between Indo-Aryan and Tibeto-Burman languages, focusing on number, gender, case, and pronoun systems. On the basis of primary field data and secondary sources, the study showed that although the two languages show superficial similarities as a result of prolonged contact, their underlying grammatical organization is remarkably different. The findings show that even in extreme contact zones, core morphosyntactic traits are resistant to contact-induced change. This study contributes to linguistics typology and contact linguistics by highlighting the limits of structural convergence.

Keywords: *Tibeto-Burman, Indo-Aryan, nominal categories, typology, morpho-syntax*

1 Introduction

This paper presents a comparative analysis of nominal categories in Bishnupriya Manipuri and Manipuri, two languages that co-exist geographically but belong to distinct language families—Indo-Aryan and Tibeto-Burman, respectively. While previous studies have described aspects of these languages independently, systematic comparison of their nominal systems remain limited.

Manipuri, also known as Meiteilon, functions as both the lingua franca and the official language of Manipur, and serves as the native language of the Meitei (Meetei) community. From a classificatory perspective, Paul K. Benedict places Manipuri within the Kuki-Naga subgroup of the Tibeto-Burman family, citing its structural similarities with related languages (Benedict 1972: 4-11). In contrast, George A. Grierson identifies Manipuri as an independent member of the Kuki-Chin group within the broader Tibeto-Burman language family (Grierson 1904: 1-5). The language possesses its own indigenous script, Meitei Mayek, and gained official recognition when it was included in the Eighth Schedule of the Constitution of India in 1992.

Bishnupriya Manipuri, also referred to simply as Bishnupriya, is the native language of the Bishnupriya community. It is classified within the Indo-Aryan language family, as reflected in the Census of India (2001). Historically, its origins have been linked to the Magadhan region, and it is often described as having developed through contact between Bengali and Meitei, while still preserving certain pre-Bengali linguistic features (Sinha 2017). The language is understood to have emerged in the region of Manipur.

According to the Census of India (2011), Bishnupriya Manipuri has a speaker population of 74,069 in India. Its speakers are distributed not only across parts of northeastern India—particularly Tripura and Assam—but also in Bangladesh. In Assam, significant concentrations are found in the districts of Cachar, Karimganj, and Hailakandi. In Tripura, Bishnupriya-speaking communities are commonly located in areas such as Dharmanagar, Kailashahar, Kamalpur, and West Tripura. Additionally, smaller populations of speakers are present in various parts of Meghalaya

This study is guided by three central research questions:

(1) How Bishnupriya Manipuri and Manipuri differ in their encoding of Number, Gender, and Case.

(2) to what extent these differences reflect genealogical affiliation as opposed to Areal contact.

(3) What these patterns reveal about typological alignment systems in contact zones.

From a typological standpoint, the comparison is particularly noteworthy, as it brings into focus the contrast between a Nominative–Accusative system and an Ergative–Absolutive system, while also considering the potential effects of contact-induced convergence.

The analysis adopts a functional-typological framework, situating the discussion within broader debates on alignment systems and language contact. Previous scholarship has demonstrated that, although lexical borrowing is frequent in contact settings, core morphosyntactic features, such as case alignment and agreement systems, tend to exhibit a high degree of stability (Comrie 1989: 35-45; Dixon 1994: 9-20; Thomason & Kaufman 1988: 14-15, 74-76). In line with these observations, the present study finds that, despite certain surface-level similarities arising from prolonged contact, the two languages remain fundamentally distinct in their underlying grammatical organization, particularly with regard to case marking and pronominal systems.

2 Literature Survey

Previous scholarship highlights the hybrid nature of Bishnupriya Manipuri and the typological distinctiveness of Manipuri. However, systematic comparative analyses of nominal categories remain limited, justifying the present study.

Language plays a crucial role in maintaining the cultural identity and distinctiveness of a community. This is particularly significant for minority groups, where language preservation becomes essential for cultural survival. Bishnupriya Manipuri, recognized by UNESCO as an endangered language, reflects this urgency for preservation.

The structure of Bishnupriya Manipuri reflects features associated with both Indo-Aryan and Tibeto-Burman language groups, indicating a history of sustained contact and interaction. In this regard, Gajarani (2004) observes that the language has been significantly influenced by Sanskrit, Maharashtri, and Sauraseni Prakrit, pointing to its Indo-Aryan heritage while also acknowledging external influences.

Bishnupriya Manipuri is generally classified as an Eastern Indo-Aryan language that has undergone extensive contact with Tibeto-Burman languages, particularly Meitei (Sinha 1981: 12). An early and comprehensive linguistic description is provided by Sinha (1960: 23), who identifies thirty-five phonemes in the language, including twenty-five consonants and eight vowels. His work also examines the phonological influence of Meitei on Bishnupriya Manipuri and offers a detailed account of nominal categories, including gender, number, case marking (including zero marking), pronouns, postpositional constructions, and verbal morphology.

Subsequent research has expanded on these descriptive foundations. Kalita et al. (2013) focus on the development of a Bishnupriya Manipuri corpus, with the aim of facilitating linguistic analysis through digitised textual data. Their findings indicate that gender is expressed through both lexical means (e.g. distinct forms such as *manu* ‘male’ and *jela*

‘female’) and morphological marking. The study also provides a descriptive account of case suffixes and mood markers, highlighting the language’s morphological richness.

More recent work by Thokchom & Chanu (2025) investigates gender distinction in Bishnupriya Manipuri from a morphological perspective. Their analysis shows that the language primarily relies on natural gender, particularly for animate referents, and employs a combination of strategies to mark gender. These include the use of lexical oppositions in kinship terms, the addition of suffixes, and the incorporation of gender-specific descriptive elements. While some nouns are inherently marked for gender, others remain neutral unless specified by contextual or morphological cues.

Research on Manipuri (Meitei), by contrast, has focused on its grammatical structure and categorisation. Purkayastha (2016) provides a computational perspective through part-of-speech tagging, identifying major word classes such as nouns, pronouns, verbs, modifiers, demonstratives, adverbs, particles, numerals, and reduplication, along with their grammatical properties and annotation processes. Similarly, Krishna B et. al (2012) examine nominal categories through the development of a finite-state morphological analyser, offering insights into the structural organisation of Manipuri nominal forms. Indrakumar Singh (2019) further contributes to this area by presenting a descriptive account of nominal morphology in Manipuri, focusing on categories such as gender, number, person, case, and numerals.

Collectively, these studies establish a robust foundation for analysing the nominal systems of both Bishnupriya Manipuri and Manipuri, while also underscoring the significant role of language contact in shaping their structural configurations.

3 Methodology

The data for the present study were drawn from both primary and secondary sources. Primary data were collected through fieldwork involving the documentation of basic lexical items and sentences from native speakers of Bishnupriya Manipuri and Manipuri. In order to capture a representative range of linguistic variation, speakers were selected from diverse age groups, social backgrounds, religious communities, and genders. Specifically, informants were drawn from three age groups, namely those above 50 years, those between 20 and 40 years, and those below 20 years, from Singari village in the Cachar district of Assam and from Imphal in Manipur.

Secondary data were obtained through a careful review of existing literature and archival materials. Sources such as the Census of India, the Linguistic Survey of India, and Benedict’s *Sino-Tibetan: A Conspectus* were consulted to provide historical and typological background on the languages under study. Nevertheless, greater emphasis was placed on primary data, particularly the spoken varieties, in order to reflect current linguistic usage.

Both direct and indirect methods of data collection were employed. The primary dataset included a range of verbal materials, such as narratives, proverbs, folktales, songs, and recorded conversations, which were preserved for further analysis. In addition, written texts and manuscripts were examined, and interviews were conducted to supplement the data. The analysis followed a qualitative approach, with secondary sources used to cross-check and validate the findings against contemporary language use.

4 Nominal Categories in Bishnupriya Manipuri and Manipuri

The term *noun classification* refers specifically to systems that involve the categorisation of nouns as linguistic forms, based on their morphological or phonological properties (Kilarski 2013: 1). Some of the morphosyntactic features of the languages under study are outlined below.

The Nouns of both the languages are inflected for number, case and gender. The instances are provided below:

4.1 Numbers

In linguistics, 'number' constitutes a core grammatical category that systematically encodes distinctions of quantity—most commonly singular and plural, and in certain languages, additional categories such as dual or trial through inflectional morphology and syntactic agreement across nouns, pronouns, adjectives, and verbs. It functions at the interface of semantics and morphosyntax, representing the cardinality of referents or events (e.g., 'dogs' vs. 'dogs') while contributing to the grammatical expression of individuation, plurality, and numerical reference within a language system.

4.1.1 Number in Bishnupriya Manipuri

Bishnupriya Manipuri exhibits a two-way number distinction, namely singular and plural. Plurality is primarily marked through suffixation, with forms such as *-gi* (as illustrated in examples (1) and *-lokei* as in examples (2)). In addition to morphological marking, plurality may also be expressed lexically through quantifiers such as *mahi* and *hani*, as demonstrated in examples (3) and (4).

Plural suffix */-gi/*

(1)	Singular	Plural
a.	<i>manu</i> man 'man'	<i>manu-gi</i> man-PL 'people'
b.	<i>kukur</i> dog 'dog'	<i>kukur-gi</i> dog-PL 'dogs'
c.	<i>muni</i> boy 'boy'	<i>muni-gi</i> boy-PL 'boys'

Plural Suffix */-lokei/*

(2)	Singular	Plural
a.	<i>bejok</i> brother-SG 'brother'	<i>bejok-lokei</i> brother-PL 'group of brothers'
b.	<i>mami</i>	<i>mami-nok-lokei</i>

aunty-SG 'aunty'	aunty- F- PL 'group of aunties'
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Quantifier /hani/

(3)	Singular	Plural
a.	<i>p^ham</i> bed 'bed'	<i>p^ham hani</i> bed QUANT 'some beds'
b.	<i>rupa</i> money 'money'	<i>rupa hani</i> money QUANT 'some money'

Quantifier /mahi/

(4)	Singular	Plural
a.	<i>kolom</i> pen 'pen'	<i>kolom mahi</i> pen QUANT 'many pens'
b.	<i>pahija</i> bird 'bird'	<i>pahija mahi</i> bird QUANT 'many birds'

Numerals

(5)	Singular	Plural
a.	<i>niɲol</i> girl 'girl'	<i>niɲol ʃfairi-go</i> girl four-CLF 'four girls'
b.	<i>atti</i> elephant 'elephant'	<i>atti noi-go</i> elephant nine-CLF 'nine elephants'

4.1.2 *Number in Manipuri*

Manipuri exhibits a relatively limited set of plural markers, primarily employing the suffixes *-siŋ* and *-k^hoi*. These suffixes function in distinct grammatical contexts. The suffix *-siŋ* is typically used with common nouns to indicate plurality, whereas *-k^hoi* is restricted in its distribution, occurring mainly with pronominal forms and proper nouns. This distinction reflects a functional differentiation in the plural marking system of the language.

Plural Suffix /siŋ/

(6)	Singular	Plural
a.	<i>nupa</i> man	<i>nupa-siŋ</i> man-PL

	man	‘men’
b.	<i>aŋaŋ</i> child ‘child’	<i>aŋaŋ-siŋ</i> child-two ‘children’

Plural Suffix /*kʰoi*/

(7)	Singular	Plural
a.	<i>naŋ</i> 2SG ‘you’	<i>na-kʰoi</i> 2SG-PL ‘you’
b.	<i>ma</i> 3SG ‘he/she’	<i>ma-kʰoi</i> 3SG-PL ‘they’

Plural Suffix /-*kʰoi*/

(8)	Singular	Plural
a.	<i>nupa</i> man ‘man’	<i>nupa-siŋ</i> man-PL ‘men’
b.	<i>aŋaŋ</i> child ‘child’	<i>aŋaŋ-siŋ</i> child-PL ‘children’

In example 8 (a), assimilation occurs due to the co-articulation of the final segments /*ŋ*/ and /*kʰ*/, both of which are articulated at the velar place of articulation. This shared phonetic environment facilitates the assimilatory process.

Quantifier /*majam*/

(9)	Singular	Plural
a.	<i>aŋaŋ</i> child ‘child’	<i>aŋaŋ majam</i> child QUANT ‘lots of children’
b.	<i>mi</i> person ‘person’	<i>mi jam (mi + majam)</i> person QUANT ‘a crowd of people’

In example (8a), the segments /*ŋ*/ (a velar nasal) and /*mj*/ (a bilabial nasal) occur in sequence; however, nasal place assimilation does not apply in this context. The phonological system of the language constrains such processes, preventing the nasal from altering its place of articulation to conform to the following consonant, and vice versa. This indicates a restriction on place assimilation across differing nasal articulations.

Example (8b) /*mijam*/ represents a compound form composed of two underlying lexemes: /*mi*/ ‘human’ and /*majam*/ ‘plural marker’. In the process of compounding, the initial syllable of the plural morpheme is elided. This reduction can be attributed to the tendency of homorganic sounds to co-occur and facilitate phonological simplification.

As a result, the derived form, /*mijam*/ exhibits a restructured syllabic pattern. The penultimate syllable remains open, with the vowel /*i*/ functioning as its nucleus, while the following syllable begins with the semivowel /*j*/ in the onset position. This reflects an interaction between morphological combination and phonological constraints in shaping the surface form.

Numerals¹

(10)	Singular	Plural
a.	<i>nupa</i> man-SG ‘a man’	<i>nupa-əni</i> man-two ‘two men’
b.	<i>aŋaŋ</i> child-SG ‘a child’	<i>aŋaŋ-əni</i> child-two ‘two children’

4.2 Gender

The term "gender" in linguistics describes a grammatical system that uses pronouns and adjectives that agree with nouns to classify them as masculine, feminine, or neuter. The relationship between numerous grammatical gender systems and biological sex, as well as other categories like size that support certain gender systems and have external correlates, are the earliest clear examples of its connections to the real world. While gender assignment to nouns is semantically apparent in many languages, it is opaquer in others.

4.2.1 Gender in Bishnupriya Manipuri

Bishnupriya Manipuri marks gender primarily through lexical and morphological means, rather than through a highly elaborated grammatical gender system. Gender distinctions are expressed through three main strategies: the use of contrasting lexical items in kinship terms, the inclusion of gender-specific descriptive modifiers for humans and animals, and the addition of suffixes such as *-i*, *-ni*, and *-nok*.

Certain nouns are inherently specified for gender and do not permit alternation—for instance, /*lerikula*/ ‘storyteller’, which is restricted to masculine reference—while others remain gender-neutral unless further specified by contextual or morphological cues. In addition, the language employs qualifying forms such as /*muni*/ and /*jela*/, which may occur alongside a noun (either preceding or following it) to indicate masculine and feminine reference respectively, for both human and non-human entities.

¹ Numerals may also function to express number, as is commonly observed in other Tibeto-Burman languages. In this language, however, numerals and plural markers are in complementary distribution and do not co-occur within the same syntactic environment. This restriction reflects a constraint in the grammatical encoding of number, whereby plurality is expressed either lexically through numerals or morphologically through plural marking, but not both simultaneously.

Kalita et al. (2013) further note that feminine forms can be derived morphologically through the addition of suffixes such as *-i*, *-ani*, and *-ni* to masculine bases. Overall, the system reflects a flexible interaction between lexical choice and morphological marking in the expression of gender.

Gender Term ‘*muni*’ and ‘*jela*’

- (10)
- | | |
|----|---|
| a. | <i>hoba muni-daktar-go</i>
good male- doctor-CLF
‘A good male doctor’ |
| b. | <i>muni sau-go</i>
male child-CLF
‘A boy’ |
| c. | <i>hoba jela sau-go</i>
good female child-CLF
‘A good girl’ |
| d. | <i>sik^hito jela-go</i>
educated female-CLF
‘An educated teacher’ |

Gender Affix /-*nok*/

Both the younger and older relationships on the maternal side might have the suffix *-nok* added to them to mark feminine gender. However, it can only be utilized to mark feminine gender with the elder one on the paternal side. For instance:

- (11)
- | | | |
|----|---|--|
| a. | Masculine
<i>mamak</i>
‘paternal uncle’ | Feminine
<i>maminok</i>
‘paternal aunty’ |
| b. | <i>baginak</i>
‘cousin brother’ | <i>baginok</i>
‘cousin sister’ |

Gender Affix /*i*/ or /-*ni*/

- (12)
- | | | |
|----|--|--|
| a. | Masculine
<i>ƒamar</i>
cobbler
‘male cobbler’ | Feminine
<i>ƒamar-ni</i>
cobbler-F
‘female cobbler’ |
| b. | <i>mekur</i>
cat
‘he-cat’ | <i>mekur-i</i>
cat-F
‘she-cat’ |

Pair terms

- (13)
- | | | |
|--|-----------|----------|
| | Masculine | Feminine |
|--|-----------|----------|

- | | | |
|----|---------------------------|--------------------------|
| a. | <i>bejak</i>
'brother' | <i>benok</i>
'sister' |
| b. | <i>ima</i>
'mother' | <i>baba</i>
'father' |

Adjectives

Gender is marked by a limited set of adjectives that suggest age differences; these adjectives are only used with animate nouns, as in 14 (a) and (b).

(14)		Masculine	Feminine
	a.	<i>jet^ha muni-go</i> elder male-CLF 'elder male'	<i>jet^hi niŋol-go</i> elder female-CLF 'elder female'
	b.	<i>k^hula muni sau-go</i> younger male child-CLF 'younger male'	<i>k^huli niŋol sau-go</i> younger girl child-CLF 'younger female'

4.2.2 Gender in Manipuri

There is no grammatical gender system in Manipuri. The language has natural gender like other Tibeto-Burman languages such as Anal, Zeme, Koirang, Paite, and Thadou. The three primary ways that a gender distinction is expressed are through the use of opposing words in kinship phrases, gender-specific descriptive adjectives for people, animals, and birds, and suffixes (-*pi/pa*) or (-*bi/-ba*). Some nouns are inherently masculine or feminine and cannot be changed, e.g. /*u su-ba*/ 'carpenter' (masculine) and /*jum sa-ba*/ 'builder' (masculine).

Gender Term /*labə*/ and /*əmom*/

(15)	a.	<i>hui labə</i>	<i>əma</i>	<i>k^hoŋ-li</i>	
		dog male	one	bark-SIM.ASP	
		'A he-dog barks'			
	b.	<i>hui əmom</i>	<i>əma</i>	<i>k^hoŋ-li</i>	
		dog male	one	bark-SIM.ASP	
		'A he-dog barks'			
	c.	<i>*nupi</i>	<i>əmom</i>	<i>əma</i>	<i>k^hoŋ-li</i>
		Woman	female one	bark-	SIM.ASP
		'A woman barks'			

From the above example the study has concluded that the gender term /*labə*/ and /*əmom*/ can only be used with non-human nouns.

Gender affix /-*pi~pa*/ or /-*bi~ba*/

(16)		Masculine	Feminine
	a.	<i>isəi-sək-pa</i> song-sing-M 'male singer'	<i>isəi-sək-pi</i> song-sing-F 'female singer'
	b.	<i>hənu-ba</i> old-M 'old man'	<i>hənu-bi</i> old-F 'old woman'

Pair Terms

(17)		Masculine	Feminine
	a.	<i>pak^haŋ</i> 'bachelor'	<i>ləisabi</i> 'maiden'
	b.	<i>piba</i>	<i>niŋol</i>

‘son’

‘daughter’

4.3 Case

Within the generative framework developed by Chomsky, particularly in Government and Binding theory and the subsequent Minimalist Program, Case (often capitalized to distinguish it from morphological case) is analysed as an abstract grammatical feature that plays a crucial role in licensing noun phrases or determiner phrases within syntactic structure. Rather than being limited to a surface morphological marker, Case is understood as a structural requirement that ensures noun phrases are properly integrated into a sentence (Chomsky 1981: 170, Chomsky 1995: 110–115).

According to Case Theory, every overt noun phrase must receive or check an appropriate Case feature in order to be syntactically well formed and interpretable at the interfaces of grammar. If a noun phrase is not assigned Case, the derivation fails, resulting in ungrammaticality. In this way, Case functions as a fundamental constraint on syntactic representation, linking structural position with grammatical legitimacy (Chomsky 1981: 49–50, Chomsky 1995: 111–113).

The following section examines the case systems of two languages belonging to the Indo-Aryan languages and Tibeto-Burman languages families in order to explore their similarities and differences.

4.3.1 Case in Manipuri

Manipuri has Ergative-Absolutive pattern.

Ergative: It describes a grammatical pattern where the subject of an intransitive clause is handled differently from an intransitive subject and similarly to the object of a transitive phrase. (Dixon 1994:6)

(18) *tombə-ø* *cət-k^hre*
Tomba-ABS go-PRF.ASP
‘Tomba went’

(19) *məjtəj -ø* *tombə -ø* *p^hu-i*
Chaoba-ERG Meitei-ABS beat-SIM.ASP
‘Meitei beats Tomba’

The subject (S) ‘Tomba’ of intransitive verb in example (18) receives the same morphological treatment as the object (O) ‘tombə’ of transitive verb in example (19).

Suffix *-nə*

The suffix *-nə* occur with the subject of intransitive verbs.
For instance:

(20) a. *cəwbə-nə* *hei-du* *ca-k^hre*
Chaoba-CONT fruit-DET eat-PRF.ASP
‘It’s none other than Tomba who ate the fruit’
b. *aŋaŋ-nə* *kəp-k^hi*
child-CONT cry-PRF.ASP
‘It was none other than the child who cried’

The suffix *-nə* indicates contrastive values in the above sentences. (Chelliah 1997: 67).

The above two Sentences show that the actor is sole individual in the group who perform the act indicated by the full verbal predicate. Therefore suffix *-nə* in the above sentences is not a case marker. Hence, the subject of intransitive verb remains unmarked for case.

Suffix *-bu~pu*

The suffix *bu~pu* is not a case marker. Hence, the object of transitive verb remains unmarked for case receiving the same treatment as the subject of intransitive verb in sentence. Instances are given below:

- (21) a. *cawbə-nə tomba-bu ta-tʰi*
Chaoba-ERG Tomba-ADVS ill-treat-SIM.ASP
‘Chaoba beats (particularly) Tomba’
- b. *ləirik-pu segəi-je*
book-ADVS tear-PRF.ASP
‘He/she tears the book’ (contrary to expectation)

- Instrumental Case

In Manipuri, the instrumental case is additionally marked by the suffix *-nə*, which functions to indicate the means or instrument associated with an action. For instance:

- (22) a. *tombə-nə caobə-(bu) tʰaŋ-nə tʰil-li*
Tomba-ERG Chaoba-ACC knife-INS stab-PROG.ASP
‘Tomba stabs Chaoba with a knife’
- b. *u ədu horəi-nə lel-li*
tree det saw-INS cut-PROG.ASP
‘The tree was cut by a saw’
- b. *hei ədu tʰaŋ-nə kʰə-i*
fruit DET knife-INS cut-PROG.ASP
‘The fruits are cut with a Knife’

- Genitive case

The language marks a noun or pronoun with the genitive case marker to indicate the possessor of the referent of another noun or to express an associative relation between the marked noun or pronoun and another noun or pronoun.

The suffix *-gi~ki* is used in Manipuri to signal genitive case, ‘*tombə-gi*’ (Tomba’s), ‘*məhak-ki*’ (his/her).

To indicate possessor

- (23) a. *əy-gi hui*
1SG-GEN dog
‘My dog’
- b. *tombə-gi pʰurit*

Tomba-GEN shirt
‘Tomba’s shirt’

To indicate associative relation

- (24) a. *jum-gi* *məniŋ*
house-GEN back
‘the back of the house’
b. *tʰəmoi-gi* *kacɪn*
heart-GEN corner
‘in a corner of heart’

- Associative Case

The associativity is shown by suffixing a bound morpheme *-gə~kə*, ‘*caoba-gə*’ (with *chaoba*) ‘*məhak-kə*’ (with him/her) in Manipuri.

- (25) a. *əy-ø* *tombə-gə* *cət-li*
1SG-ERG Tomba-ASS go-PROG.ASP
‘I go with Tomba’
b. *cawba-gə* *mani-gə* *lak-le*
Chaoba-ASS Mani-ASS come-PRF.ASP
‘Chaoba and Mani came’

- Locative Case

The suffix *-də~tə* is used to signal the locative case in Manipuri. For instance:

- (26) a. *.əy-ø* *iskul-də* *cət-li*
1SG-ERG School-LOC go-PROG.ASP
‘I go to school’
b. *tombə-ø* *pʰəmuŋ-matʰak-ta* *pʰəm-e*
Tomba-ERG bed- POST-LOC sit-SIM.ASP
‘Tomba sits on the bed’

- Ablative Case

The suffix *-dəgi~təgi* is used as ablative in Manipuri. For instance:

- (27) a. *nəŋ-gi* *siŋjəŋ-dəgi* *əe-gi* *jopək-nə* *hennə* *pʰe-i*
2SG-GEN axe-ABL 1SG-ACC shovel-NMmuch good-SIM.ASP
‘My shovel is better than your axe’
b. *tʰoibə-dəgi* *məhak-ki* *wari* *pumbə* *kʰəŋ-le*
Thoiba-ABL 3SG-GEN story all know-ASP
‘I have known the story about him/her from Thoiba’

4.3.2 *Case in Bishnupriya Manipuri*

Bishnupriya Manipuri inflects nouns for seven cases. In contrast to Manipuri, Bishnupriya Manipuri features a Nominative-Accusative case structure.

- Nominative Case

The suffixes /-j/ and /-e ~ i/ are used to mark the nominative case in Bishnupriya Manipuri. They are attached only to a Noun (+human) but not found in Noun (-human). However, the pronoun and the subject of the intransitive verb are not overtly marked with the nominative case marker in the language. For instance:

- (28)
- | | | | | | |
|----|--------------------------|-----------------|------------------------|-------------------|-----------------|
| a. | <i>caoba-i</i> | | <i>lerik</i> | <i>ahan</i> | <i>pako-er</i> |
| | Chaoba NOM | | book | one | read-PRS.IPFV |
| | ‘Chaoba reads a book’ | | | | |
| b. | <i>soma-i</i> | | <i>bat radi-r-i</i> | | |
| | Soma-NOM | | rice cook-PRS-IPFV. 3F | | |
| | ‘Soma cooks food’ | | | | |
| c. | <i>ram-e</i> | | <i>lerik</i> | <i>ahan</i> | <i>pakor-er</i> |
| | Ram NOM | | book | one | read-PRS.IPFV |
| | ‘Ram reads a book’ | | | | |
| d. | <i>kim-e</i> | <i>caoba-re</i> | | <i>kila-r</i> | |
| | Kim-NOM | chaoba-ACC | | beat-PRS.IPFV | |
| | ‘Kim beats Chaoba’ | | | | |
| e. | <i>rani-j</i> | <i>ela</i> | <i>ahan</i> | <i>di-r-i</i> | |
| | Rani-NOM | song | one | give-PRS.IPFV-3F | |
| | ‘Rani is singing a song’ | | | | |
| f. | <i>joni -j</i> | | <i>pani</i> | <i>pi-ri</i> | |
| | joni-NOM | | water | drink-PRS.IPFV-3F | |
| | ‘Joni drinks water’ | | | | |
| g. | <i>cawba gundz-er</i> | | | | |
| | Chaoba-NOM | | | sleep-PRS-IPFV | |
| | ‘Chaoba is sleeping’ | | | | |
| h. | <i>ta</i> | <i>upeit</i> | <i>ji-toi-ga</i> | | |
| | he | there | go-FUT-NMLZ | | |
| | ‘He will go there’ | | | | |
-
- | | | | | |
|----|------------------|--------------|-------------|-----------------|
| a. | * <i>caoba-j</i> | <i>lerik</i> | <i>ahan</i> | <i>pakor-er</i> |
| b. | * <i>rita-e</i> | <i>lerik</i> | <i>ahan</i> | <i>pakoriri</i> |
| c. | * <i>ram-i</i> | <i>lerik</i> | <i>ahan</i> | <i>pakor-er</i> |

The above examples illustrate that the nominative case agrees with gender in Bishnupriya Manipuri. The nominative suffix /-i/ is used with the proper noun which ends with the vowel /a/. The nominative suffix /-e/ is used with the proper noun which ends with consonants. And the nominative suffix /-j/ is used specifically with the proper noun which ends with a consonant /i/. The subject of example 1 (g) is not marked as the verb is intransitive.

Note: Nominative case is not overtly assigned to the personal pronouns of the language. For instance: *ta merik ahan pakorer* (he reads a book).

Nominative case marker as focus marker (Dual role of nominative case marker in Bishnupriya Manipuri)

The nominative case is not obligatory in the language. However, it becomes mandatory if the emphasize or more focus is given to the subject (agent) of the verb. For instance:

- (29) a. *rita-ø* *tanu-re* *bazar-e* *dek^h-l-i*
rita-null case them-Acc bazaar-LOC see-PST.3F
‘Rita saw them in the bazaar’
b. *ram-e sou-go* *dek^h-l-o*
ram-NOM child-CLF saw-PST.3M
‘It was none other than ram who saw the child’

- Accusative Case

The suffix *-re* is used to mark accusative marker in Bishnupriya Manipuri. For instance:

- (30) a. *ta* *ama-re* *bara-r*
He 1PL-ACC beat-PRS
‘He beats us’
b. *ram-e* *akaf-re* *bara-r*
Ram-NOM Akash-ACC beat-PRS
‘Ram beats Akash’

- Instrumental Case

Bishnupriya Manipuri uses a suffix *-lo* to signal instrumental case. For instance:

- (31) a. *mi* *caku-han-lo* *p^hol-go* *kap-l-u*
I Knife-DET-INS fruit-DET cut-PST-1SG
‘I cut the fruit with a knife’
b. *ami* *hil-lo* *mandir-go* *hoŋ-kor-l-aŋ*
we stone-INS temple-CLF build-do-PST-3PL
‘We build the temple with stone’
c. *mi* *mekur-go-re* *barigol-lo* *bare-l-u*
I dog-CLF-ACC stick-INS beat-PST-1SG
‘I beat the dog with a stick’

- Genitive Case

In Bishnupriya Manipuri, a suffix *-r* is used to signal genitive case, *rani-r* ‘Rani’s’, *tei-r* ‘his’. Similar to Manipuri, the genitive marker is employed to denote both the associative relationship and the possession.

To indicate possessor

- (32) a. *kukur-go-r* *les-go*
Dog-CLF-GEN tail-CLF
‘The dog’s tail’
b. *tei-r* *malok*

3SG-GEN mother
'Her mother'

To indicate associative relation

- (33) a. *sorkar-go-r* *sompat*
government-CLF-GEN property
‘Government’s property’
- b. *prinsipl-go-r* *kut^ha-go*
principal-CLF-GEN room-CLF
‘principal’s room’

The above examples show that Bishnupriya Manipuri inserts a classifier *-go* while attaching genitive case marker to the (–human) noun.

- Associative Case

In contrast to Manipuri, Bishnupriya Manipuri indicates associativity by using the independent word "*loge*" (with), which comes right before the verb. For instance:

- (34) *mi tar* *loge* *ahe-s-il-u*
1 him ASS come-PRF-PST.1SG
‘I came with him’

- Locative Case

In Bishnupriya Manipuri, the suffix *-e* is used to signal locative case.

- (35) a. *tanu ama-r gor-e ai-la*
they 1PL-GEN house-LOC come-PST.3.PL
‘They come to our house’
- b. *rita-i tanu-re bazar-e dehe-s-il-i*
Rita-NOM 3PL-ACC bazaar-LOC see-PRF-PST-3F
‘Rita saw them in the bazaar’

- Ablative Case

A word that signifies separation takes the ablative case. The suffix *-to* is used as ablative in Bishnupriya Manipuri.

- (36) a. *mi tor jari-hana-to hai jari-han harpe-l-u*
I you word-CLF -ABL fact word-CL know-PST-1SG
‘I have known the truth from your word’
- b. *banglades indija-to 1971 alade os-e*
Bangladesh india-ABL 1971 separate become-PST
‘Bangladesh was separated from India in 1971’

4.4 Post-Position in Manipuri and Bishnupriya Manipuri

Both Bishnupriya Manipuri and Manipuri make extensive use of postpositions in their grammatical structure.

In Manipuri, verbal objects may simultaneously bear case-marking suffixes alongside overt postpositions, indicating a layering of morphological and syntactic marking within the case system.

- (37) a. *tebəl* *mat^hək-tə*
table POST-LOC
‘on the table’
- b. *u* *mak^hə-də*
tree POST-LOC
‘under the tree’

Bishnupriya Manipuri has overt postpositions. Unlike Manipuri, the object does not bear any case marking suffix. For instance:

- (38) a. *gas-jarir pit^hit*
tree-DET POST
‘behind that tree’
- b. *clas-hanor* *bitore*
class-POSS. POST
‘inside the class’

4.4.1 *Uses of post-position at the sentence level in Manipuri*

At the sentence level, post-positions in Manipuri function as key grammatical devices that encode spatial relations, locative reference, and broader syntactic relations among constituents. In contrast to English prepositions, which precede their complements, Manipuri post-positions follow the noun phrase and frequently co-occur with case markers to yield semantically precise locative expressions such as ‘on’, ‘in’, ‘under’, and ‘inside’. From a structural perspective, these forms are not merely adjunct elements but are integral to clause organization, as they contribute to the explicit marking of relational meaning. Consequently, post-positional constructions play a central role in disambiguating argument structure and in establishing clear semantic and syntactic relationships within the sentence. For instance:

- (39) a. *hui-ado* *tebəl* *mat^hək-tə* *lei*
dog-DET table POST-LOC has-SIM.ASP
‘The dog is on the table’
- b. *ŋə* *əmə* *cəp^hu* *manuŋ-də* *lei*
fish one pitcher POST-LOC has-SIM.ASP
‘A fish is in the pitcher’

4.4.2 *Uses of post-position at the sentence level in Bishnupriya Manipuri*

In comparison with Manipuri, post-positional constructions in Bishnupriya Manipuri show both structural similarities and typological distinctions shaped by their different genealogical origins. Bishnupriya Manipuri tends to integrate post-positions more closely with nominal morphology, often in conjunction with possessive or classifier markers, thereby encoding locative relations within a more compact morphological structure. In contrast, Manipuri

(Meitei) typically employs post-positions alongside overt locative case markers, resulting in a comparatively more analytic pattern.

- (40) a. *lerik-han tebul hanor goje-as-e*
book-CL table POSS POST-IPFV-PRS-3p
'The book is on the table'
- b. *p^hol-go polit^hin-go bitor-as-e*
fruit-CL plasticbag-CLF POST-IPF-PRS.3P
'The fruit is in the plastic bag'

4.5 Pronouns in Bishnupriya Manipuri and Manipuri

The pronominal inventory of each language comprises of personal pronouns, relative pronouns, demonstrative pronouns, reflexive pronouns and interrogative pronouns. Some of these pronouns are discussed below.

4.5.1 Personal Pronouns

The personal pronouns of Bishnupriya Manipuri and Manipuri are given below in Table 1.

Table 1: Personal pronouns of Bishnupriya Manipuri and Manipuri

Bishnupriya Manipur					Manipuri					
Pers on	No m	Acc	Dat	Gen	NO M	Acc	Dat	Gen	Dual	Hono rific
1SG	<i>mi</i>	<i>more</i>	<i>more</i>	<i>mor</i>	<i>əy</i>	<i>əy-bu</i>	<i>əyŋon- da</i>	<i>əy-gi</i>	<i>eban-ni</i>	–
2SG	<i>ti</i>	<i>tore</i>	<i>tore</i>	<i>tor</i>	<i>naŋ</i>	<i>naŋ-bu</i>	<i>naŋ- ŋon-da</i>	<i>naŋ-gi</i>	<i>naba-ni</i>	-
3SG	<i>tei/t a</i>	<i>tare/ teire</i>	<i>tare/ teire</i>	<i>tar/tei r</i>	<i>mah ak</i>	<i>mahak- pu</i>	<i>maŋon- da</i>	<i>mahak- ki</i>	<i>maba- ni</i>	<i>ədom- gi/so m- gi</i>
1PL	<i>ami</i>	<i>amare</i>	<i>ama re</i>	<i>amar</i>	<i>əy- k^hoi</i>	<i>əy-k^hoi- bu</i>	<i>əy-ŋon- da</i>	<i>əy-k^hoi- gi</i>	<i>əy-k^hoi- ni</i>	
2PL	<i>tumi</i>	<i>tumar e</i>	<i>tanu re</i>	<i>tumar</i>	<i>nak^h oi</i>	<i>nak^hoi- bu</i>	<i>nak^hoi- da</i>	<i>nak^hoi- gi</i>	<i>nak^hoi- ni</i>	
3PL	<i>tanu</i>	<i>tanure</i>		<i>tanur</i>	<i>mak^h oi</i>	<i>mak^hoi- bu</i>	<i>mak^hoi- da</i>	<i>mak^hoi- gi</i>	<i>mak^hoi- ni</i>	

4.5.2 Demonstrative Pronouns

The demonstrative pronoun in Bishnupriya Manipuri language is used with the classifiers *ta*, *go*, *han/ ago* (this), *outa* (these), *ougo* (that), *outa* (that).

The demonstrative pronoun in the Manipuri language is *masi* (this), *mak^hoi siŋ* (these), *madu* (that), *madu-sinŋ* (those). The plural suffix 'siŋ' is attached to the root in order to make the plural demonstrative pronoun.

4.5.3 Relative Pronoun

In Bishnupriya Manipuri, we find both participial relative clauses and relative pronoun *je*, *jego*, *jehan*, *jeta* and correlative *o*, *ou*, *ogo*, *ohān*.

- (41) a. *mala oiltai ou niḡol ugo jegot jari mi dou-ri-ta*
Mala DET REL girl that whom word 1 talk-PST.IPFV-CLF
‘Mala is the girl whom I was talking about’
b. *ti jeta manouri misti uta ahul-de*
2 REL like sweet those take-PERM
‘You can take whichever sweet you like’

In Manipuri, the relative clause can be created by either utilising the quotative *-haibə*" or nominalising the sentence's verb. These clauses alter a head noun and frequently come before it, much like adjectives. Manipuri employs a process of nominalisation to form the subordinate clause rather than using a relative pronoun like "who" or "that" as some other languages do.

- (42) *əi-nə haiba nupa ədu cawba asi-ni*
1-ERG say man that chaoba this-COP
‘Chaoba is the boy whom I was talking about’

4.5.4 Interrogative pronouns

The interrogative pronouns formed with the help of classifiers show animacy distinctions in Bishnupriya Manipuri as ‘*kungo*’ ‘who’ denotes an ‘animate’ and ‘*kihān*’, ‘*kitā*’ ‘what’ refer to ‘inanimate’. Manipuri also has interrogative pronouns. However, unlike Bishnupriya Manipuri, it does not use any classifiers while forming interrogative pronouns. The personal pronouns of Bishnupriya Manipuri and Manipuri are given below:

Table 2: Interrogative Pronoun in Bishnupriya Manipuri and Manipuri

Pronoun	Bishnupriya Manipuri	Manipuri
who	<i>kungo</i>	<i>kəna</i>
what	<i>kihān/ kitā</i>	<i>kəri</i>
which	<i>kun</i>	<i>kəraṃbə</i>
how much	<i>koti</i>	<i>kəjam</i>
how	<i>kisade</i>	<i>kəmdouna</i>
when	<i>kundin</i>	<i>kəraṃbə mətəm-da</i>
where	<i>kumpei</i>	<i>kədaida</i>
why	<i>kitaja</i>	<i>kəriḡi</i>

5 Discussion

The comparative analysis indicates that the differences between Bishnupriya Manipuri and Manipuri are rooted in deeper typological distinctions rather than merely superficial variation. Bishnupriya Manipuri displays features characteristic of Indo-Aryan languages, including a Nominative–Accusative alignment and a more elaborated system of number and honorific distinctions, whereas Manipuri aligns more closely with typological patterns associated with Tibeto-Burman languages.

Despite extended geographical proximity and sustained sociolinguistic interaction, the two languages exhibit minimal structural convergence. Although lexical borrowing and the adoption of quantifier-based plural marking indicate some level of contact influence, fundamental grammatical domains—such as case marking and pronominal systems—remain largely unaffected. This pattern reinforces the widely accepted view that morphosyntactic alignment is comparatively resistant to contact-induced change, especially when contrasted with the greater susceptibility of the lexicon.

Moreover, the use of dual number and honorific distinctions in Manipuri points to a degree of grammatical elaboration that is not paralleled in Bishnupriya Manipuri. This imbalance indicates that language contact does not inevitably result in structural simplification or levelling; rather, it can allow distinct typological features to persist, maintaining differences between the languages.

This observation aligns with typological accounts of alignment systems (Dixon, 1994:6; Bernard Comrie 1989:125) and research on language contact (Thomason and Kaufman 1988:74), all of which emphasize the relative stability of core grammatical features. The present data therefore contribute to ongoing discussions about the limits of structural convergence in situations of sustained language contact.

6 Conclusion

This study offers a typological comparison of nominal categories in Bishnupriya Manipuri and Manipuri, showing that, despite prolonged contact, the two languages remain fundamentally distinct in their grammatical organisation. Bishnupriya Manipuri follows typical Indo-Aryan patterns, characterised by nominative–accusative alignment and a comparatively less complex nominal system. In contrast, Manipuri displays key Tibeto-Burman features, including ergative–absolutive alignment, a three-way number distinction, and a more elaborated honorific system.

The findings suggest that although language contact can give rise to similarities at the surface level, underlying morphosyntactic structures tend to remain relatively stable and resistant to change. This reinforces the distinction in contact linguistics between superficial convergence and the persistence of deeper structural properties.

By situating the analysis within a typological framework, this study contributes our understanding of how languages in contact can preserve their structural identities while simultaneously sharing lexical and functional features. It highlights the dynamic balance between stability and interaction in multilingual settings. Future research could extend this comparison to the domain of verbal morphology and examine diachronic developments in greater depth, thereby offering a more comprehensive account of language change and contact-induced variation.

Abbreviations

- 1-First Person
- 2-Second Person
- 3-Third Person
- SG-Singular
- PL-Plural

CLF-Classifier
M-Masculine
F-Feminine
SIM-Simple
ASP-Aspect
PERF-Perfect
INS-Instrumental
ERG-Ergative
ADVS-Adversative
GEN-Genitive
PROG-Progressive
ASS-Associative
PRF-Perfect
POST- post-position
ACC-Accusative
ABL-Ablative
PRS-Present
PST-Past
DET-Determiner
NOM-Nominative
IPFV-Imperfective
FUT-Future
NMLZ-Nominalizer
PST-Past
LOC-Locative
CONT-Contrastive
POSS-Possessive
REL-Relative

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Thokchom Dhanapyari Devi
Khurai Puthiba, Imphal East
795010 Arambam Leirak
Manipur
India
e-mail: dhanapyarithokchom16@gmail.com

Aheibam Linthoingambi Chanu
124c, Room no.14c, Major Nihal Singh Complex
Katwaria sarai, New Delhi
110016 Katwaria Sarai Bus stand
Delhi
India
e-mail: linthoiaheibam77@gmail.com

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Elision in Nzema

John Nyame

University of Education, Winneba, Ghana

This paper examines elision as a syllable structure process in Nzema, a Niger-Congo (Kwa, Bia) language spoken mainly in the Western Region of Ghana and the Ivory Coast. The paper discusses some phonological and morphological factors that necessitate elision in Nzema. The paper discusses the processes involved in elision and the contexts within which the phenomenon occurs in Nzema. It first considers V_1 and V_2 elision in some phrasal and compound constructions. It also discusses syllable elision that operates within words. The paper shows that segments, syllables, and tones are affected by elision. It is observed that although elision is purely phonological, it is also motivated by morphological factors as vowels interact during compounding, and at word boundary. The analysis shows that in Nzema, morpheme2-initial Vs (i.e., V_2) can be targeted for deletion in compounds and across word boundary, while elision of the first vowel, V_1 , only occurs across word boundary. Again, syllables that are lost word internally are compensated for by lengthening the initial vowel, V_1 of the word. Moreover, in a context of $V_1\#V_2$ where the two vowels are of the same quality, the target for the deletion process is determined by tone. The findings show a link between the phonology and morphology of Nzema in the analysis of elision.

Keywords: *Compounds, Nzema, elision, tone, syllable structure process*

1 Introduction

This paper examines elision as a syllable structure process which is observed in the formation of some compounds and phrases in Nzema, a Niger-Congo (Kwa, Bia) language spoken mainly in the Western Region of Ghana and the Ivory Coast. Nzema has five major dialects, namely Dwɔmɔɔ, Ɛlɛmgbelɛ, Adwɔmɔɔ, Egila, and Ɛvaloɛ. Nzema is one of the minority languages in Ghana that has very little literature, particularly in the area of phonology. In fact, works such as Owusu Ansah (2020), Amoh (2017), Abdul-Rahman (2013), Sibanda (2009), Abakah (2004), etc., attest to the fact that elision is a common phenomenon in most languages of the world. However, this linguistic phenomenon has not been explored in Nzema. It is therefore important to note how it operates in Nzema.

The data for this study were collected from primary sources. The information was gathered from native speakers of Nzema in the Department of Akan-Nzema Education, College of Languages Education, Ajumako. It was recorded using a tape recorder and later transcribed onto a computer. The transcribed data were cross-checked with two Nzema lecturers who are native speakers to ensure consistency and accuracy.

The paper first describes the phenomenon of elision in Nzema and finally analyses the data within the theoretical framework of autosegmental phonology (Goldsmith, 1976). Elision that targets the final V of the first syllable and the initial V of the second syllable are first discussed. The paper also considers syllable elision within words. Vowel-vowel sequence, particularly at the boundary of words and in compounds, constitutes a dispreferred configuration in most languages (Siptár 2005). As a result, Nzema deletes one of the two closely adjacent vowels.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides a brief overview of the Nzema syllable structure and elision in general. Section 3, on the other hand, looks at elision

in consecutive constructions, possessive constructions, progressive constructions, perfective constructions, and verbal noun constructions. Section 4 focuses on elision in noun-noun and noun-adjective compounds. Section 5 discusses syllable-final high vowel elision. Section 6 discusses word internal syllable elision. Section 7 looks at twin vowel elision, and finally, Section 8 concludes the study.

2 Syllable structure of Nzema

I present the syllable structure of Nzema briefly in this section. The syllable structure types in Nzema, according to Nyame (2019), are the CV, V, and N. However, among the attested syllable types, N as a syllable type is yet to be attested (see, for example, Clements & Keyser 1983:29).

Thus, based on current data, I propose an alternative presentation of what has been provided by Nyame (2019). Therefore, the syllable structures in Nzema include the V, CV, and CVC. The segments dominated by a C-element are [+consonantal], and the segments dominated by a V-element are [+syllabic]. Consider the example (1) below.

(1) Syllable types in Nzema

CV— /d́á/ ‘to sleep’
/b́ó / ‘to beat’
/d́ó/ ‘to weed’

The CV syllable type is primarily made up of a consonant, which serves as the onset, and a vowel, which serves as the nucleus, as shown above.

(2) V— /e/, /ɛ/, /a/, /n/, /m/, /ŋ/, /ɲ/

/è.tú/ ‘gun’, /è.dà/ ‘bow’, /à.wà/ ‘calabash’, /ñ.zá/ ‘wine’, /m.gbá/ ‘guinea worm’,
/ŋ.gà.kà.dzè.lé/ ‘red ant’, /ɲ.vó.á.lí/ ‘stench’, /kà.n.dà.lè/ ‘bush fowl’, /kpò.m.gbà/
‘to sew’

The V syllable type is primarily occupied by segments that are [+syllabic], without an onset. We observe that these ([+syllabic]) segments can be either vowels or sonorant consonants, which are only nasals. The nasals have free distribution and therefore can serve as the onset, nucleus and coda.

(3) CVC- /kún.dúm/ ‘a kind of festival’

/n.zèm.dɛ/ ‘humour’

The constituents of the CVC syllable type include an onset, a vowel nucleus, and a coda. The syllable types above show that, currently, consonant clusters are not allowed in the language. It should be noted that Nzema allows only the alveolar nasal /n/ and bilabial nasal /m/ in coda positions. All other nasal consonants can occur syllable-initial as onsets or syllable-medial as syllabic nasals, as shown above.

2.1 Elision

Elision or deletion refers to a situation where sounds are omitted or not articulated in certain contexts (Celce-Murcia et al., 1996). This suggests that a sound, present in its underlying form, can be removed in the surface form in certain environments. Matthews (1997) defines vowel elision as the process by which a vowel at the end of a word is lost, or elided, before another vowel at the beginning of the following word. This definition agrees with that given by Casali (1997) and Rosenthal (1997) and appears to exclude other instances of elision but focus only on first vowel (V_1) elision. Indeed, there are languages in which elision always targets the leftmost vowel. As shown in (4), Nguni (Sibanda 2009: 44-45) is one of these languages.

(4) Nguni

- | | UR | | SR |
|----|-------------------|---|-----------------------|
| a. | /ba-onke/ | → | [bonke] |
| | SUB-INDEF | | |
| | ‘all’ | | |
| b. | /ba-odwa/ | → | [bodwa] |
| | SUB-3PL | | |
| | ‘Only them.’ | | |
| c. | /ibe-ihamba/ | → | [ibihamba] |
| | 3SG-go.PAST.PROG | | |
| | ‘It was going.’ | | |
| d. | /ube-uhamba/ | → | [ubuhamba] |
| | 2SG-go.PAST.PROG | | |
| | ‘You were going.’ | | (Sibanda 2009: 44-45) |

In Nguni (4), we can see that the target of elision is not subject to whether the vowel is low or high. The target is always the leftmost vowel, V_1 . In Akan, however, both leftmost and rightmost vowel elision occur (Amoh 2017:41). Let us consider the example in (5) below.

(5) Akan

- | | UR | | SR |
|----|----------------------|---|-----------------|
| a. | /efie/ + /owura/ | → | /efiewura/ |
| | home owner | | homeowner |
| | ‘Landlord/Landlady.’ | | |
| b. | /abua/ + /efunu/ | → | /abuæfunu/ |
| | animal dead | | dead animal |
| | ‘Dead animal.’ | | (Amoh 2017: 41) |

The Akan examples in (5) above demonstrate that vowel elision does not always target V_1 as Rosenthal (1997) and Matthews (1997) posit, but also V_2 .

In the examples (4) and (5), the environment for elision is at morpheme boundaries and within compounding, respectively. Elision can also occur within a word, affecting not only vowels but also syllables. In this case, it is syllable elision. The Ganda examples in (6) demonstrate this kind of elision.

(6) Ganda

	UR	SR
i.	/Ba-ezi/	→ [be:zi]
	PL-sweeper	
	‘Sweepers.’	
ii.	/Ba-ogezi/	→ [bo:gezi]
	PL-speaker	
	‘Speakers’ (Harris 2011)	

In Ganda (6), the lost sounds involve low vowels, and the direction of elision is always to the left. Gimson (1970) observes that, aside from word-internal elisions, sounds may be elided in rapid colloquial speech, especially near word boundaries. This indicates that in languages where elision occurs frequently, the phenomenon is unavoidable, particularly for native speakers. In Dagbani, elision not only affects vowels but also nasal consonants or an entire syllable (Abdul-Rahman 2013). Additionally, as seen in the Ganda example in (6), elision in Dagbani occurs at word boundaries but always towards the left and never to the right.

In Esahie, a Volta-Comoe language, elision can target either V_1 or V_2 (Owusu Ansah 2020). Owusu Ansah (2020) argues that V_1 elision occurs in possessive and perfective constructions, whereas elision of V_2 always occurs in compounds.

According to Yule (2010), speakers tend to leave some sounds unpronounced in normal speech, which is neither the result of laziness nor a form of sloppiness. Thus, as Yule (2010) argues, deliberately avoiding the regular patterns of elision in discourse usually results in artificial talk.

The discussion above shows that elision is frequent in many languages. However, little is known about the phenomenon in Nzema. It is against this backdrop that I discuss the subject of elision in the language. I show in this study that in Nzema, elision targets vowels across word boundaries, in compounds, and at the syllable level.

3 Elision in phrasal constructions

Vowel elision usually occurs when two morphologically free forms are put together such that the vowel that ends the first word and that which begins the second word are juxtaposed. When this happens, one of the two vowels may elide. Thus, in Nzema, when two words are juxtaposed such that the first word ends in a vowel [V_1] and the second word begins with a vowel [V_2], one of the words loses its vowel. The environment for the deletion of the vowel is morphologically conditioned. In some environments, the V_1 is deleted, while in others, the V_2 is deleted. Let us examine instances of occurrence in Nzema.

3.1 V_1 elision in a consecutive construction

Consecutive verbs in Nzema are formed by adding the low-toned proclitic /à/ to verbs. The verbs can be either low-toned or high-toned, depending on their syllable constituents. In a consecutive construction where a pronominal is added to the verb, the pronominal loses its vowel in the sequence. Vowel elision occurs in this combination when first person singular /mi/ or plural /jè/, second person singular /wà/, third person singular /jì/ or plural /bè/

pronominals concatenate with verbs in their consecutive forms. In the juxtaposed vowels, the pronominals are usually [-low] while [+low] in the verbs, as shown in example (7) below.

(7)

V ₁	#	V ₂	→	V ₂
[-low]	#	[+low]		
a. /mĩ/ ‘me’	#	/àvǎ/	‘may take’ →	[mǎvǎ] ‘(That) I may take’
b. /jì/ ‘him’	#	/ǎdó/	‘may buy’ →	[jǎdó] ‘(That) he may buy’
c. /jè/ ‘our’	#	/ʌlí/	‘may eat’ →	[jʌlí] ‘(That) we may eat’
d. /wò/ ‘your’	#	/ǎlá/	‘may sleep’ →	[wǎlá] ‘(That) you may sleep’
e. /bè/ ‘their’	#	/ǎzìlì/	‘may laugh’ →	[bǎzìlì] ‘(That) they may laugh’

Elision of the first vowel (V₁) in the first elements in the contexts above can be associated with two reasons. First, the initial vowel [a] in verbs of Nzema usually marks the consecutives of the verbs, and so deleting it would make the output appear perfective (tense) instead of its intended consecutive form, and that would bring a change in meaning of the output. For this reason, it is preserved. Secondly, in a context of a V-V sequence where one of the V is a [+low], the [-low] vowels usually delete. Moreover, the low vowel [a], due to its higher sonority, can withstand elision than any other vowel (Walker 2011).

3.2 V₁ elision in a possessive construction

Another environment for V₁ elision is between pronominal and noun concatenation in possessive constructions. The possessive construction in Nzema is marked with a possessive pronoun, which is attached to a noun. In contexts where the nouns begin with a vowel, a V-V sequence is created at the word boundary. When this happens, the vowel of the possessive pronoun (V₁) is elided in the V₁ # V₂ sequence. Vowel elision in this combination also occurs when first person singular /mĩ/ or plural /jè/, second person singular /wò/, third person singular /jì/ or plural /bè/ possessive pronominals concatenate with nouns. Just as we saw from (5), the V₁s that are targeted for elision in this construction are also specified for [-low]. Consider the examples in (8).

(8)

V ₁	#	V ₂	→	V ₂
[-low]	#	[+low]		
a. /wò/ ‘your’	#	/ʌzɛl`ɛ/	‘land’ →	[wǎzɛl`ɛ] ‘your land’
b. /bè/ ‘their’	#	/ǎd`ómǎ/	‘baby’ →	[bǎd`ómǎ] ‘their baby’
c. /jè/ ‘our’	#	/ʌdú/	‘guns’ →	[jʌdú] ‘our guns’
d. /mĩ/ ‘my’	#	/ǎl`ɔŋǎ/	‘grandchild’ →	[mǎl`ɔŋǎ] ‘my grandchild’
e. /jì/ ‘his’	#	/ʌkɛ́lǎ/	‘sugarcane’ →	[jʌkɛ́lǎ] ‘his sugarcane’

Example (8) shows that in Nzema, whenever a pronominal whose vowel is [-low] meets a noun with a [+low] vowel at word boundary, the vowel in the first element elides to avoid a vowel-vowel sequence. As can be seen from the examples, pronominals in Nzema function as possessives and, whether in singular or plural, would necessarily be subject to elision when they meet nouns. V₁ elision in a possessive construction is illustrated below in Figure 1.

Figure 1: V₁ elision in a possessive construction

Figure 1 above shows V₁ elision in a possessive construction. At a morpheme juncture where the V-V sequence is realised, we observe a delinking of the -low mid-front vowel [ε] segment from its tier. This delinking results in the loss of that segment. The mid-vowel, which is weak in the output, is deleted for the preservation of the low vowel [a].

3.3 V₂ elision in a progressive construction

Progressive verbs in Nzema can be formed by attaching a low-toned proclitic /lè/ or a combination of /è/ and /lè/ to verbs. Where the subject of the construction is a pronominal, only the clitic /lè/ is attached to verbs. However, in a construction where the subject is a noun, /è/ and /lè/ combine as /èlè/ and are attached to the verbs. The clitic /è/ in a noun-subject progressive construction functions as a focus marker to the noun and the verb. We will therefore demonstrate elision in noun-subject progressive construction, as it is the domain in which elision is targeted. In a progressive construction where a noun is added to the progressive verb, the verb loses its vowel in the sequence. Let us consider example (9) below.

(9)

V ₁	#	V ₂	→	V ₁
[±high]	#	[-high]		
a. /kòdzó/ ‘name’	#	/èlèsú/ ‘is crying’	→	[kòdzólèsú] ‘Kodwo is crying’
b. /kómú/ ‘monkey’	#	/èlèwú/ ‘is dying’	→	[kómúlèwú] ‘a monkey is dying’
c. /bàkà/ ‘a tree’	#	/èlètú/ ‘is falling’	→	[bàkàlètú] ‘a tree is falling’
d. /àbèbé/ ‘locust’	#	/èlèwúlú/ ‘is hopping’	→	[àbèbélèwúlú] ‘a locust is hopping’

From (9), we observe that in Nzema, nouns retain their final vowels, whereas verbs lose their initial vowels in progressive constructions. The clitic /è/ (V₂) in /èlè/, which carries a low tone, consistently elides irrespective of the tone of the final vowels (V₁) in the nouns.

3.4 V₂ elision in a perfective construction

Another environment in which the second vowel is elided is in noun-verb concatenation in perfective constructions. Perfective verbs in Nzema are formed by attaching a low-toned proclitic /è/ to verbs. The verbs can be low-toned or high-toned depending on their syllable constituents. In a perfective construction where a noun is added to the perfective verb, the verb loses its vowel in the sequence. Let us consider the examples in (10) below.

(10)

V ₁	#	V ₂	→	V ₁
[±high]	#	[-high]		
a. /ézúlé/ ‘rain’	#	/èdó/ ‘has fallen’	→	[ézúlédó] ‘it has rained’
b. /kómũ/ ‘monkey’	#	/èwú/ ‘has died’	→	[kómũwú] ‘a monkey has died’
c. /bàkà/ ‘a tree’	#	/èdú/ ‘has fallen’	→	[bàkádú] ‘a tree has fallen’
d. /sànĩ/ ‘broom’	#	/ètúlú/ ‘has loosened’	→	[sànĩtúlú] ‘a broom has loosened’
e. /bòlò/ ‘ball’	#	/èdé/ ‘has burst’	→	[bòlòdé] ‘a ball has burst’

From the examples in (10) above, we see that whenever a noun that ends with a [±high] vowel meets a verb beginning with a [-high] vowel, the vowel prefix of the verb deletes. This shows that nouns stand stronger when they are in concatenation with verbs. It is also interesting to note that, as verbs give in to elision on the right (position) with [-high] vowel initial in noun and verb concatenation, when the position of the verb is reversed, so that nouns occupy the right position (verb-noun concatenation) with the verbs ending with [+high] vowels, this time there is no elision. Let us consider the following Nzema examples in (9).

(11)

V ₁	#	V ₂	→	V ₁ V ₂
[+high]	#	[+low]		
a. /dí/ ‘eat’	#	/àl`ìè/ ‘food’	→	[dí àl`ìè] ‘eat food’
b. /sú/ ‘fetch’	#	/`àhúlé/ ‘groundnut’	→	[sú `àhúlé] ‘fetch groundnut’
c. /tí/ ‘tear’	#	/`àlúbà/ ‘beans’	→	[tí `àlúbà] ‘harvest groundnut’
d. /bó/ ‘beat’	#	/àkà/ ‘name’	→	[bó àkà] ‘beat Aka’

What we observe from example (11) is that verb-noun concatenations in Nzema do not result in elision, unlike noun-verb concatenations, where the initial vowels in the verbs give in to elision. I argue that in Nzema, whenever verbs with [+high] final vowels meet nouns with [+low] initial vowels at a word boundary, there occurs no elision even though the position of the nouns is on the right. This implies that for vowels in verbs to elide in their concatenation with nouns, the position of the verbs should be on the right, and initial vowels of the verbs must necessarily be specified for [-high] and not [+high] as in (10) and (11).

3.5 V₂ elision in a verbal noun construction

Noun-verb concatenation in verbal noun constructions is another environment where elision of the second vowel, V₂, occurs in Nzema. Verbal nouns in Nzema are formed by circumfixing the low-toned proclitic /è/ and the high-toned enclitic /lé/ to the base verb. In verbal noun constructions where a noun is added to the verbal noun, the verbal noun loses its vowel in the sequence. Let us consider the following examples.

(12)

V₁		#	V₂	→	V₁	
[±high]		#	[-high]			
a. /ɛjá/	‘farm’	#	/ɛzǔlɛ/	‘weeding’	→	[ɛjá zǔlɛ] ‘farming’
b. /bɔlʊ/	‘football’	#	/ɛbɔlé/	‘playing’	→	[bɔlʊ bɔlé] ‘football game’
c. /ɛxɔ̀nĩ/	‘hunger’	#	/ɛɛlɛ/	‘catching’	→	[ɛxɔ̀nĩ ɛlɛ] ‘fasting’
d. /ʌhúlè/	‘groundnut’	#	/ɛlúʌlé/	‘planting’	→	[ʌhúlélúʌlé] ‘groundnut sowing’

As can be observed from (12), whenever nouns that end with [±high] vowels meet verbal nouns with [-high] initial vowels, which are always front vowels at word boundary, the vowel prefixes in the verbal nouns, V₂, readily elide.

Since verbal nouns are words formed from verb roots and affixes, these affixes are usually at risk of elision to preserve the root verb (Nyame 2019). Also, final vowels in nouns form part of the roots (Nyame 2019). As a result, noun final vowels will not yield to elision, hence the elision of the morphological prefixes in the verbal nouns. V₂ elision in a verbal noun construction is illustrated below in Figure 2.

Figure 2: V₂ Elision in a verbal noun construction

4 Elision in compounds

Compounds in Nzema are formed by joining two or more independent words to derive a new word. Usually, when two words are combined to form a compound, and the first word ends with a vowel (V₁), and the second word begins with a vowel (V₂), the second word loses its initial vowel. Therefore, in a context of V₁-V₂ sequence across syllable boundary in a compound, the V₂ is deleted. Compounds in which V₂ elision occurs in Nzema are usually between a noun-noun and a noun-adjective.

4.1 V₂ elision in noun-noun compound

Morpheme concatenations in which V₂ elision occurs, the elided vowels are always specified for [-high]. When two nouns meet at word boundary, the initial vowel of the second element is elided. Noun-noun compounds are regular in the Nzema language. Let us observe from the following examples.

(13) noun		noun	→	compound	
V ₁	#	V ₂		V ₁	
[±high]	#	[-high]			
a. /bànǎ/	#	/édzǐí/	→	[bànǎdzǐí]	‘plantain farm’
b. /bútulé/	#	/`ejá/	→	[bútuléjá]	‘quarrel plant (Fern)’
c. /mǎnzǎ/	#	/`εbà/	→	[mǎnzǎbà]	‘personal name (fem)’
d. /nd`ɔ/	#	/`εkpà/	→	[nd`ɔkpà]	‘Indian mat’
e. /`εzεnĩ/	#	/`εdǎĩé/	→	[`εzεnĩdǎĩé]	‘funeral cloth’

What we observe is that when two nouns, of which the first is specified for [±high] vowel and the second begins with a [-high] vowel, the vowel that begins the second word, V₂, elides. This means that the first vowels stand stronger than the second vowels in noun-noun concatenations. Considering the makeup or inner strengths of the two elements in a noun and noun compound, Booij (2007:176) observes that one element is strong and the other is weak. He asserts that for this to be true, the relationship between the constituents should be that of sisters in which one of them is the head of a prosodic category, such as the foot. He adds that in the case of the English language, the first phonological word in noun-noun compounds is the strongest.

In Nzema, usually, when two nouns concatenate, the first functions as a modifier while the second functions as the head. For instance, in /`εzεnĩ/ ‘funeral’ and /`εdǎĩé/ ‘cloth’, which becomes /`εzεnĩdǎĩé/ ‘funeral cloth’, it is a particular cloth used for funerals that is talked about. Therefore, the first noun, which functions as a modifier, retains its vowel to supply information about the head. Another reason for the first noun showing more strength than the second could be explained in terms of the semantic relations between the two nouns. Evidence for this assertion is given in the following subsection.

4.1.1 *Semantic evidence of strength in the first noun*

Noun-noun compounds in Nzema are endocentric, with the head always on the right. Explaining endocentric compounds with English words, Katamba (1993: 305) has remarked that, “semantically an endocentric compound indicates a sub-grouping within the class of entities that the head denotes.” He gives the following examples: schoolboy, bedroom, and explains that the underlined are a kind of boy and a kind of room, respectively, in which the first part are just specifiers giving more precise meaning to the head.

This is what we observe in (13). Therefore, in Nzema, because the first constituent in a noun-noun compound provides a more precise meaning to the head, it wields much strength. This is in line with what Stahlke (1971: 186) observes in the Ewe language that when a noun becomes the head of a nominalisation, its prefix (vowel) is deleted, and therefore tonal alternations it conditions also become absent.

4.2 *V₂ elision in noun-adjective compound*

Another instance of elision of the second vowel, V₂, at morpheme juncture in Nzema is between nouns and adjectives in diminutive constructions. In a diminutive construction where a noun, which is usually a personal name, is added to the diminutive adjective /`èteí/, the diminutive adjective loses its vowel in the sequence. Let us see how this occurs in (14) below.

(14) noun		adjective		compound	
V ₁	#	V ₂	→	V ₁	
[-low]	#	[-high]			
a. /kódzɔ́/	#	/ètéí/	→	[kódzɔ́téí]	‘Kodwo little’
b. /kàkú/	#	/ètéí/	→	[kàkútéí]	‘Kaku little’
c. /kófí/	#	/ètéí/	→	[kófítéí]	‘Kofi little’
d. /ʌxú/	#	/ètéí/	→	[ʌxútéí]	‘Ahu little’

As can be observed from example (14), when nouns meet adjectives at word boundary in Nzema, the V₂s that begin the second word, which are usually front vowels and [-high], elide. The elision thus targets the rightmost vowel in the sequence. To account for the (V₂) loss in this environment, we approach it from two perspectives: morphological and phonological conditioning.

Morphologically, the vowel that is retained in a noun-adjective compound finally belongs to the entire compound, as in the examples above. Phonologically, the reason for the elision of the initial vowel of the second element is with respect to syllabification. Syllables at some point are required to have onsets or begin with a consonant, though not obligatory in Nzema. The second constituents have only a nucleus as their initial syllables, which are usually prone to elision, particularly in compounding.

Another reason for the loss of V₂ in noun and adjective compound as also observed by Nyame (2019), is that the vowel [è] in [ètéí] is an affix and would therefore yield to elision to preserve the elements in the noun which the adjective qualifies.

5 Syllable final high vowel elision

In Nzema, vowels not only delete at morpheme juncture but also at some syllable final positions. Usually, this kind of elision occurs in fast speeches in which word-final high vowels following consonants are deleted obligatorily. The consonants that are followed by the high vowels are always nasals. This kind of elision also occurs in the Fante dialect of the Akan language.

Describing how these syllable-final high vowels delete in Fante, Abakah (2004) observes, “In standard Fante, if root morpheme terminates in a final SV-syllable (where S stands for non-vowel sonorant) the V deletes obligatorily if it has [+high] specification in its feature matrix.” (Abakah 2004:189). Let us see how this kind of elision operates in Nzema in Example (15) below.

(15)	UR	SR	
a.	/bàní/	[bàn]	‘fence’
b.	/bóní/	[bón]	‘what’
c.	/kómú/	[kóm]	‘monkey’
d.	/mídàmi/	[mídàm]	‘I/me’
e.	/bòàní/	[bòàn]	‘sheep’
f.	/ḡòàni/	[ḡòàn]	‘who’
g.	/bèni/	[bèn]	‘left’
h.	/ʌqíʌni/	[ʌqíʌn]	‘a town name (Half Assini)’

In (17), we observe a whole syllable deletion, which is compensated for by lengthening of the initial vowel. With this strategy, pronunciation is made easy for the native speakers. This is in line with Harris’s (2011) argument that syllable deletion is language-specific and that the lost syllables are compensated for with a lengthening. This syllable loss is illustrated below in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Word internal syllable elision

In the input, we observe that the number of syllables, which is three, has reduced to two in the output by means of elision. On the CV tier, we observe a feature spread from V₁ to the site of the second syllable. This paves the way for a lengthening of V₁ to compensate for the loss of the second syllable.

7 Twin vowel elision

There is a situation where it becomes difficult to determine which of the two (identical) or congruent vowels elides. This happens when the vowels in sequence are of the same quality; that is, when the vowels are identical. In this context, it is usually difficult to determine whether it is V₁ or V₂ that elides. In this sub-section, I show which one of two identical vowels that meet at word boundary elides in Nzema irrespective of word category. Let us consider the examples below in (18).

(18)	V ₁	#	V ₂	→	V ₁
	[±high]	#	[-high]		
a.	/àlìè/	#	/èbí/	→	[àlìèbí]
	‘food’	#	‘is cooked’		‘food is ready’
b.	/àbèlè/	#	/èjá/	→	[àbèlèjá]
	‘maize’	#	‘farm’		‘maize farm’
c.	/àdèlè/	#	/èvàlé/	→	[àdèlèvàlé]
	‘spoon’	#	‘to take’		‘spoon taking’
d.	/àkà/	#	/àdzàbí/	→	[àkàdzàbí]
	‘name’	#	‘name’		‘personal name’
e.	/ètú/	#	/èdó/	→	[ètúdó]
	‘gun’	#	‘has shot’		‘there is a gunshot’

From the examples, apart from (18c) and (18e) in which V₁ is a high tone vowel, the rest of V₁ are all low tone. On the part of V₂, however, all the vowels are low tone. In a situation such as this, some scholars, such as Abakah (2004), using Fante data, argue that it is the final vowel, V₁ of the first element, which elides. He argues further that the input low tone (initial vowel) of the second element survives at the output level, but the final vowel (V₁) of the first element, which is usually a high tone, is elided.

From the examples in (18) above, we observe that Nzema behaves differently. Unlike Fante (Abaka 2004), where high tone V₁ deletes, in Nzema, it is rather V₂, which is low tone, that deletes. We also observe that when V₁ and V₂ are both low-toned, as in (18a), (18b) and

(18d), the target of elision is still V_2 . Moreover, where V_1 is a high tone, and V_2 is a low tone as in (18c), V_2 is deleted.

From the observation made thus far, it can be argued that in Nzema, whenever there is an identical vowel-vowel sequence at word boundary, where V_1 and V_2 are of the same tone level, that is, low or high, it is V_2 that elides. Again, when V_1 and V_2 are of different tone levels, it is the low-toned vowel, V_2 , that deletes.

8 Conclusion

The paper has discussed how elision operates in Nzema. It has shown that vowels and syllables can be subjected to elision in the language. We observed that vowel elision is very regular across morpheme boundaries in consecutive constructions, possessive constructions, progressive constructions, perfective constructions, verbal noun constructions, and compounds in Nzema. In a context of $V_1\#V_2$, the vowel that deletes across word boundary varies. The analysis shows that in the consecutive constructions and possessive constructions, the deleted vowel is always V_1 . However, in the progressive constructions, perfective constructions, verbal noun constructions, and compounds, the deleted vowel is always V_2 . Consequently, I conclude, based on the data, that in the consecutive constructions and possessive constructions in Nzema, whenever there is a $V_1\#V_2$, the V_1 is deleted, whereas in the progressive constructions, perfective constructions, verbal noun constructions and compound constructions, V_2 is deleted.

As a preliminary conclusion, *inter alia*, we have observed that in Nzema, the morpheme2 initial V is systematically targeted for deletion as it involves more environments than it is found in V_1 elision. The vowels that are targeted for elision in V_1 elision are always specified for the feature [-low], while in V_2 elision, the vowels are [-high].

Moreover, in Nzema, whenever there is an identical $V_1\#V_2$ such that V_1 and V_2 are of the same tone level, that is, low-low or different tone level, high-low, it is V_2 that consistently elides.

The study has further shown that (at least in Nzema) the mid vowels, [ɛ, e, ɔ] surrender to [a], a [+Low] vowel. That is, whichever position [a] finds itself (whether as V_1 or V_2), it is mostly favoured against all other vowels.

Finally, the evidence in this paper indicates that there is a link between phonology and morphology when accounting for elision in Nzema.

Abbreviations

SUB	Subject marker
INDEF	Indefinite
2SG	Second person singular
3SG	Third person singular
PROG	Progressive marker
PAST	Past marker
PL	Plural marker
SR	Surface realisation
UR	Underlying representation
ATR	Advanced tongue root
V_1	First vowel
V_2	Second vowel

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John Nyame
Department of Akan-Nzema Education
College of Languages Education, Ajumako
University of Education
Winneba
Ghana
e-mail: mr.nyame@gmail.com

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The Morphosyntax and Functions of Demonstratives in Kiwoso

Aurelia Mallya

University of Dar es Salaam

This paper examines the morphology, syntax and functions of demonstratives in Kiwoso. Similarly to other nominal modifiers in Bantu language, demonstratives are closely tied to the noun class system, exhibiting agreement in number and grammatical gender. Kiwoso distinguishes three-way system of demonstratives: proximal, medial, and distal. Syntactically, demonstratives serve both as pronominal replacing nouns, and adnominal modifying nouns. Canonically, adnominal demonstratives occur post-nominally. However, depending on the functions they serve, they can appear before the nouns, for example in copular constructions. In terms of functions, demonstratives in Kiwoso serve several other functions in addition to spatial deixis, the basic function of demonstratives across languages. Demonstratives are used for emphasis and recognitional purposes. This paper offers a detailed description of demonstratives, situating Kiwoso within the broader linguistic typology of Bantu languages. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of morpho-syntactic structures, linguistic and communicative uses of demonstratives in Bantu languages.

Keywords: *morphosyntax, semantics, demonstratives, Kiwoso, Bantu*

1 Introduction

Demonstratives are words or expressions that correspond to English words *this*, *that*, *here*, and *there*, considered to be among spatial deictic elements present in all spoken languages (Diessel 1999, 2006; Dixon 2003). Despite being a universal category, cross-linguistically, demonstratives differ considerably with regard to the number, form, and function (Diessel 1999: 36). For example, with regard to number, languages may have two demonstratives only, or may have up to twelve (Diessel 1999; Levinson et al. 2018). Many Bantu languages distinguish three demonstratives (Nicolle 2012, 2014; Van de Velde 2005, 2019). However, there are some Bantu languages with four demonstrative series which indicate referent very close to the speaker, near the speaker, near the hearer, and far from both the speaker and the hearer (Nicolle 2012). Drawing on these cross-linguistic insights, the present paper examines the demonstrative system of Kiwoso, with particular attention to its morphosyntactic properties and functional range. In doing so, the study contributes to broader typological debates on demonstratives in Bantu and enhances our understanding of deictic systems cross-linguistically.

The morphological makeup of demonstratives varies considerably across Bantu languages. In several languages, demonstrative forms include an initial element, as shown for Runyankore-Rukiga (Asiimwe 2014, 2024) and Chiyao (Taji 2024). However, for Kiwoso, no study has systematically examined the morphological structure of its demonstratives. This paper describes the forms of Kiwoso demonstratives, with particular attention to how they interact with the noun class system.

Syntactically, demonstratives are commonly classified according to the types of elements they co-occur with in a clause (Diessel 1999; Dixon 2003). Diessel, in particular, distinguishes four major categories: pronominal, adnominal, adverbial, and identificational demonstratives. Despite this typological framework, there is limited research on how these

categories are manifested in Bantu languages. This paper therefore investigates the four demonstrative categories in Kiwoso, drawing on freshly data in Kiwoso, Bantu.

Languages vary in the specific functions their demonstratives perform. However, it is widely acknowledged that the core function of demonstratives cross-linguistically is to coordinate the interlocutors' joint focus of attention (Diessel 2006: 464). Moreover, demonstratives do more than indicate spatial proximity: in many languages they also encode functions such as definiteness, topicality or focus, and contrast (Skilton 2024). For Kiwoso, however, no dedicated study has examined the functional range of demonstratives. Existing works on the language (Mallya 2016, 2020, 2024) mention demonstratives only briefly, if at all. This paper therefore offers a comprehensive account of the forms, syntactic distribution, and functions of demonstratives in Kiwoso. The paper addresses the following questions: (i) what are the forms of demonstratives in Kiwoso? (ii) How are demonstratives distributed syntactically? and (iii) what roles do demonstratives play in the language?

2 Background about Kiwoso

Kiwoso is one of the Chaga languages spoken in the Kilimanjaro Region of northern Tanzania. It belongs to Guthrie's (1948) Bantu classification Zone E, Group 60 (the Chaga group), and is specifically coded as E621D (Maho 2009). The community of speakers, known as the Wakiwoso, predominantly resides on the western slopes of Mount Kilimanjaro. The speakers refer to their language as Kiwoso, whereas neighbouring groups often call it Kikibosho in Swahili. In this study, the term Kiwoso is adopted, as it is the name used by the speakers themselves. Other closely related languages within the Chaga group include Machame, Kivunjo-Chaga, and Old Moshi.

According to the Languages of Tanzania Project (LOT 2009), Kiwoso is spoken by approximately 81,181 people. However, information regarding the number of speakers of Tanzanian languages is somewhat unreliable, since national censuses generally omit questions concerning ethnic affiliation and community languages. Kiwoso remains one of the largely undocumented Bantu languages of Tanzania, and consequently, written materials are limited. The available sources include a dictionary (Kagaya & Olomi 2009), dissertations (Mushi 2005; Mallya 2012, 2016). A few morphosyntactic studies have also been conducted (Mallya 2020, 2024).

Kiwoso is primarily used in informal communication, and its speakers are bilingual in Kiwoso and Swahili. Following the post-independence language policy of Tanzania, the use of ethnic languages in education and other official domains is restricted. As a result, Kiwoso is not employed in formal contexts or for official purposes. There are currently no publications or radio broadcasts in the language. In educational settings, especially primary schools, children are discouraged from using indigenous languages, as Swahili serves as the main language of instruction. Because Kiwoso lacks official recognition, it has no standardized orthography.

The present paper does not aim to provide a comprehensive grammatical description of Kiwoso. However, a brief overview of its morphology, including its noun class system is provided. This background serves to contextualize the subsequent discussion of the forms, distribution, and functions of demonstratives, and offers insight into aspects of nominal morphology relevant to the analysis.

3 Methodology

As a native speaker of the language and a trained linguist, I prepared a list of constructions containing proximal, medial, and distal demonstratives. The demonstratives were distributed in both pre-nominal and post-nominal positions. Then, the constructions were given to four native speakers of Kiwoso to give their acceptability and grammaticality judgements. The constructions were prepared both in Kiswahili and in Kiwoso. The Kiswahili version was given to native speakers of Kiwoso, who were also fluent speakers of Kiswahili. The consultants were asked to translate the Kiswahili constructions into Kiwoso. Oral narratives were also employed to elicit data for this study. Three speakers were asked to narrate familiar traditional stories. The data extracted from the narratives and from the structured questionnaires were analysed to establish the forms, syntactic distribution, and the functions of demonstratives in the language under study. The approach employed for collecting the information analysed in this study was adopted given the fact that Kiwoso is largely undocumented, it has a limited corpus, and only a scant written texts are available in the language.

4 The morphology of demonstratives in Kiwoso

This section focuses on the description of demonstratives in terms of morphology. The morphology of demonstratives varies across languages. In many Bantu languages, demonstratives consist of an initial element (Du Plessis et al. 1992), such as *a-*, *e-*, or *o-*, depending on the vowel of the agreement prefix of the head noun (Visser 2008). However, not all demonstratives involve an initial vowel. For example, in Runyankore-Rukiga, only the proximal and the medial demonstratives exhibit an initial element *-a* (Asimwe 2014, 2024). In other languages such as Chiyao (Taji 2024), an initial element is optional when a demonstrative occurs in both pre-nominal and post-nominal positions, as examples in (1) illustrate. The examples demonstrate that it is only the pre-nominal demonstratives which host the initial vowel *a-*.

- (1) Chiyao a. *ali* *li-koswé* *li*
 5.DEM.PROX 5-rat 5.DEM.PROX
 ‘this rat’
 b. *achila* *chi-téla* *chíla*
 7.DEM.DIST 7-tree 7.DEM.DIST
 ‘that tree over there’ (Taji 2024: 20)

The findings from Kiwoso show that, as in Runyankore-Rukiga, an initial vowel *e-* is consistently realized in proximal and medial demonstratives, while distal demonstratives lack this prefix. This distribution indicates a morphophonological distinction tied to the deictic hierarchy. In addition, the morphological shape of Kiwoso demonstratives is jointly determined by the noun class system, which supplies the appropriate agreement prefix, and by the spatial location of the referent relative to the speaker and addressee, as exemplified in Table (1).

Table 1: Noun classes and demonstratives in Kiwoso

Class	Prefix	Example	Gloss	Demonstratives			Example
				Proximal	Medial	Distal	
1	<i>mu-</i>	<i>mu-na</i>	child	<i>e-tu</i>	<i>e-to</i>	<i>u-lya</i>	<i>muna etu/eto/ulya</i>
2	<i>wa-</i>	<i>wa-na</i>	children	<i>e-wa</i>	<i>e-wo</i>	<i>wa-lya</i>	<i>wana ewa/ewo/walya</i>
3	<i>n-</i>	<i>n-ji</i>	tree	<i>e-tu</i>	<i>e-to</i>	<i>u-lya</i>	<i>nji etu/eto/ulya</i>
4	<i>mi-</i>	<i>mi-ji</i>	trees	<i>e-ti</i>	<i>e-to</i>	<i>tya</i>	<i>miji eti/eto/tya</i>
5	<i>i-</i>	<i>i-du</i>	ear	<i>e-lyi</i>	<i>e-lyo</i>	<i>lya</i>	<i>idu elyi/elyo/lya</i>
6	<i>ma-</i>	<i>ma-du</i>	ears	<i>e-wa</i>	<i>e-wo</i>	<i>alya</i>	<i>madu ewa/ewo/walya</i>
7	<i>ki-</i>	<i>ki-andu</i>	knife	<i>e-kyi</i>	<i>e-kyo</i>	<i>kya</i>	<i>kyandu ekyi/ekyo/kya</i>
8	<i>shi-</i>	<i>shi-andu</i>	knives	<i>e-shi</i>	<i>e-sho</i>	<i>shya</i>	<i>shyandu eshi/esho/shya</i>
9	<i>n-</i>	<i>mburu</i>	goat	<i>e-yi</i>	<i>e-yo</i>	<i>iya</i>	<i>mburu eyi/eyo/iya</i>
10	<i>n-</i>	<i>mburu</i>	goats	<i>e-ti</i>	<i>e-to</i>	<i>tya</i>	<i>mburu eti/eto/tya</i>
11	<i>u-</i>	<i>u-dende</i>	leg	<i>e-lu</i>	<i>e-lo</i>	<i>lwo</i>	<i>udende elu/elo/lou</i>
14	<i>u-</i>	<i>u-doko</i>	laziness	<i>e-lu</i>	<i>e-lo</i>	<i>lwo</i>	<i>udoko elu, elo, lou</i>
16	<i>a-</i>	<i>a-ndo</i>	place	<i>yaa</i>	<i>yoo</i>	<i>alya</i>	<i>ando yaa/yoo/alya</i>
17	<i>ku</i>	<i>ku-ndo</i>	place	<i>kunu</i>	<i>eho</i>	<i>kulya</i>	<i>kundo kunu/eho/kulya</i>

The data presented in Table (1) indicates that Kiwoso uses a three-way demonstrative system (proximal, medial and distal demonstratives) to mark the distance of a referent in relation to the position of the speaker and the hearer. The proximal demonstrative indicates the referent near the speaker, non-proximal or medial demonstrative mark the referent near the addressee, and the distal demonstrative encode the referent far from both the speaker and the addressee. Examples in (2) demonstrate three-way demonstrative system in Kiwoso.

- (2) a. *ki-liko ekyi ki-tu*
7-spoon 7.DEM.PROX 7-small
‘this small spoon’
- b. *ki-liko ekyo ki-tu*
7-spoon 7.DEM.MED 7-small
‘that small spoon’
- c. *ki-liko kya ki-tu*
7-spoon 7.DEM.DIST 7-small
‘that small spoon’

Furthermore, the data examined in this paper demonstrate that the proximal demonstrative in Kiwoso begins with *e-* and ends with *u-*, *a-*, or *i-*. The initial element for the medial demonstrative is also *e-*, but the final element is consistently *-o*. Generally, both proximal and the medial demonstratives in Kiwoso are formed by prefixing an initial vowel to the CV noun class prefix. The distal demonstrative lacks an initial vowel, but ends with *a-*, except for the classes 11 and 14 which involve vowel *-o* at the end. The distal demonstratives are formed by

the CGV noun class prefix, but for classes 1, 2, 3, 6, 9, 16, and 17, the distal demonstratives are formed by attaching noun class prefix of the respective noun in addition to the CGV base.

Locative classes (16 and 17) present a different picture partly because Kiwoso lacks productive locative prefixes found in many Bantu languages (see Mallya 2024). Kiwoso has two locative nouns: *ando* and *kundo*, as shown in Table 1. Both nouns signify ‘place’, but they are pragmatically different. The noun *ando* is interpreted as a place which is definite, specific, known, visible, and near to both the speaker and the addressee, whereas the noun *kundo* is understood as an indefinite place, unspecific, invisible, and far from both the speaker and the addressee. The demonstratives of classes 16 and 17 refer to places or locations, as shown in Table (1). These forms are exemplified further in Table (2) and example (3) to clarify the differences between the nouns *ando* and *kundo* in relation to demonstratives.

Table 2: Demonstratives of locative classes

Proximal	Medial	Distal
<i>yaa</i> ‘here’	<i>yoo</i> ‘there’	<i>alya</i> ‘over there’ (far from both speaker and addressee)
<i>kunu</i> ‘here’	<i>eho</i> ‘there’	<i>kulya</i> ‘over there’ (broad and unspecific place)

- (3) a. *yaa/yoo/alya* *a-ndo* *ku-cha*
DEM.PROX/MED/DIST 16-place 17-nice
‘Here/there/over there is a nice place.’
- b. *kulya* *ku-ndo* *ku-cha*
17.DEM.DIST 17-place 17-nice
‘Over there is a nice place.’
- c. **ku-lya* *a-ndo* *ku-cha*
17.DEM.DIST 16-place 17-nice

Examples in (3) show that the noun *ando* can be modified by the demonstratives *yaa* ‘here’, *yoo* ‘there’, and *alya* ‘over there’, all of which refer to locations that are physically visible to the interlocutors and can be reinforced by extra-linguistic cues such as pointing. However, *ando* cannot co-occur with the demonstrative *kulya* ‘over there (out of sight)’, which denotes a location outside the immediate visual field. Instead, *kulya* is compatible with the locative noun *kundo*, as illustrated in (3b). This pattern suggests that in Kiwoso the demonstrative *kulya* is primarily reserved for non-visible or displaced locations that are either already mentioned in the discourse or are inferable through shared knowledge between speaker and addressee. Such a restriction aligns with broader Bantu tendencies in which distal non-visible demonstratives serve both spatial and discourse-anaphoric functions.

5 Categories of demonstratives in Kiwoso

Demonstratives have been classified differently by different scholars. For example, in their general typological works, Diessel (1999) and Dixon (2003) categorized demonstratives based on the type of elements with which they occur in a clause. Based on his analysis, Diessel (1999: 2) states that demonstratives occur in four different syntactic contexts: they may occur as independent pronouns in argument position, they may occur with a noun in a noun phrase, they

may function as verb modifiers, and demonstratives may occur in copular and non-verbal clauses. Based on the identified syntactic contexts, Diessel identified four categories of demonstratives, namely pronominal, adnominal, adverbial, and identificational demonstratives. These categories are largely unexplored in Bantu languages, and Kiwoso in particular, hence the sections that follow discuss the four categories of demonstratives drawing examples from Kiwoso.

5.1 *Pronominal demonstratives*

Pronominal demonstratives indicate which entity is being referred to. The pronominal demonstratives can stand alone as a complete noun phrase or independent pronouns; thus, they can replace nouns (Diessel 1999: 72), and especially those understood from contexts. The fact that these demonstratives display noun attributes, they show noun grammatical distinctions such as noun class and number agreement (see Table 1). All three forms of demonstratives in Kiwoso can be used pronominally as the subject and serve as object, as shown in (4) and (5), respectively.

- (4) a. *ewa wa- le- end-a kinaange icho*
2.DEM.PROX 2- PST- go- FV 7market the other day
'These ones went to the market the other day.'
- b. *eto ti- le- dom- a*
10.DEM.MED 10-PST- small- FV
'Those ones were small.'
- c. *walya wa- le- kumb- a nungu*
2.DEM.DIST 2- PST- sell- FV 9pot
'Those ones sold the pot.'
- (5) a. *wa- le- kund- a eshi*
2- PST- like- FV 8.DEM.PROX
'They liked these ones.'
- b. *wa- le- waanga-a walya*
2- PST- call- FV 2.DEM.DIST
'They called those ones.'
- c. *wa-le- sand-a eshi na esho*
2- PST- mix- FV 8.DEM.PROX and 8.DEM.MED
'They mixed these and those ones.'

The examples show that in both argument positions, pronominal demonstratives serve to track a referent that is identifiable in the physical context and accessible to both speaker and hearer. They may also point to a referent that has been previously introduced in the discourse, thereby presupposing shared knowledge between the interlocutors about that referent.

5.2 *Adnominal demonstratives*

Adnominal demonstratives modify nouns. In Bantu languages, they can occur before or after the noun they modify, as shown in Kirundi and Luganda (Van de Velde 2005), respectively. In other languages, adnominal demonstratives can appear in both positions, as established in

Makonde (Makanjila 2019) and Chiyao (Taji 2024). In Kiwoso, canonically, adnominal demonstratives can only appear post-nominally, as examples in (6) demonstrate. If the adnominal demonstratives appear in the pre-nominal positions, they are interpreted differently, as detailed in §5.4.

- (6) *surum-a shi-liko eshi na bakuri eto*
Hide- FV 8-spoon 8.DEM.PROX and 10bowl 10.DEM.MED
saani tya na safuria che tedu- n
10plate 10.DEM.DIST and 10pot not POSS-NEG
‘Keep these spoons and those bowls. Those plates (over there) and pans are not ours.’

The demonstratives *eshi*, *eto*, and *tya* in example (6) modify the nouns *shiliko* ‘spoons’, *bakuri* ‘bowls’, and *saani* ‘plates’, respectively. This example shows that, as with pronominal demonstratives, adnominal demonstratives exhibit concord with the noun class prefixes of the nouns they modify. In other words, each demonstrative form is morphologically aligned with the noun class of its head noun, reflecting the characteristic agreement patterns of Bantu nominal morphology.

5.3 Adverbial demonstratives

Adverbial demonstratives are expressions that indicate location, equivalent to the English words ‘here’ and ‘there’ (Diessel 1999). Other terms used to refer to demonstratives that encode location include local adverbial demonstrative (Dixon 2003: 62), locative adverb (Heine et al. 2020: 403), locative demonstrative (König 2015: 3), and demonstrative adverb (Diessel 2006: 473; Levinson 2018: 1).

In many Bantu languages, adverbial demonstratives are derived from the locative noun classes 16-18 (see Ström 2015; Asiimwe 2024). However, similarly to many other Bantu languages, adverbial demonstratives often form three-way spatial systems in Kiwoso indicating proximal, medial, and distal distance relative to interlocutors. The three forms can be used pronominally, standing as an independent pronoun or modifying the verb, as (7a) and (7b), respectively, illustrate. Also, adverbial demonstratives can be used adnominally modifying the locative nouns, as shown in (8).

- (7) a. *yaa/yoo/kulya ku-fane*
DEM.PROX/DEM.MED/DEM.DIST 17-dirty
‘Here/there/over there (this place/that place/the place over there) is dirty.’
b. *wa-ndu walya wa-le- ch- a yaa wa-le- lal- a*
2-people 2.DEM.DIST 2- PST-come-FV DEM.PROX 2- PST-sleep-FV
yoo na kulya
DEM.MED and DEM.DIST
‘Those people who came here slept there and over there.’

- (8) *yaa mmba ku-fane*
DEM.PROX 9house 17-dirty
‘Here in the house is dirty.’

In (7a), *yaa* ‘here’ *yoo* ‘there’, and *kulya* ‘over there’ stand alone as independent pronouns indicating the location or place, whereas in (7b), the demonstratives specify the location or place described by the verbs. In (8), the adverbial demonstrative *yaa* ‘here’ modifies the locative noun *mmba* ‘in the house’.

5.4 Identificational demonstratives

Identificational demonstratives are also referred to as demonstrative identifiers (Diessel 1999). These form of demonstratives are used in copular constructions to introduce, indicate, or identify a referent in speech situation. As genuine deictic expression, identificational demonstratives are primarily used with reference to entities in the speech situation. The core function of the identificational demonstrative reflects the other terms used to refer to it, namely pointing demonstratives (Rehg & Sohl 1981: 150) and deictic identifier pronoun (Carlson 1994: 160). In Kiwoso, identificational demonstratives can be used to refer to entities present in the speech situation (9), or referents which have been referred to previously (10), and entities which are not present in the current speech context or previously mentioned, but the interlocutors have a shared knowledge about them, as exemplified in (11).

- (9) *ewa nyi-wo wa-le-shaam-a n-lima*
2.DEM.PROX COP-those 2-PST-climb-FV 3-mountain
‘These are the ones who climbed the mountain.’

- (10) *kya kyo kyaamba kya wa-na*
7.DEM.DIST COP-that 7.land 7.POSS 2-child
‘That one is the children’s land.’

- (11) *tya nee ndoori mbicho*
10.DEM.DIST were 10.disease bad
‘Those were bad diseases.’

The examples in (9-11) indicate that identificational demonstratives in Kiwoso, as commonly occur in other languages involve copula and non-verbal clauses. It has been shown that all the three demonstrative dimensions in Kiwoso can be used to encode identificational demonstratives. The data indicate further that the distal demonstrative form in addition with the past tense copula *nee* ‘were’ are used to refer to entities which are not available in the speech context or which have not been mentioned before, but interlocutors have a shared knowledge about them. The examples illustrate that the copula *nee* is not compatible with proximal and medial identificational demonstratives, which denote entities that can be seen (9) or referred to previously (10).

5.5 Manner demonstratives

Manner demonstratives are a relatively under-described category of demonstratives in Bantu languages. Unlike adnominal or pronominal demonstratives that locate referents, manner demonstratives are words or expressions that indicate how actions are performed, translated as ‘this/that way’ or ‘like this/that’ (Diessel 1999). Morphologically, manner demonstratives in Bantu languages typically occur as suffixal forms that attach to an appropriate noun-class

concord or agreement marker. In Kiwoso, when the manner demonstrative modifies a noun, the manner base occurs with the agreement prefix of the corresponding noun class, as illustrated in (12). However, when it modifies the verb, the construction consistently takes the locative prefix *ku-*, as shown in (13). Similarly to many other Bantu languages, in Kiwoso, manner demonstratives are often accompanied by gestures, as indicated in example (12b) or demonstration on how an action is performed, as (13) shows.

- (12) a. *wa-ndu wadi/ wado wa-fung-w- e*
2-people 2.DEM.PROX 2.DEM.MED 2- arrest-PASS-PFV
‘People like these/those should be arrested.’
- b. *wa- le- ur- a ki-kabu kidi/ kido*
3PL- PST-buy-FV 7-basket 7.DEM.PROX 7.DEM.MED
‘They bought a basket like this/like that.’ (touching/pointing to the basket)
- (13) a. *wa- le- wad-a kudi kudo*
3PL- PST- hold-FV 17.DEM.PROX 17.DEM.MED
‘They held like this/like that.’ (showing how they hold it or gazing at someone demonstrating)’
- b. *wa- le- fin- a kudi/ kudo*
3PL- PST- dance-FV 17.DEM.PROX 17.DEM.MED
‘They danced like this/like that.’

The examples indicate that manner demonstratives in Kiwoso encode only proximal and medial distinctions and cannot refer to entities or actions located far from both speaker and hearer. Consequently, their use is restricted to referents within the immediate physical environment, where they function to anchor an entity, action, or activity in the ongoing conversation or in previously introduced discourse. This pattern suggests that manner demonstratives in Kiwoso are closely tied to perceptual accessibility in that the manner of action must be visually or contextually available to both interlocutors for the demonstrative to be used.

This section has discussed the forms of demonstratives in Kiwoso. It has been demonstrated that in addition to the four classes of demonstratives identified by Diessel (1999), there is also manner demonstratives which entail an aspect of how something is done. The section that follows focuses on the positions of demonstratives in relation to the nouns they modify and their syntactic distribution in the verbal domain.

6 The syntax of demonstratives

Bantu languages exhibit three patterns of demonstratives in terms of positions relative to the nouns they modify, namely demonstratives that occur before the nouns they modify (preposed demonstratives), those that appear after the nouns (postposed demonstratives) and the demonstratives that occur before and after the nouns they modify (circumdemonstratives or doubled demonstratives) (Van de Velde 2005). However, in many Bantu languages, the canonical position of the demonstratives is in post-nominal position, as attested in languages like Fipa, Ganda, Haya, Kikuyu, Zulu (Van de Velde 2005), Makhuwa (Van der Wal 2010), and Chiyao (Taji 2024). Example (14) from Lugwene illustrate.

- (14) Lugwene *ó- mu-sáále ogw-ó*
 AUG- 3-tree 3.DEM.MED
 ‘that tree’ (Ahn & Van der Wal 2022)

Although uncommon, in some Bantu languages including Lega, Sile, Rundi (Van de Velde 2005), Fwe (Gunnink 2018), and Ha (Harjula 2004), demonstratives occur before the nouns they modify (15). It has been established further that in Linga and Luba (Van de Velde 2005), Runyankore-Rukiga (Asiimwe 2014, 2024), and Shimwela (Taji & Mreta 2017) demonstratives can occur in both pre-nominal and post-nominal positions, as (16) exemplifies.

- (15) Ha *izo súka zì-bíri*
 10DEM.DIST 10hoe 10-two
 ‘those two hoes’ (Harjula 2004: 75)

- (16) Shimwela *aji mikóngo ji*
 4.DEM.PROX 4-tree 4.DEM.PROX
 ‘these tree’ (Taji & Mreta 2017: 12)

As there is no systematic study that has been conducted to examine the syntactic distribution of demonstratives in Kiwoso, the discussion below provides a description of demonstratives in Kiwoso to establish their positions in relation to the nouns with which they occur. Furthermore, the paper examines the properties of demonstratives in co-occurrence with other modifiers such as adjectives, numerals and possessives.

6.1 Position of demonstrative in the noun phrase in Kiwoso

In Bantu languages, demonstratives are part of nominal modifiers, as such, canonically, they follow the nouns they modify. Similarly to many other Bantu languages, the position of demonstratives in Kiwoso is after the nouns they modify, as examples in (17) indicate.

- (17) a. *mu-na etu mu-ntu*
 2-child 2.DEM.PROX 2-small
 ‘this small/young child’
 b. *kelya ekyo kya mu-na*
 7food 7.DEM.MED of 2-child
 ‘That food is for the child.’
 c. *shi-liko shya shya-ko shi-dadu*
 8-spoon 8.DEM.DIST 8-POSS 8-three
 ‘those three spoons of mine’

The examples in (17) indicate that all the three demonstrative dimensions can modify nouns, and they all occur after the respective nouns, as the proximal, medial, and distal demonstratives *etu* ‘this’, *ekyo* ‘that’ and *shya* ‘that’, respectively, in (17) illustrate.

Although many adnominal modifiers occur in post-nominal position, in many languages, demonstratives occur before the nouns they modify (Van de Velde 2005, 2019). Kiwoso do not allow adnominal demonstratives to occur before the nouns they modify. The study findings indicate that the position of demonstratives determines the role the

demonstrative plays in the nominal domain. For example, in Kiwoso, pre-nominal demonstratives *etu* ‘this’ *eto* ‘that’ and *ulya* ‘that’ in example (18) do not modify the noun *muna* ‘child’. They identify specific referents in speech situation rather than modifying the nouns (see §5.2).

- (18) *etu* *mu-na* *eto* *mu-na* *ulya* *mu-na*
1DEM.PROX 1-child 1DEM.MED 1-child 1DEM.DIST 1-child
‘This is a child’ ‘that is a child’ ‘that (over there) is a child’

Similarly to many other Bantu languages, Kiwoso allows demonstrative stacking. However, the co-occurrence of more than one demonstrative within the same clause or noun phrase is pragmatically motivated rather than semantically redundant. In particular, Kiwoso permits two identical demonstratives to appear in sequence, typically in post-nominal position, as illustrated in (19). Similarly to adnominal demonstratives exemplified in (19), the pronominal demonstratives can also co-occur, as shown in (20). Similar results have been reported in Runyankore-Rukiga (Asiimwe 2024). This pattern of doubling a demonstrative is commonly used to express insistency, emphasis, or speaker reinforcement.

- (19) a. *i-rinda elyi elyi/elyo elyo/lya lya*
5-dress 5.DEM.PROX/DEM.MED/DEM.DIST
‘this/that/that very dress’
b. *i-kumbi lyidi lyidi/lyido lyido*
5-hoe 5.DEM.PROX/DEM.DIST
‘the very same hoe (different distance from the speaker)’
- (20) a. *ekyi ekyi* ‘this very one’
b. *ewa ewa* ‘these very ones’
c. *kulya kulya* ‘that very (same) place’

The data examined show that it is also possible for different demonstratives to co-occur, one appearing in pre-nominal position and the other one positioned after the noun, as (21) illustrate.

- (21) a. *ewa* *wa-na walya*
2.DEM.PROX 2-child 2.DEM.DIST
‘These are those children.’ (we both know about)
b. *ewo* *wa-na walya*
2.DEM.MED 2-child 2.DEM.DIST
‘Those are those children.’
c. *eki* *ki-kombe kya*
7.DEM.PROX 7-cup 7.DEM.DIST
‘This is that cup.’
d. *ekyo* *ki-kombe kya*
7.DEM.MED 7-cup 7.DEM.DIST
‘That is that cup.’

The examples in (21) show that in Kiwoso, proximal or medial demonstratives may co-occur with a distal demonstrative, with each form contributing a distinct function. The proximal and

medial demonstratives occur pre-nominally, where they serve their core spatial-deictic roles. In contrast, the distal demonstrative appears post-nominally, where it conveys a recognitional meaning, signalling that the referent is assumed to be familiar or identifiable to the hearer.

6.2 Co-occurrence of demonstratives with other modifiers

Languages which exhibit postposed demonstratives show variation in terms of the position of demonstratives among the post-nominal modifiers (Van de Velde 2005). For example, in languages such as Logoli (Van de Velde 2005), Ha and Sukuma (Rugemalira 2007) the order is relatively free, as shown in (24). On the other hand, in Eton (Van de Velde 2005), Mashami (Rugemalira 2007), and Chiyao (Taji 2024) the order is restricted. In Chiyao, for example, the postposed demonstratives occur after all modifiers in the nominal domain, including the relative clause (Taji 2024: 47-48), while in Eton, the demonstratives occur after all other modifiers, but before the relative clause (van de Velde (2005:4).

- (22) Sukuma a. *a-bha-nu* *bha kwandya a-bha-tano* *a-bhane*
 AUG-2-people of first AUG-2-five AUG-POSS
a-bho
 AUG-2.DEM.MED
 ‘those first five people of mine’
- b. *a- bha-nu* *bha-tano bho-se a- bho* *a- bhane*
 AUG- 2- people 2- five 2-all AUG-2.DEM.MED AUG-POSS
 ‘all those five people of mine’
- c. *a- bha-nu* ***a- bho*** *abha kwandya a-bha-tano* *a-bha-wiza*
 AUG- 2- people AUG-2.DEM.MED of first AUG-2-five AUG-2-nice
a-bhane
 AUG-POSS
 ‘those first five good people of mine’

(Rugemalira 2007: 146)

Examples in (22) indicate that the order of demonstrative in Sukuma is free. For instance, the demonstrative is final in (22a), last but one in (22b), and immediately after the head noun in (22c). In Kiwoso, the postposed demonstratives appear before any other modifiers including possessives and adjectives (see example 17). Rugemalira (2007: 139) presents similar pattern in Mashami, a closely related language to Kiwoso.

This section has shown that syntactically, demonstratives serve pronominal and adnominal functions. The former can stand alone as a noun phrase or as independent as pronoun, whereas the latter modifies the nouns. The pronominal demonstratives display typical characteristics of nouns in that they can function as subject or object, and be cross-referenced on the verb as a subject or object marker. The adnominal demonstratives occupy post-nominal position. The adnominal demonstratives occur before any other post-nominal modifiers in Kiwoso.

7 Functions and the uses of demonstratives in Kiwoso

It has been mentioned that the core function of demonstratives in any language is to focus the interlocutors' attention on referents or locations and establish a shared understanding between the interlocutors in the surrounding speech or discourse situation by way of pointing (Diessel 1999: 2; Dixon 2003: 61-62). Diessel (1999: 7) in particular, categorizes demonstratives into two major classes based on their functions, namely exophoric and endophoric. The two roles are relevant in Kiwoso, thus the discussion on the functions of demonstratives presented in this section follow Diessel's (1999: 7) categorization. Therefore, §§7.1-7.2 focus on the exophoric and endophoric functions of demonstratives in Kiwoso, while other uses of demonstratives including emphatic and recognitional functions covered in §§7.3-7.5.

7.1 Exophoric (spatial-deictic) function

Exophoric (spatial-deictic) uses of demonstratives is the primary feature in deictic expressions, and a core function of demonstrative across languages (Diessel 1999: 94; Himmelmann 1996). In exophoric uses, the demonstratives refer to entities in the physical environment, as shown in (23).

- (23) a. *sukuma i-kongo elyi*
push 5-log 5.DEM.PROX
'Push this tree trunk (log).'
- b. *ining-a wa-na eembe elyo*
give-FV 2-child 5-mango 5.DEM.MED
'Give the children that mango.'
- c. *wa- le- ining- o ki-kombe kya*
3PL- PST- give- PASS 7-cup 7.DEM.DIST
'They were given that cup (over there).'

As mentioned in the preceding section, many Bantu languages, including Kiwoso, exhibit three degrees of spatial deixis, as illustrated in (23). Typically, speakers employ gestural expressions such as touching, pointing, or directing eye gaze to draw the addressee's attention to the intended referent. In (23a), the proximal demonstrative *elyi* 'this' denotes that the entity *ikongo* 'tree trunk' is located close to the speaker, allowing the speaker to physically touch or display the object to the addressee. In (23b), the medial demonstrative *elyo* 'that' indicates that the object is situated near the addressee. Conversely, in (23c), the distal demonstrative *kya* 'that over there' signals that the referent is distant from both the speaker and the addressee. In the latter two cases, the speaker cannot physically touch the object but can instead gesture toward it, either by pointing with a finger or using eye gaze because the referent remains within the shared physical environment of the interlocutors.

7.2 Endophoric uses

Although the primary function of demonstratives is to focus the hearer's attention on objects, persons or locations in the speech situation, they may also refer to linguistic entities in discourse, and this is an endophoric use of demonstratives. The endophoric use is categorized

into two uses: anaphoric and discourse deictic use (Himmelman 1996: 224-29). The data indicate that the two categories of uses are attested in Kiwoso, as detailed in the following:

Anaphoric function

Anaphorically, demonstratives refer to entities already mentioned in the previous discourse, and they are used to keep track of the prior referents (Diessel 1999: 95). Himmelman (1996: 26) considers anaphoric use of demonstratives as “tracking use”. In many languages, anaphoric demonstratives are restricted to the distal or medial form (Nicolle 2012). The findings of this study indicate that all three forms of demonstratives in Kiwoso can be used anaphorically, as exemplified in (24).

- (24) a. *wa-ka wa-le- ur- a umbe. umbe tya ti- ka- fo*
2-woman 2- PST-buy-FV 10.cow 10.cow 10.DEM-DIST 10-PERF-die
ti- la- shaa
10-NEG-produce
‘Women bought cows. Those cows died without reproducing.’
- b. *wa-na wa-le-fik- a wa-ka- lal- a wa-la- ly-a. ekyo*
2-child 2-PST-arrive-FV 2- PERF-sleep-FV 2-NEG-eat-FV 5.DEM.MED
keumir-a wandu
pain-FV 2-people
‘The children arrived and slept without eating. That surprised people.’

The data demonstrate that Kiwoso employs demonstratives with a range of anaphoric functions, similarly to many other Bantu languages. For instance, in (24a), the distal demonstrative *tya* encodes co-reference to the previously mentioned noun *umbe* ‘cow’, thereby fulfilling a referential function. In (24b), the antecedent of the medial demonstrative *ekyo* is not a noun but an entire clause, *wakalala walalya* ‘they slept without eating’. This shows that, in Kiwoso, the antecedent of a demonstrative may be either a nominal or a clausal expression. Notably, the proximal demonstrative is not used anaphorically in referential contexts, regardless of whether the antecedent is a noun or a clause. Instead, distal demonstratives commonly refer back to noun antecedents, while medial demonstratives typically take clausal antecedents. Demonstratives in Kiwoso also encode topic continuity. Beyond these functions, Kiwoso demonstratives perform several other anaphoric roles, including referent disambiguation, topic shift or reintroduction, and contrastive reference, as illustrated by the examples in (25a), (25b), and (25c), respectively.

- (25) a. *wa-na wa-bhi bhe-tola-a nfongo ulyo umwi kafuluk-a*
2-child 2-two 2- cross-FV 3ridge DEM.MED one fall- FV
‘Two children were crossing the ridge that one fell.’
- b. *wa-na wa-le- uk- a shuule wa-kaidyia misa.*
2-child 2- PST-leave-FV school 2-pass by church
‘The children left the school and pass by the church.’
Paadi kaamb-a shing-a nlango! wa-na walya wa-kadich-a
Priest say-FV close-FV 3door 2-child 2.DEM.DIST 2- run- FV
‘The priest says closed the door! Those children run away’.
- c. *wa-ka wa-le- ur- a nungu niini na ngitu. Iya*
2-woman 2- PST-buy-FV 9pot big and small 9.DEM.DIST

ngitu i-kabarik-a
 small 9-break- FV

‘Women bought big and small pots. That small one broke.’

In (25a), the demonstrative *ulyo* clarifies that it was only *one* of the children who fell and broke a leg, thereby identifying the specifically affected participant among multiple potential referents. In (25b), the demonstrative *walya* re-introduces the earlier referent *wana* ‘children’ after an intervening clause, signalling a return to an established topic. Example (25c) illustrates contrastive reference, where the demonstrative *iya* marks the *small pot* as the salient referent in contrast to the *big pot*. Together, these patterns demonstrate the rich anaphoric and discourse-organizing functions encoded by Kiwoso demonstratives.

Discourse-deictic usage

In discourse-deictic uses, demonstratives refer to abstract such as propositions, events, or ideas in the discourse as a whole rather than a concrete specific referent in the physical world (Diessel 1999). The demonstratives with discourse-deictic function are used to link two discourse units, namely the one in which they are embedded and the other one to which they refer (Diessel 1999). Discourse-deictic usage is closely related to anaphoric propositional reference because both refer to information already available within the discourse, though they operate at different levels of reference. In anaphoric propositional reference, the demonstrative typically points back to a specific proposition in the immediately preceding text, treating that proposition as a discrete referential entity, as shown in (24b). In discourse-deictic usage, however, the demonstrative refers to broader stretches of discourse, guiding the listener’s attention to a larger discourse segment as a meaningful unit. Such reference may involve earlier statements, ideas, events, or propositions, or may project forward to subsequent discourse, as illustrated in (26).

- (26) a. *wa- le- kumb-a mburu wa-kaur-a nguku! ekyo kye-umir-a wandu*
 3PL- PST-sell- FV 10goat 2- buy- FV 9hen 7DEM.MED 7-hurt-FV 2people
 ‘They sold the sheep and bought the hens! That hurt people.’
- b. *a- le- shind-a mi-tihani. ekyo ki- le- n - ning-a sifa*
 2SG- PST- pass- FV 4-exam 7.DEM-MED 7- PST-OM-give- FV respect
 ‘He passed the exams. That made him respected.’
- c. *a- le- waang-a n-kutanu kaded-a na wa-miku tubu*
 2SG- PST- call- FV 3-exam talk- FV with 2-elder only
Ekyo kyo wa-le- n- kund-i- a
 7.DEM-MED 7-was 2- PST-OM-love-APPL- FV
 ‘He called the meeting and talked to elders only. That was the reason they loved him.’

The examples in (26) demonstrate that, beyond their referential and tracking functions, demonstratives may also serve to structure, evaluate, and frame discourse. In such instances, they extend their deictic scope beyond specific entities, propositions, or events to encompass larger discourse segments. The demonstrative *ekyo* in the examples refers not to the individual events, ideas or propositions, but to the preceding discourse as a coherent unit.

7.3 Emphatic function

Alongside their exophoric, anaphoric, and discourse-deictic uses, demonstratives also serve an emphatic function. Pragmatically, demonstratives may be used not merely to track a referent, but to foreground it, highlighting its discourse importance. In the majority of languages, the emphatic role is achieved when the existing demonstrative is reinforced morphologically by either adding extra deictic particles or through doubling the demonstratives (Lyons 1999; Asiiimwe 2024). For example, in Kiswahili, demonstratives are reduplicated to encode emphasis (Lyons 1999: 116). The findings of the present study indicate that in order to highlight or single out the exact entity or object being referred to, the Kiwoso speakers use demonstrative reduplication. Examples in (27) illustrate.

- (27) a. *wa- le- kor- a kelya kya kya*
3PL-PST-cook-FV 7food 7.DEM.DIST 7.DEM.DIST
‘They cooked that very/same food.’
- b. *waanga wa-na ewo ewo*
call 2-child 2.DEM.MED 2.DEM.MED
‘Call those very (same) children.’
- c. *shi-adu eshi eshi ngi-sh- i- a*
8-shoe 8.DEM.PROX 8.DEM.PROX 1SG-look-APPL-FV
‘These very (exactly) shoes are what I am cooking for.’
- d. *ekyi ekyi kyo kelya kyaho*
7.DEM.PROX 7.DEM.PROX 7.is 7.food 7.POSS
‘This very one is your food.’

The examples in (27) show that the repetition of demonstratives make the objects/entities referred-to to stand out from other parts of the information conveyed. It has been realised that, in Kiwoso, emphasis can be encoded through reduplication of the same demonstrative forms, as (27) shows. However, it is possible to combine locative and non-locatives demonstratives to indicate emphasis, as shown in (28).

- (28) a. *lya kulya i-kari lyako*
5.DEM.DIST DEM.DIST (locative) 5-car 5.POSS
‘That one over there is my car.’
- b. *walya kulya wa-na wao*
2.DEM.DIST DEM.DIST (locative) 2-child 2.POSS
‘Those ones over there are their children.’
- c. *mmba iya alya yao*
9house 9.DEM.DIST DEM.DIST 9.POSS
‘That house over there is theirs.’
- d. *wa-na ewa yaa wao*
2-child DEM.PROX DEM.PROX (locative) 2.POSS
‘These children right here are theirs.’

Examples in (28) indicate that pronominal and adnominal demonstratives can combine with locative demonstratives to highlight an object or a person referred to in the discourse. The objects emphasized in the examples in (28) were described in relation to a given location. The

findings demonstrate further that speakers may also employ reduplication of locative demonstratives to emphasise location of the referents, rather than the referents themselves. Therefore, depending on the distance of location or place of a referent from the interlocutors, forms such as *kunu kunu*, *kulya kulya*, *yaa yaa*, and *yoo yoo* can be used to encode emphasis of referent’s location or place. Examples in (29) are indicative.

- (29) a. *wa- le- tan- a mmba kunu kunu*
3PL- PST- build-FV 9house here here
‘They built the house in this very place (exactly here).’
b. *wa- le- lal- a yoo yoo Muchi*
3PL- PST-sleep- FV there there Moshi
‘They spent the night exactly there at Moshi.’
c. *wa- le- id- a yaa yaa*
3PL- PST-pass-FV here here
‘They passed through in this very place (exactly here).’
d. *wa- le- baki kulya kulya*
3PL- PST-remain there there
‘They remained exactly over there.’

The locative demonstratives *kunu* and *yaa* entail that the location referred to is near/closer and visible to both speaker and addressee. On the other hand, *yoo* indicates that the location is far from both the speaker and the addressee although it can be visible (within their reach) to both. *Kulya* denotes that the location is far from both speaker and addressee, and it is invisible to them (beyond their reach). It is only the shared experience between the two interlocutors that enables them to identify the place/location being talked about.

It is not only pronominal and locative demonstratives that can be reduplicated to encode emphasis in Kiwoso. Manner demonstratives *kudi* ‘this way/like this/in this manner’ and *kudo* ‘that way/like that/in that manner’ are also commonly doubled to emphasis exactly way that something is done, or to stress the style of doing or performing something, as shown in (30). The demonstrative *kudi* unlike *kudo* is often accompanied by touching the object being indicated.

- (30) a. *wada kudi/kudo*
‘Hold this/that way/like this/that.’
b. *wada kudi kudi/kudo kudo*
‘Hold exactly this way/that way.’

Doubling demonstratives to express emphatic role is a widely used mechanism in many Bantu languages including Makhuwa (Van der Wal 2010), Fwe (Gunnink 2018) Chiyao (Taji 2024), and Runyankore-Rukiga (Asiimwe 2024).

7.4 *Recognitional use*

Recognitional function is achieved when a demonstrative is used to refer to a referent which has not been previously mentioned and which is not physically present, but which the speaker assumes the hearer can identify because it forms part of their shared knowledge (Diessel 1999: 105; Himmelmann 1996: 230-39). Recognitional uses are distinct from exophoric uses in that

in the former, the environment shared by the speaker and hearer is cognitive, whereas the context shared in the latter is physical (Nicolle 2012: 21). In recognitional uses, the referents are identified within the interlocutors' shared cognitive environment. In Kiwoso, recognitional function is encoded by medial (31a) or distal demonstratives (31b).

- (31) a. *kelya kya wa- le- kor- a ki-le-tosh-a*
7.food 7.DEM.DIST 3PL-PST-cook-FV 7-PST-enough-FV
'The food that they cooked was sufficient.'
b. *mwalimu ulyo a- le- dek- a*
1.teacher 1.DEM.MED 2SG-PST-disappear-FV
'That teacher disappeared.'

As a core characteristic, recognitional demonstratives activate information that the speaker assumes is already part of the hearer's background knowledge (Diessel 1999: 105; Himmelmann 1996: 230-239). In (31a), the demonstrative signals that the speaker knows the hearer can readily identify the cooked food being referred to, even though it has not been explicitly mentioned in the current discourse. Similarly, in (31b), both interlocutors share common knowledge about the teacher in question, perhaps because they were taught by the same individual or attended the same school where that teacher worked. The recognitional demonstrative thus relies on mutual, culturally or personally shared experience to facilitate reference.

This section has described the functions of demonstratives in Kiwoso. The analysis presented in this section has shown that in addition to marking spatial relations (deictic function) demonstratives in Kiwoso are used to emphasize a particular referent, denote definiteness, and activation of old information.

8 Conclusion

Demonstratives are among essential components of language that enables speakers and addressees develop a shared sense of reference in both physical and discourse contexts. This paper has examined demonstratives in Kiwoso in relation to form, syntactic structure and functions. The findings demonstrate that Kiwoso exhibits three-way system of demonstratives, namely proximal, medial, and distal. These forms are deeply integrated into noun class system. It has been established further that the morphological structure of demonstratives in Kiwoso involves an initial element *e-* for the proximal and medial forms.

Syntactically, demonstratives in Kiwoso display both pronominal and adnominal characteristics. The adnominal demonstratives are canonically postposed. The findings indicate that in addition to their primary function (spatial-deixis), demonstratives serve other linguistic and communicative roles such as marking emphasis and recognitional function.

This study has contributed insights into morphosyntactic typology and semantic-pragmatics of demonstratives in Bantu languages. The paper has focused on demonstratives in the spoken discourse, it would be interesting to conduct a comparative study on the morphosyntax and semantic-pragmatics of demonstratives in Kiwoso and other related Bantu languages to provide deeper insights into Bantu syntax, morphology, and linguistic typology.

Abbreviations

APPL	applicative
AUG	augment
DEM	demonstrative morpheme
DIST	distal
FV	final vowel
LOC	locative
MED	medial
NEG	negation
OM	object marker
PASS	passive
PFV	perfective
PL	plural
POSS	possessive
PROX	proximal
PST	past
SM	subject marker
SG	singular

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Aurelia Mallya

Department of Foreign Languages and Linguistics

University of Dar es Salaam

P. O. Box 35040, Dar es Salaam

e-mail: msakiphd@gmail.com

mallya.aurelia@udsm.ac.tz

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Semantic Conflation Patterns of Motion Events in Vietnamese: Cognitive and Typological Perspectives

Ly Ngoc Toan

Ho Chi Minh City University of Law, Vietnam

This study examines how Vietnamese motion events conflate semantic components in verb roots, and serial-verb constructions in light of Talmy's and Slobin's typological predictions. This study employed a qualitative, typologically guided analysis, and it was supported by descriptive frequency counts. The data were compiled from two dictionaries and seventeen online stories, which produced 119 manner-motion verbs, 250 path-motion verbs, 265 cause-motion verbs, and 300 contextual tokens. The results show that Vietnamese encodes core internal components, namely Manner, Path, Cause, and a limited range of Figure and Ground in verb roots, whereas external components such as Direction, Result, Circumstance, Purpose, Sound, Vehicle, State, Change, and Co-motion are expressed through verb phrases and serial verb constructions. These distributions point to a stable hybrid profile in Vietnamese that combines verb-internal packaging with expansion at the level of constructions. The study provides a more precise refinement of motion-event typology for Vietnamese and offers implications for language teaching, translation practice, and natural language processing applications.

Keywords: *semantic conflation patterns, motion events, lexicalization patterns, construction grammar*

1 Introduction

Motion is one of the most fundamental domains of human cognition and experience, and it is encoded across languages in a pervasive manner, but languages encode it in different ways. Talmy (1985, 2000) builds on this insight and conceptualizes motion encoding through the notion of a motion event that consists of four semantic components, namely Figure, Ground, Manner, and Path. The Figure is the entity that moves or is located. The Ground is the entity that provides the reference frame for the Figure's location or trajectory. The Manner specifies how motion is carried out. The Path specifies the course or direction of motion. Talmy also proposes that Manner and Cause can function as co events, and these co-events elaborate how motion occurs or why motion occurs. Aske (1989) analyzes Spanish and shows that the Path component in a verb-framed language is lexicalized in the main verb. This lexicalization pattern restricts the overt encoding of Manner in the main verb. However, other semantic components, such as Circumstance or Causation, may still be expressed outside the main verb, and Figure 1 schematizes this distribution.

Figure 1: An expanded motion event (Aske 1989: 1)

Cross-linguistic contrasts in motion event can be illustrated by four examples below. In satellite-framed languages such as English, Manner is lexicalized in the main verb (*to run*) and Path is expressed in a satellite, namely preposition or particle (*into*).

- (1) The boy **ran into** the house.

In this example, *to run* encodes Manner and *into* encodes Path. In verb-framed languages such as French and Spanish, Path tends to be lexicalized in the main verb; whereas, Manner is expressed peripherally or omitted.

- (2) Le garçon est **entré dans** la maison.
The boy auxiliary enter into the house
'The boy entered the house.'

Serial-verb languages like Chinese often encode both Manner and Path in two verbs in a construction:

- (3) Nán hái **pǎo jìn** wū lǐ (男孩跑进屋里)
The boy ran enter house inside
'The boy ran into the house.'

Similarly, Vietnamese allows the combination of a Manner verb (*chạy*) and a Path verb (*vào*) in a serial-verb construction:

- (4) Anh ấy **chạy vào** nhà.
He run enter house
'He ran into the house.'

In example (4), the first verb *chạy* lexicalizes Manner and the second verb *vào* lexicalizes Path. Therefore, these two verbs are contiguous, and they share the same Figure and form one macro event. Since Talmy's (1985, 2000) distinction between satellite-framed languages and verb-framed languages has been refined, a range of typologists and cognitive linguists have identified additional channels through which motion components can be encoded. Ibarretxe Antuñano (2025) and Van Hoey (2025) show that ideophones and literary motion expressions can function as independent channels for encoding Manner and Path, and their findings extend motion typology beyond the original divide between verbs and satellites. Slobin (2004) introduces a third type that he calls equipollently-framed languages, and in this type Manner and Path are encoded through two verbal elements rather than through a main verb with a satellite. This pattern is prominent in serial verb constructions that are attested in many Southeast Asian languages and many West African languages. In this expanded typology, Vietnamese is considered an equipollently-framed language because Vietnamese speakers encode Manner and Path by combining two verbs in serial verb constructions. Moreover, Bohnemeyer et al. (2022) show that the ways speakers use reference frames and encode motion differ markedly from one community to another. This variation across communities

underscores the need for language-specific analyses that are firmly grounded in a coherent and well-defined theoretical framework.

Research on motion encoding in Vietnamese has attracted myriad attention from typological and cognitive perspectives. Early studies, such as Nguyễn Lai (2001), focus on directional verbs and their inherent motion meanings, and they provide a semantic inventory of Path that is related to lexical resources in Vietnamese. Subsequent work, including Mai Thị Thu Hân (2011), compares English and Vietnamese lexicalization patterns in order to situate Vietnamese in Talmy's motion typology while Hoàng Tuyết Minh (2016) further highlights the prominence of Path in Vietnamese motion verbs. More recent studies expand the scope beyond Path verbs alone. Lưu Quý Khương and Lý Ngọc Toàn (2018) document semantic and distributional differences among manner verbs, and Lý Ngọc Toàn (2019, 2022) extends the discussion to path-motion events and cause-motion events. At the constructional level, Dương Hữu Biên (2023) examines fictive motion in Vietnamese, and Võ Từ Phương (2025) argues that Vietnamese speakers frequently encode Manner and Path together in serial verb constructions, as illustrated in example (4). In short, these studies show that Vietnamese encodes motion through a combination of lexical resources, especially Path oriented verbs, and constructional resources, especially serial verb constructions, but they also suggest that an account of how these resources interact in a theoretical framework is still needed.

Although several studies have addressed this topic, a key gap remains. Previous studies have not provided a systematic account in a coherent theoretical framework of how motion semantic components are conflated in Vietnamese across verb roots and serial verb constructions. These studies have also not explicitly and systematically situated Vietnamese conflation patterns with respect to the typological predictions proposed by Talmy and by Slobin. Moreover, though these studies draw on cognitive and typological linguistics, they usually concentrate on individual components, such as the prominence of Path or variation in Manner, rather than on the overall distribution of motion components across lexical packaging and constructional packaging. The present study addresses this gap through a language investigation of motion expressions in Vietnamese. The study adopts a typological interpretive perspective because Vietnamese patterns are evaluated against verb-framed, satellite-framed, and equipollently-framed profiles, but the study does not analyze parallel data from non-Vietnamese languages.

The central notion in this study is semantic conflation. In Talmy's (1985, 2000) framework, semantic conflation refers to the integration of multiple semantic components of a motion event into a lexical unit or into a constructional unit. Following Talmy's definition, the present study uses the term semantic conflation to describe how Vietnamese speakers integrate motion components in verb roots and also integrate motion components in larger verb phrase structures, including serial verb constructions. The study examines this integration in order to clarify the distribution of motion components across lexical resources and constructional resources in Vietnamese. Based on this objective, the study addresses the following research questions.

- RQ1. How are internal components conflated in Vietnamese motion verbs, and what internal conflation patterns emerge across verb classes?
- RQ2. How do Vietnamese motion verbs combine with external components in verb phrases and serial-verb constructions, and what recurrent external conflation patterns are observed?

RQ3. How do the distributions of internal and external conflation situate Vietnamese in Talmy’s and Slobin’s typological predictions?

To answer these questions, the study conducts two models of semantic conflation. Internal conflation refers to cases in which one or more motion event components that are semantically entailed by the verb root are integrated into that verb root, as Figure 2a illustrates. External conflation refers to cases in which motion event components that are not semantically entailed by the verb root are contributed by adjacent elements in a verb phrase, and this contribution often takes the form of serial verb constructions, as Figure 2b illustrates. In this study, the labels internal components and external components are defined on the basis of Talmy’s motion event decomposition and Levin and Rappaport Hovav’s event structure model. Internal components include Manner, Path, and Cause because these components can be encoded in Vietnamese verb roots. In addition, Vietnamese motion verbs may incorporate Figure or Ground in lexical items, and these cases will be considered instances of internal conflation. External components include semantic components that are not entailed by the verb root and that extend the motion event through elements adjacent to the verb root. These components include Change, Circumstance, Co-motion, Direction, Intensifier, Purpose, Sound, State, and Vehicle. The study treats them as external because they are contributed by separate syntactic units, such as adverbs, particles, and additional verbs that participate in serial verb constructions.

Figure 2a: Internal conflation

Figure 2b: External conflation

On this basis, Talmy’s (1985, 2000) motion event framework provides the semantic inventory and the coding criteria for distinguishing internal conflation from external conflation. Slobin’s (2004) equipollently-framed hypothesis guides the analysis of serial verb constructions as elements that contribute to the encoding of Manner and Path. Goldberg’s (1995, 2006) construction grammar offers a model of how Vietnamese forms complex motion events through conventionalized pairings between form and meaning, and this model is relevant to cases of external conflation. Levin and Rappaport Hovav’s (1995, 1998, 2010) event structure model underpins the mapping between semantic components and event templates, and it also supports the distinction in this study between components that are entailed by the verb root and components that are supplied by peripheral elements. Figure 3 summarizes this analytic

framework by showing that Vietnamese allows internal conflation that parallels English verbs that conflate Manner, and it also allows external conflation that aligns with verb-framed patterns in French and Spanish, most clearly in serial verb constructions. In short, the internal and external conflation patterns simultaneously clarify how Vietnamese distributes motion event components between internal conflation of verbs and peripheral constructional components, and this distribution occurs while Vietnamese verbs remain morphologically simple.

Figure 3: Event structures of semantic conflation

2 Methodology

2.1 Research design

The study implements two models of semantic conflation: *internal conflation* and *external conflation* that are distinguished by whether motion-event components are semantically entailed by the verb root or supplied by peripheral elements. The research design is primarily qualitative and interpretive that is supported by quantitative counts and distributional comparisons. It comprises two components. The first is a lemma inventory of Vietnamese motion verbs that are compiled from major dictionaries. The second is a contextual analysis of motion-verb tokens that are extracted from the selected stories. The lemma inventory addresses RQ1, whereas the token-based analysis addresses RQ2 and RQ3.

Internal components and external components are adopted as analytical labels, grounded in Talmy’s motion-event framework and Levin and Rappaport Hovav’s event structure mapping. Each token is decomposed into these components. Internal components include Manner, Path, Cause, Figure, and Ground, because they may be entailed and encoded in Vietnamese verb roots. External components include Change, Circumstance, Co-motion, Direction, Emotion, Intensifier, Place/Location, Purpose, Result, Sound, State, Time, and Vehicle because they are not entailed by the verb root and extend the motion event through

adjacent elements. Vietnamese conflation patterns are interpreted with reference to the satellite-framed, verb-framed, and equipollently-framed profiles in linguistic typology.

Internal conflation occurs when one or more internal components are encoded in the verb root. External conflation occurs when the root encodes the motion element while one or more external components are contributed by adjacent elements within the verb phrase (e.g. secondary verbs, directional particles, adverbs, ideophones, or NPs). For example, in *đi chợ* ‘to go to the market’, *chợ* ‘market’ contributes an external Place component; in *bắn hạ* ‘to shoot down’, *hạ* ‘down’ contributes an external Result component. Serial verb constructions involve two or more verbs sharing the same subject, with each verb contributing a distinct component; typically, the first verb encodes Manner and the second encodes Path, as in *chạy vào* ‘to run into’, where *chạy* ‘to run’ encodes Manner and *vào* ‘into’ encodes Path. These verbs are coded separately to evaluate Slobin’s typological predictions.

In terms of procedure, first, motion verbs are identified in each sentence, then each token is coded for the presence of internal and external components. Tokens are labeled as instances of internal or external conflation and tabulated for descriptive comparison. Table 1 presents the coding categories and decision rules, explicitly linked to the theoretical framework to ensure analytic transparency.

2.2 Data collection

Data were collected to examine Vietnamese internal and external conflation at both lemma and token levels from two sources. The lemma dataset comes from two major dictionaries (Quang Hùng & Khắc Lâm 2007; Hoàng Phê 2020). The token dataset comes from seventeen stories on *truyenfull.vn* (Appendix A). These stories portray rural daily life, social conflict, and psychological hardship; thus, they provide frequent and concrete descriptions of bodily motion and cause-motion events. The selection keeps author, historical period, and narrative style relatively constant, which reduce genre/register effects on motion encoding.

From the dictionaries, motion-verb lemmas were compiled to build a type inventory. The final inventory includes 119 manner lemmas, 250 path lemmas, and 265 cause-motion lemmas. Only lemmas whose primary sense denotes physical motion were retained; near-duplicate synonyms were merged when justified by dictionary definitions, and obsolete or highly technical verbs were excluded. Each lemma was assigned to a semantic class and analyzed for entailed internal components in its definition. For example, *đẩy* ‘to push’ was classified as a cause-motion lemma that entails Cause, Motion, and Path; therefore, they exemplify internal conflation at the type level. These components were used to establish lemma-level patterns in the findings.

In parallel, token data were extracted from the seventeen stories. Each story was read sentence by sentence to identify motion verbs. A token was included if its lemma belongs to the dictionary inventory and its contextual use denotes physical displacement of a Figure; metaphorical or highly abstract uses (e.g. institutional progress) were excluded. Serial verb constructions and larger verb phrases were included whenever at least one element met the motion criteria; each motion verb in these complexes was coded for its own class and conflation pattern in the same sentential context. After exclusions, the corpus contains 420 sentences, of which 300 include at least one motion-verb token.

A lemma is a dictionary headword that represents a verb type, whereas a token is an attested contextual occurrence. Lemma counts describe type coverage across the three

inventories, while token counts support descriptive distributional comparison. Each token was annotated for surface form, lemma identity, semantic class, internal components, and external components. Table 1 summarizes the coding categories and annotation decisions.

Table 1: Coding rules

Category	What it codes	Decision rule	Example
MANNER internal	How motion occurs	Verb alone entails manner	<i>chạy</i> (to run), <i>bò</i> (to crawl)
PATH internal	Trajectory / direction	Verb alone entails path	<i>vào</i> (to enter), <i>ra</i> (to exit), <i>qua</i> (to cross)
CAUSE internal	Causing subevent	Verb entails agent-caused motion	<i>đẩy</i> (to push), <i>ném</i> (to throw), <i>bắn</i> (to shoot)
External components	Added outside V ₁	Meaning not entailed by V ₁ but contributed by V ₂ /particle/ adverb/ ideophone/ NP	Direction: <i>chạy vào</i> ; Result: <i>bắn hạ</i> ; Circum/Sound/Place/Vehicle/ Time: peripheral elaborators
Internal conflation (i)	Token label	Core M/P/C packaged in verb root; no independent external predicate	<i>Anh đẩy chiếc ghế.</i> He pushes the chair.
External conflation (e)	Token label	Any external component bonds with V ₁ to form complex predicate	<i>Anh ấy bắn hạ con chim.</i> He shot down the bird.

2.3 Data analysis

Data analysis is guided by Talmy’s motion-event framework, Slobin’s equipollently-framed hypothesis, and Goldberg’s construction grammar. Therefore, these perspectives provide the semantic inventory and typological expectations for coding and interpreting internal and external conflation. The analysis involves systematic coding of motion-verb tokens and descriptive comparison of internal and external conflation distributions across verb classes and component bundles. Each token was examined in context to identify the motion verb, determine associated components, and classify the token as internal or external conflation. A token was

coded as internal conflation when one or more components entailed by the verb root are integrated into that root; it was coded as external conflation when non-entailed components are supplied by adjacent elements such as particles, adverbs, or secondary verbs. For example, *Anh ấy chạy* instantiates internal conflation because *chạy* entails Manner, whereas *Anh ấy chạy qua hàng rào* exemplifies external conflation because *qua* adds Path outside the root.

The 300 tokens were analyzed in three stages. First, each sentence was scanned to identify motion verbs and annotate present internal/external components. Second, each token was assigned to a semantic class (Manner, Path, Cause) and labeled as internal or external conflation. Third, internal/external distributions were cross-tabulated by verb class and component bundles, and the tendencies were interpreted with reference to the three theoretical frameworks.

To maintain labeling consistency, fine-grained attributes from dictionary definitions and contexts were normalized into macro-features (e.g. fast, maximum speed, urgent → Speed; steady/regular pace → Pace regularity; forceful, violent → Force intensity). Micro-labels were retained only in illustrative examples. All descriptive counts and distributional patterns are based on macro-features, reducing annotator drift and enabling systematic comparisons. Coding was conducted in two passes. In the first pass, all tokens were annotated following Table 1. Then, interval, the dataset was re-checked in a second pass, focusing on borderline cases (e.g. purposive vs. locative complements and serial complexes). Disagreements were resolved by returning to dictionary definitions and contextual evidence, and recurring ambiguous cases were used to refine the operational rules before final tabulation. Tokens that remained non-motion or irreducibly ambiguous were excluded. This verification helps reduce annotator drift and supports stable distributional generalisations.

3 Findings and discussion

3.1 VERB [CAUSE MOTION]

This section examines semantic conflation patterns in Vietnamese cause-motion verbs, which denote events where an agent causes a Figure to move. The analysis focuses on how motion-event components are integrated into verb roots and into larger verb phrases. Following Talmy’s motion event framework and Goldberg’s construction grammar, the study distinguishes two types of conflation. Internal conflation occurs when the verb root encodes Cause together with at least one other core component, such as Figure, Manner, or Path so that the verb inherently evokes a cause-motion event. External conflation occurs when a cause-motion verb combines with peripheral elements in the verb phrase, especially in serial verb constructions, and these elements contribute additional components such as Result, Direction, Change, Intensifier, or State. Table 2 summarizes three internal conflation patterns and five external conflation patterns for Vietnamese cause motion verbs, and it shows that core meanings are often compressed in the verb root while peripheral meanings are expanded through constructions.

Table 2: Semantic conflation patterns of cause-motion verbs

Semantic components	Internal conflation patterns	External conflation patterns
	Internal components	External components

Semantic conflation patterns	Cause, Figure, Manner, Path				Change, Path, Result, State			
	Cause + Figure	Cause + Manner	Cause + Path	Cause + Result	Cause + Result + Intensifier	Cause + Result + Direction	Cause + Change	Cause + State
	8	27	30	67	20	49	44	20
Total	65				200			

3.1.1 Internal conflation patterns of cause-motion verbs

After analyzing 65 cause-motion verbs in Vietnamese, the findings show that these verbs conflate internal semantic components in three patterns, namely: $V_{[C+F]}$ (8), $V_{[C+M]}$ (27), and $V_{[C+P]}$ (30). These patterns are generalized in the pattern as follows:

$$\text{VERB}_{[\text{CAUSE MOTION}]} = [\text{x CAUSE}_{(i)} [\text{F MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{Inter-coms} \rangle]]$$

In this schema, x represents the causer role, and CAUSE(i) represents a cause-motion event whose core participants and subevents are lexically conflated into the verb. The term $\langle \text{Inter-coms} \rangle$ refers to the internal semantic components that are conflated into the verb root, including Cause (C), Figure (F), Manner (M), and Path (P). Therefore, the schema reflects the claim that Vietnamese cause-motion verbs encode a causative displacement template, in which the causer role and one or more internal components are co-lexicalized, and this co-lexicalization gives rise to the three internal conflation patterns identified in the data.

To begin with, when the internal components such as (C) and (F) are conflated into the cause-motion verbs, they establish the internal conflation pattern of $V_{[C+F]}$. This pattern shows that Vietnamese speakers simultaneously encode these internal components of a cause-motion event in a lexical structure.

$$V_{[C+F]} \Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(i)} [\text{F (default) MOVES}]]$$

In this pattern, (C) denotes the causer that initiates the event, and the verb root inherently profiles a force or agentive source. (F) is encoded as a default affected entity that is conceptually required by the verb for the event to be interpretable, even when (F) is not overtly realized. In this study, any directional or manner implications that are inseparable from such default Figures are treated as part of (F) rather than as independent (M) or (P) in this pattern. Verbs such as *phà* ‘to blow’, *vắt* ‘to squeeze’, and *bắn* ‘to shoot’ illustrate this pattern because each verb entails an initiating force and a specific default Figure that undergoes displacement.

$$\begin{aligned} \textit{Phà} &\Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(i)} [\text{F (default smoke/steam) MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{outward} \rangle]] \\ \textit{Vắt} &\Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(i)} [\text{F (default water) MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{outward by squeezing} \rangle]] \\ \textit{Bắn} &\Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(i)} [\text{F bullet/projectile MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{forward with force} \rangle]] \end{aligned}$$

The group of $V_{[C+F]}$ cause-motion verbs, whose lexical semantics already encode a causative displacement with two internal components. The verb root specifies (C) in the sense that it profiles an initiator that brings about an event. Therefore, the verb requires an external causer

argument to saturate this role in syntax or discourse. The verb root also specifies ⟨F⟩ in the sense that it presupposes a particular type of Figure as a default participant, even when that ⟨F⟩ is not overtly realized. Consequently, these verbs allow Vietnamese speakers to express a full CAUSE_(i) event in a compact way because ⟨C⟩ and ⟨F⟩ are already lexicalized in the verb. Though the verb can remain minimal while it still is semantically interpretable as a cause-motion event. The internal conflation is observed in the following example from *Rừng Xà Nu* (Nguyễn Trung Thành)

- (5) Chúng nó **bắn**.
they it shoot.
‘They shoot.’

In the clause *Chúng nó bắn*, the subject *chúng nó* corresponds to x, and x performs the causal initiation encoded by ⟨C⟩ in the verb *bắn*. The verb *bắn* also encodes ⟨F⟩ as a default projectile Figure. Therefore, even without an overt object, *bắn* still represents the CAUSE_(i) pattern in V_[C+F] because the verb root supplies both ⟨C⟩ and ⟨F⟩ while the syntax externalizes only x and leaves ⟨F⟩ to be recovered from the lexical meaning of the verb.

Second, the V_[C+M] is an internal conflation pattern that reflects how Vietnamese speakers can wrap the internal component of causer with two distinct manner components in a verb by capturing complex properties in one structure.

$$V_{[C+M]} \Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(i)} [F \text{ MOVE} \wedge \langle M \rangle]]$$

This pattern denotes a CAUSE_(i) event, in which ⟨C⟩ and ⟨M⟩ are co lexicalized in the verb root. The verb profiles a force that brings about the displacement of ⟨F⟩, and it simultaneously specifies ⟨M⟩ as an internal component rather than as a modifier contributed by peripheral material. As a result, verbs that exemplify V_[C+M] encode a dual manner profile in which two tightly linked manner properties jointly characterize how the caused displacement unfolds. In this study, any directionally or positionally constrained implications that are inseparable from the manner of causation are considered part of ⟨M⟩ in this pattern. Verbs such as *ném* ‘to throw’, *quật* ‘to strike or slam’, *vác* ‘to carry’, and *đá* ‘to kick’ illustrate V_[C+M] because each verb integrates the causative force with paired manner properties that are integral to the verb’s lexical meaning.

<i>Đá</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(i)} [F \text{ MOVE}_{\langle \text{forceful} \rangle} \wedge \langle \text{directed-impact} \rangle]]$
<i>Ném</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(i)} [F \text{ MOVE}_{\langle \text{forceful} \rangle} \wedge \langle \text{forward-trajectory} \rangle]]$
<i>Quật</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(i)} [F \text{ MOVE}_{\langle \text{forceful} \rangle} \wedge \langle \text{downward-arc} \rangle]]$
<i>Vác</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(i)} [F \text{ MOVE}_{\langle \text{carried} \rangle} \wedge \langle \text{on-shoulder} \rangle]]$

This group of V_[C+M] cause motion verbs includes verbs whose lexical semantics encode a causer role together with a manner component that contains two co occurring manner features, and these features are integral to the causative displacement event. The verb root encodes ⟨C⟩ because it profiles a force or an agentive source that brings the event about; therefore, the verb selects an external causer argument in syntax or in discourse. The verb root also encodes ⟨M⟩ because it wraps two non-neutral manner features in its internal event template. In *đá*, ⟨M⟩ combines forceful action with impact direction. In *ném*, ⟨M⟩ combines forceful action with a

forward trajectory. In *quật*, ⟨M⟩ combines forceful action with a downward arc. In *vác*, ⟨M⟩ combines carrying action with an on-shoulder body configuration. In this pattern, trajectory or posture implications that are inseparable from the manner of causation are treated as part of ⟨M⟩. Accordingly, these verbs differ from cause motion verbs with only one manner feature because their manner specification is not supplied by adverbials or by secondary verbs. The manner specification is conceptually obligatory and recoverable from the verb even in clauses that lack peripheral modifiers. The internal conflation is illustrated by the following tokens from *Chí Phèo* (Nam Cao).

- (6) Năm Thọ **vác** dao xộc vào.
 Nam Tho carry knife rush enter
 ‘Năm Thọ carried a knife and rushed.’

In this pattern, x is realized by *Năm Thọ* because *Năm Thọ* is the subject that triggers and controls the action denoted by *vác*. The verb *vác* encodes ⟨C⟩ because it profiles a force produced by x, and this force causes ⟨F⟩ to move, with ⟨F⟩ realized by *dao* in the sentence. The verb *vác* also encodes ⟨M⟩ because its lexical meaning specifies a carrying manner that is canonically shoulder carrying. Hence, this example reflects $V_{[C+M]}$ because *vác* bundles ⟨C⟩ and ⟨M⟩ into one verb root while the sentence supplies x and an overt ⟨F⟩ that goes through displacement under the encoded force and manner.

Third, the $V_{[C+P]}$ pattern refers to an internal semantic conflation, in which ⟨C⟩ and ⟨P⟩ are integrated in a verb itself. In this pattern, ⟨C⟩ functions as the causative force component that is encoded in the verb to start and sustain the displacement, whereas ⟨P⟩ functions as the path component that is also encoded in the verb to specify the direction or trajectory that constrains the displacement event.

$$V_{[C+P]} \Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(i)} [F \text{ MOVE} \wedge \langle P \rangle]]$$

This pattern denotes a cause-motion event $\text{CAUSE}_{(i)}$, in which ⟨C⟩ and ⟨P⟩ are co-lexicalized in the verb root. The verb encodes ⟨C⟩ as a causative force that brings about displacement, and it encodes ⟨P⟩ as an inherent path value that specifies a non-neutral spatial direction, trajectory, or endpoint of motion. Therefore, a verb articulates $V_{[C+P]}$ when its lexical meaning simultaneously profiles causative force and fixes the directionality of the caused displacement. Vietnamese verbs such as *đẩy* ‘to push’, *nâng* ‘to lift or raise’, *ấn* ‘to press’, and *chèn* ‘to wedge’ exemplify this pattern because each verb encodes ⟨C⟩ and an inherent ⟨P⟩ within one lexical unit.

<i>Đẩy</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(i)} [F \text{ MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{forward} \rangle]]$
<i>Nâng</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(i)} [F \text{ MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{upward} \rangle]]$
<i>Ấn</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(i)} [F \text{ MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{downward} \rangle]]$
<i>Chèn</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(i)} [F \text{ MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{into} \rangle]]$

This group of $V_{[C+P]}$ cause-motion verbs includes verbs whose lexical semantics co-lexicalize ⟨C⟩ and ⟨P⟩, and both components are integral to the causative displacement event. The verb root encodes ⟨C⟩ because it profiles a causative force that acts on a Figure and produces displacement so that the event is interpreted as initiated by force rather than launched by the

Figure alone. The verb root also encodes ⟨P⟩ because it boxes a non-neutral directional value in its internal event template so that displacement is directed forward in *đẩy*, directed upward in *nâng*, directed downward in *ấn*, and directed into in *chèn*. Therefore, these verbs differ from causative verbs without inherent ⟨P⟩ because the directional specification is conceptually obligatory and recoverable from the verb root in every instantiation of $V_{[C+P]}$. This pattern is illustrated by the following tokens from *Chí Phèo* (Nam Cao).

- (7) Hãy ngấm ngấm **đẩy** người ta xuống sông.
let secretly push person that descend river
'Let us secretly push that person down into the river.'

In this token, the verb *đẩy* represents the $V_{[C+P]}$ pattern because it lexically encodes ⟨C⟩ as an exerted causative force and lexically encodes ⟨P⟩ as a path directed forward. The component ⟨C⟩ is entailed by *đẩy* because the verb profiles a force produced by x that acts on ⟨F⟩ and causes displacement. The component ⟨P⟩ is also entailed by *đẩy* because the verb constrains the displacement to proceed forward away from the force source. The phrase *xuống sông* contributes a specific endpoint and a downward orientation, but it does not replace the verb internal forward direction that is already encoded in *đẩy*. Therefore, the token matches the $V_{[C+P]}$ formula because the verb supplies both ⟨C⟩ and ⟨P⟩ within one verb root.

From the analysis of three internal conflation patterns, namely $V_{[C+F]}$, $V_{[C+M]}$, and $V_{[C+P]}$, the findings show that each pattern selects a different group of internal components, but all three patterns assign the verb root a central role in encoding causative initiation and displacement. As a result, the causing event, the participant, and the manner or direction of displacement are recoverable from the verb without necessarily requiring a separate resultative or directional complement. The three patterns differ in their internal loads because $V_{[C+F]}$ encodes a default Figure, $V_{[C+M]}$ encodes a dual Manner profile, and $V_{[C+P]}$ encodes an inherent Path.

This distribution connects with Talmy's typology because $V_{[C+P]}$ is verb framed in the sense that Path resides in the verb while $V_{[C+F]}$ and $V_{[C+M]}$ prioritize non-Path internal components but still keep the verb as the main locus of cause-motion meaning. From a construction grammar perspective, each cause-motion verb functions as a self-sufficient form meaning construction that satisfies the cause-motion frame at the lexical level, and external material typically refines telicity or trajectory rather than creating them from scratch. Event structure theory reflects the same result by considering these verbs as compact verbs that integrate a CAUSE subevent with a MOVE subevent, and that allow Figure, Manner, or Path to be internal semantic components.

Typologically, Vietnamese contrasts with several well-studied patterns of cause motion. Unlike English, which often splits cause-motion meaning between a verb and a satellite, and unlike Romance languages, which lexicalize Path in the verb while expressing goals with prepositions, Vietnamese integrates comparable meanings inside a single verb root. It also differs from Chinese, where resultative compounds are a common strategy. In Vietnamese, comparable semantic richness comes from morphologically simple, monomorphemic verbs, from which listeners can directly infer a default Figure, force initiation, and an inherent trajectory.

3.1.2 External conflation patterns of cause-motion verbs

This section examines external conflation in Vietnamese cause-motion event, namely the external integration of CAUSE(e) events. As Table 2 summarizes, Vietnamese not only compresses internal semantic components into verb roots, but also builds cause-motion meanings by combining a cause-motion verb with one or more external components. In CAUSE(e) patterns, the verb root supplies the internal core of causation and displacement while the external element contributes a peripheral component such as Result (R), Change (CH), or State (S), and Direction. Therefore, the section analyzes externally CAUSE(e) events, in which the outcome of displacement is not lexically entailed by the main verb itself, but is supplied by a secondary verb, a resultative adjective, a particle, or a prepositional element.

Two-component conflation patterns

The analysis of 131 cause-motion verbs identifies three recurrent external conflation patterns in Vietnamese, namely V_[C+R] (67), V_[C+CH] (44), and V_[C+S] (20), and all of these patterns follow the general schema

$$\text{VERB}_{[\text{CAUSE MOTION}]} \Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(e)} [\text{F MOVE} \wedge (\text{Exter-coms})]]$$

This schema articulates external conflation in Vietnamese caused-motion events and distinguishes two-component patterns and three-component patterns. In the schema, x is the causer, CAUSE(e) is the external causative event, (F) is the Figure, and MOVE is the motion element that is encoded by the main verb. In two component patterns, the main verb encodes causation and displacement, and an external component supplies an outcome component, so that the event is interpreted as cause and outcome, with the outcome contributed by (R), (CH), (S), or (V). In three-component patterns, one additional external specification is added, typically a result and a following directional or post result refinement so that the event is interpreted as causation that leads to displacement and culminates in a distinct resultant pattern. Across both types, the main verb encodes cause and motion that are linked to x, whereas (Exter-coms) is realized by a secondary verb, a particle, or a prepositional element, and this division of labor produces Vietnamese cause-motion macro-events.

The V_[C+R] pattern is the most frequent external conflation type of a cause-motion event in Vietnamese, which profiles a two-component event that links a causal action, a cause motion, and a result state as described in the schema below:

$$\text{V}_{[\text{C+R}]} \Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(e)} [\text{F MOVE} \wedge (\text{result})]]$$

In this formula, x is the causer that launches the action, (F) is the Figure that is subjected to displacement, CAUSE(e) indexes the external causative event, MOVE is the motion element that is encoded by the main verb, and (R) is a resultant state contributed by an external element, typically a secondary verb in a serial verb construction. Therefore, the pattern bundles causation and displacement inside the main verb and adds a distinct result component outside the verb root. Because (R) specifies an endpoint state, the event is telic. In Vietnamese, (R) is commonly realized by a second verb, a particle, or a prepositional element. These two-component macro events are illustrated by expressions such as *đẩy ngã* ‘push down’, *ném vỡ* ‘throw and break’, *húc đổ* ‘ram down’, and *quật chết* ‘whip to death’.

$$\text{Đẩy ngã} \quad \Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(e)} [\text{F MOVE}_{\langle \text{forward} \rangle} \wedge \langle \text{fall} \rangle]]$$

<i>Ném vỡ</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE } \langle \text{forceful trajectory} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{break} \rangle]]$
<i>Húc đổ</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE } \langle \text{impact} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{collapse} \rangle]]$
<i>Quật chết</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE } \langle \text{violent} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{die} \rangle]]$

This verb group exemplifies the pattern by distributing semantic components across a serial verb construction. The main verb encodes the causal action and an internal manner specification that constrains how MOVE unfolds, such as $\langle \text{forward} \rangle$ in *đẩy*, $\langle \text{forceful trajectory} \rangle$ in *ném*, $\langle \text{impact} \rangle$ in *húc*, and $\langle \text{violent} \rangle$ in *quật*. The secondary verb supplies an entailed result state externally, namely $\langle \text{fall} \rangle$ in *ngã*, $\langle \text{break} \rangle$ in *vỡ*, $\langle \text{collapse} \rangle$ in *đổ*, and $\langle \text{die} \rangle$ in *chết*. Because $\langle R \rangle$ is contributed outside the main verb but remains in the same macro-event, the construction gives rise to a causative telic event, in which the causal subevent canonically culminates in the result state. This organization is illustrated in the following example from *Đông Trinh Ngải* (Nghiem Dieu Linh).

- (8) Chợt bị Hà **đẩy** **ngã**.
suddenly be Hà push fall.
‘I was suddenly pushed down by Hà.’

In this sentence, x is *Hà* as the causer and $\langle F \rangle$ is *tôi* as the displaced Figure. The verb *đẩy* encodes CAUSE(e) together with the internal manner implication $\langle \text{forward} \rangle$ and supplies MOVE while the secondary verb *ngã* supplies $\langle R \rangle$ as the entailed result $\langle \text{fall} \rangle$. Therefore, the serial verb construction *đẩy ngã* expresses a macro-event that combines causation, displacement, and attainment of the result state.

The $V_{[C+CH]}$ pattern is an external conflation type that extends a cause-motion verb by adding an explicit change-of-state endpoint, and this pattern is schematized as follows:

$$V_{[C+CH]} \Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE } \wedge \langle \text{change} \rangle]]$$

In this pattern, the main verb supplies CAUSE(e) and MOVE while the change component $\langle CH \rangle$ is realized outside the verb root by a resultative adjectival element that specifies the transformation endpoint. Because $\langle CH \rangle$ is entailed by the verb adjective construction, the resulting event is telic. The adjectival outcome fixes a transformation endpoint, as in outcomes such as broken, flattened, curved, or crushed.

<i>Đạp gãy</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE } [\langle \text{downward force} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{broken} \rangle]]]$
<i>Ép bẹp</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE } [\langle \text{forceful forward} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{flattened} \rangle]]]$
<i>Bẻ cong</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE } [\langle \text{forceful manipulation} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{curved} \rangle]]]$
<i>Đè giập</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE } [\langle \text{downward-pressure} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{crush/flatten} \rangle]]]$

This group of $V_{[C+CH]}$ cause-motion verbs consists of external verb phrases, in which the cause-motion verb supplies $\langle C \rangle$ and MOVE, and a resultative adjectival element supplies $\langle CH \rangle$ as a transformation endpoint. The verb root introduces the causal action that acts on $\langle F \rangle$ and triggers displacement while the adjective specifies the resultant state that is distinct from the motion element. Verb phrases such as *đạp gãy* ‘to break with a foot’, *ép bẹp* ‘to flatten by pressing’, *bẻ cong* ‘to bend’, and *đè giập* ‘to press down and crush’ exemplify this pattern because each phrase combines a causative motion verb with an adjectival result that encodes

⟨CH⟩ and yields a telic CAUSE(e) event. The V_[C+CH] external conflation is illustrated in the following token from *Trên những con đường Việt Bắc* (Nam Cao).

- (9) Bị gọng sắt **đè** **giập** xương.
be iron-clamp press crush bone
'(He was) crushed to the bone by the iron clamp.'

In this example, the verb phrase *đè giập* is a verb-adjective construction. The verb *đè* encodes ⟨C⟩ as a downward causative pressure that acts on ⟨F⟩ and brings about displacement, which supplies MOVE in the CAUSE(e) event. The adjectival element *giập* encodes ⟨CH⟩ as the change into a crushed state, and this change endpoint makes the event telic. Therefore, the token is interpreted as a CAUSE(e) event, in which downward causation leads to displacement and culminates in a definite transformation that is supplied by the external adjectival component.

The V_[C+S] pattern augments a cause-motion verb with a stable post-event state rather than a structural transformation, and it is formalized as follows:

$$V_{[C+S]} \Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{state} \rangle]]$$

In this formula, ⟨S⟩ is a state endpoint contributed by an external complement, such as tight, closed, fixed, or rigid. The main verb supplies CAUSE(e) and MOVE while the complement adds a distinct state component outside the verb root. Because ⟨S⟩ specifies an endpoint that persists after culmination, the resulting event is telic. The state complement is typically realized by an adjective, a secondary verb, a prepositional element, or a particle, and it often implies completeness or tightness.

<i>Buộc chặt</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE} \langle \text{binding action} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{tightly bound} \rangle]]$
<i>Đóng kín</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE} \langle \text{closing action} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{fully closed} \rangle]]$
<i>Mở toang</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE} \langle \text{opening action} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{wide open} \rangle]]$
<i>Đè cứng ngắt</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE} \langle \text{pressing action} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{rigid} \rangle]]$

This group of verb phrases consists of externally componentated verbs, in which the verb root encodes ⟨C⟩ as a causative force that brings about displacement, and the external element encodes ⟨S⟩ as a stable resultant condition that persists after the event. The state complement fixes a telic endpoint by specifying the persistent pattern that reaches at the end of displacement. Typical verb phrases illustrating this structure include *buộc chặt* 'to tie tightly', *đè cứng ngắt* 'to press until rigid', *đóng kín* 'to close completely', and *mở toang* 'to open wide' because each combines a causative motion verb with a state complement that gives rise to a post event state and foregrounds ⟨S⟩ rather than ⟨CH⟩. The V_[C+S] external conflation is illustrated in the following token from *Điếu văn* (Nam Cao).

- (10) Tôi **đóng** **kín** cửa phòng.
I close tight door room.
'I closed the room door completely.'

In this pattern, *x* is realized by *tôi* as the causer. The verb *đóng* encodes ⟨C⟩ because it profiles a force produced by *x* that acts on ⟨F⟩, realized by *cửa phòng*, and brings about MOVE. The adjective *kín* encodes ⟨S⟩ by specifying the stable resultant state of being fully closed, and the combination *đóng* + *kín* forms the verb phrase *đóng kín* that packages the causative displacement element together with this post-event state. In short, this token expresses a telic CAUSE(e) event, in which causative force leads to displacement and culminates in a persistent state endpoint that is supplied by the external complement.

For the two-component external conflation patterns, the three Vietnamese patterns are manifested by the schema $\text{VERB}_{[\text{CAUSE MOTION}]} \Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(e)} [\text{F MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{Exter-coms} \rangle]]$, in which the main verb encodes CAUSE(e) and MOVE, while an external complement supplies one endpoint, such as ⟨R⟩, ⟨CH⟩, ⟨S⟩, or an added manner value. This organization suggests an endpoint externalization strategy in Vietnamese, where telicity is tracked by the complement rather than by the verb root alone. The strategy resembles satellite-framed conflation with respect to telicity, but it extends Talmy’s satellite notion because Vietnamese endpoints are realized by particles and by adjectives, secondary verbs, and prepositional elements. In comparison with Romance languages and Chinese, Vietnamese maintains morphologically simple verb roots while it still allows a productive and semantically rich slot for external endpoints. Consequently, the two-component patterns support the view that endpoint externalization is a typological parameter that interacts with, but cannot be reduced to, the verb-framed and satellite-framed distinction in motion encoding.

Three-component conflation patterns

These patterns consist of 69 cause-motion verbs as summarized in Table 1, in which two external conflation patterns, namely $\text{V}_{[\text{C} + \text{R} + \text{I}]}$ (20), $\text{V}_{[\text{C} + \text{R} + \text{P}]}$ (49) are identified. These patterns follow the schema:

$$\text{VERB}_{[\text{CAUSE MOTION}]} \Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(e)} [\text{F MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{Exter-coms} \rangle]]$$

The first pattern, $\text{V}_{[\text{C} + \text{R} + \text{I}]}$, is schematized as:

$$\text{V}_{[\text{C} + \text{R} + \text{I}]} \Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(e)} [\text{F MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{R} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{I} \rangle]]$$

This formula represents a CAUSE(e) event, in which *x* is the causer and ⟨C⟩ is the initiating force produced by *x* that triggers caused motion. ⟨R⟩ marks the final outcome brought about by that motion and functions as the result endpoint. ⟨I⟩ is an intensifier that applies after ⟨R⟩ and specifies the degree or salience of the attained result without introducing a new motion subevent. Therefore, the structure encodes three ordered components, namely ⟨C⟩, ⟨R⟩, and ⟨I⟩, and these components form one macro event of coherent multi phase while the main verb remains morphologically simple.

<i>Quạt ngã nhào</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(e)} [\text{F MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{forceful} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{fall} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{heavily} \rangle]]$
<i>Hất văng mạnh</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(e)} [\text{F MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{upward} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{fly away} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{strongly} \rangle]]$
<i>Xô đổ ập</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(e)} [\text{F MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{push} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{collapse} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{suddenly} \rangle]]$
<i>Ném vỡ toang</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(e)} [\text{F MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{throw} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{break} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{loudly} \rangle]]$

This group of $\text{V}_{[\text{C} + \text{R} + \text{I}]}$ cause-motion verbs is realized as a verb serial construction of the form $\text{V1} + \text{V2} + \text{I}$, in which V1 encodes ⟨C⟩ as the causal action, V2 encodes ⟨R⟩ as the result

endpoint, and I encodes ⟨I⟩ as a degree specification that applies after ⟨R⟩ and is realized as an adjective or an adverb. Verb phrases such as *quật ngã nhào* ‘to strike down heavily’, *hất văng mạnh* ‘to jerk away forcefully’, *xô đổ ập* ‘to push over suddenly’, and *ném vỡ toang* ‘to throw and smash wide open’ represent this pattern because they integrate causative force, resultant displacement, and post result intensification into a telic macro event. The $V_{[C+R+I]}$ external conflation is illustrated in the following token from *Mỹ Nhân Nhập Vai* (Hoắc Hương Cô).

- (11) Hấn **hất văng mạnh** chủ thủ trong tay nàng.
He toss fling strong dagger in hand she
‘He flung the dagger out of her hand forcefully.’

In this $V_{[C+R+I]}$ pattern, x is realized by *hấn* as the causer, and ⟨F⟩ is realized by *chủ thủ*. The verb *hất* encodes ⟨C⟩ by profiling the force exerted by x that sets ⟨F⟩ into displacement, while the verb *văng* encodes ⟨R⟩ by specifying the flung-away result endpoint. The adjective *mạnh* encodes ⟨I⟩ because it scales the attained ⟨R⟩ as a high degree of force and intensity in the post-result stage. Consequently, the token expresses a multi-phase CAUSE(e) macro-event, in which ⟨C⟩ launches motion, motion culminates in ⟨R⟩, and ⟨I⟩ further qualifies that result.

The second pattern, $V_{[C+R+D]}$ is formulated as follows:

$$V_{[C+R+D]} \Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE} \wedge [\langle R \rangle \wedge \langle D \rangle]]]$$

This formula represents a CAUSE(e) macro event, in which x is the causer that initiates the causal action. ⟨R⟩ marks the resultant state brought about by the primary motion, and ⟨D⟩ specifies a directional or destination value that applies after ⟨R⟩ is achieved and refines the result phase. Therefore, this pattern encodes a three-component temporal sequence that consists of the cause, the resultant state ⟨R⟩, and the result directional specification ⟨D⟩, and these components integrate into one coherent multi phase event while the main verb remains morphologically simple.

<i>Đẩy ngã ra</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE} \wedge [\langle \text{push} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{fall} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{outwards} \rangle]]]$
<i>Xô đổ vào</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE} \wedge [\langle \text{push} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{collapse} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{inwards} \rangle]]]$
<i>Hất văng lên</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE} \wedge [\langle \text{upward} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{fly away} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{upwards} \rangle]]]$
<i>Quật ngã xuống</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE} \wedge [\langle \text{forceful} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{fall} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{downwards} \rangle]]]$

This group of $V_{[C+R+D]}$ cause-motion verbs is realized as macro serial verb constructions of the form V1 + V2 + V3, in which V1 encodes ⟨C⟩ as a causative force that sets the Figure into displacement, V2 encodes ⟨R⟩ as a resultant state, and V3 encodes ⟨D⟩ as a result directional value. Constructions such as *đẩy ngã ra* ‘to push and make fall outwards’, *xô đổ vào* ‘to push and cause to collapse inward’, *hất văng lên* ‘to fling and cause to fly upward’, and *quật ngã xuống* ‘to strike and cause to fall downward’ express this pattern because they integrate causation, an telic result, and a following directional specification into one macro event. The $V_{[C+R+D]}$ external conflation is illustrated in the following token from *Trần Cừ* (Nam Cao).

- (12) Minh **đẩy** anh đội viên **ngã ra**.
Minh push male squad-member fall outwards.
‘Minh pushed the squad member so that he fell outward.’

In this example, *x* is realized by *Minh* and ⟨F⟩ is realized by *anh đội viên*. The verb *đẩy* encodes ⟨C⟩ as the pushing force that brings about displacement, the verb *ngã* encodes ⟨R⟩ as the bounded falling result endpoint, and the directional element *ra* encodes ⟨D⟩ as the outward destination that applies after ⟨R⟩ is achieved. Thus, the token *r* manifests a CAUSE(e) macro event that matches the $V_{[C+R+D]}$ formula.

For the three-component external conflation patterns, Vietnamese motivates a cautious hybrid characterization that bears on ongoing debates about motion-event typology. On the one hand, it patterns with verb-framed systems in that cause-motion verbs lexicalize the CAUSE-MOTION core and may encode non-neutral directionality in the root. On the other hand, Vietnamese regularly externalizes result-phase material in ordered three-component constructions: ⟨C⟩→⟨R⟩→⟨I/D⟩ through co-verbs, particles, or adjectives/ adverbs that produce a telic macro-event with multiple syntactically independent heads. This shows that Vietnamese is not satellite-framed in the English sense, nor straightforwardly verb-framed; rather, it exploits serial componenting depth and endpoint externalization as separable resources. Given critiques that question the ontological status of the verb and satellite dichotomy, the Vietnamese three-component patterns support a typology where culmination and post-culmination refinement are constructionally distributed, refining cross-linguistic models of event structure.

3.2 VERB _[MANNER MOTION]

This section examines semantic conflation patterns of manner motion verbs in Vietnamese, in which verbs encode Manner ⟨M⟩ together with other motion components. Two conflation types are identified. Internal conflation involves internal components, including Manner ⟨M⟩ and, in some verbs, Figure ⟨F⟩ or Ground ⟨G⟩, so that the verb root alone provides a self-sufficient motion event element. External conflation involves the combination of ⟨M⟩ with peripheral components, such as Sound ⟨S⟩, Circumstance ⟨C⟩, Vehicle ⟨V⟩, or Co-motion ⟨Co⟩, which are encoded by adjuncts or by additional verbs in serial verb constructions and expand the event at the verb phrase level. Table 2 summarizes these internal and external patterns with representative examples.

Table 3: Semantic conflation patterns of manner-motion verbs

Semantic components	Internal conflation patterns		External conflation patterns			
	Internal components (Figure, Manner)		External components (Circumstance, Sound, Purpose, Vehicle)			
	Manner + Figure	Manner + Sound	Manner + Circumstance	Manner + Purpose	Manner + Vehicle	Manner + Co-motion
Conflation patterns of manner verbs	19	28	19	21	17	15
Total	19			100		

3.2.1 Internal conflation patterns of manner-motion verbs

As shown in Table 2, these patterns belong to the group of two-component conflation. This is, these patterns involve internal semantic components (Inter-coms), such as Manner ⟨M⟩, and Figure ⟨F⟩, which are integrated into the main verbs. Moreover, these verbs encode the movement type and its qualitative features in the verb root, without relying on additional

morphological markers. There is a main pattern: $V_{[M+F]}$ with 19 verbs. The general event formula for internal conflation patterns of manner verbs is:

$$\text{VERB}_{[\text{MANNER MOTION}]} = [F \text{ MOVE}_{(i)} \wedge \langle \text{Inter-coms} \rangle]$$

The first pattern, the $V_{[M+F]}$ pattern consists of two internal semantic components in a lexical unit, namely $\langle M \rangle$ and $\langle F \rangle$. This pattern is formalized as:

$$V_{[M+F]} \Leftrightarrow [F_{\langle \text{default} \rangle} \text{ MOVE}_{(i)} \wedge \langle M \rangle]$$

In this pattern, $\text{MOVE}_{(i)}$ denotes an internal manner-motion event. $\langle M \rangle$ refines the qualitative execution of the motion by specifying the characteristic mode of movement tied to the verb, and $\langle F_{\langle \text{default} \rangle} \rangle$ encodes a prototypical participant that is lexically presupposed by the verb. More particularly, $\langle F \rangle$ is not an argument slot to be filled syntactically, but a default selectional restriction embedded in the verb's semantics, as in *bước* 'to step', *mưa* 'to rain', *gật* 'to nod', and *cúi* 'to bend'.

<i>Bước</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [F_{\langle \text{human} \rangle} \text{ MOVE}_{(i)} \wedge [\langle \text{leg-based} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{measured} \rangle]]$
<i>Mưa</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [F_{\langle \text{raindrops} \rangle} \text{ MOVE}_{(i)} \wedge [\langle \text{fall} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{downward} \rangle]]$
<i>Gật</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [F_{\langle \text{human head} \rangle} \text{ MOVE}_{(i)} \wedge [\langle \text{bend} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{downward} \rangle]]$
<i>Cúi</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [F_{\langle \text{human upper body} \rangle} \text{ MOVE}_{(i)} \wedge [\langle \text{bend} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{downward} \rangle]]$

This group of $V_{[M+F]}$ manner-motion verbs can be characterized as verbs whose lexical semantics obligatorily combines a $\langle F \rangle$ together with a $\langle M \rangle$ specification, and these two components jointly define $\text{MOVE}_{(i)}$. The verb root encodes $\langle F \rangle$ by selecting a conventional class, for instance $\langle \text{legs} \rangle$ in *bước*, $\langle \text{water/ raindrops} \rangle$ in *mưa*, $\langle \text{human head} \rangle$ in *gật*, and $\langle \text{human upper body} \rangle$ in *cúi*. The verb root encodes $\langle M \rangle$ by fixing the characteristic motion profile associated with that $\langle F \rangle$, for instance leg-based measured stepping in *bước*, water descending from above in *mưa*, downward bending of the head in *gật*, and downward bending of the upper body in *cúi*. Therefore, the $\langle F \rangle$ and the $\langle M \rangle$ are internally supported by the verb rather than supplied by external modifiers. The $V_{[M+F]}$ internal conflation is illustrated in the following token from *Mua nhà* (Nam Cao).

- (13) **Mưa** như những cái roi da quất xuống đầu.
rain like many female whip leather lash down head
‘The rain was like leather whips lashing down on (one’s) head.’

The $V_{[M+F]}$ pattern shows that the verb *mưa* lexically encodes ⟨F⟩ as default water, concretely raindrops, and it lexically encodes ⟨M⟩ as water moving downward from above in a falling or dripping profile. The simile in (13) intensifies the sensory impact of that downward water movement, but it does not introduce ⟨F⟩ or ⟨M⟩ because both components are already co-lexicalized in *mưa*. Therefore, the token exemplifies a complete MOVE(i) event, in which default water undergoes downward displacement with an internally specified manner profile.

In short, the internal conflation pattern $V_{[M+F]}$ reveals a strong lexical-compression strategy in Vietnamese manner-motion verbs. These patterns support Talmy’s view that ⟨M⟩ is a core component of manner-motion verbs because the internal event can be recovered from the verb root without an obligatory satellite or complement. At the same time, they challenge Talmy’s strict satellite-framed versus verb-framed split since Vietnamese can co-lexicalize ⟨M⟩ together with a ⟨F⟩ inside one monomorphemic verb. This level of internal integration makes Vietnamese typologically closer to equipollently-framed languages such as Thai and Chinese than to verb-framed Romance languages such as Spanish and French, which rarely encode default ⟨F⟩ in the verb and instead externalize such information. From a construction-grammar perspective, these verbs function as self-sufficient form-meaning constructions in which ⟨F⟩ are lexically presupposed selectional restrictions instead of peripheral adjuncts, so event-structure models like Levin and Rappaport Hovav’s must allow ⟨F⟩ to be internal components in some languages. Therefore, Vietnamese manner-motion verbs instantiate a high-integration internal conflation parameter that positions Vietnamese between verb-framed and equipollently-framed systems while they preserve the option of external expansion elsewhere.

3.2.2 External conflation patterns of manner-motion verbs

This section is involved in external conflation patterns of Vietnamese manner-motion verbs that belong to two-component patterns. In these patterns, the verbs encode manner ⟨M⟩ while additional external components (Exter-coms) such as Sound ⟨S⟩, Circumstance ⟨Ci⟩, Purpose ⟨Pr⟩, Vehicle ⟨V⟩, and Co-motion ⟨CO⟩ are expressed through peripheral lexical units as in $V_{[M+S]}$, $V_{[M+Ci]}$, $V_{[M+Pr]}$, $V_{[M+V]}$, and $V_{[M+CO]}$. These patterns reflect a general mechanism of core compression, peripheral expansion, in which the clause maintains a concise semantic element while they still remain open to flexible contextual elaboration. The general formula for these patterns can be represented as:

$$\text{VERB}_{[MANNER\ MOTION]} = [{}_F\text{MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [{}_{[Exter-coms]}]]$$

In this formula, $\text{MOVE}_{(e)}$ is interpreted not merely as a general motion event, but specifically as an event of external manner motion, in which the motion and its manner are encoded together, and the external element functions as a distinct semantic component.

The first pattern is:

$$V_{[M+S]} \Leftrightarrow [{}_F\text{MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [{}_{\langle M \rangle \wedge \langle S \rangle}]]$$

This pattern combines a manner component ⟨M⟩ with an external sound component ⟨S⟩ to form a verb phrase of the type V+ adverb. In this formula, ⟨F⟩ is involved in displacement, MOVE(e) represents an event of external manner motion, ⟨M⟩ specifies how ⟨F⟩ moves, and ⟨S⟩ specifies the auditory impression that accompanies that movement. The sound is not inherent to the manner itself, but adds an extra perceptual component that heightens vividness. Vietnamese exploits this pattern with ideophones and reduplication to evoke multisensory motion in narrative discourse.

<i>Chạy rầm rập</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (fast) ∧ (rumbling)]]
<i>Đi lộp cộp</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (regular pace) ∧ (clattering)]]
<i>Bay vèo</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(airborne) ∧ (fast) ∧ (whizzing)]]
<i>Bò sột soạt</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(limb-based) ∧ (slow) ∧ (rustling)]]

This group of V_[M+S] manner-motion verbs can be characterized as expressive verb-adverb complexes, in which the verb root encodes ⟨M⟩ as the qualitative displacement profile of ⟨F⟩, and the sound adverb encodes ⟨S⟩ as a co-event temporally aligned with that displacement. Typical verb phrases include *chạy rầm rập* ‘to run noisily’, *đi lộp cộp* ‘to walk steadily with clattering sounds’, *bay vèo* ‘to fly quickly with a whizzing sound’, and *bò sột soạt* ‘to crawl slowly with rustling noise’. The contrast between *đi* as neutral walking and *chạy* as fast, high-energy running helps explain why different sound co-events pair with each verb. The V_[M+S] pattern is manifested in the following token from *Nước mắt* (Nam Cao).

- (14) Nên tờ giấy bạc **bay vèo**.
so banknote fly whizzing
‘So the banknote flew off with a whizzing sound.’

In this pattern, ⟨F⟩ is *tờ giấy bạc*, this ⟨F⟩ that is displaced. The verb *bay* encodes ⟨M⟩ by profiling an airborne, rapid flight manner of displacement of ⟨F⟩. The ideophone *vèo* encodes ⟨S⟩ by contributing a whizzing sound that accompanies the flight and intensifies its perceptual force through a morphological form of adverb. Therefore, the token realizes an external manner-motion event, in which ⟨F⟩ moves by a flight manner and the movement is rendered vivid by an aligned sound co-event.

The second pattern is shown as below:

$$V_{[M+C]} \Leftrightarrow [F \text{ MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [\langle M \rangle \wedge \langle C \rangle]]$$

This pattern bundles a manner component ⟨M⟩ with an external circumstance component ⟨C⟩ to form a verb phrase of the type V + adverb. In this pattern, ⟨F⟩ is the ⟨F⟩ that is subjected to displacement, MOVE(e) is an external manner-motion event encoded by the main verb, and ⟨C⟩ frames that motion in a situational, psychological, or attitudinal context. The circumstance component does not add a new motion element, but it shapes the pragmatic interpretation by conveying meanings such as aimlessness, urgency, timidity, or playful stance.

<i>Đi lang thang</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (aimless) ∧ (wander)]]
<i>Chạy thực mạng</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (fast) ∧ (escape)]]
<i>Đi khúm núm</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (timid) ∧ (submissive)]]

Nhảy non-ton ⇔ [F MOVE_(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (playful) ∧ (lively)]]

This group of V_[M+C] manner-motion verbs consists of expressive verb-adverb complexes, in which the verb root supplies the locomotion profile and manner of ⟨F⟩, while the adverbial element contributes ⟨C⟩ as an evaluative or contextual overlay. Verb phrases include *đi lang thang* (to wander aimlessly), *chạy thực mạng* ‘to run desperately’, *đi khúm núm* ‘to walk timidly or submissively’, and *nhảy non ton* ‘to jump playfully’ because each verb retains a stable manner core and adds a circumstance that signals speaker evaluation or participant attitude. The V_[M+C] pattern is represented in the following token from *Người làng Ner* (Ngọc Tấn).

- (15) Cô ấy **đi lang thang** rồi quên mất đường về.
she walk wander then forget lose road return
‘She wandered around and then forgot the way home.’

This example shows that ⟨F⟩ is *cô ấy*, the displaced ⟨F⟩. The verb *đi* encodes MOVE_(e) with a neutral leg-based manner ⟨M⟩. The adverbial *lang thang* encodes ⟨C⟩ by framing the walking as aimless and unfocused. Therefore, this sentence realizes a external manner-motion event, in which ⟨F⟩ moves by walking and the circumstance component fixes the event as wandering.

The third pattern is represented as follows:

V_[M+Pr] ⇔ [F MOVE_(e) ∧ [(M) ∧ (Pr)]]

This pattern encodes a manner component ⟨M⟩ together with an explicit purposive goal ⟨Pr⟩ to form a serial verb complex. In this case, MOVE_(e) denotes the externally construed manner-of-motion event encoded by the main verb, whereas ⟨Pr⟩ identifies the intended motion endpoint, the goal toward which the Figure’s displacement is directed. More specially, ⟨Pr⟩ in Vietnamese may be realized either as (i) a goal-action (e.g. *học* ‘to study’, *chợ* ‘shop/ market shopping’, *dịch* ‘relief work’ or (ii) a conventionalized destination noun that functions as an intended endpoint in fixed motion expressions (e.g. *nhà* ‘home’ in *về nhà*). The key property of this pattern is that Vietnamese keeps the motion verb and the purposive goal element syntactically independent while they share the same subject, as in *đi học* ‘go to study/school’, *đi chợ* ‘go shopping/market-going’, *chạy dịch* ‘to rush to relief work’, and *về nhà* ‘to return home’.

Đi học ⇔ [F MOVE_(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (regular pace) ∧ (study)]]
Chạy dịch ⇔ [F MOVE_(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (urgent) ∧ (do relief work)]]
Đi chợ ⇔ [F MOVE_(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (regular pace) ∧ (go shopping)]]
Về nhà ⇔ [F MOVE_(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (regular pace) ∧ (return-home)]]

This group of V_[M+Pr] manner-motion verbs can be characterized as serial complexes, in which the manner-motion verb profiles displacement with ⟨M⟩, and the subsequent element contributes ⟨Pr⟩ as an intended endpoint that completes a destination-/purpose-oriented interpretation. Therefore, they differ from manner-motion verbs, in which no purposive goal component is integrated into the verb phrase. The following token from *Nước mắt* (Nam Cao) exemplifies this pattern.

- (16) Mãi đến chiều mới về nhà mà không ăn thì đói.
only until afternoon then return home but not eat then hungry
‘Only in the afternoon did (they) return, and if (they) did not eat, (they) would be hungry.’

In this example, ⟨F⟩ is the understood returning participant (Figure). The verb *về* encodes MOVE(e) together with ⟨M⟩ as a return-movement profile. The following element *nhà* contributes ⟨Pr⟩ as an intended endpoint, which gives rise to a purposive/destination-oriented return event. Even when the endpoint is only contextually recoverable rather than overtly specified, the construction still licenses a goal-oriented reading in which the motion is construed as directed toward attaining that endpoint.

The V_[M+V] pattern is schematized as follows:

$$V_{[M+V]} \Leftrightarrow [F \text{ MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [\langle M \rangle \wedge \langle V \rangle]]$$

This pattern boxes a manner verb with an external vehicle component ⟨V⟩ to form a verb phrase of the type V + noun that specifies the means of transport. In this pattern, ⟨F⟩ refers to displacement, MOVE(e) is the external manner-motion event encoded by the main verb, ⟨M⟩ specifies the displacement profile, and ⟨V⟩ identifies the transport medium that enables the movement. Therefore, the vehicle is realized as an independent lexical item in Vietnamese, which supports productive and metaphorical extensions, as in *cưỡi ngựa* ‘to ride a horse’, *chèo thuyền* ‘to row a boat’, *lái xe* ‘to drive a car’, and *lướt ván* ‘to surf’.

<i>Cưỡi ngựa</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [F \text{ MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [\langle \text{ride} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{animal-based} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{horse} \rangle]]$
<i>Chèo thuyền</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [F \text{ MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [\langle \text{row} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{water-based} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{boat} \rangle]]$
<i>Lái xe</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [F \text{ MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [\langle \text{drive} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{vehicle-based} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{car} \rangle]]$
<i>Lướt ván</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [F \text{ MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [\langle \text{glide} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{surface-based} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{board} \rangle]]$

This group of V_[M+V] verbs consists of verb-noun complexes, in which the verb root encodes ⟨M⟩ as a specific transport-based manner, and the following noun encodes ⟨V⟩ as the concrete vehicle. The two components jointly produce one coherent external manner-motion event because the vehicle is conceptually required for interpreting how the ⟨F⟩ moves. The V_[M+V] pattern is described in the following token from *Truyện người hàng xóm* (Nam Cao).

- (17) Con gái không biết cưỡi ngựa ngồi không vững.
girl not know ride horse sit not firm
‘The girl did not know how to ride a horse, so she could not sit steadily.’

In this case, ⟨F⟩ is *con gái* that involved in the transport event. The verb *cưỡi* encodes MOVE(e) together with ⟨M⟩ by profiling a riding manner in which ⟨F⟩ is carried by and controls a mount. The noun *ngựa* encodes ⟨V⟩ by specifying the vehicle medium as a horse. Therefore, the token clarifies this pattern by combining a manner verb with an explicit vehicle noun to encode transport-based displacement.

Last but not least, the pattern V_[M+CO] is formulated as follows:

$$V_{[M+CO]} \Leftrightarrow [F \text{ MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [\langle M \rangle \wedge \langle CO \rangle]]$$

This pattern represents an external manner-motion event MOVE(e), in which ⟨F⟩ is associated with displacement. In this pattern, the verb root encodes ⟨M⟩ as the qualitative profile of that displacement, and the external component ⟨C_o⟩ contributes a co-motion component. The ⟨C_o⟩ confirms that another entity moves in coordination, accompaniment, or ordered sequence with ⟨F⟩, so it adds a social or interactive alignment to the same motion event. Although ⟨M⟩ and ⟨C_o⟩ remain syntactically independent in a verb-phrase construction, they integrate into a coherent macro event that depicts both locomotion and accompanying participation without altering the morphology of the main verb as in *đi theo* ‘to follow’, *chạy cùng* ‘to run together’, *nói đũa* ‘to move in a line’, and *sánh đôi* ‘to walk side by side’.

<i>Đi theo</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (follow pace) ∧ (accompany)]]
<i>Chạy cùng</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (equal pace) ∧ (joint action)]]
<i>Nói đũa</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (sequential pace) ∧ (follow in line)]]
<i>Sánh đôi</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (equal pace) ∧ (pair up)]]

The V_[M+CO] external conflation is illustrated in the following token from *Truyện người hàng xóm* (Nam Cao).

- (18) Ngã để bà ấy cho **đi theo** đi bán hàng dăm.
 Ngã let lady that allow go follow go sell small goods
 ‘Ngã did it so that she would allow him to follow her to sell small wares.’

In this token, ⟨F⟩ is the understood follower, namely Ngã, who experiences displacement. The verb *đi* encodes MOVE(e) together with ⟨M⟩ as a neutral leg-based locomotion profile. The verb *theo* encodes ⟨CO⟩ by specifying that Ngã’s movement is aligned with *bà ấy* as a co-moving reference participant, that is, Ngã moves in accompaniment and in her trajectory. Consequently, this example sheds light on the properties of this pattern because an external manner-motion event is construed as coordinated motion between the ⟨F⟩ and another participant, and the co-motion component refines the event as following instead of independent displacement.

In short, the two-component external conflation patterns of Vietnamese manner-motion verbs show a core-periphery organization, in which the verb root encodes the manner-motion elements and peripheral lexical units add distinct co-event components. This result supports Talmy’s (2000) lexicalization framework because Vietnamese preserves a division between a manner-motion core and external enrichments. At the same time, these analyses argue against Talmy’s strict satellite-framed and verb-framed split since Vietnamese peripherals are not limited to particles or prepositions but they are often realized as ideophones, adverbs, or co-verbs that remain independent yet semantically co-equal with the manner-motion verb. In this respect, Vietnamese is typologically close to equipollently-framed languages such as Thai and Chinese, where serial verb constructions allow multiple semantic elements to share one clause without subordination, although Vietnamese differs from Chinese in that it generally avoids morphological compounding and instead keeps the components separable for flexible stacking. Vietnamese also differs from satellite-framed English, where similar meanings are usually optional adverbials or prepositional phrases, and from verb-framed Romance languages such as Spanish and French, where manner is frequently backgrounded and path or endpoint is

lexicalized in the verb. Cross-linguistically, the sound pattern parallels ideophonic systems in Japanese, but Vietnamese stands out for the productivity of reduplication, while circumstance and co-motion resemble adverbial framing in English or Korean, but they are more tightly integrated as serial components in Vietnamese. Therefore, Vietnamese external two-component conflation exemplifies a core-compression with the strategy of peripheral-component conflation, in which a compact manner-motion element is enriched by modular but constructionally expected co-event components, a profile that refines motion typology and supports Slobin’s (2004) thinking-for-speaking account by showing how Vietnamese grammar promotes the foregrounding of sensory, pragmatic, and interactional details in motion descriptions.

3.3 VERB _[PATH MOTION]

This section aims to explore the semantic conflation patterns of path-motion verbs in Vietnamese, in which these verbs denote the prominent semantic components of Path ⟨P⟩. In other words, this section aims to clarify how Vietnamese organizes path and other components in the motion events. Accordingly, the internal conflation patterns of path-motion verbs are cases, in which the components of Path ⟨P⟩, and Ground ⟨G⟩, are encoded in the verbs themselves, which enables the verb itself to evoke a relatively complete event structure. In contrast, the external conflation patterns of path-motion verbs are configurations, in which the path-motion verbs serve as the central verbs, but the motion events are expanded at the level of the verb phrase by peripheral semantic components, such as Circumstance ⟨C⟩, Result ⟨R⟩, or purpose ⟨Pr⟩, and these components are encoded by accompanying elements or by other verbs in serial verb constructions. Table 3 summarizes the internal and external conflation patterns of path-motion verbs, and it shows the distribution and the degree of productivity of each conflation type. These results provide a basis for drawing generalizations about the tendency to wrap Path meaning in Vietnamese and about the role of constructional extension mechanisms in the expression of motion.

Table 4: Semantic conflation patterns of path-motion verbs

Semantic components	Internal conflation patterns		External conflation patterns					
	Internal semantic components (Ground, Path)		External semantic components (Circumstance, Emotion, Location, Result, Purpose, Time)					
Conflation Patterns	Path +	Ground 3	Path +	Circumstance 195	Path +	Result 36	Path +	Purpose 16
Total	3		247					

3.3.1 Internal conflation patterns of path-motion verbs

This section deals with the internal conflation patterns of path-motion verbs in Vietnamese, which occur in one pattern: V _[P + G] with 3 patterns. In these patterns, the Path ⟨P⟩ is directly integrated into the lexical meaning of verb. This allows the expression of a complete trajectory without the need for extra syntactic elements, which allow Vietnamese speakers to be able to

keep a minimal syntactic form while they still preserve precise path representation. MOVE_(i) denotes internal motion, which refers to an inherent change in the figure’s location that is lexically integrated in the verb itself without requiring an external manner-motion verbs or additional syntactic markers. These patterns can be wrapped in the general formula below:

$$\text{VERB}_{[\text{PATH MOTION}]} \Leftrightarrow [{}_{\text{F}} \text{MOVE}_{(i)} \wedge [(\text{P}) \wedge (\text{Inter-coms})]]$$

The V_[P+G] pattern in Vietnamese is a relatively rare type that is attested in only three verbs: *cập bến* (to dock), *hạ cánh* (to land), and *ra khơi* (to sail out to open sea). What is distinctive about this group is that each verb simultaneously integrates two internal semantic components inside a verb root, namely a ⟨P⟩ and a ⟨G⟩. Because ⟨P⟩ and ⟨G⟩ are co-lexicalized, the verb itself specifies both the inherent direction of motion and the landmark that anchors the event, so speakers can express a complete internal motion event without adding a separate locative complement. The generalized formula is:

$$V_{[\text{P}+\text{G}]} \Leftrightarrow [{}_{\text{F}} \text{MOVE}_{(i)} \wedge [(\text{P}) \wedge (\text{G})]]$$

In this structure, MOVE_(i) denotes an event of internal motion, that is, self-initiated displacement of the ⟨F⟩ instead of motion caused by an external agent. The ⟨P⟩ functions as a directional value encoded in the verb, such as inward approach, downward descent, or outward departure. The ⟨G⟩ functions as a ground landmark encoded in the verb, and this landmark is conceptually presupposed as the spatial anchor that is required for interpreting the trajectory. Concretely, *cập bến* encodes ⟨G⟩ as *bến* ‘dock or harbor’, *hạ cánh* encodes ⟨G⟩ as a landing ground, canonically a runway, and *ra khơi* encodes ⟨G⟩ as *khơi* (open sea).

<i>Cập bến</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [{}_{\text{F}} \text{MOVE}_{(i)} \wedge [(\text{in water}) \wedge (\text{inward}) \wedge (\text{dock})]]$
<i>Hạ cánh</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [{}_{\text{F}} \text{MOVE}_{(i)} \wedge [(\text{in air}) \wedge (\text{downward}) \wedge (\text{landing site})]]$
<i>Ra khơi</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [{}_{\text{F}} \text{MOVE}_{(i)} \wedge [(\text{in water}) \wedge (\text{outward}) \wedge (\text{open sea})]]$

The V_[P+G] internal conflation pattern is illustrated in the following token from *Thi Đại Học Toàn Cầu* (Mộc Tô Lý).

- (19) Một khi đã ra khơi.
once already exit open-sea
‘Once (one) has set sail for the open sea.’

⟨F⟩ in this example is the understood sailing participant, which is subjected to internal motion. The verb *ra khơi* reflects V_[P+G] because it encodes ⟨P⟩ as an outward trajectory away from shore and it encodes ⟨G⟩ as the open sea ground landmark that anchors the motion. Therefore, the token realizes a internal motion event, in which ⟨F⟩ moves outward relative to a presupposed open-sea ground.

In short, the internal conflation pattern V_[P+G] in Vietnamese provides a compact, but it reveals test case for theories of motion lexicalization. First, the pattern is consistent with Talmy’s (2000) claim that some languages lexicalize path inside the verb because verbs such as *cập bến*, *hạ cánh*, and *ra khơi* encode an inherent ⟨P⟩ together with a ⟨G⟩, which allow a trajectory without an overt locative complement. This property makes Vietnamese comparable

to verb-framed systems such as Spanish or French, where path is frequently internal to the verb, and it also resembles lexical classes in English that incorporate goal-ground meaning (for example *dock* or *land*), even though English overall prefers satellites. However, the Vietnamese pattern indicates that path-framing can coexist with an equipollent architecture in the language. Vietnamese does not build path meaning via morphological root expansion or resultative compounding as in Chinese, nor does it depend on obligatory satellites as in English. Instead, it achieves path-ground completeness through monomorphemic verbs whose lexical semantics already integrate both the motion and path components. Therefore, the rarity of $V_{[P+G]}$ matters typologically because it reveals that Vietnamese path verbs are not a framing system on their own, but a specialized lexical niche that compresses trajectory and landmark for maximal economy and precision. In short, Vietnamese internal path-motion verbs refine motion typology by revealing a lexical-niche strategy: even in a language that extensively exploits serial constructions, a small class of verbs can still encode $\langle P \rangle$ and $\langle G \rangle$ internally that forms self-sufficient internal-motion events. This supports event-structure models, in which ground information may be part of verb meaning rather than peripheral.

3.3.2 External conflation patterns of path-motion verbs

This section addresses the external conflation patterns of Vietnamese path-motion verbs, which are attested in four constructions: $V_{[P+C]}$ (195), $V_{[P+R]}$ (36), and $V_{[P+Pr]}$ (16), which produce 247 patterns in total. Across these patterns, the main verb preserves a compact core that encodes MOVE(e), an external motion event whose semantic nucleus profiles motion together with an inherent path value, while the external component contributes an additional discourse-semantic component as an independent unit, such as an adverb, a secondary verb, or a second verb. Among the four types, $V_{[P+C]}$ is by far the most frequent because it offers the most flexible and economical expansion of a motion-path element, in which this pattern preserves the path-motion verb and adds circumstance as a peripheral component that is syntactically co-equal with the verb in serial constructions. Circumstance is also the most accessible component in natural discourse, since it readily encodes speaker evaluation, situational setting, or pragmatic stance without requiring subordination, so $V_{[P+C]}$ functions as a default option in motion description. By contrast, $V_{[P+R]}$ introduces more specific components, namely a result endpoint, and therefore occur only when those meanings are discourse-relevant. $V_{[P+Pr]}$ is the least frequent because it combines two different external components in one construction, namely a Path $\langle P \rangle$ and a Purpose $\langle Pr \rangle$. The general schema is:

$$\text{VERB}_{[\text{PATH MOTION}]} \Leftrightarrow [F \text{MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [(\langle P \rangle) \wedge \langle \text{Exter-coms} \rangle]]$$

The $V_{[P+C]}$ pattern is an external conflation type of Vietnamese path-motion verbs that is canonically realized as a verb phrase consisting of a path verb followed by an adverbial element. In this pattern, the main verb encodes MOVE(e) together with an inherent Path component $\langle P \rangle$, while the following adverbial unit contributes an external Circumstance component $\langle C \rangle$, which can be temporal, locative, psychological, situational, or evaluative. The general formula is:

$$V_{[P+C]} \Leftrightarrow [F \text{MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [(\langle P \rangle) \wedge \langle \text{Circumstance} \rangle]]$$

In this pattern, ⟨F⟩ experiences displacement, MOVE(e) designates an external motion event, and ⟨P⟩ is a non-neutral path value that is fixed by the verb root itself, such as inward entry (*vào*), outward exit (*ra*), or upward movement (*lên*). The ⟨C⟩ is contributed outside the verb root as an adverbial component. This component does not supply a second path, and it does not change the argument structure of verb. Instead, it refines the same path event by anchoring it to a contextual parameter that is conceptually independent from the trajectory but interpretively inseparable from the event in discourse. In other words, the verb supplies the directional element of displacement, whereas the adverb specifies the conditions under which that displacement is carried out, for example quiet manner, hurried pace, leisurely attitude, temporal sequence, or situational staging. This division of labor explains why V_[P + C] is highly productive in Vietnamese, in which the path-motion verb keeps the motion core compact, and the adverbial circumstance provides immediate experiential or discourse framing without resorting to subordination. Typical verb phrases include *vào lặng lẽ* ‘to enter quietly’, *ra vội vàng* ‘to go out hurriedly’, and *lên thong thả* ‘to go up leisurely’, in which ⟨P⟩ is inherent to the verb and ⟨C⟩ is a contextual component added by the adverb.

<i>Vào lặng lẽ</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(inward) ∧ ⟨quietly⟩]]
<i>Ra vội vàng</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(outward) ∧ ⟨hurriedly⟩]]
<i>Lên thong thả</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(upward) ∧ ⟨leisurely⟩]]
<i>Vào sau</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(inward) ∧ ⟨later/afterwards⟩]]

The V_[P + C] external conflation is illustrated in the following token from *Truyện người hàng xóm* (Nam Cao).

- (20) Một bọn ba bốn người **vào sau**.
 one group three four person enter after
 ‘A group of three or four people entered afterwards.’

In this example, ⟨F⟩ is *một bọn ba bốn người* that is displaced. The verb *vào* encodes MOVE(e) with ⟨P⟩ as an inward path of entry. The adverb *sau* encodes ⟨C⟩ as a temporal circumstance of succession that indicates that the entry event is ordered after a salient prior event or group. Consequently, the verb phrase Verb + adverb illustrates a path-motion element expanded by one circumstance component, exactly as specified by V_[P + C] ⇔ [F MOVE_(e) ∧ [(P) ∧ ⟨Circumstance⟩]] because the inward trajectory is provided by the verb root and the temporal sequencing is provided by the adverbial circumstance.

The V_[P + R] pattern is an external conflation type of Vietnamese path-motion verbs that is canonically realized as a verb phrase consisting of a path verb followed by a noun. In this pattern, the ⟨P⟩ is integrated into the main verb, and the following noun contributes an ⟨R⟩ that specifies the attained outcome of the motion-path event. The general formula is:

$$V_{[P + R]} \Leftrightarrow [F \text{ MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [(P) \wedge \langle \text{Result} \rangle]]$$

This group of V_[P + R] path-motion verbs can be characterized as path-verb-noun complexes, in which the verb root encodes ⟨P⟩ and the noun encodes ⟨R⟩ as the telic endpoint. Verb phrases such as *vào biên chế* ‘to enter official employment’, *ra đời* ‘to come into existence’, and *lên chức* ‘to rise in position’ exemplify this pattern because *vào*, *ra*, and *lên* encode inward,

outward, and upward path values while *biên chế*, *đời*, and *chức* encode the attained employment status, existence-state, and promoted rank. Consequently, these constructions differ from path-motion verbs because the result is not optional, but it is stated by the noun component that completes the macro-event.

<i>Vào biên chế</i>	\Leftrightarrow [F MOVE _(e) \wedge [(inward) \wedge (become officially employed)]]
<i>Ra đời</i>	\Leftrightarrow [F MOVE _(e) \wedge [(outward) \wedge (be born)]]
<i>Lên chức</i>	\Leftrightarrow [F MOVE _(e) \wedge [(upward) \wedge (promoted)]]

The V_[P+R] external conflation is illustrated in the following token from *Đời thừa* (Nam Cao).

- (21) Lúc đứa con **ra** **đời**
when one child exit life
‘When the child was born’

The ⟨F⟩ is *đứa con*, whose displacement is construed as emergence into existence. The verb *ra* encodes MOVE_(e) with ⟨P⟩ as an outward path of emergence. The noun *đời* encodes ⟨R⟩ as the resultant existence-state of being born. Therefore, the verb phrase Verb + Noun describes V_[P+R] \Leftrightarrow [F MOVE_(e) \wedge [(P) \wedge (Result)]], because the path element is supplied by the verb and the achieved result is supplied by the noun.

The V_[P+Pr] pattern is an external conflation type of Vietnamese path-motion verbs that is typically realized as a verb phrase that consists of a path verb followed by a purpose verb or goal-oriented verb. In this pattern, the first verb encodes a Path component ⟨P⟩ that profiles the direction of displacement, and the second element encodes a Purpose or goal-action component ⟨Pr⟩ that motivates the displacement and specifies what activity the motion is directed toward. The general formula is:

$$V_{[P+Pr]} \Leftrightarrow [F \text{ MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [(P) \wedge (Pr)]]$$

In this structure, ⟨F⟩ undergoes displacement, MOVE_(e) denotes an external motion event, ⟨P⟩ is the inherent path value contributed by the path verb, and ⟨Pr⟩ is the goal-oriented event contributed by the following predicate. The two components remain syntactically independent in a serial construction, but they are interpreted as one coherent macro event because they share the same ⟨F⟩ and because ⟨Pr⟩ provides the purposive endpoint that renders the path motion goal-directed rather than direction-only.

<i>Ra tòa</i>	\Leftrightarrow [F MOVE _(e) \wedge [(outward) \wedge (testify)]]
<i>Đi học</i>	\Leftrightarrow [F MOVE _(e) \wedge [(toward school) \wedge (study)]]
<i>Đi chợ</i>	\Leftrightarrow [F MOVE _(e) \wedge [(toward market) \wedge (buy goods)]]
<i>Về quê</i>	\Leftrightarrow [F MOVE _(e) \wedge [(homeward) \wedge (return to hometown)]]

This group of V_[P+Pr] path-motion verbs can be characterized as serial complexes, in which a directionally specified path verb anchors the displacement nucleus, and a following purpose predicate anchors the intended endpoint-action. Verb phrases such as *ra tòa* ‘to go to court’, *đi học* ‘to go to school’, *đi chợ* ‘to go to the market’, and *về quê* ‘to return to the hometown’

exemplify this pattern because the path verbs *ra*, *đi*, and *về* encode ⟨P⟩ as outward movement, directed going, or homeward return, while the complements *tò*, *học*, *chợ*, and *quê* encode ⟨Pr⟩ as the goal action or socially defined activity associated with that destination. Therefore, these verb phrases differ from path-motion verbs that only encode trajectory because the second element is not an optional locative supplement, but a purposive component that completes the interpretation of the motion as oriented toward a goal event. The $V_{[P+Pr]}$ external conflation is illustrated in the following token from *Sao lại thế này* (Nam Cao).

- (22) Nghi hè cũng không dám về quê.
holiday summer also not dare return hometown
'Even during the summer break, (he) did not dare to return to his hometown.'

In this example, ⟨F⟩ is the understood subject who would be the returning participant. The verb *về* encodes $MOVE_{(e)}$ together with ⟨P⟩ as a homeward path of return. The noun *quê* encodes ⟨Pr⟩ as the goal-oriented endpoint that defines the intended return event, namely reaching and re-entering the socially salient homeland domain. The modal sequence *không dám* negates the realization of the macro event, but it does not change the internal organization of the pattern. Consequently, the phrase *về quê* instantiates $V_{[P+Pr]} \Leftrightarrow [F \text{ MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [\langle P \rangle \wedge \langle Pr \rangle]]$ because the path element is supplied by the verb root and the purposive goal component is supplied by the following verb that produces a goal-directed path-motion event.

In short, the three patterns confirm that Vietnamese path-motion verbs employ a core-periphery organization: the verb root anchors $MOVE_{(e)}$ and an inherent path value ⟨P⟩, while a second unit adds a distinct external component. This organization is broadly consistent with Talmy's framework because circumstantial adverbs in $V_{[P+C]}$ and result nouns in $V_{[P+R]}$ function like satellites in the sense that they supply endpoint or contextual information outside the verb. At the same time, $V_{[P+Pr]}$ aligns with equipollent systems such as Thai and Chinese, since purpose is encoded by a co-verb that remains syntactically independent but forms one macro-event with the path-motion verb. However, Vietnamese does not fit neatly into a typological type. It differs from Spanish and French, where purpose and many results are typically expressed through subordinated or prepositional structures, not as co-equal components in the same verb phrase. It also differs from English because the external component is not restricted to particles or prepositions but can be realized as adverbs, nouns, or full co-verbs. Finally, it diverges from Chinese resultative compounding because Vietnamese components are phrasal and separable rather than morphologically fused. In short, Vietnamese combines verb-internal path anchoring with construction-level componenting, which gives rise to a stable intermediate strategy that expands event meaning without changing verbal morphology.

4 Conclusion

This study has systematically identified and classified the semantic conflation patterns of Vietnamese motion verbs through Talmy's (1985, 2000) lexicalization patterns, Slobin's (2004) thinking-for-speaking hypothesis, Goldberg's (1995) construction grammar, and Levin and Rappaport Hovav's (1995, 1998, 2010) event-structure approach as its analytical

foundations. The findings reveal a typologically hybrid system. A particularly revealing result is that Vietnamese achieves high telic density in caused-motion without morphological compounding, instead of relying on productive constructional componenting (e.g. V_1 + Result/ State/ Direction). This supports an independent typological parameter of endpoint-externalization, beyond the classic verb and satellite-framed split. In this study, hybrid encoding strategy refers to the stable coexistence of multiple motion-packaging options in Vietnamese. Internal conflation patterns show that Vietnamese can lexicalize core components such as Manner, Path, and Cause, and in some patterns Figure and Ground, directly in the verb root, so that the motion element is compact and self-contained. External conflation patterns show that Vietnamese systematically expands this core through constructional componenting, in which peripheral components such as Direction, Result, Circumstance, Purpose, Vehicle, Sound, and Time are realized as serial verbs, secondary predicates, particles, or adverbial units. Vietnamese further employs equipollent serial-verb constructions that distribute Manner and Path across co-equal verbs. Therefore, hybridity here denotes a consistent typological profile that combines verb-root packaging with construction-level componenting.

From a theoretical perspective, Vietnamese refines Talmy's typology by demonstrating a structural pathway through which verb-framed and equipollently-framed strategies can operate in one language, even though they are often treated as distinct types in cross-linguistic accounts. The patterns also substantiate Slobin's claim that grammatical affordances shape conceptualization because Vietnamese speakers recurrently encode a core motion event first and then add peripheral components to increase descriptive precision and discourse richness. In addition, treating these recurrent form-meaning pairings as constructions supports Goldberg's view that constructions themselves are meaning-bearing units capable of hosting both core and peripheral semantic components without requiring morphological alteration of the verb. Finally, the Vietnamese patterns extend event-structure models by showing that Figure and Ground can be lexically presupposed inside the verb root, and that peripheral components can contribute independent event meanings while remaining integrated into a single macro-event representation.

In practical terms, the results are relevant for second-language teaching, translation, and natural language processing. For pedagogy, recognizing the hybrid encoding strategy allows teaching materials to guide learners from different backgrounds in mapping motion components onto Vietnamese verb roots and serial constructions, which reduces cross-linguistic interference. For translation, the findings show that equivalence requires attention to how Vietnamese distributes core motion meaning and peripheral components, so that semantic nuance and structural fidelity are preserved. For computational applications, the classification of conflation patterns offers a structured resource for semantic parsing and machine translation that is sensitive to cross-linguistic variation in event packaging. The study is limited to dictionary entries and a selected narrative data, so colloquial and dialectal variation may be underrepresented. Future research should expand the dataset to spoken discourse, experimental elicitation, and systematic comparison with other Southeast Asian languages. Overall, the study contributes empirical evidence and analytical refinement to motion-event typology by clarifying how Vietnamese balances semantic compression with contextual elaboration in a hybrid system.

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Appendix A

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Appendix B

CAUSE VERBS (INTERNAL CONFLATION PATTERNS)

Semantic components	Internal conflation patterns (Cause, Motion, Manner, Path)		
Semantic conflation patterns	Cause + Figure + Motion	Cause + Motion + Manner	Cause + Motion + Path
Causative verbs	Bắn Bấm Bom Đâm Lao Phà Rạch Vắt	Bật Bò Búng Đá Đập Ép Giật Húc Khiêng Khuấy	Án Cắm Chát Chèn Chêm Dí Đẩy Đè Đồ Ép

		Lắc Lăn Lông Mang Ném Rắc Rung Thổi Quăng Quảng Rắc Rải Tung Vác Xê dịch Xoay Xô	Hạ Hắt Hút Kéo Lao Lôi Nạp Nâng Nén Nhắc Nhét Nhỏ Nhồi Phóng Phun Quật Tách Thả Vung Vốt
Total	8	27	30

CAUSE VERBS (EXTERNAL CONFLATION PATTERNS)

Semantic components	External conflation patterns (Cause, Motion, Change, Result, State, Volume)					
	Cause + Motion + Result	Cause + Motion + Result + Manner	Cause + Motion + Result + Direction	Cause + Motion + Change	Cause + Motion + State	Cause + Motion + Volume
Causative verbs	Bắn hạ Bắn roi Bắn thun Bắn văng Bè cong Bè gãy Bóp nát Bứt rời Cán bẹp Cán nát Cào đồ Cào nát Cuốn phẫ Cuốn trôi Đập đồ Đập gãy Đầm nát Đập bẹp Đập nát Đập vỡ Đề bẹp Đề dẹt Đẩy bật Đẩy lùi Đẩy ngã Đẩy sập Ép phẳng	Đẩy ngã nhào Đẩy ngã lăn Kéo đồ âm Kéo sập âm âm Hắt tung Hắt văng ra xa Húc văng ra ngoài Giật tung Giật đồ ập xuống Xô đồ nhào Xô sập mạnh Lôi tuột ra ngoài Đập vỡ tan Đập nát bầy Đề bẹp dí Ném vỡ tan tàn Quật ngã gục xuống Quật tung lên cao	Hắt văng ra Hắt văng vào Hắt tung lên t Hắt rơi xuống Hắt rơi xuống Húc văng ra Húc đồ xuống Giật tuột khỏi Giật đồ xuống Giật đồ xuống Giật sập xuống Xô đồ xuống Xô đồ xuống Xô lệch sang Xô ngã ra Xô ngã vào Xô ngã ra Quật ngã xuống Quật đồ ra Quật đồ xuống Quật ngã ra Quật văng ra Quăng nát vào	Bè cong Bè thẳng Bóp dẹp Bóp méo Cán bẹp Cán dẹt Cán mỏng Cán phẳng Cuộn tròn Cuộn lại Đề bẹp Đề bẹt Đập bẹt Đập dẹt Ép bẹt Ép dẹp Ép phẳng Ép thẳng Ép xẹp Kéo cong Kéo dẫn Kéo thẳng Kéo to ra Kéo lệch Mở rộng Nắn cong	Buộc chặt Cuộn chặt Đề cứng ngắc Đóng ghi Đóng kín Ép chặt Ép dính Ép sát Gập gọn Gập gọn Kẹp chặt Kẹp cứng Khép chặt Khép kín Mở toang Nén chặt Siết chặt Siết cố định Siết cứng Thắt chặt	Bom căng Bom phồng Kéo căng Kéo dẫn Mở bung Nổi bung Thổi căng Thổi phồng

	Ép vụn Giật đồ Giật gãy Giật phẫn Giật tung Ha gục Hắt đồ Hắt rơi Hắt tung Húc đồ Húc ngã Húc văng Kéo bung Kéo đồ Kéo nghiêng Kéo sập Lật đồ Lật úp Ném vỡ Quật gãy Quật ngã Quật đồ Rạch toạc Uốn cong Vặn gãy Xé rách Xé toạc Xô đồ Xô lệch Xô ngã Xô sập Úi sập	Xúc đồ ào ào Hắt rơi xuống đất	Quăng vỡ xuống Quăng vỡ xuống Ném vỡ xuống Ném vỡ xuống Ném vỡ ra Ném bay ra Ném tung lên Lôi tuột ra n Lôi tuột xuống Lôi tuột ra Kéo sập xuống Kéo sập xuống Kéo đồ ra ngoài Kéo nghiêng sang Kéo bật ra Đẩy bật ra Đẩy bật ra Đẩy lệch sang Đẩy lùi về Đẩy ngã ra Đập vỡ bay xuống Đập vỡ văng ra Đập gãy rơi xuống Đập nát bay ra Ép bật ra	Nấn méo Nấn thẳng Nấn tròn Nới bung Nới rộng Siết lại Thối phồng Uốn cong Uốn thẳng Vặn cong Vặn lệch Vặn méo Vặn thẳng Xòe rộng Xòe to Xoay lệch Xoay nghiêng		
Total	59	20	49	44	20	8

MANNER VERBS (INTERNAL CONFLATION PATTERNS)

Semantic components	Internal conflation patterns		
	Internal components (Figure, Ground, Manner, Motion)		
Conflation patterns of manner verbs	Motion + Manner	Motion + Manner + Figure	Motion + Manner + Ground
	Bật Bén mảng Biến Bò Cắt cánh Chạy Chìm Chòm Cút đi Dao động Dạo	Banh Bệt Bước Chành Chìa Choài Cúi Dậm Duỗi Gật Giang	Bay Bơi Cập bến Chui Đạt Đậu Hạ cánh Lấn Lội Lượn Tràn

	Dập dờn Đắm Di chuyển Điều hành Dao động Dập dờn Đắm Đung đưa Gục Hụp Lan Lách Lánh Lảo đảo Lắc lư Len Lê Lét Lộn Lướt Lúi Nhảy Rào bức Rẽ Roi Rũ Sà Sập Sụt Trào Trườn Trượt Tuôn Tuột Vẩy tay Vọt Vung	Dang Khom Mưa Ngảng Run Toài Uỡn Vươn	Trèo
Total	45	19	12
		76	

MANNER VERBS (EXTERNAL CONFLATION PATTERNS)

Semantic components	External conflation patterns				
	External components (Circumstance, Sound, Trajectory, Vehicle)				
	Motion + Manner + Sound	Motion + Manner + Circumstance	Motion + Manner + Purpose	Motion + Manner + Vehicle	Motion + Manner + Co-motion
Conflation patterns of manner verbs	Bay phành phạch Bay vèo Bay vù vù Bò sột xoạt Chạy cồm cộp Chạy rầm rập Chạy thình thịch Đi lạch bạch Đi lộp cộp Đi lẹp xẹp Đi loẹt quẹt	Bay bông Bay nhảy Chạy bần Chạy tung tang Đi chập chững Đi khệnh khạng Đi loanh quanh Đi lòng vòng Đi lạch Đi lang thang Đi lững thững	Chạy chợ Chạy trốn Chạy chữa Chạy vốn Chạy quảng cáo Chạy giao hàng Chạy dịch Đi chợ Đi chùa Đi học Đi câu	Bay máy bay Chạy tàu thủy Chèo nghe Chèo thuyền Chèo xuống Cưỡi ngựa Cưỡi trâu Cưỡi voi Đi ca nô Đi cà kheo Đi phà	Bám theo Bám sát Chạy cùng Chạy đồng hành Chạy lẻo đẻo Chạy sát bên Chạy theo Đẫn theo Đắt theo Dí theo Đi cùng

	Đi phịch phịch Lăn lóc cóc Kéo sột soạt Lao vun vút Lôi rầm rập Ném phịch Ngã ụych Nhảy bộp Roi loảng xoảng Roi lách tách Roi lộp bộp Roi ào ào Roi leng keng Roi rào rào Roi tí tách Roi bịch bịch Quăng bộp	Đi rón rén Đi thơ thần Đi vội vã Đi gáp gáp Đi khập khiễng Đi khúm núm Nhảy non ton Nhảy xa	Đi làm Đi du lịch Đi hành hương Đi giao lưu Đi vận động Đi sơ tán Đi lễ Đi tập thể dục Đi săn Đi xin việc	Đi taxi Đi xe buýt Đi thuyền Lái xe Lướt ván Trượt ván	Đi kèm Đi theo Nối đuôi Sánh đôi
Total	28	19	21	17	15
	100				

PATH VERBS (INTERNAL CONFLATION PATTERNS)

Semantic components	Internal semantic components (Ground, Motion, Path)	
	Motion + Path	Motion + Path + Ground
Conflation patterns of path verbs	Đến Lên Lùi Xuống Vào Về Ra Rút lui Tới Lại Tiến Trở lại Quay về	Cập bến Hạ cánh Ra khơi
Total	13	3
	16	

PATH VERBS (EXTERNAL CONFLATION PATTERNS)

Semantic components	External semantic components (Circumstance, Emotion, Location, Result, Purpose, Time)			
	Motion + Path + Circumstance	Motion + Path + Result	Motion + Path + Time	Motion + Path + Purpose
Conflation patterns of path verbs	Đến dần Đến chậm Đến gấp Đến hạn	Đến đích Lên đỉnh Lên chức Lên giá	Đến trễ Đến đúng giờ Đến kịp Đến lâu	Đi học Đi chợ Đi chùa Đi viện

Đến ngay	Lên lớp	Đến liền	Đi làm
Đến nhanh	Lên ngôi	Đến muộn	Đi lễ
Đến liền lập tức	Lên hạng	Đến sớm	Đi cầu
Đến đều đặn	Lên sàn	Đến trễ	Đi chơi
Đến liên tục	Lên sóng	Vào đúng giờ	Đi họp
Đến ngay lập tức	Lên tiếng	Vào kịp	Đi sản
Đến tạm thời	Lên truyền hình	Vào lâu	Đi bơi
Đi hồi hả	Lên bục vinh quang	Vào liền	Vào viện
Đến tức thì	Tới đích	Vào muộn	Đến trường
Lên đều đặn	Vào biên chế	Vào sớm	Ra viện
Lùi chậm rãi	Vào đảng	Vào trễ	Về nước
Ra ào ào	Vào khuôn khổ	Ra chậm	Về quê
Lên chậm	Vào nếp	Ra đúng giờ	
Lên từ từ	Vào giường	Ra kịp	
Lên dần	Vào số đen	Ra lâu	
Lên gấp	Vào thể trận	Ra muộn	
Lên nhất thời	Vào thị trường	Ra nhanh	
Lên lâu	Vào vòng chung kết	Ra sớm	
Lên liền	Về đích	Ra trễ	
Lên nhanh	Về hưu	Rút lui đúng giờ	
Lên liền lập tức	Ra đề	Rút lui kịp	
Lên liên tục	Ra quân	Rút lui muộn	
Lên ngay	Ra đời	Rút lui sớm	
Lên ngay lập tức	Ra trường	Rút lui trễ	
Lên tạm thời	Ra tòa	Trở lại đúng giờ	
Lên tức thì	Ra khỏi tổ chức	Trở lại kịp	
Ra đều đặn	Ra khỏi danh sách	Trở lại lâu	
Ra ngay	Rút lui khỏi chính	Trở lại muộn	
Ra dần	trường	Trở lại sớm	
Ra gấp	Trở lại ghế nóng	Trở lại trễ	
Ra liền	Xuống bâng xếp hạng	Tới chậm	
Ra liền lập tức	Xuống chức	Tới đúng giờ	
Ra ngay lập tức	Xuống cấp	Tới kịp	
Ra nhất thời	Xuống sức	Tới lâu	
Ra vĩnh viễn		Tới muộn	
Ra liên tục		Tới sớm	
Ra tạm thời		Tới trễ	
Ra tức thì		Tiến lên đúng giờ	
Rút lui nhất thời		Tiến lên kịp	
Rút lui tạm thời		Tiến lên lâu	
Rút lui ngay		Tiến lên liền	
Rút lui ngay lập tức		Tiến lên muộn	
Rút lui nhanh		Tiến lên sớm	
Rút lui dần		Tiến lên trễ	
Rút lui gấp		Về đúng giờ	
Rút lui liền		Về kịp	
Rút lui chậm		Về lâu	
Rút lui vĩnh viễn		Về liền	
Rút lui liên tục		Về muộn	
Rút lui tức thì		Về sớm	
Trở lại chậm		Về trễ	
Tiến dồn dập		Lên đúng giờ	
Tới dồn dập		Lên kịp	
Tới tức thì		Lên muộn	
Tới nhanh		Lên sớm	
Xuống rón rén		Lên trễ	
Vào chậm		Xuống đúng giờ	
Vào đều đặn		Xuống kịp	
Vào tạm thời		Xuống lâu	
Vào lạng lẽ		Xuống muộn	
Vào dần		Xuống sớm	

	<p>Vào gấp Vào liên tục Vào liên lập tức Vào tức thì Vào ngay Vào ngay lập tức Vào nhanh Về thông thả Về nhất thời Rút lui âm thầm Tiến lên chậm Tiến lên đều đặn Tiến lên dần Tiến lên liên lập tức Tiến lên ngay Tiến lên gấp Tiến lên ngay lập tức Tiến lên tạm thời Tiến lên tức thì Tiến lên nhất thời Tiến lên nhanh Tiến lên vĩnh viễn Tiến lên liên tục Trở lại liên tục Về chậm Về dần Về gấp Về ngay Về ngay lập tức Về nhanh Về liên tục Về tức thì Về tạm thời Về liên lập tức Về đều đặn Tới đều đặn Tới dần Tới gấp Tới liên Tới liên lập tức Tới liên tục Trở lại đều đặn Trở lại gấp Trở lại liên Trở lại liên lập tức Trở lại ngay Trở lại ngay lập tức Trở lại nhanh Trở lại nhất thời Trở lại vĩnh viễn Trở lại tạm thời Trở lại tức thì Xuống liên tục Xuống ngay Xuống ngay lập tức Xuống nhanh Xuống nhất thời Xuống tạm thời Xuống tức thì Xuống vĩnh viễn Xuống liên</p>		<p>Xuống trễ</p>	
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	Xuống liền lập tức Xuống chậm Xuống đều đặn Xuống dần Xuống gấp			
Total	129	36	66	16
247				

Ly Ngoc Toan
Ho Chi Minh City University of Law
02 Nguyen Tat Thanh, Xom Chieu Ward
Ho Chi Minh City
Vietnam
e-mail: lntoan@hcmulaw.edu.vn

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Iconicity in the Igbo Sign Language (ISL)

Maureen Azuka Ezeani & Martha Chidimma Egenti
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria

Iconicity is a relationship of resemblance or similarity between the two aspects of a sign: its form and its meaning (Meir & Tkachman (2018), and it is a general feature in all sign languages. This work sets out to investigate the manifestation of iconicity in the signing patterns of Igbo home signers, with a view to identifying the forms iconicity take in the language. A wordlist containing some iconically motivated Igbo lexical items is administered to selected deaf Igbo home signers to sign. The pictorial representations of these lexical items are presented and motivations behind them also given. Using the descriptive approach and borrowing a leaf from Edward (2005), the data so collected are analyzed and discussed under the concepts of size and shapes, expression of time, emotive and cognitive signs, and directional verbs. The study observes that the Igbo sign language is highly iconic, and has a great similarity with iconic signs in other African Indigenous Sign Languages such as Adamorobe Sign Language (AdaSL). The study concludes, in line with cross-linguistic findings, that iconicity is an essential of sign languages. The study recommends more scholarly works on iconicity in other African indigenous sign languages.

Keywords: sign language, iconicity, home signs, Igbo, deaf

1 Introduction

An icon is a visual representation of something else. It can be an object, person, place, idea to mention but a few. Icons have iconicity when they are similar in some way to what they represent. Iconicity is the characteristic of a sign where the form of the sign mirrors its meaning. What this implies is that the sign resembles what it depicts. It is a general feature in all sign languages. An iconic sign is that whose form looks like its meaning in some way. For example, wall street bull representing a bull stock market, a restroom sign showing a picture of a man or a woman represents which rest room is for men and which one is for women, a stethoscope can represent a profession of a doctor and so on. White (2020) states that it is not all iconicity is visual in nature, she acknowledges that linguistic symbols, such as sounds and sign language can also be iconic.

The focus of this study is on “Iconicity in the Igbo Sign Language” which tries to investigate the manifestation of iconicity in the Igbo sign language, by exploring the communication system of the Igbo home signers: an informal basic sign system that is sometimes developed within a single family in the Igbo community, especially when hearing parents who have no skills in sign language have a deaf child. The study informed by understudied and underdeveloped situation the Igbo Sign Language is presently facing, the researchers set to carry out this research in order to align with 2020 declaration of the International Decade of Indigenous Languages by United Nations/ UNESCO, and to bring the Igbo Sign Language to limelight as other indigenous sign languages. The above-mentioned problem is actually the gap which this work wants to bridge.

Ajavon (2006), Orié (2013), Nyst (2007) and Asonye et al. (2018) which are on native Nigerian sign systems are true evidence that indigenous African sign languages can and should be studied. As Ajavon (2006: 1) aptly puts it, “Persons with special needs in Nigeria have a history of neglect and marginalization within their families and communities”. Her work reveals the discrimination and social exclusion suffered by the deaf, dumb and hard of hearing Nigerians due to difficulties they have communicating with hearing people around them. The reality seen in Ajavon’s (2006) assertion spurred the researchers’ interest more on how the Igbo Sign Language (ISL) can be developed just like other indigenous African languages. Interestingly, Orié’s (2013) work on Yoruba Sign Language, Nyst’s (2007) on Village Signs in Ghana, Mali and Nigeria also had a snowball effect on the decision to embark on this research.

The subsequent parts of the study come in the following five sections: section two reviews the related and relevant literature and elucidates the concepts used in the study, section three provides the methodology of the study, section four presents the data and analyses them, while section five concludes on the study.

2 Elucidation of basic concepts

2.1 Sign

Sign can be seen as an object, quality, event, or entity whose presence or occurrence indicates the probable presence or occurrence of something else. It can be a gesture or action used to convey information or an instruction. Sign is a general feature in all sign languages. According to Bussmann (1996: 936), “Sign is an abstract class of all sensually perceivable signals that refer to the same object state of affairs in the real world”. MCGregor (2009) sees sign as a fundamental item made up of two inherent components, a form sometimes called “signifier” and a meaning also called “signified.” Crystal (2007) says that in such phrase as sign language and sign system, the term “sign” has a very restricted sense, referring to the system of manual communication used by certain groups as an alternative to oral communication. For the purpose of this work, the definition of ‘sign’ by Crystal is considered.

2.2 Sign language

The term sign language is also known as Dactylology. In Encyclopedia Britannica, fingerspelling or dactylology is defined as the representation of letters or numerals using only the hands. It is a method of communication in which letters or numbers are represented through specific positions or movements of the fingers and hand, commonly used in manual alphabets of sign languages. Riekehof (1987) put it that sign language is a language that uses manual symbols to represent ideas and concepts. The term, according to her is generally used by the deaf people where both manual signs and finger spelling are employed. MCGregor (2009) also captures the same phrase “sign language” saying that it uses gesture to represent words, ideas and concepts. The National Association of Deaf (NAD) recognizes sign language as a language which uses manual communication and body language to convey meaning as opposed to acoustically conveyed sound patterns. It added also that sign language can involve simultaneously combining hand shapes, orientation and movement of hands, arms or body and facial expression to fluidly express a speaker’s thought.

From the foregoing, we see that sign language can be considered to be a visual gestural language which is expressed through the hands and face, and is perceived through the eyes. Therefore, this work adopts the description which says that sign language is a language that uses manual communication and body language to convey meaning as opposed to acoustically conveyed sound patterns for the term sign language. The concept of sign language is not just waving one's hands in the air. One can add meaning or change meaning in the language furrowing the eyebrows, tilting the head, glancing in a certain direction, leaning one's body a certain way, puffing one's cheek or any other type of inflections. Examples of signs and information they represent in American Sign Language are shown below:

Figure 1: Some American Signs and their Explanations (Rickehof 1987: 24)

Figure 2: How some words are signed in ASL (<https://www.handspeak.com>)

2.3 Gesture

Crystal (2007) describes gesture as a term used in the phonology for a matrix of features specifying a particular characteristic of a segment. In his example, an oral gesture would specify all supraglottal characteristics such as place and manner of articulation, and a laryngeal gesture would specify characteristics of phonation. McGregor (2009) talks about gesture saying that it is the distinctive movement of a body part conveying meaning, for example, a manual gesture conveying meaning “Ok”, or shaking the head in denial. Gesture is part of what Hall and Hall (1971) call “Nonverbal communication” in their study on *The Language of the Body: Kinesics and Proxemics*. They mention that nonverbal communication which includes gesture is the first form of communication one learns, and the only language used throughout most of the history of humanity. Evans (2019) says that gesture refers to the use of hand, arm, head and torso movements, as well as facial expressions, that that are co-timed with language. Kendon (2004) claims that gesture constitutes visible action as utterance: gestures complement and often supplement information conveyed via the spoken medium, adding meaning not otherwise

apparent. The description of the term “gesture” by Evans (2019) is adopted in this work, as it has a closer relationship with the field of linguistics we are researching on.

2.4 Iconicity

Iconicity is basically seen as the resemblance of a symbol to its referent. It is an essential tool in creation of language, spoken or signed (e.g. Imai & Kita 2015; Perniss & Vigiliocco 2014). Meir & Tkachman (2018) assert that iconicity is a relationship or similarity between the two aspects of a sign: its form and its meaning. In their further explanations, they mention that because iconicity has to do with the properties of sign in general and not only those of linguistics signs, it plays an important role in the field of semiotics. They identify various kinds of iconicity saying that the form of a sign may resemble aspects of its meaning in several ways: it may create a mental image of the concept (imagic iconicity), or its structure and the arrangement of its element may resemble the structural relationship between components of the concept represented (diagrammatic iconicity). An example of imagic iconicity for them is the word “*cukoo*”, whose sounds resemble the call of the bird, or a sign such as RABBIT in Israeli Sign Language, whose form (the hands representing the rabbit’s long ears)-resembles a visual property of the animal. Example of diagrammatic iconicity is given as *vēnī, vīdī, vīcī*, where the order of clauses in a discourse is understood as reflecting the sequence of events in the world. Crystal (1987) points out that icons are symbols which show a physical resemblance of objects they represent. Because of the similarities between object and icon, he says that symbols are usually interpreted with little difficulty.

2.5 Iconicity in Sign Language

The initial studies on Iconicity in American Sign Language (ASL) have their publications in late 1970s and early 1980s. During that period, a good number of sign language linguists did not accept the notion that iconicity was an essential part of sign language. This is seen in the words of Frisberg (1975) when she declares that many early sign language linguists rejected the notion that iconicity was an important aspect of the language. Klima and Bellugi (1979) also add that though these early sign language scholars recognized that some aspects of the language seemed iconic, they still considered it as merely extra linguistic, a property which did not influence the language. A very influential paper on the relationship between arbitrariness and iconicity in ASL written by Frisberg (1975) concludes that though originally present in many signs, iconicity is degraded over time through the application of grammatical processes. This is to say that over time, the natural processes of regularization in the language obscures any iconically motivated features of the sign. However, the rejection of iconicity in the traditional research of sign languages, owing to the fact that it is believed that having iconicity in a system does not entail arbitrariness has been disputed by the pioneers of sign language linguistics, who were overwhelmed with the task of trying to prove that.

Nyst (2013) describes iconicity in African Sign Languages referring to it as the perceived resemblance between the form of a sign and its meaning. For her, it is a powerful structuring force in many, if not all sign languages. However, she says that how iconicity takes shape may differ from one sign language to another. For example, where the sign language of Guinea-Bissau (SLGB) signs for “elephant” refers to the ears of the animal, the AdaSL sign represents its trunk.

Figure 3: Signs for Elephant in SLGB and AdaSL (Nyst 2013: 79)

From Edward (2015), it is understood that sign language is iconic or picture-like. Because icons are, in most cases, visible symbols, it is understandable that observers may relate shape and symbol when they study language. According to her, a close and careful look will clarify whether or not iconicity is a significant factor in sign language. In her further explanations, she has it that the relationship between a word and the concept it represents is considered thus: the word “dog” neither looks, smells, sounds, feels nor tastes like the object to which it refers. The same applies to “table” and “human”. The relationship between words (whether spoken or written) and the concept they represent is generally arbitrary. Since arbitrary symbols share no physical characteristics with the things they symbolize, it can be said that arbitrariness is the opposite of iconicity. The concept represented by the word *house* is represented by *casa* in Spanish, *maison* in French, *don* in Russia and *bait* in Hebrew. These words are not related to each other, nor are they like the concept they represent, although the icon (picture) may be clear to all the speakers of these languages. She mentions that in American Sign Language (ASL), when house is made by itself, it appears to be iconic; the image of a roof and two walls are outlined by both hands. Many other signs tend to be iconic such as eat, milk, sit, and cat.

Figure 4: Examples of icon signs in American Sign Language (ASL) (www. quora.com)

In further review of iconicity in sign language, a study done on iconicity in the Adamorobe Sign Language (AdaSL) by Edward (2015) analyzes iconicity in Adamorobe, explaining the signs under the following concepts: size and shapes, expression of time, emotive and cognitive signs and verb directionality. This is actually where this study borrowed leaf in analyzing iconic signs in Igbo.

Summarily, from the literature so far reviewed, no work has been specifically done on iconicity in the Igbo Sign Language. This is actually a worrying situation, a gap which this study sets out to bridge by venturing into studying the Igbo iconic signs, to see the different ways they manifest in the signing patterns of Igbo home signers, with the aim of bringing the Igbo Sign Language to the limelight among other indigenous African Sign Languages.

3 Methodology

The area where this research was carried out is the Igbo region of Nigeria. The states in the core Igbo region include Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo. The Igbo language is primarily spoken as L1 by the Igbo people in Nigeria who occupy the southeastern part of the country. Some Igbo communities viz: Lekwesi in Abia, Nteje in Anambra, Ugbenyim in Ebonyi, Ovoko in Enugu and Alike Umulumo in Imo were randomly selected for the fieldwork. We choose these linguistic communities because they harbor deaf signers that have not acquired any formal education, this is to say that these deaf persons have Igbo as their L1.

According to Williamson and Blench's (2000) classification, Igbo belongs to the West Benue-Congo sub family of the Proto Benue-Congo language family. The CIA World Factbook puts the Igbo population of Nigeria at 18% or approximately a total population of 44 million people. There is no known resource or research done on the already endangered language of the deaf group of people in Igbo. This is part of the stigmatization and negligence as no one cares to know much about them. There is little or no trace of a well-researched work done on their language of communication. In the 2016 Ethnologue, the Igbo language is shown by a large coloured (Purple) dot meaning that the language has been developed to the point that it is

used and sustained by institutions. The Igbo deaf individuals who reside in their various homes and their relatives who understand them better were used as informants for this study.

Data elicitation for the study was from among the deaf individuals found in Igbo locality. In the elicitation of information, the researcher made use of structured interview and wordlist. The informants hail from the five mentioned Igbo states. Through simple random sampling technique, five deaf persons were chosen, one from each state, plus one relative of each of the chosen deaf individuals, making it ten informants altogether. These relatives of the deaf were useful in the interpretation of signs. Our corpus targeted up to 25 words were collected through videos and snapshots for analysis and proper documentation purposes. The pictures depicting signs of each of the words in the wordlist administered to the informants were presented according to how a signer from a named Igbo state expresses it. The selected informants were not found in a deaf community but in isolation as they live with their hearing relatives in their respective homes. Each sign is rightly labeled and phonemically transcribed in the local language and then glossed. The transcriptions so given are also tone marked as the language of our research is a tone language. High tone is marked with the acute accent [´], the low tone with grave accent [˘] and the down step tone with macron [-]. By adopting qualitative method, the researchers borrowed leaf from Edward (2015) and analyzed the data under the concepts of size and shape, expression of time, emotive and cognitive signs, and directional verbs.

4 Discussion and findings

4.1 *The Igbo sign language*

Igbo sign language is a yet to be standardized language of the deaf persons in the Igbo communities, which is still under investigation. Ezeani (2023), is a PhD dissertation, titled “Igbo Sign Language Development: A Case for Igbo Home Signs” which focuses on developing the communication system of the home signers. Just like Adamorobe Sign Language and other indigenous African sign languages, Igbo Sign Language is not yet a documented or a formal language that is employed in official businesses. The history of this system of communication is still vague and deaf population in Igbo region is not known yet. This is due to poor attitudes played against them through neglect, marginalization and stigmatization in the Igbo area, such that only a handful of hearing individuals care to know about them and get their means of communication developed. There are little or no scholarly studies on the Igbo Sign Language. The only few noticed are yet to be published or recently published (e.g. Ezeani & Eme 2023 and Chikeluba 2022).

4.2 *Iconicity in the Igbo sign language (ISL)*

Iconicity is evident in most lexical structures in the Igbo Sign Language (ISL). For the purpose of this study, we are going to focus on iconic elements that indicate size and shape, expression of time, emotive and cognitive signs, and directional verbs. The signs for the above concepts in Igbo are those that have iconic intent. Here, some of the iconically motivated signs in the Igbo Sign Language (ISL) are presented. The motivations behind these iconic signs are given alongside the pictures of the signs.

4.2.1 Iconicity in expression of size and shape in the Igbo sign language (ISL)

The structure of sign here focuses on the shape and size of the entity that is being represented. In the Igbo Sign Language, the signs that depict size and shape entities are highly iconic. For instance, the signs for *efere* (plate) and *achicha* (bread) in Igbo home signs are depicted by making a circular movement with two hands to show the round shape of the plate and a vertical raising of the dominant hand to show the long size of the bread as in figures 5 & 6:

The motivation behind this sign, *efere/éféré/* “plate” is the circular movement of the two hands made by the signer indicating the normal round shape and portable size of plates.

Figure 5: *efere /éféré/* “plate”

The motivation behind the sign *achicha/àfìfà/* “bread” is the vertical raising of the right (dominant hand) to show the shape and size of the entity in question.

Figure 6: *achicha/àfìfà/* “bread”

4.2.2 Iconicity in expression of time in Igbo sign language (ISL)

Another area where iconic signs are expressed in the Igbo Sign Language is in expression of time. Alkoby (1999) identifies two types of signs that express time in American Sign Language (ASL): Lexical tense markers which are lexically independent time signs, and Time adverbials that function as adverbs. There are evidence of lexical tense markers and time adverbials in the Igbo sign language and both of them are what we grouped under signs that express time. In American Sign Language (ASL), time indicators are usually referred to as time signs, for example, words like *finish* and *will* indicate time. *finish* indicating past or completed actions while *will* indicate future actions. Words like *now* and *today* are also referred to as present time signs in American Sign Language (ASL) according to Alkoby (1999). He stressed that these time signs have a relative location on the time line, which corresponds to their meaning (i.e past is behind and present and future are in front, and they are deictic in nature. Figure 7 is a pictorial illustration of time line:

Figure 7: Culled from Alkoby (1999: 5)

In the Igbo Sign Language (ISL) also, there are signs that indicate past (back), present or future (present), indicated in figures (8) – (10) respectively:

The motivation behind the sign *unyaahu/òjàáhò* “yesterday” is the backward pointing of one finger (either the index finger or the thumb) to indicate time in the past.

Figure 8: *unyaahu/òjàáhò* /“yesterday”

Figure 9: *taata/táàtá*/ “today”

The motivation behind the sign *taata/táàtá*/ “today” is the downward and steady pointing of the two-index fingers to indicate present time. Thus, *taata/táàtá*/ “today” and *ugbua/ùgbùà*/ “now” can be signed the same way.

Figure 10: *echi/éfi* “tomorrow”

The motivation behind the sign *echi/éfi* “tomorrow” is the forward pointing of the index finger to indicate future time.

4.2.3 Iconicity in expression of emotive cognitive signs in the Igbo sign language (ISL)

Edward (2012) mentions that cognitive signs in Ghanaian Sign Language are limited to the forehead while emotive signs are limited to the chest area. This shows the iconicity of these signs in the sense that emotions are related to the heart which positioned at the chest and cognition related to the mind located at the forehead. These same limitations are equally applicable to the Igbo Sign Language (ISL). There are also certain facial expressions that usually accompany emotive and cognitive signs in the language which give additional meaning to the signs. Illustrations of iconic motivated emotive and cognitive signs from the Igbo Sign Language are shown figure 11:

Figure 11: *ara/árá*/ “madness”

The motivation behind the sign *ara/árá*/ “madness” is the steering movement with the two-index fingers beside the two sides of the forehead indicating disorderliness of the brain future time.

The motivation behind the sign *ufu/ófó/* “pain” is the shaking of the two hands indicating pains, accompanied with squeezing of the face.

Figure 12: *ufu/ófó/* “pain”

The motivation behind the sign *onu/ónò/* “happiness” is bright and cheerful look accompanied with jovial display.

Figure 13: *onu/ónò/* “happiness”

4.2.4 Iconicity in expression of directional verbs in the Igbo sign language (ISL)

Directional verbs are outstanding iconic signs in the Igbo Sign Language (ISL). Most verbal signs from our data directional and the direction of the signer’s hand has to do with location of the signer and the addressee. Sign movement from the signer to the addressee and vice versa depends mostly on being passed across. As the speaker is the deictic point in spoken languages, the signer is the deictic point in sign languages in discussions of verbal agreement thus, achieving the rule of economy and iconicity. Deixis is associated with the location of the speaker and the addressee. Edward (2014) mentions that the distance relevant to the speaker or the addressee could be proximal or distal and the spatial deixis are used to communicate the information that has to do with change in direction or the use of direction. Directional verbs are seen as agreement verbs showing that they agree iconically with the subject or object of reference (Edward 2014; Nyst 2007). Some directional verbs noticed in the Igbo Sign Language (ISL) are presented in figures (14) & (15):

The motivation behind the sign *kwu/kwú* “talk” is the two-way directional movement of the dominant hand toward the signer and the addressee.

Figure 14: *kwu/kwú* “talk”

The motivation behind the sign *weta/wètá* “bring” is the one-way directional movement of the dominant hand toward the signer alone.

Figure 15: *weta/wètá* “bring”

From our discussions above, the researchers found out that in the Igbo Sign Language, iconicity is a predominant element of signs that manifests at a high level under the core concepts of iconicity analysis: size and shape (figs. 5 & 6), expression of time (figs. 8, 9 & 10), expression of emotive and cognitive signs (figs. 11, 12 & 13) and expression of directional verbs (figs. 14 & 15).

Cross-linguistically, the researchers found out that most examples of iconicity in indigenous African sign languages that are yet to be official/standardized are very much similar to each other than to the already standardized and official American Sign Language. This, we say might be the reason why these African sign languages are still at the verge of being developed at every level of language development.

5 Conclusion

Iconicity is a vital and prominent element of sign languages that refers to the characteristics of a sign where the form of the sign conveys its meaning. It is evident in all languages, both spoken and signed. This study is a step in the right direction to promote the development of indigenous languages especially the most endangered ones as declared by United Nations/UNESCO in 2020, the international decade of indigenous languages. Following the

declaration, it becomes expedient to promote the study of African languages (the Igbo sign language inclusive) in order to accord them equal growth and development opportunity in the global space. This study is therefore a good contribution to knowledge as it aims at bringing an already endangered Igbo Sign Language to the limelight, beckoning on the African linguistic scholars to join the trend to get the language developed and standardized.

6 Recommendation

The researchers recommend that more intensive cross-linguistic study on iconicity of many other indigenous African sign languages should be carried out to ascertain clearly the iconic similarity and differences that exist among them.

Abbreviations

AdaSL	Adamorobe Sign Language
ASL	American Sign Language
CIA	Central Intelligence Agency
FIG	Figure
ISL	Igbo Sign Language
NAD	National Association of Deaf
SLGB	Sign Language of Guinea-Bissau

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Maureen Azuka Ezeani
Department of Linguistics,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria
e-mail: ma.chikeluba@unizik.edu.ng

Martha Chidimma Egenti
Department of Linguistics,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria
e-mail: cm.egenti@unizik.edu.ng

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Understanding Strategic Manoeuvring through the Lens of Perspective-Taking

Denis Shuvalov
University of Szeged

This article examines the cognitive foundations of strategic manoeuvring (SM) within the pragma-dialectical (PD) framework. Although PD is grounded in the principle of externalisation, which prioritises publicly attributable commitments over private mental states, the strategic character of SM implies goal-directed planning and anticipatory orientation towards interlocutors' likely responses. Building on Kraus's (2025) analysis of what the term strategic designates, the paper argues that this orientation presupposes a specific socio-cognitive capacity: perspective-taking (PT), understood here as the ability to model another agent's epistemic, evaluative-affective, and inferential stance. Three analytically relevant modes of PT — epistemic, evaluative-affective, and inferential — are distinguished and mapped onto the three aspects of the SM triangle: choices from topical potential, audience adaptation, and presentational devices. This mapping shows that SM may be understood as the discourse-level realisation of perspective-sensitive cognitive operations: selecting arguments from topical potential requires managing common ground and tracking the interlocutor's epistemic landscape; audience adaptation depends on modelling the addressee's values and affective orientation; and presentational devices involve anticipating inferential uptake and processing effort. The paper further argues that integrating PT into a PD account need not violate the principle of externalisation, because the two operate at different explanatory levels: externalisation governs what may be reconstructed and normatively evaluated, whereas PT provides a psychologically realistic account of how arguers navigate the argumentative predicament. The framework is illustrated through a brief constructed example. The paper concludes that PT supplies the cognitive infrastructure for strategic calibration, while SM constitutes its argumentative implementation in discourse.

Keywords: *pragma-dialectics, strategic manoeuvring, perspective-taking, externalisation, argumentation*

1 Introduction

1.1 *Perspective-taking as a cognitive point of departure*

In developmental and social cognition research, *perspective-taking* (PT) is treated as a behavioural manifestation of theory of mind: the capacity to reason about others' intentions, beliefs, knowledge, and desires, recruited across virtually every domain of social interaction (Bezuidenhout 2013; Davis 1983). PT will accordingly be understood here as a core socio-cognitive capacity that enables individuals to construct, maintain, and update representations of other agents' mental states.

For the purposes of the present account, it is useful to distinguish three analytically relevant modes of PT:

- 1) Epistemic PT: the modelling of what the interlocutor knows, believes, or accepts as common ground, which allows a speaker to assess which premises are likely to be treated as acceptable starting points and which require explicit support (Clark & Brennan 1991; Clark 1996).
- 2) Evaluative-affective PT: the modelling of what the interlocutor values, feels, or is likely to find desirable, threatening, or objectionable in a given situation, enabling the speaker to attune the move to the addressee's evaluative and emotional orientation (Healey & Grossman 2018; Bacha-Trams et al. 2020).
- 3) Inferential PT: the anticipation of how a particular formulation will be interpreted, what inferences it is likely to generate, and how much processing effort it will require. This mode is operationalised in audience design, where speakers tailor utterances by modelling the interlocutor's knowledge, goals, and attentional focus (Ferreira 2019), and is captured in relevance theory by the notion of *optimal relevance*, which presupposes expectations about the addressee's inferential resources and likely cognitive effects (Sperber & Wilson 1995). Brandom's inferentialist pragmatics makes a parallel claim at the level of semantic theory: the content of an utterance is to be understood in terms of its *inferential role*, that is, in terms of the commitments and entitlements that articulate what follows from saying it (Brandom 1994). From a more explicitly social-cognitive perspective, Forgács (2024) likewise treats mentalisation as central to utterance interpretation.

These distinctions are introduced here as analytically useful rather than as fully discrete categories. In actual discourse, epistemic, evaluative-affective, and inferential orientations frequently overlap and interact. They are differentiated here only in order to provide a more systematic basis for the later argumentative analysis.

If these three modes of PT are operative in ordinary communication, they can be expected to play a comparable role in argumentative discourse, where speakers continuously anticipate and manage addressees' responses. The following section introduces the pragma-dialectical framework within which this expectation will be developed.

1.2 *Pragma-dialectics and strategic manoeuvring*

The pragma-dialectical theory of argumentation (PD), developed by van Eemeren & Grootendorst (2004: 1–5), conceptualises argumentative discourse as a regulated form of social interaction aimed at resolving a difference of opinion on the merits. It combines pragmatic insights into language use with dialectical norms of critical discussion, evaluating argumentative moves in terms of their contribution to the resolution process. For the purposes of the present paper, the most central of these meta-theoretical commitments is the principle of externalisation. It postulates that analysts should set aside arguers' private mental states and reconstruct argumentative discourse in terms of the commitments and obligations publicly attributable to the participants, whether explicit or implicit, insofar as the latter are reconstructible from what has been said and from the roles and starting points the participants have adopted.

Argumentation unfolds through a sequence of stages — confrontation, opening, argumentation, and concluding — governed by the ten rules of critical discussion, which together form the ideal model of a critical discussion. Violations of these rules constitute fallacies in pragma-dialectical terms: moves that hinder or obstruct the resolution process rather

than advance it (van Eemeren & Grootendorst 2004; van Eemeren 2010). This is because arguers are not always disposed to comply fully with dialectical rules, often pursuing rhetorical objectives as well, namely, to make their standpoint as acceptable and persuasive as possible. The resulting need to balance reasonableness with effectiveness is what PD addresses through the concept of *strategic manoeuvring* (SM) and, more specifically, through what van Eemeren (2010) and van Eemeren & Houtlosser (2002) term the “argumentative predicament”. This balancing act is executed across three interconnected aspects:

1. Topical potential: the strategic selection of arguments and premises from the available argumentative stock relevant to the current stage of the discussion — that is, the set of possible standpoints, starting points, lines of argument, and argument schemes. SM from topical potential concerns how arguers choose among these alternatives to remain reasonable while achieving rhetorical effect (van Eemeren 2010).

2. Audience adaptation: the attuning of argumentative moves to the commitments, expectations, and values of the addressee. Adaptation aims at establishing resonance or “communion” with the audience, often through audience-directed framing or the strategic use of persuasive definitions that align a concept with the audience’s existing commitments (van Eemeren & Houtlosser 2002, 2006; van Eemeren 2015; Zarefsky 2008).

3. Presentational devices: the strategic deployment of stylistic and linguistic resources in shaping the argumentative move (van Eemeren & Houtlosser 2002). These may include rhetorical figures, deliberate choices in discourse arrangement, and the selection of lexical items or specialised terminology — for instance hyperbole, metaphor, rhetorical questions, or standalone expressions (Snoeck Henkemans 2009, 2013; Zhang & Xu 2018; Pilgram & van Poppel 2021; Jansen & Henkemans 2021; van Haaften 2019).

When coordinated across a succession of moves, these three aspects constitute what van Eemeren (2019: 165) describes as an arguer’s “argumentative style”. The defining constraint on all three, however, is accountability to dialectical norms: where the pursuit of rhetorical effectiveness overrides commitment to critical standards, SM crosses into fallacious derailment (van Eemeren & Garssen 2023). This refinement allows fallacies to be understood not merely as logical errors but as identifiable strategic derailments within argumentative practice. While this completes the brief outline of SM as theorised within PD, it leaves open what the term strategic itself implies about the capacities required to perform such manoeuvring — an issue brought more sharply into focus in the following subsection.

2 What *strategic* means in strategic manoeuvring

Kraus (2025) reflects on what the term *strategic* in *SM* actually designates, dissecting the martial metaphor from both semantic and historical perspectives. Drawing on work in military history and strategic studies, he traces how *strategy* originally referred to the art of the general and was sharply distinguished from *tactics*: strategy concerned long-term goals, the overall conduct of a conflict, and the direction of resources, whereas tactics dealt with local moves on the battlefield. As Kraus shows, this distinction gradually evolved, and the term “strategy” has since been extended far beyond warfare, yet certain core elements remain remarkably stable: orientation towards a goal, the constrained use of limited means, and, crucially, premeditation and anticipation of other agents’ actions.

In his discussion of modern strategic theory, Kraus (2025) highlights definitions that explicitly foreground thinking ahead and anticipating the opponent's moves as central to what counts as *strategic* action. For instance, he cites work in strategic studies where strategy is described as maintaining a balance between ends, ways, and means, and as necessarily involving a “dialectic of wills” in which at least two parties are engaged in potentially conflicting projects. On this view, strategy is not a mere label for any planned activity, but a mode of conduct that presupposes agents who are able to form long-term objectives, mentally rehearse possible courses of action, and adjust those courses in light of expected counter-moves. The strategic agent, in other words, is not simply acting, but acting with an internal model of other actors' likely responses.

The implication is direct. If manoeuvring in argumentation is described as strategic, then the relevant moves cannot be characterised merely as patterns of discourse choices identifiable after the fact; they also presuppose an anticipatory orientation, on the part of the arguer, towards the interlocutor's likely responses. A move becomes strategic not simply because it is rhetorically effective, but because it is selected under conditions of projected uptake: from the available topical potential, with regard to what the audience is likely to accept, and by means of formulations whose interpretation and impact are in some measure foreseen.

The audience-oriented dimension of SM has a deep affinity with the classical rhetorical tradition. Aristotle's *Rhetoric* already treats attention to the audience's beliefs, emotional dispositions, and probable reactions as constitutive of persuasion rather than incidental to it (*Rhetoric*, I.2, 1356a), and this insight remained central to rhetorical theory in its modern revival, most notably in Perelman & Olbrechts-Tyteca's *The New Rhetoric* (1969), where the projected model of the addressee grounds the entire theory of argumentative effectiveness.

Kraus's (2025) reconstruction brings into focus a question of direct relevance to pragma-dialectics: what conceptual implications follow from describing argumentative manoeuvres as *strategic*? Is *strategic* here merely a softened metaphor — a way of labelling the integration of rhetorical considerations into a dialectical framework; or does it also carry some of the connotations that *strategy* has acquired in military and strategic studies, such as goal orientation, planning, and the anticipation of another party's moves? Put differently: when we describe arguers as engaging in SM, are we not implicitly treating them as agents who (a) pursue argumentative goals, (b) allocate their discursive resources accordingly, and (c) anticipate the interlocutor's interpretive and evaluative reactions? If so, the martial metaphor does more than provide a convenient label; it suggests a particular picture of what arguers are capable of doing when they argue.

This suggestion finds support, at least indirectly, in how SM is described elsewhere in the pragma-dialectical literature. Van Eemeren & Houtlosser (2002) characterise discussion moves as being oriented not only toward the dialectical aim of resolving a difference of opinion, but also toward the rhetorical aim related to making one's standpoint acceptable and persuasive within the discussion. At a minimum, this idea presupposes that arguers treat their contributions as means to an end and therefore as subject to choice rather than as mechanically determined responses. More explicitly audience-oriented considerations enter the picture in the notion of *audience demand*, where SM is linked to assumptions about what the audience is likely to accept, reject, or find persuasive at a given stage of the discussion (van Eemeren & Houtlosser 2002: 156).

Zarefsky's (2014: 142) analysis of SM through persuasive definitions makes a similar assumption: persuasive definitions work only if the arguer can anticipate how a redefinition

will appeal to, or clash with, the audience’s existing commitments. Greco et al. (2022) argue that the explicit naming of emotions can fulfil constructive functions within mediation, such as clarifying the core of the conflict, supporting the parties’ participation as co-arguers, and facilitating progress in the interaction. Crucially, however, emotion naming is treated as a delicate and potentially risky presentational choice: the authors note that bringing emotions to the surface may also fuel escalation if handled inappropriately. For this reason, mediators do not introduce emotional formulations indiscriminately; rather, they attribute emotions tentatively and routinely invite confirmation from the parties themselves. This practice presupposes an ability to recognise emotionally salient aspects of the interaction and to assess whether their explicit formulation is interactionally warranted at a given moment, even if the cognitive processes underlying such assessments are not themselves theorised. Haafte’s (2019) treatment of argumentative strategies and stylistic devices likewise situates presentational choices within the aspect of *audience demand*. He argues that rhetorical figures and stylistic means are analytically relevant because they realise an argumentative strategy aimed at making a discussion move acceptable to a particular audience in a given communicative context, rather than serving as mere stylistic embellishments.

Across these cases, the label *strategic* appears to rely on an understanding of arguers as, in some sense, looking ahead: they choose, formulate, and time their contributions with regard to projected audience uptake. Without making any explicit psychological commitments, we can at least observe that the strategic vocabulary used in pragma-dialectical scholarship presupposes certain abilities: to identify goals, to weigh alternative options, and to judge how a particular move is likely to be interpreted within a given interactional context.

The ability to weigh different options from the topical potential, to estimate which formulations will resonate with a particular audience, or to foresee where a line of argument might be vulnerable in cross-examination seems to require more than mechanical rule-following. It appears to presuppose the capacity to form second-order representations of the interlocutor’s beliefs, expectations, and possible reactions — in short, some form of PT or theory of mind. This resonates with cognitive-pragmatic approaches, such as relevance theory that is explicitly presented as “a framework for the study of cognition, proposed primarily in order to provide a psychologically realistic account of communication” (Allott 2013: 57). On Sperber & Wilson’s account (1995), verbal communication is *ostensive–inferential*: a communicator produces an ostensive stimulus which raises precise expectations of relevance, and the addressee recovers the intended meaning by a process of inference guided by those expectations. Central to this model is the notion of a *cognitive environment* and a *mutual cognitive environment*, i.e. the set of assumptions that are manifest to an individual or shared between interlocutors. For an utterance to be optimally relevant, the communicator must design it against a representation of the addressee’s cognitive environment: what the addressee is likely to know, believe, or be able to infer. And the addressee must integrate the decoded linguistic material with those background assumptions to derive the intended conclusions. In this sense, successful communication in relevance-theoretic terms does indeed depend on the capacity to model the addressee’s informational state and to anticipate which inferences will naturally follow from a given stimulus in that state, a point further emphasised in subsequent relevance-theoretic work on humour, where interlocutors’ “collective representations” are explicitly foregrounded (Yus 2016).

Against this background, the pragma-dialectical talk of SM can be read in at least two ways. On a minimalist reading, *strategic* functions as a purely discursive notion: it refers to

patterns of choices in argument selection, audience adaptation, and presentational form, reconstructed at the level of externalised commitments, without any claim about the psychological processes that give rise to them. On a richer reading, however, Kraus's analysis invites us to ask whether the very choice of this term does not already lean towards a more mentalistic picture of the arguer, as someone who plans ahead, simulates possible developments of the discussion, and continuously adjusts their moves in light of projected responses. Although the pragma-dialectical framework does not reconstruct arguers' actual private mental states since they are not directly accessible, its strategic vocabulary already presupposes capacities that invite cognitive clarification.

In what follows, I adopt this second, richer reading as a heuristic. I suggest that the *strategic* in SM can be illuminated by asking what kind of cognitive architecture would be required to perform the kind of balancing act that the theory describes. If strategy, in Kraus's historically informed sense, involves premeditation, anticipation of other agents' moves, and the coordination of means to ends in a context of potentially conflicting wills, then it seems natural to hypothesise that SM in argumentation presupposes a faculty of PT — an ability to represent and reason about the interlocutor's epistemic and affective stance.

This brings into focus two questions that the remainder of the paper seeks to address:

- (1) what kinds of capacities must arguers possess in order to engage in SM at all;
- (2) and second, how can PT be theorised as the cognitive infrastructure that enables SM.

If *strategic* in SM implies anticipatory modelling of other agents' responses, the question that follows is whether existing cognitive approaches to argumentation have already supplied the conceptual tools to account for this modelling. The following section argues that they have not — or not fully or explicitly: while the relevant intuition is widely present across the literature, PT as a named and theorised capacity tends to be presupposed rather than thematised in its own right.

3 Cognitive approaches to argumentation

Across cognitive approaches to argumentation, scholars routinely employ an explicitly mentalistic vocabulary, appealing to notions such as *mental models* and *conceptual frameworks* to explain how arguers organise, retrieve, and structure knowledge in discourse (Popova & Pushkarsky 2023). Others introduce multidimensional thought spaces as the internal architecture within which argumentative positions are organised and compared (Akramova 2024). Cognitive pragmatics contributes the notion of *cognitive environments* — the sets of manifest assumptions that interlocutors are presumed to navigate during inferential communication (Sperber & Wilson 1995). Recent work at the interface of pragmatics and argumentation makes this connection more explicit. Oswald's cognitive-pragmatic approach shows that argumentative interpretation is shaped not only by normative commitments but also by processing constraints and contextual selection, especially in cases involving manipulation, strategic framing, and fallacious argumentation (Maillat & Oswald 2011; Oswald 2023). In a related vein, Zufferey's work on discourse connectives and pragmatic processing, together with the study by Schumann, Zufferey, and Oswald, shows that linguistic formulation affects how argumentative relations are processed and evaluated, including in the case of straw man fallacies (Schumann et al. 2021; Zufferey & Degand 2024). Taken together, these studies

suggest that argumentative moves are constrained not only by dialectical norms, but also by the cognitive-pragmatic conditions under which they are interpreted. What these approaches still leave relatively unnoticed, to my view, is a more explicit account of PT as the mechanism through which arguers anticipate uptake and coordinate strategic choices in real-time argumentative interaction.

In epistemic argumentation, researchers appeal to *cognitive diversity*, *epistemic perspectives*, and *distributed cognition* to account for variation in how groups generate and evaluate reasons (Pesonen 2022). Further contributions emphasise *mental models* of arguments (Johnson-Laird & Byrne 1991), argument schemes as cognitive templates (Walton et al. 2008), and conceptual metaphors as cognitively grounded schemata shaping argumentative framing (van Poppel 2020). Yet, for all this proliferation of cognitive constructs, the specific mechanism that would allow arguers to coordinate these structures in real-time interaction, namely PT, is barely mentioned explicitly and remains partially theorised, especially in regards to argumentation discourse. A closer look at Akramova (2024) makes this point explicit. The author provides an overview in which argument is presented as a text that changes the addressee’s model of the world and treats communication as creating in the addressee’s cognitive system new conceptual constructions and “models of the world”, structured by frames and mental “thought spaces” whose contents and salience are carefully selected with an eye to the addressee’s cognitive base and national-linguo-cultural knowledge. Her article underlines that effective argumentation presupposes accessing and exploiting the opponent’s structured knowledge, value orientations, and discourse frames, but the required ability to simulate that opponent’s perspective, or PT, remains implicit, described only as drawing on the addressee’s cognitive base rather than as a distinct capacity with its own typology or constraints. Baranov’s (1990) seminal cognitive approach to argumentation is repeatedly cited as grounding this view, insisting that cognitive processes not only precede argumentation but are constituted as socially acceptable arguments. However, what is foregrounded is the internal organisation of knowledge and frames in the speaker’s mind, not the systematic modelling of interlocutors’ minds as such. Lisanyuk’s (2015) logical-cognitive approach deepens the picture by explicitly assuming that agents engaged in argumentation are cognitively diverse and by distinguishing justification, conviction, and persuasion according to how positions are coordinated and assessed before a “rational judge” using a “light” version of abstract argumentation frameworks. This already presupposes that arguers have some representation of the other’s epistemic profile, otherwise cognitive diversity would have no sense. However, the approach did not aim to specify the micro-level operations involved in tracking interlocutors’ commitments and reactions. Mercier & Sperber’s (2011) argumentative theory of reasoning famously recasts reasoning as an evolved, meta-representational module whose function is to “devise and evaluate arguments intended to persuade” (Oaksford 2011: 84), regulating information flow through the interplay of a biased but productive speaker-side search for supporting arguments and an audience-side “epistemic vigilance” that filters them. Here again, much of what they describe: meta-representing others’ beliefs, anticipating objections, and selecting arguments they expect to be persuasive to a critically evaluating audience looks, from a linguistic-pragmatic perspective, very much like a cluster of PT operations. Nonetheless, the theory is framed at the level of generic cognitive functions (persuasion, vigilance), without a fine-grained account of how arguers actually construct and update models of their interlocutors’ perspectives in discourse. Mitrofanova & Gong’s (2025) cross-cultural study of the concept of argumentation in Russian and Chinese linguistic cultures reinforces the

centrality of audience-related cognition by showing how historically grounded value systems, communicative traditions and culturally specific discourse models shape what counts as persuasive. Their focus, however, remains on macro-patterns (argumentation strategies, ways of expressing disagreement, culturally typical evidence structures) rather than on the cognitive mechanism that would allow a concrete speaker to inhabit, even temporarily, a Chinese or Russian addressee's vantage point.

Finally, Tindale's (2015) audience-centred philosophy of argument develops a strongly social and "cognitive environment"-oriented model: arguers and audiences are described as co-constructors of discourse, with audiences providing much of the content and "common places" that make enthymematic arguments work, and argumentation is treated as a dynamic practice embedded in shared, historically layered cognitive environments. Yet, the audience is characterised in terms of its role in shaping constraints and warrants, not in terms of the arguer's active, step-by-step simulation of what that audience knows, expects, feels or is likely to infer at each move.

Across these traditions, then, we see a converging intuition: argumentation manipulates mental models, exploits cognitive diversity, and is constrained by shared cognitive environments and culturally specific discourse schemas; but the mechanism that would naturally unify these insights, PT as the ability to construct and use a model of another's epistemic and affective stance, tends to be presupposed, hinted at through notions like "cognitive base," "epistemic vigilance," "universal audience," or "cognitively diverse agents," rather than named and theorised in its own right.

Within this landscape, Bryushinkin's (2009) cognitive approach is arguably the closest to the perspective-sensitive view of argumentation, precisely because it draws a sharp line between internal argumentation and its external expression. In his view, argumentation is defined as a form of mental activity of the persuader, where a "system of arguments" (*sistema argumentov*, Russian: *система аргументов*) is first generated as a product of the subject's "mental activity" (*umstvennaja dejatel'nost' sub"ekta ubezhenija*, Russian: *умственная деятельность субъекта убеждения*) and encoded in a "language of internal representations" (*jazyk vnutrennikh reprezentacij*, Russian: *язык внутренних репрезентаций*); and only in a second step is this system expressed in overt speech, which belongs to the wider domain of "persuasive communication" (*ubezhdajushchee obshchenie*, Russian: *убеждающее общение*) rather than to argumentation per se. On this view, the decisive factor for generating a system of arguments is the "representation of the addressee in the mind of the subject" (*predstavlenie adresata v уме sub"ekta*, Russian: *представление адресата в уме субъекта*): cognitive modelling of argumentation must take into account the content and structure of the subject's and addressee's representations, and this internal representation is explicitly singled out as the key determinant of argumentative success or failure. The well-known example of the daughter twice asking her father for money makes this particularly vivid: the unsuccessful request is made without a worked-out internal model of the father's evaluative landscape, whereas the successful version carefully mobilises his values, interests, and psychological dispositions — what Bryushinkin calls the "supports of conviction" (*opory ubezhenij*, Russian: *опоры убеждений*), comprising values, interests and psychological attitudes — as elements of the internal addressee-representation that guide argument generation. Khizanishvili (2014, 2025) shows how this conception can be formalised via "cognitive maps" (*kognitivnye karty*, Russian: *когнитивные карты*): nodes encode the subject's hypothesis about the network of representations in the addressee's mind, links encode causal or support relations, and

argumentation is modelled as the construction and selection of “situation models” (*modeli situacii*, Russian: *модели ситуации*) that will, if things go well, shift the balance between competing beliefs or decisions in the addressee’s cognitive system. In this sense, Bryushinkin’s “cognitive model of argumentation” (*kognitivnaja model' argumentacii*, Russian: *когнитивная модель аргументации*) already presupposes something very close to PT: the subject must form and continually refine a structured hypothesis about how the addressee’s beliefs, values, and dispositions hang together, and about how a given set of arguments will reverberate through that structure. Khizanishvili’s reconstruction makes this background even more explicit by characterising argumentation as a first-order reflexive activity that is “usually described as mind-reading,” whose “structure and content” fall within the domain of folk psychology (*refleksivnaja dejatel'nost' pervogo ranga, kotoraja obychno kharakterizuetsja kak chtenie myslej ... struktura i sodержanie takoj dejatel'nosti javljaetsja ob'ektom folk-psikhologii, ili psikhologii zdravogo smysla*, Russian: *рефлексивная деятельность первого ранга, которая обычно характеризуется как чтение мыслей ... структура и содержание такой деятельности является объектом фолк-психологии, или психологии здорового смысла*). In doing so, he clarifies that argumentation presupposes an ability to operate with commonsense psychological concepts: belief, desire, intention, — as the medium through which arguers represent both their own reasoning and the cognitive states they attribute to their addressees (Khizanishvili 2014, 2025). While Khizanishvili occasionally invokes contemporary research on reasoning and attribution to motivate the mentalistic orientation of the model, this engagement remains at a relatively general, meta-theoretical level. It situates argumentation within the space of reflexive cognition but does not yet articulate the specific cognitive mechanisms through which such mind-reading is realised in concrete communicative practice.

As a result, the emphasis in the Russian cognitive tradition continues to fall on the *formal* or *modelling* aspects of argumentation: internal representations, logical competence, cognitive capacities of the arguing subject, and the construction of cognitive maps or situation models that encode the persuader’s hypotheses about the addressee’s mental states (Bryushinkin 2009, 2011; Khizanishvili 2014, 2025). These constructs offer a valuable conceptual architecture, but they develop largely in parallel to, rather than in explicit dialogue with, the extensive body of work in (mainly Western) psycholinguistics and pragmatics that investigates similar phenomena under headings such as PT, theory of mind, audience design, accommodation, and common-ground management.

For present purposes, Bryushinkin’s framework, as interpreted by Khizanishvili, remains an especially congenial precursor. Although recent work by Oswald, Zufferey, and others has brought argumentation theory closer to contemporary cognitive-pragmatic concerns, Bryushinkin’s model speaks more directly to the present argument, since it relocates argumentation into the inner space of modelling another’s mind and explicitly links this to folk-psychological mind-reading; at the same time, it leaves open, and thus invites, the more fine-grained, PT account of the cognitive infrastructure that I propose to bring into contact with pragma-dialectical SM.

4 Mapping the strategic manoeuvring triangle onto perspective-taking

The SM triangle — choices from *topical potential*, *adaptation to audience demand*, and the *use of presentational devices* — captures, in pragma-dialectical terms, the three principal ways in which arguers attempt to reconcile dialectical reasonableness with rhetorical effectiveness in real argumentative practice (van Eemeren 2010: 93-122). In making “an expedient choice from the options constituting the topical potential,” “a responsive adaptation to audience demand”, and an “appropriate” use of presentational devices (van Eemeren & Houtlosser 2002: 139), arguers are portrayed as selecting arguments, framings, and linguistic formulations they expect to work best for a particular audience at a particular stage of the discussion. Such expectation-driven decision-making already presumes that arguers work with some representation, however externalised, of what their interlocutors will regard as acceptable, relevant, persuasive, or stylistically felicitous. This brings the manoeuvring triangle into contact with cognitive-pragmatic accounts of PT.

This implicit cognitive orientation also resonates with broader pragmatic theories. In audience design, speakers systematically adjust their utterances to what they know or assume about their audience’s knowledge, preferences, and inferential dispositions (Clark & Murphy 1982; Bell 1984). Similarly, communication accommodation theory (Giles & Powesland 1975; Giles et al. 1991) shows that speakers actively converge toward, or diverge from, their interlocutors’ linguistic style to manage social alignment, rapport, or distance — an interpersonal calibration that is fundamentally anticipatory. Common ground¹ theory likewise holds that speakers design their utterances against a model of what they take their addressees to know or be able to infer; however, in Clark’s account, such assumptions are not static, but are continuously tested, updated, and grounded through interaction (Clark, 1996). Research on expectation-based processing in psycholinguistics (Levy 2008; Jaeger & Ferreira 2013) further demonstrates that speakers routinely choose grammatical structures and formulations based on predictions about how difficult or easy they will be for the addressee to process.

When viewed against this combined pragmatic and psycholinguistic backdrop, each corner of the SM triangle can be interpreted as a discursive manifestation of perspective-sensitive behaviour. Exploiting topical potential requires anticipating which arguments an audience will treat as acceptable starting points. Adapting to audience demand requires attuning one’s moves to the commitments, values, and emotional orientations attributed to the addressee. And selecting presentational devices requires predicting how a given formulation will be cognitively processed, pragmatically enriched, or stylistically evaluated. Although PD

¹ It is important to distinguish between the cognitive status of common ground and its dialectical status in the opening stage of a critical discussion. From a cognitive perspective, PT allows an arguer to form a provisional hypothesis about what starting points the interlocutor is likely to accept. Such hypotheses, however, may be inaccurate: research on PT has shown that perspective estimates are often biased towards one’s own viewpoint, may worsen under time pressure, and are not always corrected simply by trying to take the other’s perspective; in some cases, more accurate understanding requires information obtained directly through interaction (Damen et al. 2019; Epley et al. 2004; Eyal et al. 2018). In pragma-dialectical terms, therefore, such assumptions count as starting points only once they are externalised and mutually accepted as commitments. PT may thus guide the arguer’s anticipation of which material and procedural starting points can plausibly be advanced, but it does not determine their dialectical status by itself. When PT leads an arguer to assume common ground that is not in fact shared, the resulting strategic move may become publicly visible as a contested premise or an unsuccessful manoeuvre, and in some cases may contribute to strategic derailment. In this sense, the interaction itself functions as a site in which the arguer’s PT-based assumptions are tested against the interlocutor’s actual commitments.

does not reconstruct arguers' actual private mental states, it does, however, allow the reconstruction of implicit premises and other commitments insofar as these are licensed by the discourse and publicly attributable to the speaker. Against this background, the functional logic of the manoeuvring triangle aligns closely with cognitive models in which communicators anticipate, simulate, and adjust to the interlocutor's perspective. In this sense, SM can be seen as the *externalised, discourse-level reflection of cognitive mechanisms of PT*.

In their account of audience adaptation within SM, van Eemeren & Houtlosser (2002: 140–149) introduce the notion of “communion” to characterise attempts to align argumentative moves with the audience, thereby presupposing an orientation toward how such moves are likely to be received, even though this orientation is not elaborated in cognitive terms. *Audience adaptation*, perhaps, is most directly connected to PT, insofar as it requires the arguer to operate with expectations about how the addressee is likely to think and respond.

With respect to *topical potential*, the arguer must manage common ground, which involves tracking shared assumptions and drawing inferences about the audience's epistemic landscape in order to ensure that selected premises are relevant and acceptable to them. This requirement closely parallels pragmatic and psycholinguistic accounts in which speakers design contributions relative to attributed shared knowledge and presuppositions (Clark & Brennan 1991; Clark 1996; Bell 1984; Brown-Schmidt 2016).

Finally, the *use of presentational devices* engages a linguistically mediated form of cognitive PT: arguers must anticipate how particular formulations will be interpreted, processed, or pragmatically enriched by the addressee. Psycholinguistic research demonstrates that speakers routinely choose forms that facilitate the addressee's processing effort or guide their inferential trajectory (Levy 2008; Jaeger & Ferreira 2013), and rhetorical-pragmatic analyses of hyperbole, rhetorical questions, and related stylistic devices treat such choices as strategic precisely because their expected uptake has been forecasted (Snoeck Henkemans 2009, 2013). In this sense, all three dimensions of SM reflect the very kinds of perspective-dependent operations that cognitive-pragmatic accounts regard as central to successful communication. Recent work explicitly linking argumentation and PT argues that argumentative discourse requires the use of PT from disputants and that this ability underpins the design, targeting, and interpretation of argumentative moves (Shuvalov & Németh T. 2023).

Taken together, these considerations suggest that, even though PD remains methodologically committed to analysing only publicly externalised moves, the operational logic of the manoeuvring triangle nevertheless presupposes the very inferential simulations, both cognitive and affective, that enable arguers to calibrate their contributions to the perspective they attribute to their interlocutors. In this light, PT emerges not as an optional psychological add-on but as the underlying cognitive capacity that makes SM possible in the first place. Conversely, SM can be viewed as the discursive and observable manifestation of these internal simulations, the point at which perspective-sensitive reasoning becomes externalised in argumentative practice. Consequently, *PT constitutes the cognitive precondition for SM, whereas SM represents the external, interactional realisation of PT in argumentation.*²

² At this point, however, one clarification is necessary. While PT naturally facilitates rhetorical effectiveness by allowing arguers to tailor their moves to an audience's preferences, it is also implicated in the arguer's orientation

5 Externalisation as a methodological condition on perspective-taking analysis

PT, as a cognitive and psychological capacity, poses a specific methodological challenge when brought into contact with PD analysis. To explain how arguers anticipate their interlocutors' epistemic and affective responses is, potentially, to make claims about private mental states — precisely the kind of move that a pragma-dialectical framework seeks to avoid in reconstruction and evaluation. Without explicit methodological constraints, a PT-based account of SM risks collapsing into psychological speculation. The present section therefore specifies the conditions under which PT-based explanation is and is not warranted within a pragma-dialectical framework. The principle of *externalisation*, as the central meta-theoretical safeguard for present purposes, provides exactly these conditions.

As it has been mentioned earlier the theoretical coherence of PD rests on several meta-theoretical principles, namely, *functionalisation*, *socialisation*, *dialectification*, and, most crucially for present purposes to answer aforementioned questions, *externalisation*. In order to integrate the pragmatic and dialectical dimensions, PD treats argumentation as a complex speech-act activity and “achieves” *externalisation* by capturing the propositional and interactional commitments created by the speech acts performed (van Eemeren et al. 2014: 38). On this view, the obligations created by performing certain speech acts in argumentative discourse e.g., accepting a starting point, advancing a standpoint, casting doubt, retracting a claim and etc., are understood as public commitments that can be attributed to the speaker, rather than as private psychological states such as belief or intention (van Eemeren 2015: 112, 155). As Drid (2016: 22) formulates it, pragma-dialecticians are “concerned with what is said actually by a speaker in terms of implicit or explicit speech acts”: the verbally expressed difference of opinion and “the commitments undertaken when performing argumentative speech acts in a given context and the resulting consequences form a focal object of study”. In other words, the speaker is only held responsible for a position when it is “publicly projected in discourse”. *Externalisation* thus “shifts the investigation of argumentation from the philosophical sphere to a more objective sphere” by tying analysis to observable utterances rather than “speculations, intentions or other non-empirical constructs”. Crucially, the principle underpins the reconstruction of implicit elements: even unexpressed premises or commitments are only attributed to a speaker when they are licensed by what has been actually said and can be treated as part of the speaker's public responsibility (van Eemeren et al. 2002: 49–60).

To bring PT into explicit relation with strategic manoeuvring, however, methodological clarity is required. The principle of externalisation excludes appeals to arguers' actual private mental states as objects of reconstruction and evaluation. It does not, however, exclude all reference to perspective-sensitive processes. What remains admissible are claims about the perspective-sensitive inferential logic embedded in the observable text itself — that is, claims

towards dialectical reasonableness. Because SM involves a continuous effort to balance rhetorical goals with dialectical constraints, an arguer must be able to anticipate how an interlocutor may critically evaluate a given move. By simulating the addressee's epistemic stance, the arguer models not only what the audience will find persuasive, but also what is likely to withstand critical scrutiny within the discussion. In this sense, PT allows the arguer to anticipate potential objections or charges of unreasonableness before a move is externalised. If the pursuit of rhetorical advantage risks crossing into fallacious derailment, the capacity for PT may enable the arguer to anticipate the interlocutor's likely rejection and adjust the choice of topical potential or presentational devices accordingly. Thus, PT does not replace external dialectical norms but provides part of the cognitive infrastructure through which arguers may navigate them during interaction.

about how a move is textually and argumentatively configured in ways that become intelligible only in light of an anticipated addressee response. In this sense, externalisation does not rule out PT; it specifies what kind of PT claim is methodologically warranted.

This yields a positive rule of inference. A PT-based explanation is warranted when the textual evidence supports a contrastive account of strategic choice — that is, when the analyst can ask why this premise, framing, or formulation was selected rather than another available one, and when the answer is traceable in the structure of the move itself. The operative question is therefore not what the speaker actually had in mind, but why the observable configuration of choices is non-arbitrary. If a speaker could have selected a different premise, a different alignment, or a different presentational device, yet instead chose one that is particularly well calibrated to a projected audience response, then the analyst may hypothesise a perspective-sensitive calibration without stepping beyond the bounds of externalisation. PT thus serves not as evidence about an inner state, but as a constrained explanatory lens for understanding the production of externally reconstructible strategic choices.

The theoretical mapping established in the preceding sections is therefore directly operationalisable within a pragma-dialectical framework, provided that PT claims remain anchored in publicly observable argumentative and linguistic choices. What *externalisation* provides are the methodological conditions under which this operationalisation can proceed without psychologisation. The analysis that follows does not seek to adjudicate between PT and strategic manoeuvring, but to demonstrate what a PT-based reading of manoeuvring looks like when conducted under these conditions, using the contrastive question of why one available option was selected over another as its primary analytical question, while remaining appropriately tentative about anything that lies beyond the discourse itself.

6 Methodological application: a brief illustrative example

To make the proposed mapping more concrete, consider the following brief constructed example:

Director (A): To foster a stronger culture of collaboration and innovation, we are mandating a full return to the office starting next month.

Employee (B): Given that our division has just achieved record-breaking Q3 profits under the current remote model, a mandated return might inadvertently disrupt the very workflows that are driving our shared success.

The purpose of this constructed example is not to provide a full pragma-dialectical reconstruction of the exchange, but to illustrate, in a deliberately selective way, how PT may be brought into relation with the three dimensions of the SM triangle. Accordingly, the exchange is analysed in terms of those three dimensions, while using PT in a limited and carefully delimited sense: not as a means of establishing the speakers' actual inner states, but as a heuristic for showing why the externally observable configuration of choices is unlikely to be arbitrary.

From the perspective of *topical potential*, A does not justify the mandate by appealing to managerial authority, contractual obligation, or operational logistics. Instead, A selects a premise grounded in organisational culture, namely the promotion of collaboration and innovation. This choice is itself strategic: other topical options were available but were not selected. In pragma-dialectical terms, what is reconstructible is the externally observable fact

that the directive is anchored in an aspirational premise rather than a formal one. At the same time, this choice becomes more intelligible if one assumes that A is orienting to what the addressees are likely to regard as legitimate and difficult to reject openly. The point is not that the analyst can know this with certainty, but that the selection of this premise over available alternatives invites explanation in terms of anticipated uptake. Furthermore, A's formulation *to foster a stronger culture* carries the presupposition that the existing remote arrangement already produces a weaker one. This premise is never stated explicitly and therefore never formally opened to contestation; any challenge to the mandate must begin from a wording that has already installed the relevant default. This illustrates how topical selection and presentational design may work together to narrow the space for critical discussion rather than open it up, which is precisely the kind of interdependence the PT-SM framework is intended to capture.

B, by contrast, does not appeal to employee comfort, commuting time, or personal preference, but selects an argument grounded in institutional performance: the record-breaking Q3 results achieved under the remote model. This move instantiates what van Eemeren and Grootendorst (2004) describe as a pragmatic argument from consequences, that is, a scheme in which a course of action is evaluated in terms of its likely effects on outcomes already treated as desirable. The selection of this scheme, rather than one oriented towards individual welfare or procedural fairness, is consistent with a PT-based account in which B is orienting to what A is most likely to regard as weighty, acceptable, or relevant. Yet the reconstruction itself remains grounded in the observable fact that the defence of the standpoint is built around financial success rather than personal welfare.

From the perspective of *audience adaptation*, A frames the mandate not as an imposition, but as a means of fostering collaboration and innovation. This purpose-oriented formulation presents the directive as serving values likely to be regarded as legitimate and desirable within an institutional setting. It thus functions as a communion-seeking move in van Eemeren and Houtlosser's sense: A aligns the standpoint with a value orientation the addressees may be less inclined to contest openly. Again, the analyst need not claim privileged access to A's actual assumptions. What matters is that the move is publicly framed in a way that narrows the space for resistance by appealing to apparently shared institutional commitments.

B, in turn, frames the remote model not as a private benefit, but as the source of *our shared success*. The inclusive possessive *our* performs a comparable communion-seeking function from the opposite dialectical position. It recasts B's standpoint as an expression of shared institutional interest rather than self-interest, thereby aligning it, at least lexically, with the value horizon already invoked by A. B could have adopted a more oppositional alignment — for instance, by contrasting employee interests with management interests — yet the actual formulation does neither. The observed choice therefore lends itself to a PT-based explanation in which the move is calibrated to what the addressee is likely to regard as institutionally legitimate.

The heuristic role of PT becomes especially clear in relation to *presentational devices*. Consider first A's choice of the word *mandating*. The term is unhedged and performatively authoritative, leaving little room for negotiation. This presentational choice signals that the directive is issued from a position whose institutional asymmetry is taken for granted and need not be argued for explicitly. That effect is reconstructible from the lexical register of the utterance itself.

B's presentational strategy operates quite differently, and it is here that the explanatory value of PT becomes most visible. Several choices deserve attention. First, B opens with *Given that*, a formulation that presents the Q3 profit premise not as a claim requiring defence, but as presupposed — that is, as shared background rather than as a proposition in need of support. In this way, the formulation reduces the immediate contestability of the premise without explicitly arguing for it. B could instead have used a more openly adversarial framing, or a more cautious evidential introduction, but opts for neither. Second, B employs the phrase *the very workflows* in the clause *the very workflows that are driving our shared success*. This does more than add emphasis: it binds B's criticism closely to A's own value orientation by implying that the proposed intervention may undermine the precise outcomes A claims to be pursuing. The move is effective precisely because it reuses the addressee's projected priorities rather than replacing them with an unrelated standard.

Third, and most directly illustrative, B formulates the standpoint through the mitigated construction *might inadvertently disrupt*, rather than through a more direct and confrontational alternative such as *will damage productivity*, *will undermine our performance*, or *will harm the company*. These unrealised alternatives matter analytically because they show that the observed wording is not simply dictated by the standpoint itself. Two distinct functions are performed by the formulation actually chosen. The modal *might* renders the prediction tentative, allowing B to advance criticism without committing to an overly categorical forecast. The adverb *inadvertently* performs a further function: it attributes any projected harm to unintended consequences rather than to incompetence or bad faith, thereby criticising the likely effects of the policy without directly attacking A's intentions or judgement. This is a face-protecting device, and its strategic logic is reconstructible from the lexical choice itself. From a PT perspective, the choice of this mitigated formulation over sharper available alternatives may be treated as consistent with an anticipatory calibration to how the move is likely to be received. It does not prove what B in fact thought, but it does render the observed configuration of choices analytically non-arbitrary.

This brief example illustrates how the PT-SM framework may be applied without abandoning the pragma-dialectical commitment to externalisation. PD provides the means for reconstructing the externally observable move in terms of standpoint, argument, audience adaptation, and presentational design. PT, by contrast, is not invoked here as a method for establishing the speakers' actual inner states or exact intentions. Rather, it functions as a theoretical lens through which the analyst may ask why one available argumentative or stylistic option was selected over another. Since the speaker could have chosen different premises, different alignments, or different formulations, the fact that these particular options were selected invites the hypothesis that the move was calibrated, at least in part, to the perspective attributed to the interlocutor. Such an account remains necessarily tentative and does not license strong claims about what the arguer in fact thought. What it does support, however, is the broader claim developed earlier: *SM presupposes a cognitive infrastructure through which arguers orient their moves towards anticipated uptake, even though the object of reconstruction remains the publicly externalised, textually observable form of the strategic move itself.*

7 Future research

The framework developed here lends itself to further empirical investigation. Rather than remaining at the level of conceptual mapping, future work may combine PD reconstruction of SM with experimental and neurocognitive methods capable of operationalising perspective modelling during the production and interpretation of argumentative moves. For instance, researchers could design tasks that instantiate specific stages of a critical discussion and specific manoeuvres (choices from topical potential, audience adaptation, and presentational devices) and examine when and how participants recruit mentalising resources while anticipating objections, estimating acceptability, or calibrating framing. Such work would connect the discourse-analytic level with measurable processing profiles, drawing on established findings on mentalising networks in language comprehension and pragmatic inference, as well as emerging neurocognitive research on persuasion and message effectiveness (Enrici et al. 2019; Lamm et al. 2007; Mercier & Sperber 2011; Scholz et al. 2025; Tokimoto & Tokimoto 2023).

A more specific empirical question concerns whether variation in PT accuracy affects the persuasive uptake, strategic calibration, or interactional effectiveness of argumentative moves under different discourse conditions. Addressing this question would require treating PT not as a normative criterion but as an experimentally tractable variable, thereby opening a productive interface between argumentation theory and psycholinguistic research.

8 Conclusion

SM, as theorised within pragma-dialectics, presupposes a set of cognitive capacities that allow the arguer to anticipate the interlocutor's interpretive and evaluative responses. In this respect, the process of PT provides the *mental architecture* for manoeuvring: by simulating the addressee's epistemic and emotional stance, the speaker can select arguments (topical potential), calibrate tone and modality (audience adaptation), and frame propositions linguistically (presentational devices) in a way that maximises both reasonableness and persuasive force. More specifically, the analysis has argued that these operations can be differentiated into three analytically relevant modes of PT — epistemic, evaluative-affective, and inferential — corresponding, respectively, to the management of common ground, the attunement to the addressee's value orientation, and the anticipation of how particular formulations will be interpreted and processed. Conversely, each instance of SM observed in discourse constitutes empirical evidence of PT at work — it is the *externalised or linguistically instantiated* form of this cognitive faculty.

The relationship between SM and PT is best described as reciprocal dependency. While the pragma-dialectical model conceptualises manoeuvring as a discursive strategy that balances dialectical reasonableness with rhetorical effectiveness, cognitive-pragmatic approaches reveal the mental operations that make such balancing possible. PT supplies the cognitive infrastructure that allows arguers to infer, simulate, and align with the interlocutor's epistemic and affective states. Through these inferential simulations, arguers can foresee the acceptability of potential standpoints and adjust their presentational forms accordingly. It should be emphasised that the accuracy of PT does not in itself determine whether an argumentative move is dialectically sound or unsound. In pragma-dialectical terms, that judgement depends

exclusively on whether the move conforms to the rules of a critical discussion. What PT may help to explain, by contrast, is how arguers calibrate their manoeuvring to the interlocutor's anticipated uptake and thereby increase, in some cases, the persuasive force of a move. Whether such calibration results in a reasonable contribution or in a fallacious derailment, however, remains a matter for pragma-dialectical evaluation rather than for cognitive explanation. Hence, PT may be viewed as the enabling condition of SM, whereas SM represents the linguistic realisation of PT in argumentative discourse. The two processes are therefore *mutually constitutive* dimensions of the same cognitive-communicative phenomenon: *SM is the argumentative implementation of PT, and PT is the cognitive prerequisite for SM*. This also clarifies the paper's broader position within cognitive approaches to argumentation: while such approaches frequently presuppose audience-sensitive modelling, they rarely theorise PT itself explicitly as the mechanism through which strategic calibration is achieved in argumentative interaction.

The plausibility of this mapping was also tested through the brief illustrative analysis, in which a managerial directive and an employee's counter-argument were examined in terms of all three aspects of the SM triangle. That example showed that a PT-based explanation can be operationalised by means of a contrastive question: why was this particular argumentative or stylistic option selected over other hypothetical available alternatives? When the observable configuration of choices is non-arbitrary — when a selected premise, framing, or formulation appears calibrated to the interlocutor's likely epistemic and evaluative stance — the analyst may hypothesise perspective-sensitive calibration without invoking the speaker's private mental states. In this way, the analysis remains anchored in the publicly reconstructible discourse, while PT functions as a constrained explanatory lens rather than as a source of psychologising claims.

Moreover, there is no contradiction between incorporating PT and maintaining the pragma-dialectical principle of *externalisation* because the two operate at different explanatory levels. *Externalisation* governs *what* argumentative behaviour can be analysed: publicly attributed commitments and discourse moves. PT concerns *how* arguers mentally simulate the interlocutor's perspective in order to select those moves. SM is the point where the internal PT process is transformed into externalised argumentative choices.

Thus, PD remains non-psychological in its evaluation, while PT provides the cognitive explanation for the very possibility of SM. Or in other words, in the present framework, PT serves as a psychologically realistic explanation of how arguers may navigate the argumentative predicament and anticipate the uptake of their strategic choices, whereas the normative evaluation of argumentation, including the identification of fallacious derailments, remains strictly tied to externalised moves and the rules of critical discussion.

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Denis Shuvalov
University of Szeged
Doctoral School in Linguistics
13 Dugonics Square, Szeged H-6720
Hungary
e-mail: dns_shv@icloud.com

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Camel-Related Proverbs as Pragmatic Resources in Jordanian Arabic: A Speech-Act-Based Elicitation Study

Oday Alshorafat, The University of Jordan
Sharif Alghazo, University of Sharjah & The University of Jordan
Ghaleb Rabab'ah, University of Sharjah & The University of Jordan

This study investigates the use of camel-related proverbs as speech acts in Jordanian Spoken Arabic (JSA), drawing on Searle's (1969, 1976) Speech Act Theory. The data were collected from 150 native speakers of JSA aged 30-60. The participants were divided into three groups: 20 individuals provided data during the preliminary questionnaire phase, which guided and informed the data collection process; 80 participants completed an extended questionnaire; and 50 individuals participated in an acceptability agreement/judgment task. The analysis revealed that camel-related proverbs in JSA perform 10 distinct illocutionary forces: criticizing, expressing anger, praising, offering condolence, blaming, offering sympathy, threatening, advising, rejecting, and asserting. These illocutionary forces were categorized into four illocutionary acts: expressives, commissives, directives, and representatives. The findings highlight the versatility and contextual sensitivity of camel-related proverbs in JSA, underscoring their role as dynamic communicative tools rather than mere static folklore. Given the study's focus on JSA, future research could explore the illocutionary acts and forces of camel-related proverbs in other Arabic dialects, offering insights into both shared and dialect-specific pragmatic patterns across the Arab world.

Keywords: pragmatics, speech act theory, camel-related proverbs, Jordanian Spoken Arabic

1 Introduction

Proverbs have long been recognized as a significant object of pragmatic and discourse-based inquiry, particularly because they convey evaluations, advice, criticism, and social norms through indirect, culturally grounded language. Rather than functioning as static folkloric expressions, proverbs are widely understood as context-sensitive communicative resources whose meaning and force emerge from use in interaction (Mieder, 2004; Dundes, 1981). In everyday discourse, speakers employ proverbs strategically to perform actions, negotiate relationships, and manage face, often more effectively than through direct forms of expression.

A growing body of research has used the framework of the Speech Act Theory to show how language frequently performs indirect illocutionary acts such as advising, warning, blaming, or asserting (Lawal, Ajayi, & Raji, 1997; Benyakoub et al., 2022; Yankah, 1989; Ali & Makhlef, 2011). Within Arabic linguistics, several studies have highlighted the pragmatic richness of proverbs and their sensitivity to social context and speaker intention (Lutfi, 2007; Ali & Makhlef, 2011). More specifically, research on Jordanian and Bedouin Arabic has shown that animal-related proverbs occupy a central place in everyday interaction, functioning as tools for moral evaluation, social regulation, and interpersonal stance-taking (Alshorafat, 2019; Farghal, 2021; Rayyan et al., 2024). Recent work on animal metaphors in Jordanian proverbs further confirms that culturally salient animals serve as powerful carriers of pragmatic meaning (Alshorafat, 2023).

Despite this growing interest, camel-related proverbs—despite their cultural prominence in Jordanian society—have not yet been systematically examined from a speech-act perspective using empirically validated data. The present study addresses this gap by investigating how camel-related proverbs in Jordanian Spoken Arabic function as speech acts in naturally occurring contexts. Drawing on Speech Act Theory (Austin, 1962; Searle, 1969, 1976), the study identifies the illocutionary acts and forces performed by these proverbs as interpreted and evaluated by native speakers.

For clarity and transparency, all Arabic proverbs discussed in this study are presented in Latin (IPA-based) transcription alongside English translations, ensuring that the original linguistic forms are accessible to both Arabic-speaking and non-Arabic-speaking readers. It is important to clarify the analytical scope of the present study. Rather than examining naturally occurring spoken interaction, this research investigates speakers' metapragmatic knowledge of proverb use, elicited through contextualized scenarios and native-speaker judgments. The analysis, therefore, focuses on shared pragmatic interpretations of camel-related proverbs and the speech-act functions speakers attribute to them in culturally recognizable situations. While this approach does not constitute an analysis of recorded speech in the conversation-analytic sense, it provides insight into culturally entrenched norms governing proverb use and pragmatic inference in Jordanian Arabic.

The paper is structured as follows. The next section outlines the theoretical framework of Speech Act Theory as adopted for the analysis. This is followed by a review of relevant literature on proverb pragmatics. The methodology section details the data collection procedures and participant profiles. The results section presents the identified illocutionary acts and forces, followed by a discussion of their pragmatic and cultural implications. The paper concludes with a summary of findings and suggestions for future research.

2 Speech Act Theory and Context

This study adopts Speech Act Theory as its analytical framework, building on the foundational work of Austin (1962) and its subsequent refinement by Searle (1969, 1976). Over the past six decades, Speech Act Theory has developed from a philosophical account of performative utterances into a widely used linguistic framework for analyzing how speakers perform actions through language across cultures and discourse types. Contemporary pragmatic research has demonstrated its particular usefulness in examining indirectness, speaker intention, and context-dependent meaning, especially in culturally embedded forms of expression such as proverbs (Searle, 1976; Levinson, 1983). In this study, the theory is applied descriptively to identify the illocutionary acts and forces realized through camel-related proverbs in Jordanian Spoken Arabic, as interpreted and validated by native speakers.

Context is treated as an integral component of speech act interpretation rather than as a separate analytical construct. The illocutionary force of a proverb is determined by situational factors such as speaker–hearer relations, social roles, and communicative goals. Accordingly, camel-related proverbs are analyzed within clearly defined interactional scenarios, allowing their pragmatic functions to be inferred from use rather than from decontextualized form. This integrated approach ensures that Speech Act Theory is directly linked to the study's objective of capturing how proverbs function as communicative actions in real-life Jordanian discourse.

3 Literature Review

Previous research has consistently demonstrated that proverbs function as pragmatically rich units of discourse rather than as fixed or purely aesthetic expressions. Early pragmatic studies applying Speech Act Theory to proverbs revealed that they frequently perform indirect illocutionary acts, such as asserting, advising, warning, and blaming, depending on context and the speaker's intention (Lawal, Ajayi, & Raji, 1997; Yankah, 1989). These studies collectively emphasize that proverb meaning cannot be reduced to literal content but must be understood in relation to communicative purpose and situational use.

Subsequent work extended this pragmatic perspective to different languages and cultural settings. Comparative and language-specific studies have shown that proverbs across languages commonly express representative, directive, and commissive illocutionary forces, although the distribution of illocutionary forces varies according to cultural norms (Ali & Makhlef, 2011; Yan, 2006; Lutfi, 2007). A recurring finding across these studies is that proverbs often function indirectly, allowing speakers to perform face-threatening or evaluative acts in socially acceptable ways. This confirms the suitability of Speech Act Theory as a framework for analyzing the use of proverbs across linguistic contexts.

Within Arabic and African contexts, several studies have highlighted the multifunctionality of proverbs and their role in social regulation and moral instruction. Research on Yoruba proverbs, for instance, shows that a single proverb may perform multiple speech acts simultaneously, with assertive and directive functions being particularly prominent (Dairo, 2010; Jombadi & Juliana, 2014). Similarly, studies focusing on Arabic proverbs—especially within Jordanian and Bedouin communities—demonstrate that animal-related proverbs serve as powerful pragmatic tools for expressing criticism, advice, threat, and social judgment (Alshorafat, 2019; Alshorafat & Al Hassi, 2025). These studies intersect with the present research in their emphasis on context, indirectness, and culturally salient animal imagery, but they stop short of offering a focused, empirically validated analysis of camel-related proverbs in Jordanian Spoken Arabic.

4 Data Collection and Participants

4.1 *Participants and Demographic Profile*

A total of 150 native speakers of Jordanian Spoken Arabic participated in the study. Participants were recruited from the North-Eastern Badia region of Jordan, including the cities and surrounding areas of Mafraq, Ruwashed, and Zarqa, where camel-related proverbs remain actively used in everyday discourse. The age range of participants was 30–60 years ($M = 43$), a demographic group identified through preliminary observation as the most frequent users of traditional proverbs. The sample included 82 male and 68 female participants. Regarding educational background, 41 participants had completed secondary education, 76 had undergraduate degrees, and 33 had postgraduate qualifications. The relatively large sample size was chosen to allow for triangulation across elicitation tasks and to ensure reliable validation of proposed pragmatic functions through acceptability judgments.

4.2 *Data Elicitation Procedures*

Data were collected using a multi-stage elicitation approach designed to balance contextual control with native-speaker intuition. In the first stage, a mini questionnaire (n = 20) was used to identify commonly used camel-related proverbs and the types of situations in which they occur. Participants were asked to recall proverbs from casual conversations and to describe the contexts in which they are typically used.

In the second stage, an extended questionnaire (n = 80) presented participants with short situational prompts reflecting everyday social interactions (e.g., workplace exchanges, family discussions, conflict situations). These prompts were intentionally brief but contextually grounded, encouraging participants to supply proverbs they would naturally use in such situations and to indicate the intended pragmatic function. While the data are elicited rather than naturally occurring, this method has been widely used in pragmatic research to access speakers' metapragmatic awareness and culturally shared interpretations.

4.3 *Validation and Contextual Interpretation*

In the final stage, an acceptability judgment task (n = 50) was conducted to validate the proposed illocutionary forces. Participants evaluated each scenario–proverb pairing using a five-point Likert scale and were invited to suggest alternative functions when they disagreed. This step enhanced the reliability of the analysis by grounding interpretations in collective native-speaker judgments rather than researcher intuition alone.

4.4 *Analytical Scope and Nature of the Data*

The data analyzed in this study consist of elicited metapragmatic judgments rather than naturally occurring speech. Participants were asked to evaluate the use of proverbs in constructed, but culturally plausible, scenarios and to identify the intended communicative function. Such judgments represent shared cultural knowledge (doxa) regarding appropriate proverb usage rather than direct evidence of real-time interactional behavior. Accordingly, the findings are interpreted as reflecting conventionalized pragmatic expectations within the speech community, not as claims about actual conversational sequencing. This methodological choice allows the study to capture culturally stable interpretations of proverb meaning, while acknowledging that future research based on naturally occurring discourse would offer complementary interactional insights.

5 Results

The term Jordanian Spoken Arabic is used in this study to refer to spoken varieties used by Jordanian speakers, particularly in Bedouin-influenced regions, rather than to a distinct written code. While several expressions examined here are attested across Levantine Arabic, the analysis focuses on their pragmatic interpretation among Jordanian speakers.

Before presenting the pragmatic analysis, two clarifications are necessary. First, the term Jordanian Spoken Arabic is used in this study to refer to naturally occurring spoken varieties used by Jordanian speakers, particularly in Bedouin-influenced regions, rather than to

a standardized written variety. Second, the expressions analyzed here are treated as proverbial sayings—that is, culturally conventionalized utterances with figurative meaning and pragmatic force—regardless of whether they meet narrow folkloristic definitions of proverbs. While several of these expressions are attested across Levantine Arabic, their pragmatic interpretation and usage patterns were examined specifically as employed by Jordanian speakers in the present dataset.

Table 1 presents the illocutionary acts and illocutionary forces of camel-related proverbs in Jordanian Spoken Arabic, as agreed upon by more than 50% of the subjects. The table also highlights the number and percentage of participants who accepted each interpretation. This data provides insight into how native speakers pragmatically interpret these culturally rooted proverbs, reflecting shared norms and communicative strategies. The consistency in responses above the 50 percent threshold indicates a relatively high level of agreement on the intended illocutionary force of the proverbs, such as advising, warning, criticizing, or consoling, within specific social contexts.

Table 1: The speech acts (illocutionary acts) and illocutionary forces (pragmatic functions) of the camel-related proverbs and their acceptability judgments

Speech Act	No.	Illocutionary forces	No	Acceptability judgments (%)
Expressives	1	Criticising	46	84%
Expressives	2	Expressing anger	44	70%
Expressives	3	Praising	44	64%
Expressives	4	Offering condolence	43	64%
Expressives	5	Blaming	41	60%
Expressives	6	Offering sympathy	40	60%
Commissives	7	Threatening	46	70%
Directives	8	Advising	45	74%
Directives	9	Rejecting	40	56%
Representatives	10	Asserting	27	50%

Below is a descending presentation of each illocutionary force within its specific context, followed by an illustrative example. Each example is provided in two formats: an IPA transcription and an English translation.

(1) *Criticizing*

(Context) Ahmed constantly criticizes people. The following conversation happened between Ahmed and Mona:

Ahmed: "People make many mistakes."

Mona:

al-zæmæl ma: jifu:f ʕawʒ raqabatih

‘The camel can’t see the crookedness of its own hump.’

The proverb literally means the camel does not see the crookedness of its own hump. It is metaphorically used to describe a person who is blind to their own faults or mistakes but quick to notice and criticize others'. This proverb is occasionally used to point out hypocrisy or unfairness, highlighting others' shortcomings while ignoring one's own. Thus, this proverb can convey a range of pragmatic meanings depending on its context.

From the perspective of the Speech Act Theory, when Mona uses this proverb in response to Ahmed, the illocutionary force is one of criticism. Mona's goal is to express disapproval of Ahmed's behavior, especially his lack of self-awareness. The illocutionary act here is expressive, as the speaker, Mona, conveys her negative attitude toward Ahmed's fault indirectly through the proverb.

(2) *Expressing anger*

(Context) A young man tries to teach an elderly man how to deal with different life problems. The elderly man replies angrily:

la: təd'dil al-baʕi:r ʕala al-raʕi ʕuyūnuhə: aʕwæʕ min ʕuyūnək
'Don't guide the camel on grazing; its eyes are bigger than yours.'

The proverb above means that you should not try to advise or direct someone more experienced, as they already know better. It warns against giving unsolicited advice to those who are wiser or more capable.

From the perspective of the Speech Act Theory, when the elderly man says this proverb angrily, the illocutionary force performed is one of expressing anger. The illocutionary act is primarily expressive, as it conveys the speaker's emotional reaction—specifically irritation and disapproval—toward being instructed by someone younger or less experienced.

(3) *Praising*

(Context) In a workplace, the manager notices that one of the team members, who is usually very quiet and reserved, consistently delivers excellent work. One day, the manager says to him:

al-xalæ: saba:q
'The tamed desert camel is swift.'

This proverb highlights that someone who appears calm, humble, or submissive outwardly may, in reality, be quick, capable, and proactive. The 'tamed desert camel' symbolizes a creature that seems docile and controlled but is actually able to race ahead when needed. It warns against underestimating individuals based on their quiet or modest demeanor. The proverb warns against judging someone's abilities solely by their outward calmness or humility, as they may have surprising strength or initiative beneath the surface.

The expression *ðalu:l al-xalæ: saba:q* was reported by participants from Bedouin backgrounds as a conventional saying used to praise quiet competence. Although this expression may not be uniformly attested across all Jordanian dialects, its inclusion reflects regional Bedouin usage within Jordan. Importantly, the analysis focuses not on dialect

exclusivity but on the pragmatic function of the expression as Jordanian speakers use it in context.

The manager's use of the proverb carries the illocutionary force of praise, expressing recognition of the employee's quiet yet effective work style. Primarily, this serves as an expressive speech act, conveying the manager's positive attitude toward the employee's performance.

(4) *Offering condolences*

(Context) Ahmad's house burned down in a fire. The following conversation took place between Ahmed and Khaled.

Ahmad: "I can't believe even my Persian carpet was ruined in the fire."

Khaled: *ʔiða ɖa:ʕal zæmæl la: hæsaefatan ʕala: ar-ræsn*

'If the camel is lost, there's no point in grieving over the rope.'

Literally, the above proverb means if you lose something major or essential (e.g., a camel), there's no need to regret the minor things (e.g., a rope). It is often used to downplay the importance of small losses when something greater has already been lost. When it is said, this proverb can perform an array of pragmatic meanings depending on the context in which it is said.

Based on the above context, the speaker uses the proverb to console the hearer, who is expressing sorrow over a minor loss following a major disaster. Thus, the proverb's illocutionary force is consolation. It serves to deliver an empathetic message, encouraging the hearer to shift focus from smaller losses to the greater one and come to terms with it. The speech act performed here is an expressive speech act, as the speaker is expressing his own feelings toward the hearer.

(5) *Blaming*

(Context) A business owner makes a risky decision that not only causes financial loss for himself but also negatively affects his employees' livelihoods. Someone blames him by saying:

ʔæ ðæ:biħ al-næ:qæ wæ mælħaqhæ walu:ðæh

'O you who slaughter the she-camel and also harm her calf!'

This proverb is used metaphorically to describe someone who not only causes harm but also goes further to destroy what is connected to it — showing cruelty, betrayal, or injustice in an extreme form. Depending on the context, this proverb can convey a variety of pragmatic functions when said.

The illocutionary force behind the utterance is blaming, where the speaker explicitly holds the hearer responsible for causing harm and expresses disapproval and condemnation. The illocutionary act is primarily an expressive speech act, as the speaker conveys negative emotions such as frustration, disappointment, or anger toward the hearer's actions.

(6) *Expressing sympathy*

(Context) A man of high social status loses his reputation due to a scandal. People who used to praise him now attack him. Ali said to him:

ʔiða waqafa al-zæmæl kathræt sa 'kæ:ki:nih
'If the camel falls, the knives multiply.'

The proverb means that when a powerful, respected, or successful person experiences a downfall or loses their status, many people who were once supportive or silent suddenly begin to criticize, attack, or take advantage of them. It is used to describe situations in which someone who was once influential or admired becomes vulnerable and, as a result, others turn against them.

Based on the above context, Ali uses the proverb to express sympathy toward the hearer, who is suffering betrayal and criticism after losing his reputation. Thus, the proverb's illocutionary force is expressive, conveying empathy and understanding of the hearer's difficult situation. The speech act performed here is an expressive speech act, as Ali indirectly shows compassion and acknowledges the emotional pain caused by the change in how others treat the hearer.

(7) *Threatening*

(Context) Salem accidentally wronged Mahmoud and caused him many problems, so Mahmoud said to him:

al-zæmæl ma: jinsa: ʔawātih
'The camel does not forget those who hurt it.'

This proverb literally means that the camel does not forget those who have wronged it and may seek revenge later. People use this proverb to describe someone who never forgets those who mistreat, hurt, or do wrong to them. When said, this proverb can perform many different pragmatic meanings based on the context in which it is uttered.

In this situation, the illocutionary force of this proverb is threatening, as Mahmoud's words imply a warning of future retaliation. The illocutionary act is a commissive, as the speaker indirectly commits to a possible future response by indicating he will not forget the harm done.

(8) *Advising*

(Context) In a workplace meeting, a young, new employee (Ali) begins aggressively criticizing the decisions of senior managers. His colleague (Hassan) pulls him aside and says:

la: taʃa:dem al-zæmæl wiʔantæ ʔa:fi:
'Don't clash with the big camels when you are just a calf.'

This proverb is used to advise someone with little experience, power, or status not to confront or challenge those who are much stronger, more experienced, or in positions of authority. The *zamel* (الزمل) refers to strong, adult camels, while the *hashi* (الحاشي) is the young, weak camel.

Based on the context provided above, the speaker, Hassan, used this proverb to advise the hearer, Ali, about the potential consequences of his confrontational behavior toward authority figures. The illocutionary act here is a directive speech act, as the proverb functions to influence the hearer's future actions.

(9) *Rejecting*

(Context) Sami is seeking a promotion and asks Maher for help, acknowledging that it requires a lot of work. In response, Maher says:

ʔiða taħibb al-laħm ʔaθbaħ zæmælak
'If you love meat, then slaughter your camel.'

The above proverb conveys the idea that in order to obtain something you desire or value, you must be willing to make sacrifices or put in the necessary effort. It suggests that wanting something desirable (symbolized by "meat") comes with a price (symbolized by the "slaughter of the camel"). It emphasizes the relationship between desire and the cost associated with achieving one's goals.

The pragmatic force of this expression is highly context-dependent. In the scenario presented above, it functions as an indirect rejection. However, in a different context—such as advising a family member about starting a business—the same expression may perform an advisory rather than rejecting function, emphasizing personal responsibility rather than refusal. This illustrates that the illocutionary force of camel-related sayings does not reside in the expression itself, but emerges from contextual cues such as speaker intention, relational dynamics, and situational goals.

Importantly, the same proverb may realize different illocutionary forces in different contexts. For example, the expression "If you love meat, then slaughter your camel" may function as advice in one interaction, but as rejection in another. This demonstrates that pragmatic force emerges from contextual configuration rather than lexical meaning alone.

From the perspective of the Speech Act Theory, the illocutionary force is one of rejecting, as Maher subtly declines to assist. The illocutionary act is primarily directive, since Maher implies that Sami must take action himself if he truly wants the promotion.

(10) *Asserting*

(Context) Maryam had a very strong personality, and many people feared her. One day, Rakan harmed her, so people warned him about the consequences. He said to them:

al-næ:qæ næ:qæ wælc: ħadarat
'A she-camel remains a she-camel even if it grunts.'

The proverb "The she-camel is a she-camel even if it grunts" means a person's true nature or role does not change just because they act differently or put on a show. For example, even if a

woman has a strong personality, she remains limited by her nature, and she cannot possess the qualities of men or become a man. Similarly, even if a she-camel resembles a camel, it is still a she-camel. Generally, it means that no matter how much someone tries to imitate or act differently, their true nature or identity remains unchanged.

From the perspective of the Speech Act Theory, based on the above context, the illocutionary force is asserting—the speaker makes a definitive statement about Maryam’s nature. The illocutionary act is representative as the speaker expresses a belief or judgment about the world, specifically about gender and identity.

6 Discussion

The findings of this study confirm the pragmatic richness and functional diversity of camel-related proverbs in Jordanian Arabic. Far from being mere cultural artifacts or decorative language, these proverbs perform active communicative roles and fulfil a wide array of speech acts. The ten identified functions—ranging from expressive acts like praising and criticizing to commissive acts like threatening—underscore the nuanced ways speakers use proverbs to manage interpersonal relationships and express attitudes in context-sensitive ways. Notably, expressive speech acts were the most dominant category, suggesting that these proverbs often convey emotions, judgments, or social evaluations rather than simply relay factual information. This aligns with the cultural role of proverbs in Bedouin and rural Jordanian communities, where indirectness, politeness, and metaphor are preferred strategies in maintaining social harmony.

The variation in the frequency and acceptability of different functions, as shown in the judgment task, also indicates that some proverbs and their uses are more socially conventionalized than others. For instance, proverbs used to offer consolation or express sympathy were rated more favorably, likely reflecting cultural values such as solidarity and empathy. Furthermore, the use of proverbs for directive or commissive acts, such as warnings or threats, reflects the speaker’s intent to influence future behavior, underscoring the persuasive power of these expressions. The study also highlighted the importance of context, tone, and social roles in shaping the illocutionary force of a proverb, echoing Hymes’ (1974) emphasis on the social embeddedness of language.

The findings can be further interpreted through politeness theory, particularly Brown and Levinson’s (1987) concept of face-threatening acts. Many camel-related sayings perform evaluative or directive functions—such as criticizing, rejecting, or warning—that would constitute direct threats to the hearer’s face if expressed explicitly. By embedding these acts within culturally familiar metaphorical expressions, speakers mitigate potential face damage while maintaining social norms of respect and indirectness. This strategy aligns with Bedouin and broader Jordanian communicative practices, where social harmony, hierarchy, and reputation are highly valued. In this sense, camel-related sayings function not merely as rhetorical devices but as culturally sanctioned mechanisms for negotiating interpersonal tension and authority.

Moreover, the results highlight the dynamic nature of proverbs as tools for socialization and moral instruction. The high acceptability ratings for advising and consoling functions indicate that these proverbs continue to play a pedagogical role in transmitting values such as patience, endurance, and respect for social hierarchy. This aligns with Yankah’s (1989) view of proverbs as instruments of cultural continuity that guide behavior and reinforce community

norms. In modern contexts, where oral traditions face challenges from digital communication and globalization, the persistence of camel-related proverbs in everyday speech underscores their resilience and adaptability. These findings open avenues for further research into how proverbs evolve in digital discourse, for instance, in memes or social media posts, and whether their illocutionary force is maintained, softened, or intensified in online interactions.

7 Conclusions and Recommendations

This paper examined camel-related proverbs in Jordanian Arabic based on the Speech Act Theory. The analysis revealed that proverbs about camels are pragmatically multifunctional in JSA, performing 10 distinct illocutionary forces (pragmatic functions). They are as follows: criticizing, expressing anger, praising, offering condolences, blaming, offering sympathy, threatening, advising, rejecting, and asserting. These illocutionary forces were categorized into four illocutionary acts: expressives, commissives, directives, and representatives. It also revealed that their use is deeply influenced by contextual factors, including speaker-hearer relationships, tone, and social expectations. The findings underscore the value of applying the Speech Act Theory to proverbs, revealing their performative nature and communicative impact in real-life situations. Importantly, the study demonstrates that traditional expressions continue to serve vital roles in contemporary Jordanian discourse, especially in rural and Bedouin settings where oral traditions remain influential.

Substantial effort was dedicated to identifying, categorizing, and validating the illocutionary forces conveyed by camel-related proverbs in their respective contexts. However, I recognize that the proposed classifications may not be universally accepted, whether by native speakers of Jordanian Arabic or by academic scholars. Naturally, a certain degree of subjectivity has shaped the analysis, interpretation, and labeling of these functions. Complete consensus is unlikely, as alternative labels or interpretations may appear equally valid upon further examination. Such variability is an inherent and expected aspect of linguistic inquiry, and it calls for a degree of openness and interpretive tolerance from both readers and evaluators. Future studies should compare camel-related proverbs in Jordanian Arabic with similar animal metaphors in other Arabic dialects or cultures to reveal whether their pragmatic functions are universal or culture-specific.

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Oday Alshorafat
The Language Center, The University of Jordan
e-mail: alshorafat123@gmail.com

Sharif Alghazo
University of Sharjah, College of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences, Department of Foreign Languages
The University of Jordan, School of Foreign Languages, Department of English Language and Literature
e-mail: salghazo@sharjah.ac.ae

Ghaleb Rabab'ah
University of Sharjah, College of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences, Department of Foreign Languages
The University of Jordan, School of Foreign Languages, Department of English Language and Literature
e-mail: grababah@sharjah.ac.ae

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A Variational-Pragmatic Account of Hearer-Oriented Clitics in Jordanian Arabic

Saleem Abdelhady

American University of the Middle East, Kuwait

This study aims to analyze the hearer-oriented clitic in Jordanian Arabic from a variational perspective. Even though there has been extensive research to examine this clitic, earlier studies have focused mainly on analyzing this clitic from a grammatical or socio-pragmatic perspective. Recent studies that examine this clitic from a generative perspective show that this clitic is subject to dialectal variation. However, such a claim lacks empirical evidence. This study, therefore, seeks to answer questions related to the sociolinguistic status of this pragmatic marker in Jordanian Arabic. The study examines the impact of sociolinguistic factors, namely age, gender, and region, on realizing this clitic. The data is collected through face-to-face sociolinguistic interviews with sixteen persons from Jordan. To analyze the data quantitatively, the researchers used GoldVarb X. The findings show that Haddad's (2018) conclusion may lead to hasty generalization. Nevertheless, the study supports Al-Raba'a (2020) observation that hearer-oriented clitics are subject to dialectal variation.

Keywords: *language variation and change, hearer-oriented clitics, pragmatic variation, social factors*

1 Introduction

This study analyzes hearer-oriented clitics in Jordanian Arabic from a sociolinguistic perspective. Following Haddad (2018), Kalnača & Lokmane (2019: 150) define a hearer-oriented clitic as an “optional dative pronominal clitic that functions as an interpersonal pragmatic marker.” Many studies (e.g., Haddad 2018; Al-Raba'a 2022; Kalnača & Lokmane 2019) demonstrate that speakers use hearer-oriented clitics in their communication to encode a representation of a hearer in a discourse setting. The following examples are representative.

(1)

a.

<i>Zijaad</i>	<i>biʔaḏḏi-lak</i>	<i>kil</i>	<i>waʔt-o</i>	<i>neejim.</i>
Ziyad	spend-2.M.SG ¹	all	time-his	sleeping

‘Ziyad spends-[you] all his time sleeping.’ (Lebanese Arabic, Haddad, 2020)

b.

<i>fuft-lak</i>	<i>ʔiʃi</i>	<i>yariib</i>	<i>eljoom.</i>
saw.1.SG-2.M.SG	thing	strange	today

‘I saw-[you] a strange thing today.’ (Jordanian Arabic, Al-Raba'a 2023)

¹ This manuscript follows Leipzig Glossing rules and the list of standard abbreviations for glosses.

(2)

a.

<i>Es</i>	<i>tev</i>	<i>gan</i>	<i>gaidīšu!</i>
I.NOM	you.DAT.SG	PRT	wait.FUT.1SG
<i>Kur</i>	<i>tas</i>	<i>ir</i>	<i>redzēts!</i>
Where	it.NOM.SG	be.AUX.PRS.3	see.PTCP.PST.PASS

‘I am not going to wait! That is unheard of!

(Latvian, Kalnača & Lokmane 2019: 150)

b.

<i>Kur</i>	<i>tev</i>	<i>tik</i>	<i>vēlā</i>	<i>rudenī</i>
Where	you.DAT.SG	so	late.LOC.SG	autumn.LOC.SG
<i>pērkons</i>	<i>rasies!</i>			
thunderstorm.NOM.SG	turn_on.FUT.3			

‘How on Earth should there be thunderstorm so late in the autumn!’

(Latvian, Kalnača & Lokmane 2019: 150)

Al-Raba’a (2022: 5) notices that the clitic does not impact “the truth condition of the sentence. This is confirmed by the fact that the sentences will still have the very same meaning if the clitics are deleted.” In addition, eliminating the clitic does not lead to ungrammatical constructions. This is evident in the following examples.

(3)

a.

<i>smiʕit</i>	<i>xabar</i>	<i>kwajjis</i>	<i>elyoom.</i>
heard.1.SG	news	good	today

‘I heard good news today.’ (Jordanian Arabic, Al-Raba’a 2023)

b.

<i>smiʕit-lak</i>	<i>xabar</i>	<i>kwajjis</i>	<i>elyoom.</i>
heard.1.SG-2.M.SG	news	good	today

‘I heard good news today.’ (Jordanian Arabic, Al-Raba’a, 2023 adapted)

In Jordanian Arabic, research on the topic has been mostly restricted to limited attempts to view this clitic in light of generative grammar. Perhaps the most notable contribution of Al-Raba’a’s (2022) study is that it explains the presence of the clitic in some utterances. However, problems arise when an attempt is made to implement the generalization to Jordanian Arabic on a wider scale. Al-Raba’a (2022) mentions that the clitic appears commonly in informal settings and in rural areas. A note of caution is due here. Does the clitic appear on formal occasions? How often do speakers use the hearer-oriented clitic in their speech? Do male speakers use this clitic more than female ones? There has been no quantitative analysis to answer those questions, but those questions trigger enough inquiries to study this clitic from a sociolinguistic perspective. By employing quantitative modes of inquiry, this study attempts to illuminate that this clitic, contrary to expectations, is not solely governed by the pragmatic context. This work contributes to existing knowledge of hearer-oriented clitics by providing a comprehensive view of what governs the use of such clitics in spontaneous speech. The study aims to view the hearer-oriented clitic as a variable and to shed light on the impact of sociolinguistic factors on the emergence of this clitic.

The overall structure of the study takes the form of five sections. The first section lays out the theoretical dimensions of this research. The second section presents a review of related literature. The purpose of the next section is to present the methodology that is followed in conducting this research. The goal of the next section is to discuss the data and presents the findings. The final section concludes the study and reflects on the extent to which this study has contributed to understanding the sociolinguistic context that governs the use of hearer-oriented clitics in Jordanian Arabic.

2 Theoretical background

This section contextualises the research by providing background information on variational pragmatics and sociolinguistic factors and their relevance to contextualise hearer-oriented clitics. The section highlights key theoretical concepts in this area and presents key features of clitics. Understanding the link between sociolinguistics and clitics will help solidify the assumptions of this research.

2.1 *Variational pragmatics*

Pragmatic variability refers to the availability of numerous possibilities for language users to produce and understand meanings, considering the situational context (Verschueren 1999). The area that studies the variability and diversity of language use in different contexts and communities is called variational pragmatics. According to Ren et al. (2013: 283), this subfield of pragmatics “focuses on the influence of geographical and social factors on language in interaction and intra-lingual variation.” This area of pragmatics looks at the impact of social factors, such as gender, age, power, and the like, on the realization of a particular pragmatic phenomenon. It is involved with the examination of how linguistic and non-linguistic factors interact to produce variations in language use and how these variations are related to the communicative needs and goals of different speakers and communities (Barron & Schneider 2009; Ren et al. 2013).

Barron (2021) indicates that pragmatic variability helps with understanding various areas of inquiry. Those areas include levels such as a stylistic variation in address terms, a variation in discourse-pragmatic markers, an actional variation in speech acts, an interactional variation in sequential patterns, a variation in topic content and management, an organizational variation in terms of turn-taking) a prosodic variation, such as a variation in intonation and pitch of a sound and a variation in body language. This is exemplified by Harting (2005). He shows that there is an impact of age and gender on the variable use of ‘*G'day*’ in an Australian context. This expression is used for greetings; nevertheless, his study shows that males and those above 30 years old tend to use ‘*G'day*’ more in their greetings than other speakers.

In this paper, the term variational pragmatics is used in its local sense to study variation in the hearer-oriented clitic as a discourse-pragmatic marker; more specifically, this paper aims to view how Jordanians use hearer-oriented clitics in spontaneous speech, and it aims to figure out if there is a link between social factors and the emergence of the hearer-oriented clitic in their speech. For this purpose, variational pragmatics will be used as a framework to understand how this clitic varies across different age groups, genders, and other factors in this culture. Before we continue, it is crucial to understand pragmatic markers.

2.2 Pragmatic markers

According to Romero-Trillo (2019), pragmatic markers are linguistic elements that signal contextual information about the speaker's intended meaning and the social relationship between the speaker and the listener. They provide cues about the speaker's intentions, attitudes, and degree of certainty, among other things. Examples of pragmatic markers include intonation, stress, discourse particles (such as *well* or *you know*), and nonverbal cues (such as gestures or facial expressions) (Aijmer & Simon-Vandenberg 2022; Erman, 2001; Maschler & Schiffrin 2015; Norrick 2009; Romero-Trillo 2019; Zienkowski 2011).

Norrick (2009) argues that pragmatic markers play an important role in determining the meaning of an utterance, as they provide additional information beyond the literal meaning of the words. For example, the intonation used when asking a question can indicate the speaker's level of certainty or doubt, while a discourse particle like *you know* can signal a speaker's desire for the listener's agreement (Columbus 2010; Tagliamonte 2006; Van Dijk 1979; Wiltschko 2017). In this way, pragmatic markers help to create a more nuanced and complete picture of the speaker's intended meaning, and they are an essential aspect of effective communication.

One of the pragmatic markers is those clitics that are used to express the speaker's attitude or stance towards the content of their utterance, and to create a more direct or intimate relationship with the listener (Al-Raba'a 2022; Barron 2021; Haddad 2018; Haddad 2013; 2014; 2019; 2020 2022; Harting 2005; Kalnača & Lokmane 2019; Ren et al. 2013). Those clitics are commonly used in spoken language and can have various functions, such as softening commands or requests, expressing politeness, seeking agreement, or expressing uncertainty. For example, in English, the clitic *huh* is often used to check if the listener is following what is being said, while in French, the clitic *n'est-ce pas* is used to seek agreement from the listener (Hansen, 2005).

In some languages, hearer-oriented clitics can play a major role in shaping the tone and style of the utterance and can greatly impact the interpretation of the speaker's intended meaning. These clitics are, therefore, an important aspect of language that help to create a more nuanced and interactive communicative experience between the speaker and the listener.

2.3 Sociolinguistic variables

Sociolinguistics deals with language variation across societies and cultures (Al-Wer & Horesh 2019; Bayley et al. 2012; Campbell-Kibler 2010). In language variation and change, sociolinguistic variables refer to facets of language use that are associated with particular social groups, such as age, gender, ethnicity, level of education, socioeconomic status, and geographic location (Abdelhady 2019; Campbell-Kibler 2010; Eckert 2017; Eckert & Rickford 2001; Edwards 1992; Osborne 1999; Preston 2009; Yaeger-Dror 2014). These variables can involve several linguistic features such as morphological features (Haddad 2014; Säily 2011; 2016), phonological aspects (Abdelhady 2019), semantic selections (Hasan 1989), and structural patterns (Edwards 1992).

For instance, in American English, there are several sociolinguistic variables that are associated with regional dialects, such as the use of *y'all* in the South, *pop* vs. *soda* in different parts of the country, and variations in vowel sounds (Holmes & Hazen 2013). Age is another sociolinguistic variable that can affect language use, with younger generations often adopting new slang and expressions, while older generations may stick to more traditional language patterns (Abdelhady 2019). For instance, in the Jordan Valley, a rural area in the Hashemite

Kingdom of Jordan, Abdelhady's (2019) study shows that older generations do not follow the phonological rule of the definite article assimilation (/l/ changes to +coronal/-coronals). Older generations prefer assimilating the definite prefix with all sounds. However, his study shows that younger generations refrain from doing so.

The variation in the use of pragmatic markers is influenced by several factors. Different cultures have different norms and expectations regarding the use of language in social interactions. Therefore, speakers from different cultural backgrounds may use pragmatic markers differently, based on their cultural norms. The social context of communication, such as the social relationship between speakers, their status, and the setting of the interaction, can affect the use of pragmatic markers. For example, speakers may use different pragmatic markers in a formal business meeting than in an informal conversation with friends. Research has shown that gender can influence the use of pragmatic markers. Women, for example, tend to use more hedging and polite markers than men, reflecting social norms of femininity. Speakers of different ages may use pragmatic markers differently, reflecting generational differences in language use and cultural norms. The use of pragmatic markers is also influenced by cognitive factors, such as the speaker's linguistic proficiency, communicative competence, and their ability to understand and interpret the social cues in a conversation. Sociolinguistic variables are important for understanding how language use reflects and shapes hearer-oriented clitics in Jordanian Arabic, as well as for analyzing language variation and change over time.

3 Review of related literature

This section aims to present a review of those studies and highlight the gap in the current literature that our study aims to bridge. Before proceeding to examine those studies, it is important to briefly present key studies that investigate language variation and change in Arabic. Previous research findings in language variation on Arabic will help in understanding the sociolinguistic context needed for building the framework for analyzing the variable under investigation.

Many seminal studies examine language variation and change in different Arabic cultures and contexts: Jordanian Arabic (Abdelhady 2019; Abdel-Jawad 1981), Syrian Arabic (Habib 2014), and Lebanese Arabic (Ibrahim 2009). Together these studies provide important insights into language variation and show the impact of sociolinguistic factors on the realization of diverse sociolinguistic variables. In Jordanian Arabic, a considerable amount of literature has been published on language variation and change (e.g., Abdel-Jawad 1981). These studies examine a diverse of sociolinguistic variables: phonological variation in the production consonants (Abdel-Jawad 1981), acoustic variation in the production of emphasis and interdental (Omari & Herk 2016; Omari & Jaber 2019), lexical variation (Abdel-Jawad 1981), variation in the production of definite articles (Abdelhady 2019), variation in the production of vowels (Al-Deaibes et al. 2021) grammatical variation (Herin & Al-Wer 2013). According to Abdelhady (2019), the linguistic status in Jordan shows that “females are the ones who use urban variants, educated speakers use standard variants more than other speakers, and that young speakers are usually the ones who lead a change” (p. 15). Abdel-Jawad's (1981) studies show similar findings.

Many researchers have studied hearer-oriented clitics in Arabic from a generative perspective. (Abdelhady 2020; Al-Raba'a 2022) generally place an emphasis on the role of speech act projections (Abdelhady 2020; Abdel-Hady & Branigan 2019; Haegeman & Hill

2013; Hill 2007) in generating those clitics in the syntax proper. Other studies focus on analyzing this clitic from a pragmatic or sociopragmatic perspectives (Haddad 2018; Haddad 2020; 2022). The pioneering work of Haddad (2018) reports that those clitics are governed pragmatically. His observations suggest that there may be a link between context and those clitics because it is evident for him that those clitics do not contribute to the semantic interpretation of utterances, and because omitting those clitics do not lead to ungrammatical constructions.

There remain several aspects of those clitics about which relatively little is known. This study, therefore, aims to highlight variation in such a pragmatic marker, namely, the study analyzes how sociolinguistic factors impact hearer-oriented clitics. By doing this analysis, the researchers aim to figure out if there is a dialectical variation in the realization of those clitics or not.

4 Methodology

4.1 Regional setting

This study quantifies hearer-oriented clitics in Jordan. Jordan, a country in the Middle East, has Arabic as its official language, but there are many variations and changes in the language due to different factors. Historical, social, and geographical influences have contributed to these variations. Throughout history, Jordan has been ruled by different powers, and their language has influenced Jordanian Arabic dialect. Socially, there are different dialects based on social class, ethnicity, and age group. Geographically, rural and urban areas also have distinct dialects. The Jordanian dialect is continually changing, reflecting the country's complex history, diverse society, and changing cultural practices. Two main regions are selected for the purpose of our study: Irbid (urban center in the north of Jordan, almost 80 KM from the capital Amman) and Al-Shouna Al-Shamlia (a rural area in the Jordan Valley located in the north-west part of Jordan). See the map below.

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Atlas_of_Jordan#/media/File:Jordan_nahias.png

The choice of two regions is because they represent an urban center and a rural area in which the researchers consider themselves in-group members with the communities living in those regions. This will help in eliminating the observer’s paradox and result in having natural and spontaneous conversations with the participants.

The participants in this study were recruited from the two regions. Following Author (2019), the researchers selected the sampling of the study based on their own social network. The speech sample consists of the naturally occurring speech of sixteen speakers. The participants are stratified based on their level of intimacy, their gender, and their age. Because this clitic is oriented towards a hearer in a conversation, the researchers noted information related to both the speaker and the hearer. This helps in forming a better picture with those questions in mind: Who used this clitic? And who did the speaker use the clitic for?

4.2 *Problem of the study*

Most researchers (e.g., (Al-Raba’a 2022; Haddad, 2018) investigating hearer-oriented clitics have utilized a pragmatic contextual analysis or a generative approach in their studies. Researchers of those studies, therefore, are concerned with finding and analyzing data that helps in describing the phenomenon from a qualitative perspective. However, such studies remain narrow in focus because both studies do not offer a quantitative view for those clitics. Moreover, the data helps only in understanding the phenomenon from scripted or written sources. To highlight, for Haddad (2018: 16), it is enough to support his social-pragmatic approach by eliciting examples from “soap operas, movies, plays, talk shows, and Facebook.” It is not clear how (Al-Raba’a 2022: 4) collected his data; however, he framed his analysis by “relying on data from JA [Jordanian Arabic] as well as Classical Arabic.”

Together these studies provide important insights into how hearer-oriented clitics function in their context and how they are generated syntactically. Nevertheless, a major drawback of those studies is that they might lead to hasty generalizations. First, “hearer-oriented clitics in JA [Jordanian Arabic] are commonly used in informal situations” [...], especially in the rural dialect spoken in Inba, a village that is part of the Northern Al-Mazar District” (Al-Raba’a 2022: 5). It seems that Al-Raba’a’s (2022: 16) comment is questionable when it compared to (Haddad’s, 2018) claim that “the exclusion of other varieties is informed by the observation that the [attitude datives] in the four varieties of Arabic under examination behave uniformly in terms of their structure, meaning contribution, and social functions.”

It is not known till the date of the current investigation the impact of the sociolinguistic factors on the realization of those clitics in spontaneous speech. As mentioned in his response to one of the reviewers of the Italian Journal of Linguistics, Al-Raba’a (2022) clearly points out that there is a chance for a dialectal variation in the use of hearer-oriented clitics. He states this idea as follows.

It must be noted that a reviewer who is a native speaker of another sub-variety of JA [Jordanian Arabic] has indicated that the hearer-oriented clitics are acceptable in subjunctive, interrogative, and future clauses *in his/her sub-variety, so it appears to be that we are dealing with some dialectal variation here* (emphasis is mine). Crucially for us, though, the arbitrary gap test fully applies to the JA Arabic sub-variety under investigation.

(Al-Raba’a, 2022: 30)

This comment clearly leads us to reject Haddad’s (2018: 16) overgeneralization that “attitude datives] in the four varieties of Arabic under examination behave *uniformly* (font style is mine).” Therefore, this research is meant to address this sociolinguistic variational gap in our knowledge of those clitics.

4.3 *Questions of the study*

Research to date has not yet determined answers to the following questions.

1. How common do the hearer-oriented clitics appear in spontaneous speech?
2. What is the impact of sociolinguistic factors, such as age, gender, and the like, on the emergence of hearer-oriented clitics?
3. What are the differences between main regional varieties: Urban and Rural? Does the hearer-oriented clitic appear in one variety but not in others?

4.4 *Population and sampling*

The population of the study consists of Jordanian people living in cities and rural areas. To select the sample of the study, the researchers use the social networks technique. Using this technique helps in building a corpus of natural speeches spoken in natural settings. The sample of the study consists of sixteen individuals, stratified according to age, gender, and region. The age category is viewed in terms of (young vs old). The gender category is based on biological gender (males vs females). We divide region into rural and urban depending on the residential location of the participant. Those participants from Irbid city are classified as urban. On the other hand, participants from the Jordan Valley are categorized as rural.

4.5 Data collection

Because hearer-oriented clitics “are used to mark the hearer’s involvement or engagement with the at-issue content of an utterance and/or with the speaker as an in-group member” (Haddad, 2020: 10), the researchers designed their interviews in informal setting gatherings. Doing so helps in looking at the interviewer as an in-group member and creates the setting that triggers the use of hearer-oriented clitics in conversations. This method is particularly useful in studying hearer-oriented clitics because defining the type of activity is important to “help social actors [to] determine what types of utterance are appropriate and how an utterance will be understood” (Levinson 1979, cited in Haddad, 2020: 30).

The data was collected by informal interviews with sixteen persons. The interviews lasted for twenty to thirty minutes each. After taking participants’ permission to record the interviews, the researchers asked the participants to talk about general topics relating to their dreams, childhood, social media, superstitions, and descriptions of memorable incidents. The aim of selecting those topics is to encourage participants to speak naturally.

To increase the reliability of measures, the researchers met participants in group gatherings along with the presence of family members or close friends. The interviews were recorded using iPhone 16 ProMax, transcribed, and coded to ensure the anonymity of the participants. Prior the recording of the conversations, the researchers informed the participants to sign a consent form in which the researchers clarified the procedures that are followed during the recorded session. All participants were sent the consent form, for three days or more to read the details and know the general purpose of the study. During the session, informants were told that they can stop or pause the recording or interview at any time during the session.

4.6 Data analysis

After recording the conversations, the researchers immediately coded the interviews into texts and added symbols and markers to highlight any paralanguage or contextual cues that may help in analyzing the data.

The researchers distinguished hearer-oriented clitics from core-arguments (bound pronouns) following the literature. According to Al-Raba’a (2022) hearer-oriented clitics are distinguished by three features. First, deleting the clitics does not change the meaning of the sentence, and they do not contribute to the truth condition of the sentence. Second, these clitics cannot be categorized as either a beneficiary or a recipient. Third, a unique characteristic that sets hearer-oriented clitics apart from other bound pronouns (subject/object) is that the former cannot be involved in any binding relationship, which is not the case for the latter. The researchers excluded any clitic did not meet those features or that was ambiguous to ensure the clarity of the analysis. See the following examples.²

(3)

- | | |
|----------------------------------|----------------------|
| a. <i>ʕawwaft-ak</i> | <i>ħaalak</i> |
| made.exhaust.1.SG-you.M.SG | yourself |
| ‘I made you1 exhaust yourself1.’ | (Al-Raba’a, 2022: 6) |

² Based on the variety that Al-raba’a (2020) used in his study.

confirming that the zero variant is used much more frequently and is strongly preferred over the *-ak* form across the data.

Table 1: Distribution of the variable (*-ak* vs. \emptyset) across the dataset

Participants	Gender	Age	Region	<i>-ak</i>	\emptyset
P1	M	O	U	9	76
P2	M	O	U	8	80
P3	M	O	R	30	90
P4	M	O	R	29	50
P5	M	Y	U	17	67
P6	M	Y	U	18	46
P7	M	Y	R	35	76
P8	M	Y	R	37	57
P9	F	O	U	4	88
P10	F	O	U	5	90
P11	F	O	R	12	67
P12	F	O	R	15	86
P13	F	Y	U	7	95
P14	F	Y	U	9	84
P15	F	Y	R	19	50
P16	F	Y	R	17	66

Thus, across age, gender, and region, the zero variant dominates in frequency, showing that speakers overwhelmingly prefer \emptyset over *-ak* in their speech. Let us now examine these categories more closely. By looking at gender (Table 2), age (Table 3), and region (Table 4) separately, clearer patterns of variation emerge. This breakdown highlights how each social factor plays a role in shaping the distribution and preference between the *-ak* and \emptyset variants.

Table 2: Distribution of the variable (*-ak* vs. \emptyset) across gender

Gender	<i>-ak</i>	\emptyset	Total	<i>-ak</i> %	\emptyset %
F	88.0	626.0	714.0	12.3	87.7
M	183.0	542.0	725.0	25.2	74.8

Table 3: Distribution of the variable (*-ak* vs. \emptyset) across age

Age	<i>-ak</i>	\emptyset	Total	<i>-ak</i> %	\emptyset %
O	112.0	627.0	739.0	15.2	84.8
Y	159.0	541.0	700.0	22.7	77.3

Table 4: Distribution of the variable (-ak vs. Ø) across region

Region	-ak	Ø	Total	-ak %	Ø %
R	194.0	542.0	736.0	26.4	73.6
U	77.0	626.0	703.0	11.0	89.0

The chi-square test revealed a significant difference in variant use by gender ($\chi^2 = 38.42$, $df = 1$, $p < 0.001$). Males show a higher tendency to use the -ak form (25.2%) compared to females (12.3%). In contrast, females overwhelmingly prefer the zero variant (87.7%). This demonstrates that gender strongly influences the choice of variant. In addition, age also shows a significant effect ($\chi^2 = 12.95$, $df = 1$, $p < 0.001$). Younger speakers use the -ak variant more frequently (22.7%) compared to older speakers (15.2%). While the zero variant remains dominant in both groups, younger participants are noticeably more inclined to retain the -ak form. Region emerges as the strongest factor, with a highly significant result ($\chi^2 = 54.82$, $df = 1$, $p < 0.001$). Furthermore, rural speakers use the -ak form far more often (26.4%) than urban speakers (11.0%). Urban speakers show a very strong preference for the zero variant (89.0%). Therefore, while rural speakers, although still favoring zero overall, maintain the -ak form to a greater extent.

Table 5: Distribution of the variable (-ak vs. Ø) cross tabulating age and gender

Age	Gender	-ak	Ø	Total	-ak %	Ø %
O	F	36	331	367	9.8	90.2
O	M	76	296	372	20.4	79.6
Y	F	52	295	347	15.0	85.0
Y	M	107	246	353	30.3	69.7

The chi-square test yielded $\chi^2(3) = 13.80$, $p = 0.003$. This indicates a statistically significant relationship between age and gender in the distribution of the two variants. Young males show the highest relative use of -ak (30.3%), while old females favor the zero variant (90.2%). Thus, age and gender together strongly influence variant choices.

Table 6: Distribution of the variable (-ak vs. Ø) cross tabulating age and region

Age	Region	-ak	Ø	Total	-ak %	Ø %
O	R	86	293	379	22.7	77.3
O	U	26	334	360	7.2	92.8
Y	R	108	249	357	30.3	69.7
Y	U	51	292	343	14.9	85.1

The chi-square test gave $\chi^2(3) = 15.96$, $p = 0.001$. The relationship between age and region is significant, with rural young speakers showing the strongest preference for -ak (30.3%), while urban old speakers overwhelmingly prefer the zero variant (92.8%). This suggests that both social factors jointly constrain variant selection.

Table 7: Distribution of the variable (-ak vs. Ø) cross tabulating gender and region

Gender	Region	-ak	Ø	Total	-ak %	Ø %
F	R	63	269	332	19.0	81.0
F	U	25	357	382	6.5	93.5
M	R	131	273	404	32.4	67.6
M	U	52	269	321	16.2	83.8

The chi-square test produced $\chi^2(3) = 45.62$, $p < 0.0001$. This is highly significant, showing a strong association between gender and region. Rural males are the heaviest users of -ak (32.4%), while urban females are the most consistent users of the zero variant (93.5%). The findings highlight that male speakers in rural areas maintain traditional forms, whereas urban females shift toward innovative or prestige forms.

5.2 Discussion

The results of this study reveal a clear quantitative preference for the zero (Ø) variant over the -ak form, suggesting that speakers overwhelmingly favor the unmarked option in everyday speech. With almost four times as many instances of Ø compared to -ak, this distribution is not random but highly significant, as confirmed by the chi-square test. From a sociolinguistic standpoint, such a strong bias indicates that zero form has acquired the status of the socially unmarked or default variant in the community. Following Labov's (2001) framework of linguistic change, when a variant becomes overwhelmingly dominant, it often reflects either a completed change or an ongoing process of standardization (Abdel-Jawad 1981; Al-Deaibes et al. 2021; Habib 2014; Ibrahim, 2009). In this sense, the high frequency of Ø could be interpreted as evidence of linguistic leveling and the gradual retreat of -ak from colloquial use. This confirms Al-Raba'a's (2022) view where -ak is not dominant.

The predominance of the zero variant may also reflect broader social meanings attached to standardization and prestige (Abdel-Jawad 1981). In many Arabic-speaking contexts, forms associated with urban or educated speech are perceived as more prestigious, while older or rural variants tend to be marked as traditional or localized (Abdelhady 2019). The preference for Ø, therefore, may not only be phonological simplification but also a social alignment with norms of education, modernity, and upward mobility. Speakers often evaluate linguistic forms in terms of symbolic capital, where language choice indexes social aspirations and belonging (Aditya et al. 2025; Amjad 2025; Kjällström 2025; Muxtulova & Tasheva 2025; Zschomler 2019). In this case, the high proportion of zero forms could be understood as the community's shift toward a prestige norm, consciously or unconsciously aligning with the urban standard (Abdelhady 2019; Abdel-Jawad, 1981).

Gender differences in variant use support this interpretation (Al-Harabsheh 2014). The data show that men employ the -ak form approximately twice as often as women. This pattern resonates strongly with the classic findings of sociolinguistic research: women tend to use more standard or prestigious forms, while men often favor vernacular or nonstandard variants (Trudgill 1972; Romaine 2003). Women's linguistic behavior has frequently been interpreted

as reflecting greater social awareness and sensitivity to overt prestige norms (Brouwer 2011; Eckert 1989; Kjällström 2025; Kulick 2003; Lakoff 2003; Livia 2003; Romaine 2003; Wodak & Benke 2017). As Trudgill (1972) observed in his study of Norwich English, women's preference for standard forms often reflects a desire to project status and respectability in societies where language use can carry symbolic value (Trudgill 1972). Similarly, in Arabic-speaking societies, female speakers may be more attuned to social judgments associated with language, favoring variants that connote refinement or education. Men, on the other hand, may preserve older or localized forms such as, *-ak* because this carry covert prestige, forms that, while stigmatized in formal contexts, signal solidarity, toughness, or authenticity within male peer networks (Labov 2001; Holmes 2013). The strong gendered contrast in this dataset thus aligns well with long-standing observations that linguistic variation is deeply tied to gendered identity performances rather than biological sex differences.

Age also appears to exert a significant influence on the realization of the variable, but the direction of the effect is particularly interesting (Eckert 2017). Contrary to expectations in apparent-time studies, younger speakers in this sample use *-ak* slightly more frequently than older speakers. In most cases of linguistic change in progress, younger generations tend to lead the shift toward innovative or prestige forms (Eckert 2017). However, in this case, the younger cohort's slightly higher use of *-ak* may suggest the opposite: rather than abandoning the traditional form, they may be re-appropriating it as a stylistic resource. Such reversal is not uncommon in sociolinguistic change; younger speakers sometimes revitalize older features to express local identity, irony, or resistance to urban or institutional norms. The finding could therefore point to the emergence of a new social meaning for *-ak*, especially among young males, who appear to use it as a symbolic marker of masculinity or authenticity. The age-gender interaction supports this interpretation, with young men being the most frequent users of *-ak* and older women the least. This suggests that the form's survival may depend not on structural necessity but on its social indexicality, its power to convey identity and stance in interaction (Silverstein 2003).

Region emerges as the most powerful conditioning factor, as evidenced by the highest chi-square value. Rural speakers use *-ak* more than twice as often as their urban counterparts, revealing a classic urban-rural linguistic divide. Sociolinguistic research consistently shows that rural communities tend to retain older or conservative linguistic features, partly because of denser social networks and slower exposure to normative pressures from education and media (Milroy & Milroy 1992). By contrast, urban speakers are more susceptible to standardization and language contact, accelerating the adoption of prestige or innovative forms. The present results fit this model precisely: the zero variant dominates in urban contexts (nearly 89 %), indicating convergence toward an urban-based standard, while rural speakers maintain a stronger attachment to *-ak* (26 %), preserving it as part of local linguistic identity. Such distribution echoes findings from studies of Arabic dialect leveling, where rural forms gradually recede as speakers align with urban norms in the pursuit of social mobility (Abdel-Jawad 1981; Aditya et al. 2025; Al-Wer & de Jong 2017; Habib 2014). Nonetheless, the persistence of *-ak* among rural participants demonstrates that local identity remains an important sociolinguistic force, even within broader processes of change.

The interaction between gender and region further reinforces the significance of social meaning in variation. Rural males are the heaviest users of *-ak*, whereas urban females are the most consistent users of the zero variant. This polarization exemplifies the interplay between overt and covert prestige. In Trudgill's (1972) model, overt prestige corresponds to the social value of standard forms, while covert prestige is associated with nonstandard forms that carry

positive in-group value. For rural men, *-ak* may symbolize solidarity, local pride, and authenticity; for urban women, \emptyset indexes modernity, education, and sophistication. Such complementary distributions are rarely accidental; they reflect stable social meanings attached to language that reinforce group identities. These patterns also illustrate the principle that language variation operates as a semiotic system through which speakers perform belonging and differentiation. The *-ak*/ \emptyset alternation therefore transcends phonological or morphological difference; it operates as a social index through which speakers negotiate local and supra-local identities.

The consistent statistical significance of all three factors – gender, age, and region – and their interactions indicates that the variation is socially structured rather than random. The evidence suggests that language change and social differentiation are intertwined processes: linguistic forms do not merely reflect social divisions but help construct them. Speakers use variants not only because of social position but to actively signal stance, affiliation, and ideology. The recurrent pattern of urban females leading the adoption of the prestige form and rural males preserving the conservative one reflects the gender paradox described by Labov (1990): women lead changes from above (toward prestige forms), while men often lead changes from below or maintain vernacular norms. Your results correspond closely to this paradox, illustrating how universal sociolinguistic tendencies manifest within specific Arabic dialectal contexts.

Interpreting these findings within the theory of indexical order (Silverstein 2003), the *-ak* form may have shifted from a first-order index of grammatical possession to a second-order index of social identity. That is, its linguistic function is now intertwined with social meaning: using *-ak* is not simply grammatical but socially meaningful, indexing rurality, masculinity, and perhaps conservatism. Conversely, using the zero variant signals education, urbanity, and social mobility. Such indexical layering explains why both forms persist even under strong asymmetry in frequency; speakers maintain them because they carry contrasting social meanings that remain useful in different contexts. This semiotic social dimension aligns with recent studies in Arabic sociolinguistics that highlight how morphological alternations can embody identity negotiations and ideologies of modernity versus tradition.

The data portray a community undergoing gradual linguistic change, where the zero variant is becoming dominant through standardization and prestige pressure, while *-ak* survives as a socially meaningful relic of traditional identity. The chi-square results provide quantitative support for the structured nature of this variation: gender, age, and region all interact to produce a complex sociolinguistic pattern consistent with universal principles of language change. The dominance of \emptyset demonstrates convergence toward a supra-local norm, yet the persistence of *-ak* among rural and male speakers illustrates the resilience of local forms as markers of authenticity and solidarity. These findings thus reaffirm the core sociolinguistic insight that language variation is not arbitrary but socially motivated, reflecting the dynamic balance between prestige and identity, innovation and continuity, standardization and diversity (Labov 2001; Holmes 2013).

6 Conclusion

This study has provided a comprehensive sociolinguistic examination of hearer-oriented clitics in Jordanian Arabic, particularly the alternation between the *-ak* and zero (\emptyset) variants. By integrating quantitative analysis with theoretical insights from variational pragmatics, the

findings reveal that the use of hearer-oriented clitics is systematically constrained by gender, age, and region, rather than being an arbitrary feature of informal discourse. The results demonstrate that the zero variant (\emptyset) overwhelmingly dominates in frequency and functions as the socially unmarked or prestige form, reflecting broader processes of linguistic leveling and standardization within Jordanian Arabic. Conversely, the *-ak* form remains a salient index of rurality, masculinity, and local identity, illustrating the persistence of conservative linguistic features as markers of authenticity and solidarity.

The study also reinforces long-established sociolinguistic patterns: women, particularly those in urban environments, tend to favor prestige and innovative variants, while men and rural speakers retain vernacular or conservative forms associated with covert prestige. These patterns underscore the dynamic interplay between language, identity, and social meaning, confirming that linguistic variation operates as both a reflection of and a mechanism for constructing social differentiation. Furthermore, the results highlight how younger speakers, especially young males, may re-appropriate older features like *-ak* as stylistic resources, thereby maintaining their social relevance within contemporary discourse. This research bridges an empirical gap in previous pragmatic and generative studies by offering quantitative evidence of sociolinguistic conditioning in hearer-oriented clitics. It underscores that such clitics are not merely grammatical artifacts but socially embedded markers of interactional stance and identity negotiation.

Future research should extend this investigation to other parts of Jordan and digital communication contexts to determine whether these patterns persist across written discourse and broader regional varieties. In doing so, further insights can be gained into how Arabic speakers continually balance linguistic innovation and tradition in shaping their sociolinguistic realities.

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Data availability

The author has reported the outcome of the interviews in this manuscript.

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Saleem Abdelhady
English Language and Communication Department
American University of the Middle East
Egaila, Kuwait
e-mail: saleem.abdelhady@aum.edu.kw

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Evaluating Corpus Interface Usability for Linguistic Research: The Case of the Kazakh National Corpus

Timur Akishev

KIMEP University, Almaty, Kazakhstan

This study examines the web interface of the Kazakh National Corpus (KNC) to assess its usability for general corpus-linguistic research. Drawing on established literature, we determine whether the corpus interface supports core analytical techniques, including frequency lists, concordances, keyword lists, and collocations and n-grams. We assess the presence, accessibility, functionality, and overall usability of these tools, identifying areas for improvement. To complement this theory-driven evaluation, we compare the KNC interface with those of two established national corpora, the British National Corpus (BNC) and the Russian National Corpus (RNC), to extract practical insights from their interface design and application of these analytical techniques. This two-level approach allows us to highlight both the theoretical requirements and practical considerations for enhancing the usability of the corpus interface for the purposes of international-standards linguistic research.

Keywords: *linguistic research, corpus linguistics, analytical techniques, corpus tools, corpus interface*

1 Introduction

In the modern digital world, language plays an important role as not only the means of communication but also the subject of research at the level of big data. Large-scale studies are conducted worldwide on a multitude of languages in order to understand the specificities of their structure, meaning, and use. The role of language data analysis-focused fields like corpus linguistics, computational linguistics, and natural language processing (NLP) is becoming increasingly important, especially in the era of AI-driven research (Levy et al. 2025). These fields, particularly corpus linguistics, are concerned with analysis of large digital or digitized collections of language data, or corpora. Corpora, classified into multiple types, developed for multiple purposes, and assembled from different types of data, play a key role in determining the characteristics of language in use (Stefanowitsch 2020: 22–23). Unlike general linguistics, which relies on theory-driven, intuitive interpretation of linguistic and sociolinguistic phenomena, corpus linguistics deals with practical analysis of ‘living’ language data (McEnery & Brookes 2024; Troiani et al. 2024), which includes spoken and written texts and many other configurations of data types that reflect the real-life, contextual use of language.

Historically, one of the key objectives of corpus linguistic research has been the development of large-scale, ‘national’ corpora for different languages. National corpora are officially created and maintained by national institutions to represent the standard language of a country, often for purposes such as language planning, education, lexicography, and research. Cultural representation and preservation are also important aspects in the design of such large-scale corpora, especially taking into account their role in capturing linguistic variation and supporting the analysis of how language differs and changes across time, regions, and cultural contexts (McEnery & Hardie 2012: 94). In terms of its structure, a national corpus is per se a

general or reference corpus. It is not really a distinct type of corpus in linguistic terms, but rather a designation based on its purpose, scope, and institutional status (Xiao 2008: 383).

The first steps in developing national corpora were taken by the creators of the British National Corpus. A number of other national corpora followed, including the American National Corpus, the Czech National Corpus, the Hungarian National Corpus, the Russian National Corpus, and so forth (Xiao 2008: 384–388). There have also been two significant attempts to develop a large-scale corpus for Kazakh, an agglutinating Turkic language spoken primarily in Kazakhstan and neighboring regions of Central Asia, Russia, and China. These attempts include the Kazakh Language Corpus (Makhambetov et al. 2013), whose website is no longer available, and the Almaty Corpus of the Kazakh Language (2016), which is still available and somewhat queryable. A Kazakh corpus is also available via Sketch Engine (n.d.), based on texts collected from the web, but it is not clear how usable it is for research purposes.

The first large-scale National Corpus of the Kazakh Language (2025) (NCKL; henceforth the Kazakh National Corpus or KNC¹) was developed at the Akhmet Baitursynuly Institute of Linguistics (n.d.), the national research center focusing primarily on Kazakh and other Turkic languages and operating under the country’s Ministry of Science and Higher Education. Since its release to the general public around 2020, the platform has undergone a number of updates that primarily focused on expanding subcorpora. While the KNC grows as a dataset, the publicly available interface, including analytical tools, does not appear to be under further development, while the existing documentation shows little information about past interface changes. The interface currently functions as an access and analysis tool to the corpus data and is presented as part of a research and educational resource, which means that it is already intended for scholarly use. As with many publicly released corpus platforms, potential issues in interface design and analytical functionality may limit researchers’ ability to interact effectively with the linguistic data. Addressing these issues requires rigorous research and improvement.

The main purpose of this paper is to evaluate the usability of the web interface of the Kazakh National Corpus for standard corpus-linguistic research by examining whether the interface supports core analytical techniques. We also compare its data analysis and visualization functionality to that of established national corpora for other languages to determine potential areas for improvement. Our goal is not to criticize, but to provide constructive feedback that can help improve the corpus interface. Our suggestions are informed by prominent literature in corpus linguistics, examples of other national corpora and their web interfaces, and our experience in working with corpora and corpus analysis tools.

2 Literature review

Despite an increasing number of linguistic projects focusing on Kazakh, it is still considered a low-resource, underresearched language, especially in terms of corpus linguistics and NLP (Joshi et al. 2020). Such languages naturally have a number of issues when it comes to corpus

¹ The official English abbreviation of the name of this corpus is “NCKL.” However, some web pages of the online corpus platform, as well as several recent scholarly publications, also use the shorter form “Kazakh National Corpus” and the abbreviation “KNC.” In this article, these two forms are used for brevity, while their correspondence to the official name is made explicit here to avoid confusion.

design and maintenance. These issues typically include data scarcity (Agić & Vulić 2019), limited resources (Sekeres et al. 2024), and the lack of progress in the development of tools (Ahmadi et al. 2023).

Recently launched corpora, especially those for low-resource languages, often face a number of issues that typically need to be addressed after launch. Apart from the obvious post-launch evaluations of the size, balance, and representativeness aspects, there are concerns about maintaining the quality and consistency of annotation (Voutilainen 2012), updating metadata and enriching it with NLP tools (Ecker et al. 2024), and improving the accessibility, customizability, and user-friendliness of the corpus interface (Soehn et al. 2008; Machálek 2020), including the development and maintenance of built-in tools to support open research practices corresponding to international standards (Hartmann 2024).

This study draws insights from Evison (2010) and Brezina & Gablasova (2018) to examine the analytical techniques integrated into the main web interfaces of the corpora. The use of guidelines from corpus linguists and developers of multiple corpora ensures that this study and its recommendations are grounded in research. It is important to note that the analytical techniques discussed in this paper are not exclusive to the guidelines developed by these authors. On the contrary, they have long been central to corpus design, and a large number of corpora have been developed on their basis to improve the understanding of language use. What this study borrows, specifically, is the authors' approach to evaluating how these core analytical techniques are implemented in a corpus interface.

Frequency lists are a fundamental analytical technique that enables corpus users and researchers to analyze the frequency information of specific linguistic items encountered within a corpus. Frequency analysis can be used to identify dominant lexical items within a dataset (Lijffijt et al. 2011), assess the lexical diversity of a text or corpus (Gregori-Signes & Clavel-Arroitia 2015), and compare word usage patterns across languages, corpora, and subcorpora (Taylor & del Fante 2020), among other purposes. Because frequency information can be sorted and filtered using a web interface of a corpus in various ways, it can serve as a solid foundation for both quantitative and qualitative research projects. However, it should be emphasized that the generation of frequency lists often serves as a foundational step for more complex analytical procedures.

Concordances, also known as KWIC (Key Word In Context), are one of the most basic techniques employed in corpus data analysis and visualization. They are used to display the target word or phrase centered, with a fixed number of words shown to its left and right, providing immediate context. This tool can be used to obtain information about the usage and meaning of words and phrases within authentic examples (Hunston 2002: 39). Analyzing how words occur in context contributes to improving the understanding of grammar, vocabulary, and stylistic preferences (Rauscher et al. 2013; Wulff & Baker 2021). While simple in nature, the generation of concordances often underpins more sophisticated forms of linguistic analysis. Concordances can also be a powerful tool in corpus-driven discourse analysis studies (Liu et al. 2022; Nonnenmacher & Naismith 2023). Aside from their applications in linguistics, concordances are widely used in language teaching and translation studies (Jones & Waller 2015; Zanettin 2023).

Keyword lists are ranked inventories of lexical items that are identified through frequency analysis as being unusually frequent in a given dataset relative to a reference corpus. This process requires quantitative comparisons between the target corpus, which is a specific dataset that a researcher is analyzing, and a reference corpus, which is a larger, more general

dataset (Rayson & Potts 2021; Moreno-Ortiz 2024). Depending on the research goals and the analytical platform, such comparisons may rely not only on statistical significance measures, but also effect-size measures. By highlighting words that are prominent in relation to a reference corpus, keyword lists help reveal specific patterns and themes in discourse analysis as well as in genre and register studies (Baker 2004). In addition, keyword lists are useful for language instructors aiming to teach specific vocabulary characteristics, translators seeking to simplify their texts (Rayson 2019), and other scholars interested in exploring or comparing domain-specific terminologies (Gries 2021).

Collocations and n-grams are two closely related corpus analysis techniques used to investigate how words combine in natural language. Collocations can be used to produce a list of collocates, i.e., co-occurrences of lexical items that have a tendency to be recurrent within a certain span and may be identified using a range of statistical or distributional measures focusing on the strength of association between words (Evert 2008: 1214–1215). N-grams, by contrast, focus on contiguous sequences of words of a specified length (*n*), and are identified on the basis of their frequency of occurrence in a corpus without focusing on association measures between individual words (Lyse & Andersen 2012). Both methods can be useful not only in corpus linguistics but also in language learning research (Gablasova et al. 2017) and general corpus-based exploration of register- and genre-specific language characteristics (Gries et al. 2011).

In the context of this study, these analytical techniques are examined within the web interface of the Kazakh National Corpus, which can serve as a valuable resource for exploring linguistic patterns. Several studies by Kazakhstani linguists, including researchers at the Akhmet Baitursynuly Institute of Linguistics, have examined the Kazakh National Corpus and its interface. These studies have addressed metadata and markup issues (Zhubanov 2015; Slyambekov & Sadyk 2024), the development of various subcorpora within the corpus (Amanbayeva et al. 2025; Fazylzhanova et al. 2025), and its applicability in linguistic research (Pirmanova et al. 2024). However, when they include data analysis, such studies typically rely on specialized standalone software tools to process corpus-elicited data (Ormanova et al. 2025) rather than using the corpus platform-internal, web-based analytical techniques. Importantly, in the present study, the web platforms are not evaluated as substitutes for these standalone corpus analysis applications, but rather as platforms designed to provide direct access to corpus data independently, accompanied by a set of analytical techniques for exploratory purposes.

3 Data and methods

The KNC contains 90 million word usages across 20 purpose-specific subcorpora, each hosted on a separate web page. The subcorpora vary in content and size, which reflects the developers' goal of achieving representativeness across different genres, text types, authors, and other domains. The platform contains such subcorpora as Spoken, Educational, Historical, Proverbs and Sayings, Parallel, and Terminological, among others. The web pages hosting these subcorpora provide various interface design and analytical functionality options that could also be evaluated for usability in research. This study, however, focuses only on the main part of the corpus and its interface and analytical functionality.

In order to determine whether the KNC interface is suitable for general corpus-linguistic research, we have compiled a list of core analytical techniques typically employed to work with

large-scale general corpora and evaluated the extent to which this platform supports them. This list of techniques includes (1) frequency lists, (2) concordances, (3) keyword lists, and (4) collocations and n-grams. It is based on a synthesis of ideas from seminal works by Evison (2010) and Brezina & Gablasova (2018). These authors established that these fundamental analytical techniques can be employed either within a corpus using its own web interface features or outside of the corpus using specialized software applications that work well with exported data. The current study aims only to examine whether these techniques are supported by the web interface, excluding discussion of any software applications.

In order to compare the interface of the Kazakh National Corpus to those of established national corpora for other languages in terms of data analysis and visualization functionality, we selected two such corpora, the British National Corpus and the Russian National Corpus, to analyze their features corresponding to the above-mentioned core techniques. These platforms were chosen as benchmarks for this study because they represent widely applied corpus resources that exemplify established interface design and analytical functionality solutions for large-scale national corpora. The British National Corpus (BNC) was selected due to its status as a well-established national corpus. Its availability through multiple platforms, especially BNCweb (CQP-Edition), enables effective querying, data collection, analysis, and visualization (Hoffmann and Evert n.d.). The Russian National Corpus (RNC) was selected due to its comprehensive structure, flexible search mechanisms, and a range of useful features. It provides a robust platform for linguistic research (Savchuk et al. 2024). The main objective of this comparison is to develop recommendations for the developers of the KNC corpus platform based on the insights obtained from the other two platforms.

Importantly, our review focuses only on the main corpus interfaces. Both the KNC and RNC have comprehensive websites that contain multiple pages, including these main corpus interfaces, links to subcorpora, about pages, documentation, and other materials. These websites allow users to explore corpus data, metadata, and design. Most of these features are not available through BNCweb, which is not structured as a comprehensive website with a main corpus interface, additional subcorpora, and other supporting resources. Rather, it is designed as a simplified queryable platform for direct research purposes. This structural difference reflects the fact that the BNC, unlike the KNC and RNC, is hosted by several platforms and has multiple versions. Due to such fragmentation and the absence of a unified website for the BNC, we selected BNCweb as the most user-friendly resource that is diverse in terms of its analytical features. While the BNC is also available via English-Corpora.org (Davies 2004), Sketch Engine (n.d.), and the Oxford Text Archive (OTA) (2007), we excluded these platforms because they require subscription or additional tools. Similarly, we excluded other widely used and updated large-scale corpus platforms, such as the Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA) (Davies 2008), as they operate under subscription-based access models. In this context, while BNCweb may not represent the most recent or complete version of the BNC, it remains the most accessible and reliable version for the purposes of the current study.

The differing structures and aims of these corpus platforms reflect differences in interface design and intended modes of use, rather than differences in corpus design. Comprehensive national corpora typically aim to represent the entirety of a language in relation to a certain culture, with representativeness and coverage being primary corpus design goals. BNCweb, by contrast, is neither a comprehensive resource nor intended to capture a language as a reflection of a culture. Rather, it functions as an access and analysis interface to an existing

corpus. While such resources may differ in scope and design, the present review deliberately sets corpus-design considerations aside to focus exclusively on interface- and technology-related aspects. To ensure a rigorous evaluation of the usability of the KNC interface for linguistic research, we adopt a two-level approach. Combining theory-driven analysis and practical comparisons across different corpus web interfaces, this approach allows us not only to identify the missing or underdeveloped analytical features in this corpus interface, but also to explain how existing corpus interfaces can serve as models for further interface-related corpus development research.

Our review of the KNC interface was guided by the following criteria and questions, which together constitute the evaluation framework adopted in this study (see Table 1). This framework was developed specifically for this study and is informed by the body of literature in corpus linguistics referenced throughout this paper. Importantly, the same framework was also used to examine BNCweb and the RNC platform, but they were analyzed more generally,² with the primary aim of identifying insights from their overall structure, interface design, and analytical functionality.

Table 1: Criteria and guiding questions for reviewing the main KNC interface

#	Criterion	Guiding question	Description
1	Presence or absence	Is this analytical technique available within the main KNC interface?	We determined whether each analytical technique could be located.
2	Accessibility (visibility and ease of access)	How easily can a corpus user find and use this corpus interface feature without relying on supporting documentation?	We navigated the main corpus interface, and if the techniques and features enabling them were present, we tested how easy they were to find and work with.
3	Functionality (operational status)	Does the feature work as expected? How well does it work?	We tested each available technique and its associated interface feature to observe whether they operated correctly and efficiently.
4	Overall usability for research purposes	To what extent do the corpus interface features representing the core analytical techniques support linguistic research?	We synthesized our findings related to the above criteria to determine whether the corpus interface is suitable for linguistic research purposes.

Regarding the potential shelf-life of this evaluation, it is important to mention that this study focuses on core and stable interface- and analytical feature-related decisions that are typically changed slowly over time, rather than on temporary, cosmetic interface update

² For the sake of brevity and comparability, however, the findings for all three platforms are nevertheless presented in a single summary table in the Results and Discussion section.

aspects. Therefore, the observations made in this study may remain relevant over time and be useful not only for future major updates to the KNC interface and analytical tool functionality, but also for other publicly released corpus platforms that may contain related issues.

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Introduction

In most corpus interfaces, analytical techniques typically become available on the query results page, i.e., once a corpus search has been completed. In the RNC interface, for example, they are presented as separate tabs, which users can click to access specific information about a word obtained through different analyses. In BNCweb, similar tools also appear on the query results page, but they can be found and selected using a drop-down menu, which makes them less immediately visible or easy to find. In the KNC interface, by contrast, such tools are not automatically activated upon completing a query. They are often hard to locate, underdeveloped, non-functional, or entirely absent.

In order to provide a systematic evaluation, the results are organized based on a fixed set of interface design and data analysis criteria that were applied to each core analytical technique within each corpus platform: (a) availability within the main interface, (b) accessibility (visibility and ease of access), (c) functionality (operational status and analytical depth), and (d) overall usability for corpus-linguistic research. Each analytical technique is examined according to these criteria in the KNC interface and subsequently compared with its implementation in BNCweb and the RNC interface.

Although the study focuses on the characteristics of the built-in analytical techniques within the main corpus interfaces, it is also important to mention that the KNC platform features a number of tools that are not directly integrated with the corpus-internal data (see Figure 1). These include *Transliteration* for converting Cyrillic Kazakh text into Latin script; *tbisozdik*, a dictionary offering thesaurus-like information; *Orthoepic Converter* for generating orthoepic transcriptions; *Word Frequency*, which generates frequency lists from user-uploaded documents; *Keyboard* for typing Kazakh in Latin script, available as a downloadable application; and several other tools. Some of these tools allow users to paste text or upload text documents directly into the interface, while others require downloading and installation. It is unclear whether this input should be derived from the corpus itself, as there is no built-in functionality that would support exporting query results in text or table format. Importantly, as of December 2025, several of these tools are not operational and appear to function only via the Kazakh-language version of the website.

Search Through Tools

Figure 1: Corpus analysis features of the KNC interface (website accessed June 21, 2025)

It is important to note that the above tools, although web-based, demonstrate functionality similar to popular corpus compilation and analysis software like *AntConc* (Anthony 2024) or *#LancsBox X* (Brezina & Platt 2025) that allow users to upload text documents into their interface to learn about and visualize the data within the documents, and to compile small and large-size corpora on the basis of a collection of such documents. We decided not to include these software corpus tools into our analysis, as our focus is limited to only web-based corpus platforms that process pre-compiled corpus data.

The following discussion focuses on two main objectives: (1) evaluating whether the main KNC interface supports the core analytical techniques by examining their presence or absence, accessibility, functionality, and usability for research purposes; and (2) reviewing the web interface of the RNC and BNCweb to draw useful suggestions for improving the KNC platform based on the characteristics of the analytical techniques available through their main (the RNC) and default (BNCweb) interfaces.

4.2 Scrutiny of the core analytical techniques available within the main KNC interface

Word frequency lists

The main KNC interface does not provide a frequency lists feature on the search results page, so users cannot see which words are most frequent or how many occurrences of a word can be encountered in the corpus or its subcorpora. Instead, there is only a ‘Word Statistics’ feature that can be accessed by clicking a word in the results, which shows raw frequencies by style, year, author, gender, and topic (see Figure 2). While some of these categories, like style and year, are clearly useful, others seem less relevant. There is no supporting documentation explaining these corpus design choices. Therefore, because the frequency technique is hidden behind additional clicks and lacks corpus-wide and subcorpus-specific distribution information, it is very limited in form and scope and not fully aligned with standard corpus linguistic research practices. In order to make the corpus interface more usable for research purposes, this analytical technique and its associated features should be integrated directly into the search results interface. It should show frequency data comprehensively, so that researchers can access and use this information more intuitively and efficiently.

Figure 2: Frequency distribution of *sōz* ‘word’ by year (available via *Word Statistics*)

Concordances

This analytical technique is offered in the KNC interface in a very limited form. It is available but consists only of highlighting the search term in red within the results, which are presented as separate paragraphs labeled by author. Because there is no clear KWIC view option, it may not be obvious to corpus users how to view and analyze the concordances efficiently. Furthermore, there is no option to adjust the size of the left and right contexts. The results cannot be aligned or sorted to support systematic analysis. However, it is a positive feature that the query interface provides some options for users to interact with the search results (see Figure 3). Overall, the concordance feature appears to be very limited, and researchers cannot reliably study words in context because of its current limitations. Adding more advanced concordance settings, such as sorting, aligning, filtering, adjusting context size, and export options, would create more opportunities for systematic analysis, making this analytical technique and its associated web interface features more suitable for linguistic research.

Figure 3: The query interface of the main part of the KNC platform

Keyword lists

In the KNC interface, this analytical technique is currently unavailable. The platform does not support the extraction of keyword lists or comparison functions. As a result, corpus users

cannot identify and compare keywords or statistically prominent words in relation to a reference corpus or across different subcorpora of the KNC. It is also not possible to highlight specific vocabulary characteristic of particular genres or registers in the corpus. This technique and its associated web interface features, if implemented, would work best for cross-corpus or cross-subcorpus comparisons. This tool would facilitate more corpus linguistic research aimed at identifying the distinctive lexical patterns, which would help researchers analyze variation more efficiently.

Collocations and n-grams

These techniques are currently unavailable in the main KNC interface. The tool labeled ‘Collocations’ does not retrieve collocates (see Figure 4). Instead, it performs simple searches within user-provided text, with unclear methods and no documentation to explain its use. This tool should not only be considered limited in accessibility and functionality, but also separate from the corpus platform itself, since it does not rely on the corpus-internal data but rather on text that users are invited to paste into its interface. As for n-grams, there are also no features supporting their extraction and analysis. Overall, the usability of these tools for research is minimal. If implemented transparently, they could facilitate corpus-linguistic research on recurring patterns and lexical combinations.

Figure 4: The Collocations feature of the KNC platform³

4.3 Drawing insights from BNCweb and the RNC interface: A cross-corpus comparison

While the previous subsections focus on reporting the observed characteristics of the analytical techniques available through corpus interfaces, this subsection adopts a more comparative and interpretive perspective, relying on the findings obtain in relation to BNCweb and the RNC interface as reference points to contextualize the findings related to the KNC.

³ Note that the detailed description of this tool is provided in the text above. This figure is provided here only for visualization purposes. It has text in Kazakh only because there are no other language options provided on the web page hosting this corpus tool.

By conducting a similar review of the RNC interface and BNCweb, we have found that most of the above-mentioned analytical techniques and their associated features are available within their online interfaces. However, for reasons of space, we are not providing full, detailed overviews of the two corpus platforms in a similar way as we have for the KNC. Instead, we briefly summarize some aspects of the analytical techniques that they provide, and then compare all three corpus platforms in table format. Importantly, it was not our goal to determine whether one corpus platform can be used for more research projects than the others. The three resources under study contain different data obtained from different sources and are not comparable in terms of the recency of their materials or how regularly the materials are updated or corpus updates are performed. It should be understood that such considerations are beyond the scope of this study.

The RNC interface supports all the core analytical techniques under study, and BNCweb fully supports most of them. These techniques can be used to collect, analyze, and visualize corpus data to answer a wide range of research questions. However, in both corpus platforms, some features are not always easy to find and may require additional effort to learn to use for general corpus querying and research.

The frequency lists technique is fully integrated into the main RNC interface, allowing users to generate frequency lists and explore the distribution of a search term across multiple categories (author, gender, domain, text type, theme, genre, style, text category). Data visualization tools such as the *Graph* (or distribution by date) feature produce visual representations of frequency data over time. All such information is based on transparent statistical analysis, with relevant statistical measures and scores provided in the output. In BNCweb, the frequency technique is provided with a detailed frequency breakdown and distribution information by multiple categories. It is possible to compare frequency lists, especially across the spoken and written components of the corpus platform. As for concordances, the RNC's main interface separates concordance results from KWIC. Although both display instances of use of a search term in context, they serve different purposes. Various settings allow corpus users to adjust concordance and KWIC views, with some sorting options available exclusively for KWIC. In contrast, BNCweb integrates KWIC directly with concordancing results, and there is no distinction between these aspects. Regarding keyword lists, BNCweb provides a fully functional keyword analysis feature. This feature allows users to directly compare items and lists of items pertaining to the spoken and written components. The RNC platform, by contrast, does not have an easily accessible and intuitive keyword lists function within its main interface. This technique and its associated interface features may either be available under a different name or require an alternative method of access. The process of generating keyword lists may also be more manual within the RNC's interface than in BNCweb. However, it is worth mentioning that more intuitive and advanced keyword list generation is generally performed using standalone desktop software like *AntConc* or *#LancsBox X*, rather than relying solely on the web interface of a corpus. Regarding collocations and n-grams, the RNC platform supports both analytical techniques in a research-ready form, allowing corpus users to perform the procedures directly within its main interface. While the n-grams function is available as a series of clickable tabs based on the size of the n-gram, the collocations tool is slightly more difficult to locate within the corpus interface. Still, both analytical techniques and their features are presented in a straightforward manner, with supporting documentation, tips, and examples of use. By contrast, BNCweb includes a fully developed collocations feature, but it does not provide an n-grams tool within its interface.

The following table synthesizes the results of the systematic evaluation by summarizing the availability and research readiness of each analytical technique across the three platforms.

Table 2: Comparative evaluation of analytical techniques across corpus web interfaces

#	Corpus platform	Frequency lists	Concordances	Keyword lists	Collocations and n-grams	Additional data visualization
1	KNC	Very limited	Very limited	Unavailable	Unavailable	Available, but limited
2	BNCweb	Available and research-ready	Available and research-ready	Available and research-ready	BNCweb has only collocations. This tool is research-ready.	Available, but limited
3	RNC	Available and research-ready	Available and research-ready	Available, but not intuitive or easily accessible.	Both are available and research-ready.	Available and research-ready

4.4 Implications and recommendations for improving the KNC interface

The following categorized list of suggestions is based on our review of the corpus platforms. These suggestions do not all pertain to the analytical techniques and their associated web interface features. Some of them arose during the corpus platform review procedures and also reflect more general aspects pertaining to enhancing the search and annotation systems and ensuring the transparency of corpus interface design and development of data analysis functionality.

Analytical techniques and their features

- (1) Introduce new analytical techniques that match those found in established corpus platforms;
- (2) Redesign existing techniques and their features so they can work with the corpus data itself, reducing dependence on desktop corpus tools;
- (3) Enhance data export options to make it easier for researchers to extract the data they need;

Annotation and querying

- (4) Ensure that the corpus and its subcorpora are consistently structured, annotated, and tagged to support uninterrupted querying and advanced analytical procedures;
- (5) Integrate more advanced linguistic settings into the corpus query tool to make corpus querying more flexible;

Corpus platform navigation and data presentation

- (6) Improve navigation between subcorpora and ensure consistency in how analytical tools and interface features work across the platform;
- (7) Fix broken links and ensure that all interface aspects operate as intended;
- (8) Improve how data is categorized and presented to make interacting with it more convenient;

Open research practices and community engagement

- (9) Maintain a log of corpus platform updates so external linguists can understand internal procedures and offer feedback;
- (10) Share information about the corpus and corpus platform with Kazakhstani and international researchers to encourage collaboration;
- (11) Ground all further corpus and corpus platform developments and updates in current theory and practice in the field of corpus linguistics.

These suggestions are important to implement for a variety of reasons, including but not limited to (1) making the corpus platform and its interface more usable for high-quality and international-standards linguistic research (Artetxe et al. 2022); (2) improving the ability of the corpus platform to accurately represent the language-in-use data in a more detailed way (Hurtado Bodell et al. 2022); (3) enabling more sophisticated forms of linguistic analysis, including topics like syntactic parsing, code-switching, and sociolinguistic variation (Rybka et al. 2015; Çetinoğlu 2016; Baker & Heritage 2022; Akishev & Kravtsova 2024; Miletic et al. 2024); (4) facilitating cross-linguistic comparisons based on corpus data (Stave et al. 2022); and (5) increasing the usability of the corpus platform for interdisciplinary projects including natural language processing, education, and language planning (Ilaio 2017; Almujaivel 2018; Alsop et al. 2020). It is our understanding that these improvements can contribute to transforming the corpus platform from a simple data repository to a high-level research resource.

5 Conclusion

This study has focused on the discussion of the usability of the web interface of the Kazakh National Corpus for research purposes. Our analysis has highlighted several ways in which the interface and architecture of the corpus could be significantly improved. The analytical techniques discussed here are widely recognized as essential components of any corpus platform. To provide more research opportunities, the KNC platform should evolve into a highly queryable resource whose interface and architecture would contain extensive built-in features for researchers to engage with and explore corpus data efficiently and intuitively. Additionally, further research is needed to address potential issues related to the internal organization of the corpus, data quality, data preprocessing and annotation, and, importantly, the deployment of the corpus on a modern, accessible web platform.

One of the limitations of this study is the sole focus on the core analytical techniques, especially in terms of the comparison between the selected corpus platforms. We decided to step away from the discussion of differences in terms of content, size, source of data, number and types of subcorpora, and other aspects of corpus compilation, corpus annotation, and corpus architecture. While we acknowledge that it would be possible to provide additional suggestions based on these aspects, they are simply beyond the scope of this paper. Further research can focus on these dimensions of the architecture and usability of the KNC platform.

The limitation of our corpus review process is the decision to focus solely on the main corpus interfaces. This decision applies to the KNC and RNC platforms, but it is less applicable to BNCweb, whose interface separates Spoken and Written parts but lacks a comprehensive collection of subcorpora. Including subcorpora in our analysis would be problematic, as the KNC and RNC have different types and numbers of subcorpora, and BNCweb does not offer subcorpora in the same way. Additionally, it was difficult to determine which version of the BNC should be considered the most relevant and reliable. The BNC is also hosted by other platforms, including English-Corpora.org, Sketch Engine, and the OTA. Each of these platforms offers a different version of the BNC, different levels of accessibility, and different functionalities. Furthermore, identifying the most recent or complete version of the BNC is difficult. Therefore, we chose to analyze only the web-accessible, default (BNCweb) and main (the KNC and RNC) interfaces of the corpora. We understand that further analysis of subcorpora and platform-based features may offer valuable insights and represent an important direction for future work.

In closing, it is important to highlight the scarcity of sources that specifically focus on improving the functionality and applicability for research purposes, especially in the case of recently launched corpus platforms. It is possible to assume that such considerations are discussed internally during corpus design, without the need to document them in research papers. Consequently, developers of corpora for low-resource languages do not always have access to specific guidelines on corpus compilation, architecture, and interface design. There is a substantial amount of research on corpus building, but it is mostly fragmented and outdated, offering few generalizable ideas for corpus developers to use when designing and maintaining their corpora. As a result, corpora of different types are still developed by linguists, educational institutions, and government bodies around the world without following any unified guidelines. Developing and sharing such guidelines would be an important first step in ensuring that corpora and corpus interfaces for all languages, including the low-resource ones, are based on the international standards of corpus building and usable for high-quality linguistic research.

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Timur Akishev
Department of Linguistics and Cognitive Science
College of Human Sciences and Education
KIMEP University
Almaty, Kazakhstan
e-mail: t.akishev@kimep.kz

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Interview with
Kimi Akita

Bonnie McLean (BM)

Since completing your PhD thesis on ideophones in Japanese and other languages at Kobe University (Akita 2009), to your postdoctoral fellowship at the University of Tokyo and UC Berkeley, and now as Associate Professor at Nagoya University, where you've just hosted one of the largest international symposiums on iconicity (IcoLL2026), you've devoted your career to the study of ideophones and iconicity. You've written countless articles, authored several books—including a recent Japanese bestseller with the psychologist Mutsumi Imai, Gengo no honshitsu [The nature of language] (Imai & Akita 2023)—as well as editing many more, among them landmark publications like Ideophones, mimetics and expressives (Akita & Pardeshi 2019) and, more recently, the mammoth Oxford handbook of iconicity in language (Fischer et al. 2026). In both English and Japanese, for the general public as well as scholars, you've analyzed virtually every aspect of ideophones—their phonology, morphology, syntax, semantics, pragmatics, semiotics, typology, history, and acquisition. Tell me, what is it about ideophones that keeps you coming back for more? What makes them so special to you? I'm curious to know where this passion comes from.

Kimi Akita (KA)

Thank you, Bonnie, for your kind introduction. What first attracted me to this word class was its seemingly random but highly systematic behavior. New ideophones can be created rather freely on the fly, but they nonetheless exhibit grammatical constraints. For example, Japanese ideophones for laughter include *ahaha*, *ehehe*, *ufufu*, and *geragera*. We also have ideophones for smiling, like *nikoniko*, *nitanita*, *niyari*, and *ninmari*. While all these smile ideophones can form verbs in light verb constructions, as in *nikoniko suru* (IDPH do) and *niyari to suru* (IDPH QUOT do), laughter ideophones generally cannot: forms like **ahaha to suru* and **geragera suru* sound odd. The same pattern extends to newly coined ideophones. If *nyaranyara* is intended to mimic laughter, **nyaranyara suru* is unacceptable. But if it's used as a smile ideophone, *nyaranyara suru* is perfectly acceptable.

Another impressive thing about ideophones is their expressive power. Let's take *ukkari* as an example. This Japanese ideophone refers to inadvertent carelessness resulting in forgetting to do something important. We use *ukkari* when we get home and realize we've forgotten to buy milk at the supermarket. It's remarkable that such a complex scenario can be compressed into a word of only three syllables!

BM

I agree, it's what makes ideophones so useful! In fact, often when I'm trying to express myself in English, the perfect Japanese ideophone for the scenario will jump out at me, and then it's so hard to try to find how to say the same thing in English without it. Ukkari is like that, I need it far more often than I'd like... and girigiri is another example. It depicts two things very close together, with hardly any space in between, but you can use it in all kinds of scenarios, not only when talking about physical space, but also, for instance, space in time, like when you barely make a deadline... which is how things unfortunately are for me most of the time. Anyway, we can say "oh that was tight" or whatever in English, but you don't feel that tightness in your body in the same way as when you use girigiri in Japanese. There's just something so visceral about the meanings of ideophones, I guess because of their iconicity.

KA

Girigiri feels very *girigiri* to me, too. The high front vowel /i/ is iconic of spatial narrowness, and the voicing of /g/ intensifies urgency or danger.

BM

Indeed. Before we get into this more, perhaps you could provide a brief definition of ideophones? We've mentioned their iconicity, but that's not their only defining feature.

KA

The term “ideophone” was coined by the Bantu linguist Clement Martyn Doke (Doke 1935). Similar types of words have also been referred to as “expressives” in South and Southeast Asian linguistics and as “mimetics” (*giongo/gitaigo*) in Japanese linguistics. Ideophones are imitative words like *meow* and *ding-dong*, but they go far beyond onomatopoeia. For example, in Mundari, an Austroasiatic language, *jilab-jolab* represents the “small, periodic shining lights [e.g. of fireflies] in many places” (Badenoch & Osada 2019: 138), while *sonda-sonda* refers to the “fragrant smell of beans or rice that is being fried” (Badenoch & Osada 2019: 236). Doke’s original definition described an ideophone as a “vivid representation of an idea in sound” and a “word, often onomatopoeic, which describes a predicate, qualificative or adverb in respect to manner, colour, sound, smell, action, state or intensity” (Doke 1935: 118). However, it’s now more common in linguistics to cite Mark Dingemans’s (2019: 16) cross-linguistic definition of an ideophone as a “member of an open lexical class of marked words that depict sensory imagery.”

BM

And what do you think of this definition?

KA

I agree with Mark’s definition, although I don’t think it should be taken as the final version—and I suspect Mark himself would agree. More specifically, I’m not sure that structural markedness should be mentioned as such in the definition. Ideophones “depict,” or are iconic of, what they represent. This semiotic property appears to allow ideophones to violate regular morphophonological constraints, resulting in structurally marked forms such as reduplication or unusual syllable structures. For example, in Japanese, initial /p/ is not permitted in native lexemes but is common in ideophones, as in *pachipachi* ‘clapping’ and *pikapika* ‘flashing’. This marked phonology may be attributed to the iconicity of /p/ in these ideophones, whose articulatory or acoustic properties are associated with a sense of tension. In short, markedness appears to be a secondary feature deriving from the depictive semiotics of ideophones.

BM

Do you have any other concerns about the definition?

KA

I’m also interested in the common characterization of ideophones as “sensory” words. Japanese linguists often distinguish between sound ideophones (*giongo*, phonomimes) and non-sound or “manner” ideophones (*gitaigo*, phenomimes). However, it’s less common to distinguish further among different sensory types of manner ideophones. If ideophones are defined primarily in terms of sensory meaning, they would resemble adjectives. Indeed, both the ideophone *pikapika* ‘flashing’ and the adjective *mabushii* ‘dazzling’ convey visual information, and both *subesube* ‘silky’ and *nameraka* ‘smooth’ represent tactile experience. However, Japanese ideophones most commonly occur as adverbs—for example, *pikapika hikaru* (IDPH shine) ‘to shine

flashingly’—followed by verbs such as *pikapika suru* (IDPH do) ‘to flash’. For this reason, Japanese linguists often emphasize the eventive, rather than sensory, semantics of ideophones (Kita 1997; Kageyama 2007). Unlike nouns and adjectives, ideophones generally represent dynamic events, using dynamic speech sounds to imitate them. Whether ideophones should be defined in terms of sensory modalities or eventivity might therefore be a language-specific issue.

BM

*True, the meanings of many ideophones seem inherently dynamic, regardless of the sensory domains involved. While we’re on the topic of ideophone meanings, I wonder if I could get your opinion on something I’ve also been thinking about lately, which is the relation between ideophones and abstraction. It’s been argued that since the meanings of ideophones are so grounded in sensory experience, this hinders them from expressing abstract meaning (Dingemanse et al. 2015; Lupyán & Winter 2018), but lately I’ve been questioning whether this is really the case. The example you gave with *ukkari* ‘careless’, for instance, is not exactly concrete. What are your thoughts on this?*

KA

I agree ideophones can express abstract meaning. Japanese has numerous ideophones representing inner feelings and mental states, such as *kirikiri* ‘having a sharp, stabbing pain’, *iraira* ‘irritated’, and *unzari* ‘fed up’. Ideophones are more than just imitative. Let’s compare the Japanese ideophone *garagara* and its English equivalent *rattle*. *Rattle* can imitate a wide range of similar sounds, including those made by a rattlesnake, a sliding door, a train, and dishes. *Garagara* can also mimic the sounds of a rattlesnake and a sliding door, but different ideophones would typically be used for other sources: *gatagoto* for a train noise, and *gachagacha* or *kachakacha* for dishes. This suggests that onomatopoeic ideophones in Japanese encode not only auditory information but also non-auditory aspects of events. Indeed, Japanese speakers would use different ideophones for the same sound when it’s presented alongside different images, like a train versus a sliding door (see Yu 2014 for a related experiment). I think this non-purely imitative aspect of ideophone semiotics enables them to incorporate abstract, even non-sensory meaning. Ideophones are prototypically imitative, but imitation doesn’t capture the full range of their semantics.

BM

Yes, in fact, I was recently reading a review paper (Reilly et al. 2025) which discusses properties of abstract words, and I was struck by how many of these properties were shared by ideophones, such as the association with affective experience, high contextual salience, and their meanings residing in language. Of course, the meanings of all words can be found in language, but the semantics of ideophones have perhaps been oversimplified as being purely concrete and grounded in real perceptual experiences, when as you say to use ideophones correctly requires more than just perceptual knowledge. So the boundaries between concrete and abstract are actually blurred in both directions. Anyway, it’s a bit much to get into here, but definitely ideophones as a word class are less clear-cut than existing definitions imply. In your thesis, you characterize them as a prototype category with fuzzy boundaries and this has always appealed to me. It fits with the canonical definition we have of phonesthemes from Kwon & Round (2015), under the framework of Canonical Typology. I wish we had a similar canonical definition for ideophones!

KA

Very interesting. That may be related to the fact that some researchers characterize ideophones as “highly specific” (Akita 2012), while others describe them as “elusive” (Tsujimura 2001). Perhaps both views are valid: ideophones may have inherently ambivalent semantic properties.

Thank you also for reminding me of Canonical Typology. In fact, about a decade ago, when Nahyun Kwon was a postdoc in my lab, we tried to apply Canonical Typology to ideophones. It’s regrettable that we did not publish the work, as our attention was directed toward other topics at the time.

Ideophone researchers tend to focus on what constitutes a prototypical ideophone, and this is certainly a necessary approach. But to fully define ideophones, we must also consider what does not count as an ideophone. So, it’ll be worthwhile to examine the diachronic processes of ideophonization and deideophonization (Akita 2009; Dingemanse 2017; Flaksman 2017). New ideophones can arise from non-ideophonic words, as in Japanese *mochimochi* ‘chewy’, which is derived from the noun *mochi* ‘rice cake’. Conversely, many verbs and nouns have putative ideophonic origins; for example, Japanese *hikaru* ‘to shine’ is associated with the ideophone *pikapika* ‘flashing’. Some of these ideophonized and deideophonized words do not seem fully ideophonic and appear to lie near the fuzzy boundaries of the category. I think a better understanding of ideophones can be achieved by examining the factors that contribute to increase and decrease in ideophonicity.

BM

Very true! And what do you think of the relation between ideophones and onomatopoeia? In your Oxford encyclopedia article with Mark (Akita & Dingemanse 2019), you argue that onomatopoeias are sound-mimicking ideophones that constitute a subset of the ideophone category. However, this does not seem to be a universally accepted view. Some studies clearly distinguish onomatopoeia from ideophones, while others appear to treat onomatopoeia as interjections (see Körtvélyessy & Štekauer 2024). Where do you stand on this?

KA

I now take a more moderate position. In Japanese, onomatopoeia and non-sound ideophones are formally and functionally indistinguishable. Both appear in the same set of morphophonological templates, such as reduplicated or nasal-ending forms, and are typically followed by the quotative particle *to*, functioning as adverbs, as in *piyopiyo to naku* ‘to cry tweet-tweet’ and *fuwafuwa to ukabu* ‘to float fluffily’. Moreover, many ideophones have both auditory and non-auditory meanings. For example, *kachikachi* depicts both the ticking sound of a clock and a hard surface that would produce a high-pitched sound when struck. By contrast, English arguably lacks a clearly distinct word class just for depiction. Onomatopoeic verbs and nouns such as *clap* and *splash* do not form a coherent open lexical class with systematic features that distinguish them from ordinary words. Holophrastic sound effects—as in *He lit the fuse, ran back, and—kaboom!—the rock split in two*—do stand out distinctly, and one might say they resemble interjections. But essentially, ideophones and interjections are semiotically different categories: ideophones are iconic, while interjections are indexical.

One possible way to account for this cross-linguistic diversity is, again, to define the status of onomatopoeia language-specifically. Whether onomatopoeia constitutes a subset of the ideophone lexicon may depend on how well developed the ideophone system of a given language is.

BM

Speaking of language-specificity, are there any particularly interesting properties that distinguish Japanese ideophones from those in other languages?

KA

Japanese ideophones are particularly interesting in at least two respects. First, they've been studied extensively by numerous researchers—most of them native speakers—using historical texts, dialect materials, large corpora, and experimental methods. Ideophones are also widely discussed by ordinary speakers in everyday life. As you can see on my website (Akita 2005-2010), there are now well over a thousand publications on Japanese ideophones. This contrasts sharply with the situation in African linguistics and Southeast Asian linguistics, where ideophones are often documented by nonnative-speaker linguists through fieldwork. Japanese has therefore made a distinctive contribution to ideophone research, as illustrated by landmark studies such as Kita (1997), Hamano (1998), and Imai et al. (2008). Unfortunately, most papers and books on Japanese ideophones are written in Japanese, and I've been trying to make their insights more accessible to an international audience by citing them in my English publications.

BM

Yes, I'm constantly referring to your bibliographies of sound symbolic phenomena (in Japanese and other languages)! For many years they've been a crucial resource for researchers studying ideophones and sound symbolism, and I want to say that myself personally, and I know many other people in the field are so grateful to you for providing this resource! There's just so much research coming out of Japan all the time, and as you say so much of it is in Japanese so just making those articles locatable for English speakers is a huge service. But sorry, you were talking about the uniqueness of Japanese ideophones, please go on!

KA

Thank you, I'm glad my bibliographies are so helpful. The other unique thing about Japanese that I wanted to mention here again is that it's particularly rich in ideophones describing interoceptive experiences and emotions, such as *zukizuki* 'throbbing pain in the head or teeth' and *wakuwaku* 'excited'. Some linguists refer to these as *gijōgo* (psychomimes). Their abundance is what first drew me to the study of ideophones when I was a master's student. One day I'd like to clarify why Japanese so readily depicts such abstract concepts through speech sounds. To answer that question, we'll likely need to combine typological and anthropological perspectives.

In this connection, it's also worth reconsidering the term "ideophone." Current research often assumes that "ideophones," "expressives," and "mimetics" represent equivalent lexical classes. However, this assumption should not necessarily be taken as definitive. The lexical status of ideophones may vary across languages, just as the status of onomatopoeia probably does (Kulemeka 1995; Dingemanse 2017; Dingemanse & Akita 2017).

BM

Yes, I found your recent finding in Iida & Akita (2023) that the interoceptive quality of Japanese ideophones is actually a quality shared by the wider Japanese lexicon really interesting. I agree with your intuition that culture probably plays quite a significant role in shaping ideophone lexicons, and I hope that future work will highlight more of this type of cross-cultural variation in the expression of iconicity. And while we're on the subject of culture, we really need to talk about the column you've been writing since 2024 for NHK's monthly haiku magazine (Akita 2024-2026). I think it's so fantastic that the general public in Japan is so interested and enthused by ideophones, and of course haiku is the perfect medium to showcase ideophones'

expressive prowess. When you have a limited number of syllables you really need to make every one count, and ideophones do this so well. Could you tell us a little more about their role in haiku?

KA

Japanese ideophones are frequently used in haiku, lyrics, and other forms of verbal art. They vividly depict both the external world and people’s internal states in a fine-grained way. While some haiku poets avoid using ideophones in haiku, as they can sound playful and even childish, others seem to be conscious of their efficiency and effectiveness. And they are creative enough to make new ideophones in haiku. Let me give you an example.

くやくやと思ひめぐらす春の夢

Kuyakuya to omoi megurasu haru no yume
IDPH QUOT thought surround spring GEN
dream

‘A spring dream filled with brooding thoughts’

(Yoshio Matsuyama)

This haiku features *kuyakuya*, which appears to have been coined from the conventional ideophone *kuyokuyo* ‘regretting’. Using the unrounded vowel /a/ instead of the rounded vowel /o/, this ideophone gives a brighter image to the brooding thoughts in a spring dream. Thanks to the established sound-symbolic system of Japanese, new ideophones can be created, and their meanings can be shared between poets and readers.

More crucially, as you say, ideophones’ expressive prowess enriches haiku. In haiku, we must, in principle, follow the 17-mora format (5 + 7 + 5) and include a seasonal word called *kigo*. The dense semantics of ideophones helps us pack emotionally rich, multisensory imagery into the short line without breaking the rules. Let me give you another example.

しんみりと虎が雨夜の咄かな

Shinmiri to toraga’ameyo no hanashi kana
IDPH QUOT early.summer.rainy.night GEN story SFP

‘Softly pensive—a story on a rainy night in early summer’

(Rotsu Yasomura)

Shinmiri is a psychomime that represents a somewhat sentimental yet tranquil scene—one that is tinged with sadness but not overwhelmingly so. I believe the rich semantic content of Japanese ideophones is partly related to a cultural sensibility that finds beauty in imperfection and transience.

BM

That’s so poetic! Do you also write your own haiku with ideophones?

KA

Not yet. I’m looking forward to composing haiku after I retire.

BM

That sounds like a lovely retirement plan. And what is your favorite Japanese ideophone?

KA

I love all ideophones, but let me mention *geragera* once again. It’s often cited as an ideophone

depicting a guffaw. Indeed, *geragera to iu warai goe* ‘laughter that sounds like *geragera*’ is a perfectly natural collocation. However, if I say, “Please laugh *geragera*,” no one can actually do it. People end up laughing *ahaha*, *wahaha*, or *gahaha* instead. Producing *geragera* while laughing is simply unnatural. This is because *geragera* depicts the vulgarity or coarseness of a laugh, rather than the laughter itself, and in that sense it’s a manner ideophone. My hypothesis is that the ideophone can evoke the auditory aspect of laughter through a subjective conceptualization of a guffawing scene—playful enough to make us “hear” a fictive laugh, much like in manga. This ideophone nicely illustrates how flexible and playful the semantics of ideophones can be.

BM

I love that! It’s like shiin, or other ideophones depicting silence. Lots of languages seem to have them, even though they’re a contradiction. Ideophones, even onomatopoeia, can be a lot more complex than people assume! Speaking of, are there any other misconceptions people have about ideophones, or iconicity more generally, that you’d like to address?

KA

I think people can sometimes assume that there is a degree of objectivity or universality to ideophones, or even that this is what it means to be iconic, but this is not what we actually find. A key component of iconicity is really subjectivity, so much so that subjectivity has now become a keyword in the ongoing debate on iconicity in cognitive science (Winter et al. 2026).

Ideophones are real words, and this allows them to reveal aspects of language that might be difficult to uncover using nonce forms such as *maluma–takete* (Köhler 1929) or *bouba–kiki* (Ramachandran & Hubbard 2001). Because they are part of the lexicon, ideophones are constrained by the morphophonological system of a language and exhibit language-specific form–meaning correspondences, or “systematicity” (Dingemans et al. 2015; see also Childs 2014). An often-cited example is the counter-universal sound symbolism found in ideophones in Bahnar, an Austroasiatic language. In this language, vowel openness inversely correlates with size, as in /halul/ ‘an enormous wedged-up object’, /halol/ ‘a big wedged-up object’, and /halol/ ‘a small wedged-up object’ (Diffloth 1994: 112).

Japanese provides another example. It has a historically based, semi-productive paradigm of sound symbolism in which /h/, /p/, and /b/ contrast in the initial position of ideophones. For instance, *horohoro*, *poroporo*, and *boroboro* can all refer to tears running down one’s cheeks, with the amount of tears increasing in that order. Although /h/ does not form a natural class with /p/ and /b/, native speakers of Japanese find this sound-symbolic pattern entirely natural.

These examples invite us to reconsider the traditional definition of iconicity as resemblance between form and meaning (Peirce 1932). If the perception of form–meaning resemblance is language-specific, then iconicity itself may need to be understood as a language-specific, learned property (Akita & Imai 2022; Iida & Akita 2024, 2025; Winter et al. 2026; see also McLean et al. 2023; Punselie et al. 2024). It’ll therefore be important to examine how such language-specific senses of resemblance emerge and what roles they play in language.

BM

I’m glad you mention the systematic aspects of ideophones. I think people sometimes underestimate the complexity that exists under the surface when you use ideophones. It can look like you’re just inventing random words or sounds for things, but there are rules and depictive conventions and things to follow if you want to be able to integrate, for instance, a novel ideophone into the wider ideophone lexicon. You can’t actually just do whatever you want, and I think it’s where iconicity and systematicity come together in ideophone lexicons, and then

when you add on things like metaphor, that you get the most expressive power. Now you've written about all three of these concepts—iconicity, systematicity, and metaphor in ideophone lexicons—so I wonder, could you explain these and how they relate to each other and to ideophones?

KA

That's a thought-provoking question. As I said, I now think that lexical iconicity is best understood as a language-specific sense of form–meaning resemblance acquired through systematic form–meaning correspondences. On this view, iconicity is distinguished from the objective similarity between form and meaning that is accessible to speakers of any language—or even to infants—which may instead be termed “transparency” (Iida & Akita 2025).

As for metaphor, Japanese rhetorical theory sometimes characterizes ideophones as *seiyu* ‘voice metaphor’, insofar as they iconically represent various types of information through speech sounds. Non-onomatopoeic ideophones may be metaphorical in that they involve a subjective perception of resemblance between sound and non-auditory experience. For example, Japanese speakers may perceive the phonological form /teikuteiku/ as resembling prickliness. It may be possible to argue that such subjective resemblance is mediated by metaphor or metonymy linking sound and touch. As mentioned earlier, *kachikachi* is a polysemous ideophone that can represent both the ticking of a clock and a hard surface. This type of crossmodal semantic extension appears to underlie the broad semantic range of ideophones in Japanese and many other languages. If I'm on the right track, the semantic range of ideophones in a language may correlate with the degree to which the relevant semantic extensions are established. However, further discussion is required to fully evaluate this hypothesis, particularly in light of the pluripotentiality of sound in sound symbolism and its relationship to crossmodal correspondences (Akita et al. 2024; cf. Hinton et al. 1994; Winter 2025).

BM

So many interesting ideas here, thank you! It gives me a lot to think about. I agree that it's good to be able to distinguish between iconicity that is acquired, especially through experience with language, and iconicity that is independent of linguistic experience—or, transparency, as you say. However, I would be wary of using terms like “objective similarity,” as I think the concept of similarity itself can never be objective, since it is a process based on construal which is necessarily subjective (see McLean & Motamedi 2026). I love what you say about metaphor and crossmodal semantic extension though, as well as the pluripotentiality of sound symbolism. I agree these are really crucial to understanding how ideophones work, and I hope there'll be a lot more research into this in the future! They're topics I'm really interested in too.

KA

Thank you for pointing out the problem with the idea of “objective similarity.” This is indeed something we frequently discuss in my lab as well. Even when we evaluate form–meaning resemblance in an unfamiliar language, our judgments are likely to be influenced by our L1, and possibly additional languages. For example, my ratings of form–meaning resemblance for Swahili words would likely differ from yours.

This brings us to another question: why do children learn more iconic words earlier than less iconic ones, where “iconicity” is operationalized using adults' subjective ratings (Perry et al. 2015; Winter et al. 2024)? I think scholars have assumed that the sense of form–meaning resemblance is shared between adults and infants, which may not necessarily be the case. It is likely that some form–meaning resemblances are more widely shared—or more accessible—than others, and that these facilitate children's word learning. However, I should hasten to add

that the language-specific sense of iconicity (or “iconic-systematicity” in Sidhu’s 2024 terms) might also help language learning. According to Mutsumi Imai’s research team, Japanese-speaking three-year-old children succeeded in generalizing verbs created from novel Japanese ideophones about 80% of the time (Imai et al. 2008), while English-speaking children had a success rate of only 70% (Kantartzis et al. 2011).

BM

Interesting, yes studies with children are a good way to tease apart the mechanisms behind these so-called “iconic effects.” There is a tendency to treat form-meaning resemblances as a “silver bullet” (as Nielsen & Dingemanse 2021 put it), and I’d agree that in so doing we risk underestimating the contributions of things like systematicity and perhaps overestimating the role of transparency. In fact, as well as children, typological variation could be useful to consider here. I feel Japanese is quite an extreme example of an ideophone lexicon that is also highly systematic. Of course, the two go together, but not every ideophone lexicon is quite so systematic as Japanese, so I wonder if transparency then becomes more important, and what the effects of that are. So many interesting avenues for future research!

KA

Another great point! The other day, one undergrad asked me which language is most iconic—“transparent” in our terms—and I couldn’t give a clear answer. It’d be very interesting to compare the overall degree of transparency across languages and discuss the results in terms of systematicity.

BM

Sounds fun! Now we are approaching the end of the interview, and we’ve talked a lot about ideophone research in general, but I think readers would also like to hear more about your own work specifically. What do you think your most important contributions to ideophone research have been so far?

KA

That’s a very kind question. I believe three of my contributions are particularly important. The first is what I call the “lexical iconicity hierarchy,” which I proposed in my dissertation (Akita 2009). According to this hierarchy, sound ideophones (phonomimes) are more iconic than manner ideophones (phenomimes), which are in turn more iconic than inner-state ideophones (psychomimes). The idea is that the more iconic a type of ideophone is, the more likely it is to be found across languages (see also Dingemanse 2012, McLean 2021, and Van Hoey 2024 for related proposals), and the more likely it is to occur in the periphery of a main clause. In other words, onomatopoeias such as *bowwow* and *squeak* are especially widespread across languages, and they are more likely than non-onomatopoeic ideophones to function as adjuncts. The hierarchy also accounts for the verbalizability of Japanese ideophones for laughter and smiling I mentioned in the beginning of this interview. I think these iconicity-based patterns in ideophone syntax is a type-level manifestation of the more widely reported inverse relation between expressiveness and morphosyntactic integration. The latter is a token-level generalization in which ideophones are most expressive in morphosyntactically independent constructions, such as holophrases (Dingemanse & Akita 2017; Akita & Dingemanse 2019). Both of these implicational generalizations remain hypotheses and will need to be further tested in future research.

BM

I remember in your thesis you even found the same hierarchy reflected in the acquisition of

ideophones by Japanese children. More recently, I saw it in Dutch participants' ratings of the iconicity of ideophones in foreign languages (Punselie et al. 2024). It pops up again and again when you work with ideophones or iconicity, you really laid the groundwork there for what's become a very powerful explanatory tool! What about some of your other proposals?

KA

Thank you. I think my second important contribution is my theoretical considerations of ideophones. I've applied general linguistic frameworks to the description and analysis of ideophones, including Construction Grammar (Akita 2009; Akita & Usuki 2016), prototype theory (Akita 2009), Conceptual Metaphor Theory (Akita 2010, 2013), Frame Semantics (Akita 2012, 2017a), Generative Lexicon (Usuki & Akita 2013), Leonard Talmy's "framing typology" (Akita 2017b; Akita & Matsumoto 2020), and the semantic map (Akita et al. 2024). These approaches are important to place ideophones in general linguistic discussions, as they've been marginalized in linguistics. Sometimes I even collaborate with generative linguists to evaluate which theoretical framework works better to deal with specific aspects of ideophones.

The third contribution I consider important concerns the semantic relevance of ideophone prosody. The multimodality of ideophone use has been repeatedly noted in the literature. Ideophones are often synchronized with iconic gesture strokes because of their depictive nature, and paralinguistic features such as intonation also contribute to their depictive force. In my work, I've added voice quality to this discussion, publishing several papers on its iconic function (or "phonational foregrounding"; Dingemanse & Akita 2017; Akita 2019, 2020, 2021, 2025a, b; Akita & Kawahara 2025). Ideophones are often pronounced with marked voice quality, which is usually not recorded in corpora. For example, falsetto can be iconic, or indexical, of fast motion, round shapes, or pleasure, while whispering can be iconic of small size or quiet motion. I've also observed that, much like gesture and emphatic intonation, marked voice quality tends to occur more frequently with non-predicative ideophones in the periphery of a main clause than with predicative ideophones. In the near future, I'd like to undertake a qualitative analysis of individual ideophone tokens in order to identify the specific meanings associated with different types of voice quality.

BM

Now that we are talking about the future, what other projects are you planning?

KA

As this interview has shown, many questions in ideophone research remain unresolved, and I'd like to address them one by one. I'm also currently planning a cross-linguistic project that asks the following question: when speakers of one language use ideophones, what do speakers of another language do in comparable situations? Do they also use ideophones, or do they instead rely on non-ideophonic words combined with iconic prosody or gesture? The question actually dates back to some of my earliest work on ideophones. My BA thesis was on English psychological verbs, or "psych-verb," such as *worry* and *amaze*. I had planned to continue this line of research in my master's thesis, but my supervisor Yo Matsumoto was not very enthusiastic about the idea. Instead, he suggested that I compare English and Japanese expressions of psychological states. Around the same time, I happened to learn about ideophones in Yo's course on framing typology. I was surprised to find that many English psych-verbs correspond to psychomimes in Japanese. For example, *worry* corresponds to *kuyokuyo*, *amaze* to *bikkuri*, *excite* to *wakuwaku*, and *disappoint* to *gakkari*. It taught me that ideophones need to be considered within the broader context of lexical typology rather than studied in isolation, and I'm looking forward to getting back to this. My hypothesis is that in some cases, metaphors may compensate for the absence of psychomimes in a language—for

example, *a splitting headache* for Japanese *gangan* or *over the moon* for Japanese *ukiuki*. I hope this project will help us better understand the role that ideophones play in communication.

BM

That sounds fascinating, I've always wondered why some languages (like Japanese) are so rich in ideophones, while others (like English) are so relatively impoverished. I guess we must make up for it with other means like you say. Iconicity is certainly far too important to communication to do without! I look forward to hearing more about your future projects. And as one of the most prolific researchers in the field, thank you for taking the time to share your thoughts about ideophones and iconicity with me today. It's been a real pleasure!

KA

Thank you for all your inspiring questions and thoughtful comments. It's been a pleasure to reflect on what we've studied and to consider what remains to be done. I also look forward to seeing the progress of your research. I also sincerely thank SKASE, especially Livia Körtvélyessy, for giving me this opportunity. I hope our conversation will help readers deepen their understanding of language, communication, and the human mind.

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Bonnie McLean
Department of Linguistics and Philology
Uppsala University
Box 635, 751 26 Uppsala, Sweden
e-mail: bonnie.mclean@lingfil.uu.se

Kimi Akita
Graduate School of Humanities
Nagoya University
Furo-cho, Chikusa-ku, Nagoya, Aichi 464-8601, Japan
e-mail: akita.kimi@nagoya-u.jp

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